

TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI: ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLARI, TARAQQIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

MATERIALLARI

2025-yil 29-30-sentabr

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
SIRDARYO VILOYATI HOKIMLIGI
GULISTON DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI BALIKESIR UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI FIRAT UNIVERSITETI,
YANGLING KASB-HUNAR VA TEXNIKA KOLLEJI**

**“TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI:
ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB
MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLARI,
TARAQQIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI”**

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

MATERIALLARI

2025-yil 29-30-sentabr

**“BOOKMATY PRINT”
TOSHKENT – 2025**

UO‘K: 811(075)

KBK: 81.1

T 42

Tilshunoslikning amaliy masalalari: zamonaviy tilshunoslikning dolzarb muammolari, yechimlari, taraqqiyoti va istiqbollari [Matn]: to‘plam. – Toshkent: Bookmany print, 2025. – 654 b.

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020-yil 20-oktabrdagi “Mamlakatimizda o‘zbek tilini yanada rivojlantirish va til siyosatini takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi PF-6084-sonli Farmoniga muvofiq “2020-2030-yillarda o‘zbek tilini rivojlantirish va til siyosatini takomillashtirish konsepsiyasi”da belgilangan vazifalarning ijrosini ta’minlash maqsadida hamda Oliy ta’lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligining 2024-yil 27-dekabrdagi 490-sonli buyrug‘iga asosan **Guliston davlat universitetida 2025-yil 29-30-sentabr kunlari** o‘tkazilgan **“TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI: ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLARI, TARAQQIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI”** mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari. Anjuman zamonaviy tilshunoslikning eng dolzarb ilmiy mavzulari va amaliy masalalariga doir uslubiy ishlanmalarni aks ettirishga qaratilgan.

Mas’ul muharrirlar:

f.f.f.d. (PhD), dotsent A.Axrоров, f.f.d., professor F.Sharipov, f.f.d., professor I.Ermatov, f.f.n., dotsent J.Abdullayev, f.f.n., dotsent I.Pardayeva, f.f.f.d. (PhD), dotsent. M.Latipov, Prof. Dr. Banovsha Mammadova Gulog‘hlan, Prof. Dr. Ertan Örgen, Prof. Dr. Suheylya Demirkol Orak.

Tahrir hay’ati:

A.Axrоров, A.Mamatqulov, Sh.Ro‘ziqulov, Z.To‘ychiyeva

To‘plamga keltirilgan ma’ruza tezislarning mazmuni, undagi ma’lumotlar va me’yoriy hujjatlar hamda fikr-mulohazalar, takliflarning to‘g‘riligiga mualliflarning o‘zlari mas’uldirlar

ISBN 978-9910-06-724-2

© Guliston davlat universiteti, 2025.
© “Bookmany print” nashriyoti, 2025.

8. Ellis, R. (2003). *Task-Based Language Learning and Teaching*. Oxford University Press.
9. Jones, L. (2011). *The Student-Centered Classroom*. Cambridge University Press.
10. Gibbons, P. (2002). *Scaffolding Language, Scaffolding Learning: Teaching Second Language Learners in the Mainstream Classroom*. Heinemann.
11. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Xalq ta’limi vazirligi. (2020). *Ingliz tili o‘qitish metodikasi bo‘yicha qo‘llanma*. Toshkent.
12. Akbarov, A. (2018). Ingliz tilini o‘qitishda individual yondashuv: nazariy va amaliy jihatlar. *Til va Adabiyot*, 3(2), 45-53.
13. Karimova, M. (2021). Ta’limda individual yondashuvning samaradorligi. *Pedagogika Ilmi*, 4(1), 78-84.
14. Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes*. Harvard University Press.
15. Gardner, R. C., & Lambert, W. E. (1972). *Attitudes and Motivation in Second-Language Learning*. Newbury House Publishers.

NEW METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES IN TEACHING THE ENGLISH ARTICLE

Gullu T. Mammadova,
Azerbaijan University of Languages
gullu.mammad@mail.ru

Abstract. The article explores new methodological approaches in teaching the article system in English. The limitations of traditional grammar-translation and rule-based teaching are highlighted and the advantages of modern, communicative and context-based methods are highlighted. It discusses how methods such as inductive learning, task-based learning and interactive activities affect students' correct use of articles in real-world communication. In conclusion, it is stated that contextual and communicative approaches are more effective for functional mastery of the article and increase both grammatical accuracy and fluency of the student.

Key words: *article, communicative, interactive activities, to discuss, non-native learners*

Articles occupy a special place in the grammatical system of the English language. Their use indicates the degree of certainty of the object, the level of familiarity between the speaker and the listener. For those who learn English as a foreign language, the correct use of the article creates many difficulties. Among the grammatical categories in teaching English, the topic of the article is of particular complexity for both language learners and teachers.

The article is a noun sign. In English, the fact that some words are nouns is determined by the use of the article in front of them. When a noun is known, a definite article is used in front of it, and when it is unknown, an indefinite article is

used in front of it. Therefore, in English, the article acts as both an indicator and a means of expression of the category of uncertainty and certainty inherent in the noun.

There are words in English that are used both as nouns and verbs. For example, we can give examples of words such as answer, hand, question, etc. When used as a noun, the article must be used in front of them so that it is clear that they are used as nouns, i.e., an answer, a hand, the hand, a question, etc.

The lexical classification of English common nouns into count and noncount nouns is a very important preliminary to correct use of articles. It is a conceptual distinction that accounts for many systematic patterns in article usage. [1, p 273]

The main task of the article in speech is to express the categories of uncertainty and certainty inherent in the noun. [5, p 293]

It should be noted that common nouns in English are divided into various groups, which, as well as differing in a number of other characteristics, also differ from each other in their use with the article. That is why the issue of the use of nouns included in these groups with the article is studied separately.

The article presents the student with one of the most difficult and intricate problems of language structure. [3, p 49]

Despite the fact that many studies have been conducted on articles, there are still controversial issues in this area.

Since the correct use of articles varies depending on the context, whether the noun is counted or not, the level of certainty, and the speaker's intention, their acquisition requires a long-term and systematic approach. For this reason, the joint application of both grammatical explanation and communicative contexts is necessary when teaching articles.

Articles are understandably problematic from a cross-linguistic perspective: most Asian and Slavic languages and many African languages have no articles. Even those languages that do have articles or article-like morphemes often use these morphemes in ways that differ from English. [1, p. 271] For this reason, the application of new, communicative and contextual approaches to teaching articles, along with traditional methods, is relevant.

In traditional teaching methods, article rules are presented to the student and memorized with sample sentences based on translation. However, this method does not ensure that the student actively uses the language. The methodological approaches that are considered more effective in modern times are as follows.

1. Communicative approach: In order for these activities to be truly communicative, it was suggested from the very beginning, students should have a desire to communicate something. [2, p 69]

Articles are used in conversational practice, stimulating students' use in real communication situations. For example, role-playing tasks and daily life scenes are created and students are asked to construct sentences using articles correctly, so that students understand how important the use of the article is in these sentences.

2. Contextual learning: Articles are taught within the text. Students analyze the purpose for which articles are used in the texts they read or listen to. For example, such a text is given and they are asked to explain the reason for which article is used

or not used in this text for which purposes. Kite is a toy made of a paper that you fly in the air. The earliest written history of kite flying was about 200 B.C. when the Chinese General Han Hsin of the Han Dynasty flew a kite over the walls of the cities he was attacking.

3. Inductive method: The student is guaranteed to deduce the rule based on the presented examples without the teacher saying it. This method helps in the functional acquisition of the article. For example, I have a dog. The dog is barking now. or I bought a book yesterday. I want to give the book for you to read.

4. Task-based approach: Task-based learning makes the performance of meaningful tasks central to the learning process. Instead of a language structure or function to be learned, students are presented with a task they have to perform or a problem they have to solve. [2, p. 71]

Through tasks based on real language materials, students learn the authentic use of articles. This method practically shows how the article changes depending on the context. For example, the teacher asks. What is it? - It is a book. What color is the book? - The book is red.

5. Interactive tools. Multimedia, online platforms and games not only increase the interest of students, but also teach the use of the article in a fun way.

During the interactive method of teaching the article, the teacher hangs a picture on the board and asks the students to describe the picture using the indefinite article. Then, the objects in the picture are described using the definite article. Examples of this type of task strengthen both visual memory and communicative skills and teach the functional use of the article.

Teaching the article can be made more functional and user-oriented with modern methods. Context-based and communicative methods develop both grammatical and practical skills of the student. Modern pedagogical approaches give the teacher the function of not only providing knowledge, but also organizing language use.

LITERATURE

1. Celce-Murcia, M., Larsen-Freeman, D. The Grammar Book: An ESL/EFL Teacher's Course, 1999.
2. Harmer J. The Practice of English Language Teaching. Longman, 2007.
3. Ilyish B., The Structure of Modern English, Leningrad 1971.
4. Mammadova G., English Grammar Rules and Exercises. Baku, 2025.
5. Musayev O., Huseynov A., Hadjiyev E., Contemporary English Grammar, 2013.
6. Mahmudova Sh, A. Intensive Grammar in Contrast. Baku. 2024, 400 p.
7. Richards J. C., & Rodgers T.S. Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching. Cambridge University Press. 2014.
8. Swan M. Practical English Usage. Oxford University Press. 2005.
9. <https://owl.purdue.edu> > owl
10. <https://learnenglish.britishcouncil.org> > ...

TALABALAR UCHUN INGLIZ TILI O‘QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI VA YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR

Karimova Sevara Gulamovna,
sevaraxonkarimova12@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini talabalar uchun samarali o‘qitishda qo‘llanilayotgan zamonaviy metodlar va yangi pedagogik texnologiyalar tahlil qilingan. Xususan, kommunikativ yondashuv, mazmun va til integratsiyasi asosida o‘qitish, topshiriq asosida o‘qitish, aralash ta‘lim va loyiha asosida o‘qitish kabi metodlarning afzalliklari yoritilgan. Shuningdek, multimedia vositalari, mobil ilovalar, virtual muhit, gamifikatsiya va sun‘iy intellekt dasturlaridan foydalanish imkoniyatlari ko‘rib chiqiladi. Maqola ta‘lim jarayonida talabalarni faol ishtirokchi sifatida shakllantirish, ularning nutqiy kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish va mustaqil ta‘lim olish malakalarini kuchaytirish zarurligini asoslaydi.

Kalit so‘zlar: ingliz tili, zamonaviy metodlar, pedagogik texnologiyalar, kommunikativ yondashuv, mazmun va til integratsiyasi, topshiriq asosida o‘qitish, aralash ta‘lim, loyiha asosida o‘qitish, gamifikatsiya, raqamli ta‘lim.

Abstract. This article analyzes modern methods and new pedagogical technologies applied in teaching English to students effectively. In particular, the advantages of communicative approach, content and language integrated learning, task-based learning, blended learning, and project-based learning are highlighted. In addition, the use of multimedia tools, mobile applications, virtual environments, gamification, and artificial intelligence programs is discussed. The article substantiates the importance of shaping students as active participants in the learning process, developing their communicative competence, and strengthening their independent learning skills.

Keywords: English language, modern methods, pedagogical technologies, communicative approach, content and language integrated learning, task-based learning, blended learning, project-based learning, gamification, digital education.

Globalashuv davrida ingliz tili xalqaro muloqot va axborot almashishning eng muhim vositasiga aylandi. Bugungi kunda oliy ta‘lim muassasalarida talabalar uchun ingliz tilini o‘qitish jarayoni grammatik bilimlarni o‘zlashtirish bilangina cheklanmaydi. Undan tashqari, talabalarni erkin muloqotga kirisha olish, kasbiy faoliyatda ingliz tilidan foydalana olish, mustaqil bilim olish va ijodiy fikrlash ko‘nikmalariga ega bo‘lishga yo‘naltirilmoqda. Shu sababli ingliz tili ta‘limida zamonaviy metodlar va yangi pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish ta‘lim samaradorligini oshirishning muhim omillaridan biri hisoblanadi.

Ingliz tili o‘qitishda kommunikativ va interaktiv metodlar tobora keng qo‘llanilmoqda. Kommunikativ yondashuv talabalarni faol muloqot jarayoniga jalb etadi. Mashg‘ulotlarda suhbat, munozara, rol o‘ynash va juftliklarda ishlash metodlari qo‘llaniladi. Mazmun va til integratsiyasi asosida o‘qitish yondashuvi esa tilni boshqa fanlar bilan uyg‘unlashtirilgan holda o‘qitishni nazarda tutadi. Bu orqali talabalar nafaqat tilni, balki sohaga oid bilimlarni ham ingliz tilida egallaydilar. Topshiriq asosida o‘qitish usuli mashg‘ulotlarni amaliy topshiriqlar asosida tashkil etib,

talabalarda tilni hayotiy vaziyatlarda qo'llash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi. Aralash ta'lim metodida esa an'anaviy darslar bilan onlayn mashg'ulotlar uyg'unlashtiriladi va bu talabalarning qulay hamda samarali o'rganishini ta'minlaydi. Loyiha asosida o'qitish orqali talabalar ijodiy loyihalar ishlab chiqib, ingliz tilidan faol foydalanadilar, hamkorlik va mustaqil ishlash ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradilar.

Zamonaviy metodlarni samarali qo'llash uchun o'qituvchilardan yangicha pedagogik yondashuvlar, texnologiyadan foydalanish madaniyati va didaktik kompetensiya talab etiladi. Masalan, o'qituvchi nafaqat bilim beruvchi, balki talabaning til o'rganish jarayonini boshqaruvchi, yo'naltiruvchi va rag'batlantiruvchi shaxsga aylanadi. Shu bilan birga, darslarni talabalarning kasbiy ehtiyojlariga moslashtirish, ularning shaxsiy qiziqishlari va bilim darajalarini hisobga olish zarur. Til o'rganishda differensial yondashuvni joriy qilish, ya'ni har bir talabaga individual topshiriqlar va mashqlar taqdim etish ham samarali natija beradi.

So'nggi yillarda ingliz tili ta'limida raqamli texnologiyalar keng joriy qilinmoqda. Multimedia vositalari darslarni qiziqarli qiladi va eslab qolishni osonlashtiradi. Mobil ilovalar, xususan Kahoot, Quizlet va Memrise talabalarni mustaqil mashg'ulotlarga jalb etadi. Virtual va kengaytirilgan haqiqat texnologiyalari esa til o'rganishda sun'iy muhit yaratib, talabalarni muloqotga undaydi. Gamifikatsiya dars jarayonini o'yin shaklida tashkil qilib, talabalarni faol ishtirok etishga majbur qiladi. Onlayn platformalar – Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Padlet – masofaviy ta'lim imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi. Sun'iy intellekt vositalari, jumladan ChatGPT va Grammarly, yozma va og'zaki nutqni rivojlantirishda yordamchi sifatida xizmat qiladi.

Shuningdek, talabalarni ingliz tili o'rganishga qiziqtirishda madaniyatlararo muloqot kompetensiyasini shakllantirish ham muhimdir. Tilni o'rganish jarayonida ingliz tilida so'zlashuvchi mamlakatlarning madaniyati, qadriyatlarini, turmush tarzi bilan tanishish talabalar uchun motivatsion omil bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Shu bois darslarda autentik materiallar – ingliz tilidagi maqolalar, filmlar, podkastlar, nutqlar va intervyularni qo'llash samarali hisoblanadi.

Zamonaviy metodlar va texnologiyalarni qo'llashning bir qator afzalliklari mavjud. Avvalo, talabalar passiv tinglovchi emas, balki faol ishtirokchi sifatida shakllanadi. Mustaqil ta'lim olish va o'zini rivojlantirish ko'nikmalari rivojlanadi. Nutqiy kompetensiya kuchayadi, kasbiy tayyorgarlik oshadi. Talabalarning motivatsiyasi va til o'rganishga qiziqishi ortadi, axborot texnologiyalaridan samarali foydalanish malakalari shakllanadi. Eng muhimi, bunday metodlar ta'lim jarayonini shaxsga yo'naltirilgan, zamon talabalariga mos va ijodiy yondashuv asosida tashkil etishga imkon beradi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, ingliz tilini o'qitishda zamonaviy metodlar va yangi pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish ta'lim samaradorligini sezilarli darajada oshiradi. Bu esa talabalarni xalqaro miqyosda raqobatbardosh mutaxassislar sifatida tayyorlashga xizmat qiladi. Shu bois o'qituvchilar dars jarayonida innovatsion yondashuvlardan faol foydalanishlari, darslarni shaxsga yo'naltirilgan tarzda tashkil etishlari va talabalarning ehtiyojlariga mos metodlarni tanlashlari muhimdir.

Adabiyotlar

1. Krashen, S. D. (1982). Principles and practice in second language acquisition. Pergamon Press.
2. Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. (2014). Approaches and methods in language teaching (3rd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
3. Harmer, J. (2007). The practice of English language teaching (4th ed.). Pearson Education.
4. Brown, H. D. (2001). Teaching by principles: An interactive approach to language pedagogy (2nd ed.). Longman.
5. Coyle, D., Hood, P., & Marsh, D. (2010). CLIL: Content and language integrated learning. Cambridge University Press.
6. Larsen-Freeman, D., & Anderson, M. (2011). Techniques and principles in language teaching (3rd ed.). Oxford University Press.
7. Prensky, M. (2001). Digital game-based learning. McGraw-Hill.
8. Warschauer, M., & Kern, R. (2000). Network-based language teaching: Concepts and practice. Cambridge University Press.
9. Mirziyoyev, Sh. M. (2021). Yangi O‘zbekiston – yangi ta’lim konsepsiyasi asosida oliy ta’limni rivojlantirish strategiyasi. Toshkent.
10. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasi. (2021). Xorijiy tillarni o‘qitish tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida Qaror. Toshkent.

TURKIY ASARLARDAGI MAQOL VA MATALLARNING BADIY NUTQNI IFODALI QILISHDAGI ROLI

Raximova Sulurxan Djumaniyazovna,
UrDPI Filologiya va tarix fakulteti “O‘zbek va rus tili
adabiyoti “ kafedrası v.b.dotsenti, (PhD).
sulurrahimova@gmail.com <tel:+998904381658>

Annotatsiya: Maqollar xalq og‘zaki ijodi janri. O‘z xususiyati bilan o‘zbek tilining ajralmas bir bo‘lagi hisoblanadi. Ayrim maqollarning kelib chiqish tarixi uzoq tarixlarga borib taqaladi va insonlarning yashagan davri, osha paytda qamrab turgan muhit, davr mentaliteti, dunyoqarashlari ham ahamiyatlidir. Ushbu maqolada maqol va matallarning xalq so‘zlashuv hayotidagi ahamiyati, uning ijodkorlar asarlaridagi tutgan o‘rni haqida fikr yuritiladi. Shuningdek, leksikologiyaning barqaror til birliklari bilan chambarchas bog‘liq ekanligi ko‘rsatib o‘tiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Leksikologiya, maqol, ibora estetik tuyg‘u. Navoiyning asarida ishlatilgan maqol matallarning roli, funksiyalari va didaktik ahamiyati yoritilgan.

Аннотация: Пословицы – жанр устного народного творчества. По своей природе они являются неотъемлемой частью узбекского языка. История происхождения некоторых пословиц восходит к глубокой древности, при этом важны эпоха, в которой жил народ, царящая в то время обстановка, менталитет эпохи, мировоззрение. В данной статье рассматривается значение пословиц и поговорок в жизни народной речи, их место в произведениях творцов. Показано также, что лексикология тесно связана с устойчивыми языковыми единицами.

Ключевые слова: лексикология, пословица, выражение, эстетическое чувство. Подчеркиваются роль, функции и дидактическое значение пословиц, использованных в произведении Навои.

Abstract: Proverbs are a genre of folk oral creativity. By their nature, they are an integral part of the Uzbek language. The history of the origin of some proverbs goes back to ancient times, and the era in which people lived, the environment prevailing at that time, the mentality of the era, and worldviews are also important. This article discusses the importance of proverbs and sayings in the life of folk speech, their place in the works of creators. It also shows that lexicology is closely related to stable language units.

Keywords: Lexicology, proverb, expression, aesthetic feeling. The role, functions, and didactic significance of proverbs used in Navoi's work are highlighted.

KIRISH.Maqol – xalq og‘zaki ijodi janri; qisqa va lo‘nda, obrazli va obrasiz, grammatik va mantiqiy tugallangan ma’noli hikmatli ibora, chuqur mazmunli. Muayyan aniq shaklga ega Maqollarni “Hayot qomusi”,og‘zaki ensiklopediya o‘ziga xos bir badiiy tarixiy salnoma deyish mumkin.Ular kishilarning aqlini o‘tkirlashtiradi,nutqini ravshan va ta’sirchan qiladi,hayotda to‘g‘ri yo‘lni tanlay bilishga hayotiy jumboq va muammolarni togr‘i yechishga o‘rgatadi.a avlod-ajdodlarning hayotiy tajribalari, jamiyatga munosabati, tarixi, ruhiy holati, etik va estetik tuyg‘ulari, ijobiy fazilatlari mujassamlashgan. Maqollar mavzu jihatdan nihoyatda boy va xilma-xil. Vatan, mehnat, ilm-hunar, do‘stlik, ahillik, donolik, hushyorlik, til va nutq madaniyati, sevgi va muhabbat kabi mavzularda, shuningdek, salbiy hislatlar xususida rang-barang maqollar yaratilgan. Maqol uchun mazmun va shaklning dialektik birligi, ko‘p hollarda qofiyadoshlik, ba‘zan ko‘p ma’nolilik, majoziy ma’nolarga boylik kabi xususiyatlar harakterli. Maqollar ba‘zan matal, zarbulmasal, naql, hikmat, hikmatli so‘z, tanbeh, mashoyixlar so‘zi, hikmatli maqol, donishmandlar so‘zi, otalar so‘zi kabi nomlar bilan ham yuritiladi. Maqollarning ijtimoiy-siyosiy va tarbiyaviy ahamiyati g‘oyat katta. Matalda narsa tasviri, uning harakteristikasi beriladi, maqolda esa to‘la tugallangan fikr-xulosa ifodalanadi.

Alisher Navoiyning asarlari – axloq-tarbiya, ijtimoiy va falsafiy mavzularni o‘z ichiga olgan didaktik asar.Unda ko‘plab maqol-matallar, aforizmlar va hikmatli iboralar mavjud. Ushbu elementlar asarga xalq og‘zaki ijodining go‘zalligi va chuqur ma’naviy mazmunini qo‘shadi Asarda keltirilgan maqollar – “Ko‘p degan ko‘p yengilur, ko‘p yegan ko‘p yiqilur”,ma’lumki, kishilarning jamiyatdagi o‘zaro munosabatlari avvalo so‘z bilan boshlanadi. Xalqimizning boshqa bir maqoli – Adabning boshi – til – bejiz aytilmagan (Qutadg‘u bilik”),“Vafosizda hayo yo‘q, hayosizda vafo yo‘q”, “Tilga ixtiyorsiz, elga e’tiborsiz”, “Chin so‘z mo‘tabar, yaxshi so‘z muxtasar” – bular ijtimoiy-ma’naviy ibratlarni aniq va qisqa ifodalashda xizmat qiladi. Xalq og‘zaki adabiyoti bilan uyg‘unlik: Navoiy bu maqollarni o‘z zamonining ma’naviy talablari va xalq hayotining og‘ir tajribasiga tayangan holda moslashtiradi. Yolg‘on so‘zlik nazmda nomaqbul,yoqimsizlikdir va uning qoyili, unga qoyil qoladiganlar esa ahmoq ,aql dan ozganlardir. So‘z ichraki yolg‘on erur nopisand, Chu nazm etilur qildi dono pisand. Asarning tuzilishi: Xaloyiqning ahvoli, ijtimoiy tabaqalar bo‘yicha tahlil. Yaxshi sifatlar va yomon xislatlar – ularning ta’riflari va

ta'siri. Yaxshilik va yomonlik natijalari. Har bir keltirilgan maqol va matal asarning asosiy mavzulari – axloqiy kamolot, illatlardan qochish, ijtimoiy mas'ullik kabi g'oyalarga asoslanib joylashtirilgan. Ular yosh avlodni to'g'ri yo'ldan adashmaslikka, go'zal fazilatlarni izlashga undaydi. Navoiyning maqol va matallari qisqa, ommabop, mazmunli bo'lishi bilan ham, ta'lim-tarbiya va axloqni shakllantirishda kuchli vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Umuman olganda, Navoiyning "Mahbub-ul-qulub" asarida ishlatilgan maqol-matallar moddiy jihatdan matnni boyitadi, madaniy merosimizga chuqur ildiz otgan xalq hikmatini yangicha ifoda qiladi hamda o'quvchini ma'naviy yetuklik sari yetaklaydi:

Yaxshilik qila olmasang hech bo'lmasa yomonlik qilma;

O't ishi –qovurmoq, Yel ishi-sovurmoq;

Suvning mazasi muz bilan oshning mazasi tuz bilan;

Sihat istasang - ko'p yema, Izzat istasang- ko'p dema;

"Saxovat insoniyat bog'ining hosildor daraxti, balki u daraxtning foydali mevasidir."

– Bu yerda saxovat (saxiylik) odamlar, jamiyat barqarorligining hosili sifatida qaraladi. Shuningdek, bu fazilatdan kelib chiqqan ijobiy natijalar ('meva') muhim ramziy vositalar orqali ochib beriladi. "Saxovatsiz odam yog'insiz bahor bulutiga va hidi yo'q mushk-anbarga o'xshaydi."

– Befoyda matn yoki fazilatsiz insonni hayotiy, ruhiy jihatdan "bo'sh" bir holat sifatida ochib beradi. Bu taqqoslash orqali saxovatning borligi – hayotga lahzali-jazibali lazzat qo'shadi, yo'qligi esa go'yo nafas yo'qdaydir. "Saxovatsiz odamdan ichida gavhari bo'lmagan sadafning farqi yo'q; dursiz sadaf bilan qurib qolgan toshbaqa chanog'ining farqi yo'q."– Bu misollar orqali dursiz (zarky bir zar) zarb buyumlar bilan saxiy bo'lmagan odam o'rtasidagi farqsizligi tasvirlanadi – ig'vogar, go'yo tashqi aks etish bo'lmasa ham, ichki mazmun ham yo'qdir. "Himmat ahlining ixtisosi saxovatdir; bu ulug' sifat pokiza kishilarga xosdir."

– Himmat (qadr) bilan saxovat bir-birini to'ldiradi, ularni faqat ulug' va pokiza kishilarda ko'ramiz – bu esa axloqiy kamolni ko'zda tutadi. "Odam bir badan bo'lsa, himmat uning jonidir; himmatlilardan olam ahli uchun yuz ming sharaf va shukuh yetishadi."

– Himmat – insonning ruhiy yuragi, badiiy ramzi. Uni buzgan odam, jasurlikni yo'qotadi; himmati bor odam esa nafaqat o'z qiyofasiga, balki keng olamga ham shon-shuhrat olib keladi. "Oliyhimmat odam balandparvoz lochindir; behimmat – sichqon ovlovchi kalxatdir."

– Bu misollarda qarama-qarshi sifatlar aniq tasvirlangan: oliyhimmat (yuqori fazilatli) inson balandparvozloq shoh orbiterga o'xshaydi, behimmat (bekar, beqadr) esa past fazilatli, kichik hayvonga – sichqonga – o'xshatiladi. Aqlli odam kelishmovchilik joydan qochar va kelishish muvofiqlik eshigin ochar.

XULOSA. O'ziga ravo tutmaganni do'stiga ravo tutmas. Ehsonsiz boy-yog'insiz bulut. Har kimniki so'zi yolg'on, yolg'oni ochilg'och uyolg'on. Qiymati oz – hurmati oz. "G'azab vaqtida sabr qilmoq – podsholikning yarmini saqlamoqdur" tanbehi orqali Navoiy insoniy fazilatlar orasida sabrning eng kuchli qalqon, hissiy yetuklik mezoni va axloqiy yetuklik belgisi ekanini ko'rsatadi. Bu tanbehni ijtimoiy

hayot, psixologiya, yetakchilik madaniyati, oilaviy munosabatlar, pedagogika va hatto bugungi zamonaviy menejment konsepsiyalariga ham qo‘llash mumkin.

Adabiyotlar

1. Bahodir Qobul. “Mahbub ul-qulub”, “Muhokamat ul lug‘atayn”– Toshkent : G‘.G‘ulom nomidagi nashriyot, 2021-yil.50-200 – betlar
2. Shuhrat Sirojiddinov, Dilnavoz Yusupova, Olimjon Davlatov.Navoiyshunoslik [МАН] Q. 1: darslik / Sh. Sirojiddinov [vaboshq.]. – Тошкент: «Т А М А D U N », 2018. – 520 b.
3. Rashidova Umida Mansurovna.O‘zbek tilidagi somatik iboralarning semantik-pragmatik tahlili (ko‘z, qo‘l va yurak komponentli iboralar misolida). Monografiya. – Samarqand: SamDU nashriyoti, 2023. – 144 bet.
4. Alisher Navoiy asarlarining izohli lug‘ati. – Toshkent.1985-yil

DISLEKSİLİ ÖĞRENCİLERDE OKUMA BECERİSİNİN ARTIRILMASINA YÖNELİK DİLBİLİM YAKLAŞIMLARI

Yazar: Günay Bədəlzadə,

Akademik Unvan: Doktorant, Müəllim

Kurum: Azərbaycan Dövlət Pedaqoji Universiteti, Xüsusi Təhsil Kafedrası

E-posta: gn.badalzade@adpu.edu.az

Özet. Bu çalışma, disleksili öğrencilerin okuma becerilerinin geliştirilmesine yönelik dilbilimsel yaklaşımları incelemektedir. Disleksi, normal veya üstün zekâyâ sahip bireylerde okuma, yazma ve heceleme alanlarında kalıcı güçlüklerle tanımlanan nörogelişimsel bir bozukluktur. Fonolojik farkındalık, morfolojik çözümleme, çok duyulu öğretim ve teknoloji destekli araçların bireyselleştirilmiş eğitim planlarına entegre edilmesi önerilmektedir. Araştırmalar, bu yöntemlerin öğrencilerin yalnızca okuma hızını değil, aynı zamanda anlama ve özgüven düzeylerini de artırdığını göstermektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Disleksi, dilbilim, fonolojik farkındalık, morfoloji, okuma becerisi

Abstract. This study examines linguistics-based approaches to improving reading skills in students with dyslexia. Dyslexia is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by persistent difficulties in reading, writing, and spelling, despite normal or above-average intelligence. Research indicates that phonological awareness training, morphological analysis, multisensory teaching, and technology-supported tools significantly improve reading fluency, comprehension, and self-confidence. The study recommends integrating these approaches into individualized education plans for sustainable outcomes.

Keywords: Dyslexia, linguistics, phonological awareness, morphology, reading skills

1. Giriş

Disleksi, okul çağı çocuklarının yaklaşık %5–10’unu etkileyen bir öğrenme güçlüğüdür [Snowling & Hulme, 2012, s. 27]. Normal veya yüksek zekâ düzeyine sahip olmasına rağmen disleksili bireyler okuma ve yazma süreçlerinde kalıcı

güçlükler yaşar. Bu durum akademik başarıyı, özgüveni ve sosyal uyumu olumsuz etkiler.

Son yıllarda, disleksinin yalnızca pedagojik değil, aynı zamanda dilbilimsel bir problem olarak ele alınması gerektiği vurgulanmaktadır. Özellikle fonolojik farkındalık eksiklikleri, hızlı adlandırma yetersizlikleri [Wolf & Bowers, 1999, s. 417] ve ortografik kodlamadaki zayıflıklar [Ehri, 2014, s. 8] temel nedenler arasında görülmektedir. Rus araştırmacılar da ses–harf eşleşmesi ve morfolojik çözümlemedeki zorluklara dikkat çekmiştir [Kornev, 2003, s. 55; Dorofeeva, 2017, s. 190].

Bu bağlamda, dilbilimsel yaklaşımlar fonolojik, morfolojik ve çok duyulu yöntemlerin bir arada uygulanmasıyla disleksili öğrencilerin okuma becerilerinin artırılmasında etkili araçlar olarak öne çıkmaktadır.

2. Kuramsal Çerçeve ve Literatür

Dilbilim, dilin ses, biçim, anlam ve yapı boyutlarını inceleyen bilim dalıdır. Disleksili öğrencilerde okuma gücünü çoğunlukla fonolojik işleme eksiklikleri ile açıklanmaktadır [Snowling & Hulme, 2012, s. 31]. Ehri'nin ortografik haritalama modeli, kelimelerin belleğe yerleşmesinde ses–harf ilişkilerinin önemini vurgular [Ehri, 2014, s. 12].

Wolf ve Bowers'ın çift eksiklik hipotezi ise, fonolojik farkındalık ve hızlı adlandırma becerilerindeki yetersizliklerin birlikte okuma performansını sınırladığını ileri sürer [Wolf & Bowers, 1999, s. 419].

Rus araştırmacılar Kornev [2003, s. 61] ve Dorofeeva [2017, s. 195] disleksinin psikolinguistik temellerine odaklanarak, fonolojik ve morfolojik becerilerin birlikte ele alınmasının önemine dikkat çekmiştir. Carlisle [2000, s. 172] ve Melloni [2022, s. 4] morfem tanıma çalışmalarının okuma anlama üzerinde olumlu etkilerini göstermiştir.

Bu bulgular, disleksili öğrenciler için geliştirilen müdahalelerde dilbilimsel yaklaşımların merkezi rolünü ortaya koymaktadır.

3. Yöntem ve Uygulama Önerileri

Disleksili öğrencilerde okuma becerilerini geliştirmek için aşağıdaki yöntemler önerilmektedir:

1. **Fonolojik Farkındalık Eğitimi:** Ses–harf eşleştirme, heceleme ve fonem ayrıştırma etkinlikleri okuma hızını ve doğruluğunu artırır [Snowling & Hulme, 2012, s. 34].

2. **Morfolojik Çözümleme:** Kök–ek çalışmaları, sözcük bilgisi ve okuduğunu anlama becerilerini destekler [Carlisle, 2000, s. 174; Mendes, 2024, s. 126].

3. **Çok Duyulu Öğretim:** Görsel, işitsel ve kinestetik kanalların birlikte kullanılması öğrenmenin kalıcılığını artırır [Birsh & Carreker, 2018, s. 89].

4. **Teknoloji Destekli Araçlar:** Sesli kitaplar ve dijital okuma uygulamaları erişilebilirliği artırır [Romanovska, 2021, s. 15].

5. **Bireyselleştirilmiş Eğitim Planı (BEP):** Öğrencinin güçlü ve zayıf yönlerine göre planlanan destekler başarıyı artırır [Kornev & Ishimova, 2010, s. 72].

4. Tartışma

Dilbilimsel yaklaşımlar, disleksili öğrencilerin yalnızca okuma hızını değil, aynı zamanda anlamlandırma, sözcük dağarcığı ve özgüvenini de geliştirmektedir. Fonolojik ve morfolojik yaklaşımların birlikte uygulanması, okuma becerilerinde kalıcı gelişmeler sağlamaktadır [Dorofeeva, 2017, s. 197].

Çok duyulu öğretim, öğrenmeyi desteklemekte ancak tek başına yeterli olmamaktadır. Fonolojik ve morfolojik eğitimle desteklendiğinde etkisi artmaktadır [Birsh & Carreker, 2018, s. 93]. Ayrıca teknoloji destekli araçlar, öğrencilerin motivasyonunu artırarak öğrenme sürecini kolaylaştırmaktadır [Romanovska, 2021, s. 19].

5. Sonuç ve Öneriler

Çalışmanın bulguları, dilbilimsel yaklaşımların disleksili öğrencilerde okuma becerilerini artırmada etkili olduğunu göstermektedir.

Öneriler:

- Öğretmen yetiştirme programlarına fonoloji ve morfoloji dersleri eklenmelidir.
- Disleksili öğrenciler için bireyselleştirilmiş eğitim planlarında dilbilimsel etkinliklere yer verilmelidir.
- Çok duyulu yöntemler günlük öğretime entegre edilmelidir.
- Aileler evde uygulanabilecek dil etkinlikleri ile sürece dâhil edilmelidir.
- Teknoloji destekli materyaller düzenli kullanılmalıdır.

Sonuç olarak, dilbilimsel temelli stratejiler disleksili öğrencilerin okuma hızını, anlam düzeyini ve motivasyonunu artırarak akademik ve sosyal başarılarına katkı sağlamaktadır.

Kaynakça

1. Birsh, J., & Carreker, S. (2018). Multisensory teaching of basic language skills. Baltimore: Brookes.
2. Carlisle, J. (2000). Awareness of the structure and meaning of morphologically complex words. *Reading and Writing*, 12(3), 169–190.
3. Dorofeeva, S. (2017). Linguistic aspects of dyslexia and dysgraphia correction. *Voprosy Psikholingvistiki*, 3(33), 184–201.
4. Ehri, L. (2014). Orthographic mapping in the acquisition of sight word reading. *Scientific Studies of Reading*, 18(1), 5–21.
5. Kornev, A. (2003). *Narusheniya chteniya i pis'ma u detey*. Saint Petersburg: Rech.
6. Kornev, A., & Ishimova, O. (2010). *Metodika diagnostiki disleksii u detey*. Saint Petersburg.
7. Melloni, C., Barca, L., & Burani, C. (2022). Morphological awareness in dyslexia. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 1–12.
8. Mendes, B. (2024). Effects of morphological awareness intervention. *Journal of Research in Reading*, 47(2), 123–140.
9. Romanovska, L. (2021). Technology-based support for students with dyslexia. *Education Today*, 12(4), 12–21.

10. Snowling, M., & Hulme, C. (2012). Interventions for children's literacy difficulties. *IJLCD*, 47(1), 27–34.

11. Wolf, M., & Bowers, P. (1999). The double-deficit hypothesis. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 91(3), 415–438.

FAN O'QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI VA YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR

To'rayeva Maftuna Abdiraim qizi,
Samarqand davlat chet tillar instituti magistranti
maftunaturayeva.uz@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada fan o'qitishning eng so'ngi zamonaviy usullari va yangi pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ta'lim jarayonidagi ahamiyati va afzalliklari, ularning mazmun- mohiyati haqida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Texnologiya, ta'lim, pedagogik, innovatsion texnologiya, zamonaviy o'qitish.

Abstract. This article presents information about the latest modern methods of teaching science and the importance and advantages of using new pedagogical technologies in the educational process, as well as their content and essence.

Keywords: Technology, education, pedagogy, innovative technology, modern teaching.

Kirish. Bugungi kunda mamlakatimizda amalga oshiralayotgan tub o'zgarishlar, ta'lim tizimida ham chuqur islohotlar olib borishga zamin yasadi. Ta'lim jarayonini jahon andozalariga mos ravishda qayta tashkil etish va yanada takomillashtirishga kirishildi. Raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda o'qitish tizimini zamonaviy usullar va pedagogik modellar yordamida boyitish, o'quvchi yoshlarning ijodiy va mustaqil faoliyatlarini yanada rivojlantirish uchun qator tadbirlar, Respublikamizda o'tkazilib kelinmoqda. An'anaviy ta'limdan farqli ravishda, ta'lim tizimida innovatsion metodlardan, foydalanish, va bu jarayonni isloh qilish davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biri bo'lib kelmoqda.

Asosiy qism. Yuqorida ta'kidlab o'tganimizdek, ma'lum bir fanni o'qitish jarayonida zamonaviy usullardan va pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida va oliy ta'lim tizimida tobora ommalashib bormoqda. Darhaqiqat, keng dunyoqarashli, bilimli kelajak avlodni o'qitish uchun, pedagoglardan dars jarayonlarida yangicha metodlardan foydalanishni talab qiladi va chuqur mas'uliyat yuklaydi.

Jaxon ta'lim standartlariga mos va fan o'qitishning zamonaviy usullari va pedagogik texnologiyalariga quyidagilar misol bo'la oladi:

- Aralash ta'lim – o'rganuvchilar uylarida video darsliklar yordamida yangi mavzuni mustqail ko'rib o'rganishadi, sinf xonasida esa qayta takrorlab , amaliyotda tatbiq etishadi.

- Teskari ta'lim modeli – o'quvchilar kerakli bilimni uyda mustaqil o'zlashtirishadi, dars vaqtida esa faol o'quv faoliyati bilan shug'ullanadilar.

- Ta'limni o'yinlashtirish – bu o'quv muhitida video o'yin dizayni va o'yin elementlaridan foydalangan holda talabalarni rag'batlantirishga qaratilgan ta'lim yondashuvidir.

- Kooperativ ta'lim – bu o'qituvchining rahbarligi ostida umumiy ta'lim maqsadiga erishish uchun talabalar kichik guruhlarda ishlaydigan o'qitish usuli.

- Loyihaga asoslangan ta'lim – muammoni hal qilish, qaror qabul qilish va savol – javob ko'nikmalaridan foydalangan holda real muammolar va qiyinchiliklarga qaratilgan o'qitish uslubi hisoblanadi.

- So'rovga asoslanga ta'lim modeli – yuqori darajadagi savollar orqali o'quvchilarni jalb qiladigan o'quv jarayonidir. Bu o'quvchilarni muammoni yechish va tajriba asosida o'rganishga undaydigan ta'limga yondashuv texnologiyasi hisoblanadi.

- Krossover o'qitish – bu model orqali o'quvchilar o'z bilimlarini darsdan tashqari bo'lgan norasmiy o'quv muhitlari orqali mustahkamlashadi.

Ushbu innovatsion metodlardan foydalanish ilm-fan o'rganuvchilariga qator imkoniyatlar beradi:

- dars samaradorligini oshirish;
- mustaqil o'rganish ko'nikmasini shakllantirish;
- tanqidiy fikrlash;
- o'qituvchi va o'quvchi orasidagi munosabatni yaxshilash;
- o'rganilgan bilimlarni amaliyotda erkin qo'llay olish;

Fanni zamonaviy usullar va pedagogik texnologiyalar yordamida o'qitish ta'lim samaradorligini oshiribgina qolmay, ta'lim tizimini modernizatsiyalashga ham o'z hissani qo'shadi.

Xulosa va takliflar. Yuksak ma'naviyatli, bilimli kadrlarni tayyorlashda bizga an'anaviy ta'limdan bir muncha yiroq bo'lish, dars jarayonini zamonaviy usullar, raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda tashkillashtirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Shuningdek, ushbu modellarni ta'lim tizimida qo'llash, ta'lim samaradorligini sezilarli darajada o'sishiga yordam beradi. Zamonaviy jamiyatning barcha jabhalarida raqamlashtirish va innovatsion texnologiyalar asosiy o'rin egallayotgan bir paytda, ta'limda zamonaviy usullardan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiq hisoblanadi.

Adabiyotlar

1. Xolmirov B. O'quv jarayonini teskari sinf (flipped classroom) texnologiyasi asosida takomillashtirish. Metodik qo'llanma. –T.: “Yetakchi nashriyoti”, 2024. – 32 b.

2. **Xamrayeva. N.** Fanlarni o'qitishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarning amaliyotdagi tadbiqi. “ Ilmiy ommaviy maqolalar”, 2023. –6 b.

3. Belozertsev, E.P. Kasbiy ta'lim pedagogikasi: darslik / E.P. Belozertsev, A.D. Goneev, A.G. Pashkov, ed. V. A. Slastenin, 4-nashr, akademiyasi, 2008. – 368 b

4. Ro'ziyeva D., Usmonboyeva M., Holiqova Z. Interfaol metodlar: mohiyati va qo'llanishi / metodik qo'llanma. – Toshkent: Nizomiy nomidagi TDPU nashriyoti, 2013. – 136 b.

5. Olloqulova F. Tadqiqotchilik faoliyatini shakllantirishning psixologik-pedagogik tavsifi. Tadqiqotlar jahon ilmiy metodik jurnal. 6-son 2-to'plam yanvar 2023. 336-339-b.

6. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ta-limda-innovatsion-texnologiyalarning-orni>

7. https://tsuull.uz/sites/default/files/14.innovatsion_texnologiyalarning_talim_sohasidagi_orni.pdf

NEW THEORETICAL APPROACHES AND MODELS IN TEACHER PREPARATION

MÜƏLLİM HAZIRLIĞINDA YENİ NƏZƏRİ YANAŞMALAR VƏ MODELLƏRİ

Gunel Mahammad Mammadova,

AZERBAIJAN STATE PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITY

FACULTY OF PRIMARY EDUCATION

THE TEACHER OF DEPARTMENT OF PRIMARY EDUCATION

PEDAGOGY

BAKU, AZERBAIJAN

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6248-9265>

gunelmemmedova2806@gmail.com

055 912 32 12

Abstract. The most relevant issue in an ideal education system is the model of teacher preparation. Although technological innovations and teaching methods have developed in the field of education, teachers remain the main determining subjects and leading elements of the system. Teaching is primarily a specialized field of practice based on human relations and quality communication. As such, the teaching profession is an activity that constantly requires innovation, development, and progress, and it influences all areas of society. For this reason, teachers should be regarded as individuals who, together with students, embark on a journey of learning, share knowledge and skills, discover talents, motivate and guide, and at the same time serve as role models and leaders for society. From this perspective, it is not appropriate to limit the teacher preparation process to certain years. The model presented in this article is limited to the actual 8-year period covering secondary school and university education (4+4), and also envisions continuous innovation and development. Teaching, as a profession requiring dedication, is not static, but a continuous and committed activity. The teacher preparation model discussed in this article is presented as a model that can be applied across the Turkic World and is proposed as an exemplary model consisting of a 10-stage process.

Keywords: Education, Teaching, Teacher, Training, Model.

Xülasə

İdeal təhsil sistemində ən aktual məsələ müəllim hazırlığı modelidir. Təhsil sahəsində inkişaf edən texnoloji yeniliklər və tədris metodları mövcud olsa da, müəllimlər hələ də sistemin əsas təyinedici subyektləri və aparıcı elementləridir.

Tədris, ilk növbədə, insan münasibətlərinə və keyfiyyətli ünsiyyətə əsaslanan ixtisaslaşmış bir təcrübə sahəsidir. Belə ki, müəllimlik daim yenilik, inkişaf və tərəqqi tələb edən bir fəaliyyət sahəsi olaraq cəmiyyətin bütün sahələrinə təsir göstərir. Bu səbəbdən də müəllimlər şagirdləri ilə bərabər öyrənmə səyahətinə çıxan, bilik və bacarıqlarını paylaşan, istedadları kəşf edən, motivasiya edən və istiqamətləndirən, eyni zamanda cəmiyyət üçün nümunə və lider kimi xidmət edən fərdlər hesab olunmalıdır. Bu baxımdan müəllim hazırlığı prosesini müəyyən illərlə məhdudlaşdırmaq məqsədəuyğun deyil. Məqalədə təqdim olunan model yalnız orta məktəb və universitet təhsilini (4+4) əhatə edən səkkiz illik faktiki təhsil dövrü ilə məhdudlaşmır, həm də davamlı innovasiya və inkişafı nəzərdə tutur. Müəllimlik fədakarlıq peşəsi olmaqla yanaşı, statik deyil, daimi öhdəlik tələb edən bir fəaliyyətdir. Bu məqalədə müzakirə olunan müəllim hazırlığı modeli bütün Türk Dünyasında tətbiq oluna biləcək nümunəvi bir model kimi təqdim olunur və 10 mərhələdən ibarət bir prosesi ehtiva edir.

Açar sözlər: Təhsil, Tədris, Müəllim, Təlim, Model.

Introduction

The main element and leading subject of the education system is undoubtedly teachers. The teacher preparation process is considered one of the most crucial determinants of a well-planned education system. This is because the majority of studies related to education are directly connected to the teacher training system. Considering the relevance of this topic, various research, discussions, and theoretical-practical explorations in this direction continue. It becomes clear that solving the issue of teacher preparation is a top priority on the path to an ideal education and teaching system. To evaluate this issue objectively, it is first necessary to clearly identify expectations from teachers and to define the concept of “teacher” accurately [1, p.116-117]. Teaching, as a central component of educational activity, is a unique field that constantly requires renewal, freshness, and development. Since teachers are pedagogues in all professions and fields of activity, their knowledge and skill levels directly influence the development of society. Therefore, teachers are expected to have high motivation, dedication, and idealism in shaping future generations. At the same time, teachers must pay special attention to their professional growth and always strive to improve themselves. Because to teach, one must first and foremost be willing to learn. For this reason, teachers can be described as dedicated educators who are always open to learning. In other words, the teacher can be explained through the concept of the “learning pedagogue.” Teachers are not only transmitters of knowledge but also those who, along with students, embark on a journey of learning, share their skills, discover talents, motivate, guide, and act as role models and leaders in society. These expectations underline the necessity of new conceptual approaches in teacher training. As a result, the “Learning and Sharing Teaching Approach” may be emphasized as a new theoretical approach [5].

The resolution of teacher preparation stands as the first and most crucial step on the path toward establishing an ideal educational system. Despite ongoing advancements in educational technologies and teaching methodologies, the role of the teacher remains central and indispensable. Both today and in the future, teachers will

continue to serve as the leading, defining agents and active participants within the educational framework. Teaching, fundamentally rooted in human interaction and effective communication, represents a specialized field of professional practice. The instructional process, widely regarded as the core element of educational activity, is inherently dynamic—requiring continuous innovation, growth, and progress. Given that teachers function as pedagogues across all professional and disciplinary domains, their knowledge and competencies play a critical role in shaping societal development. In this regard, teachers must be characterized as lifelong learners—open to change, innovative, and dedicated. They are not merely transmitters of knowledge but active participants in the learning journey alongside their students. Teachers are expected to facilitate learning by sharing knowledge and skills, identifying and nurturing talents, motivating and guiding learners, and simultaneously embodying exemplary and leadership roles within society. Teaching is, above all, a philosophical and ethical vocation; the teacher's core aspiration should be to contribute to the cultivation of human potential. It is therefore inappropriate to constrain the teacher preparation process to fixed timeframes or rigid stages. As demonstrated in our experimental model, the proposed approach encompasses both the eight-year duration of formal secondary and higher education (structured as 4+4 years) and emphasizes a sustained commitment to innovation and professional growth. Teaching, viewed as a profession grounded in dedication, cannot be static; rather, it demands ongoing responsibility and engagement. The “Teacher Preparation Model” presented herein comprises ten stages and outlines a holistic process in which each stage is interrelated and implemented in continuity with the others [2].

Stage I: Teacher Candidacy Selection Examination

Teaching is such a valuable and sensitive profession that it cannot be limited to just a four-year university education. Therefore, it is considered essential that the pedagogical preparation process begin as early as the secondary education level. Based on international pedagogical experience and developments, the re-establishment of teacher training schools should be evaluated as a priority step in this direction.

Secondary school graduates who demonstrate interest in the teaching profession are identified through a special selection examination. Based on the results, successful candidates are admitted to teacher training schools considered equivalent to four years of secondary education. These examinations aim to objectively assess the candidates' personality traits, character qualities, intellectual capacity, and communication skills. Conducting such examinations at the national level is expected to ensure transparency and fairness in the selection process.

Stage II: Teacher Training Schools

In four-year teacher training schools, a special curriculum is implemented that distinguishes students from others. The aim of this program is to ensure the personal and professional development of future teachers, based on the understanding that teaching is not only a profession but also a field of morality and philosophy.

During the first two years of education, emphasis is placed on the emotional development of students, the formation of value systems, enrichment of thinking

styles, behavioral culture, and the strengthening of personality and character traits. This stage gives particular importance to the development of empathy, responsibility, and the internalization of pedagogical ethics in human relations.

In the final two years, the focus shifts to the acquisition of fundamental knowledge related to teaching, including pedagogical and psychological sciences, as well as the development of competencies in modern educational technologies. This process should support both the moral-philosophical and scientific-technological aspects of the teaching profession in a parallel and integrated manner. Students enrolled in teacher training schools are provided with full scholarships for four years. During this period, they are expected to internalize the exemplary and leadership roles of a teacher and develop a strong sense of belonging and responsibility toward the homeland, nation, state, spiritual-moral values, and national-cultural heritage. Teachers must instill a sense of belonging, responsibility, and respect for values in students even before imparting knowledge and skills. Without these foundational values, future generations may fail to feel loyalty to their country, nation, or state, and will lack the motivation to serve society with dedication.

Stage III: Teacher Selection Exam (University Entrance Exam)

For students who successfully complete four-year teacher training schools, a special Teacher Selection Examination is organized. This exam is a crucial stage in selecting candidates who wish to pursue higher education in pedagogical fields. Graduates of teacher training schools who wish to be admitted to faculties of education are granted additional advantages. Specifically, these graduates receive bonus points in the entrance examination based on their previous academic performance.

This approach encourages students who have set their goal on the teaching profession and who have undergone appropriate training to pursue pedagogical specialties in universities. It promotes a more targeted and prepared pathway for entering the teaching profession.

Stage IV: Faculty of Education

Students who successfully graduate from Teacher Training Schools and are admitted to the Faculty of Education follow a three-stage specialized program.

- First Stage: Covers the first two academic years of the faculty. The focus during this phase is on delivering professional courses directed toward the foundations of educational sciences.

- Second Stage: Implemented in the third year of study. During this phase, students explore the essence of the teaching profession from both global and local perspectives, while deepening their subject-specific knowledge.

- Third Stage: Encompasses the final year of study. Students experiment with new and innovative teaching methods within the faculty and also participate intensively in practical training processes in secondary schools.

The core programs of the Faculty of Education must be structured with 50% pedagogical courses and 50% field-specific courses. The focus of instruction should be on developing pedagogical competence, as well as linguistic and expressive skills. Additionally, special attention is given to students' internships in secondary schools.

Prospective teachers are encouraged to nurture highly intellectual and creative learners. All students enrolled in the Faculty of Education are provided with full scholarships.

Stage V: Teacher Appointment Examination

In order to select teacher candidates with the highest potential from among the graduates who have successfully completed their studies at the Faculty of Education, a Teacher Appointment Examination is conducted. This exam is based on the score threshold determined by the Ministry of Education. Candidates who pass the written phase of the exam proceed to the next stage, which consists of objective and practical oral examinations. The main aim of this stage is not only to assess theoretical knowledge but also to evaluate candidates' pedagogical skills, communication abilities, and creative approaches to the teaching process.

Stage VI: Assessment of Communication and Presentation Skills

During the summer months, candidates' communication and presentation skills must be evaluated face-to-face by a mixed committee comprising representatives of the Ministry of Education, scholars, expert teachers, and parents who have completed training. This assessment is conducted in the provinces and districts designated by the Ministry. The purpose of these practical experiences is to allow candidates to demonstrate their teaching skills in a real classroom environment. Successful candidates are appointed to teaching positions transparently and based on merit.

Stage VII: Probationary Period

The teacher preparation process cannot be limited solely to the university years; prospective teachers must continue to receive support even after graduation. Newly appointed teachers are initially assigned to elementary classes and are provided with the opportunity to engage in classroom observation and practical experience for at least one year. During this period, appropriate time and conditions are provided for teacher candidates to share experiences with expert mentor teachers in the schools where they are initially assigned. At the same time, in order to support their professional development, they are encouraged to stay informed about new publications and are granted special access to teaching materials and books.

Stage VIII: In-Service Training

To ensure the professional development of teachers, expand experience-sharing opportunities, and strengthen the values-based education system, the reorganization of professional development courses is of vital importance. For this purpose, selected teachers should participate in centrally organized, planned training courses and seminars held in retreat centers and professional development institutions under the guidance of experienced educators. Teachers participating in these professional development courses must undergo rigorous assessment at the end of the course. Those who succeed should be rewarded with additional salary benefits and recognition. This approach creates opportunities for teachers' continuous development and enhancement of their professional competencies.

Stage IX: Academic Specialization

It is of particular importance that teachers maintain strong connections with the academic world and engage in scholarly activities, as this contributes significantly to

the future of education. Therefore, teachers should be encouraged to pursue further education at the master's and doctoral levels through various methods and programs, as well as to produce academic outputs. Relevant authorities should support these initiatives promptly and foster the academic development of teachers. Additionally, the currently inactive and suspended National Academy of Education, which operates under the Ministry of Education, should be reactivated to provide opportunities for academic specialization for teachers.

Stage X: Transition to Educational Administration

Teachers who have successfully completed ten years of pedagogical activity are granted the opportunity to voluntarily take an administrative exam within educational institutions. Those who qualify for administrative roles typically serve as educational administrators for the remainder of their professional careers.

Conclusion

The teacher preparation model presented above can be expanded by considering the specific conditions of Turkic republics. This approach not only ensures the formation of generations grounded in shared roots and values, but also creates opportunities for aspiring teachers to teach in various regions across the Turkic world. Furthermore, the proposed model contributes significantly to the integration of the educational systems and the harmonization of pedagogical standards within the.

References

1. Bülent, Y. (2004). Parental sensitivity in students' reading and library usage habits. *Bilgi Dünyası*, 5(2), 115–136.
2. Ertuğrul, Y. (2011). *Human and communication*. Ankara: Akçağ Publications.
3. Ertuğrul, Y. (2017). *Values education (5th ed.)*. Ankara: Akçağ Publications.
4. Kubilay, Y. (2006). A general overview of values education. *Journal of Turkic Studies Research*.
5. Mustafa, A. (2006). Values, their functions and ethics. *Perspective Journal*, 7(19).
6. Ertuğrul, Y., & Oğuzhan, A. (2016). *The idealist teacher*. Ankara: Eysem Publishing.s and ensures the training of future generations based on national values.

UZLUKSIZ TA'LIM TIZIMIDA MORFEMANI O'QITISH MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI

Muratkulov Amanulla Tursunkulovich,

*Guliston davlat universiteti
o'zbek tilshunosligi kafedrasida
katta o'qituvchisi*

Muratkulova Munisa Omonulla qizi,

*Guliston davlat pedagogika instituti
Boshlang'ich ta'lim yo'nalishi 4-bosqich talabasi*

Annotatsiya: Morfemika va uning birligi morfema maktabda boshqa, litseyda boshqa, oliy maktabda yana boshqa o'qitilmoqda, hatto oliy ta'lim yo'nalishlari bo'yicha farqli holatlar kuzatiladi. Ilmiy hayotda hali ta'lim tizimiga kirib bormagan, bulardan ham farq qiluvchi yana bir boshqacha qarashlarga ham duch kelib qolishingiz mumkin. Maqolada morfemaning o'qitish bo'yicha ayrim muammolar va ularning yechimi bayon etilgan

Kalit so'zlar: morfema, morfemika, lisoniy birlik, shakl, so'z shakli.

Abstract. The concept of morphemes and their teaching varies across educational levels: it is taught differently in schools, colleges, lyceums, and higher education institutions, with even more discrepancies observed between different university programs. In academic circles, there are also alternative perspectives that have yet to enter the education system. This article discusses some key issues related to teaching morphemes and suggests possible solutions.

Keywords: morpheme, morphemics, linguistic unit, form, word form.

Biz olib borgan kuzatishlar hozirda uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida lisoniy birliklardan biri bo'lgan morfema turli talqinda o'qitilayotganini ko'rsatdi. Bu esa ana shu talqin-tavsiflar o'quvchi-talabalar, magistrantlar, tinglovchilar ongiga singdirilmoqda deganidir. Talqinlar bir-birini izchil to'ldirib, takomillashtirib borsa, inkor etmasa, ziddiyatlar bo'lmasa, buning hech qanday ziyoni yo'q, aksincha, shunday bo'lishi zarur. Biroq, amaldagi ahvol bunday emas. Morfemika va uning birligi morfema maktabda boshqa, litseyda boshqa, oliy maktabda yana boshqa o'qitilmoqda, hatto oliy ta'lim yo'nalishlari bo'yicha farqli holatlar kuzatiladi. Ilmiy hayotda hali ta'lim tizimiga kirib bormagan, bulardan ham farq qiluvchi yana bir boshqacha qarashlarga ham duch kelib qolishingiz mumkin.

Ilmda shunday bo'lgani yaxshi, chunki u shunaqa maydon: har kim o'z nuqtai nazarini aytishga haqli va har xil qarashlarning bo'lishi odatdagi, tabiiy hol. Fikrlar "jangi"da kimning, qaysi talqinning zo'rligi, kuchi bilinadi. Biroq ta'lim tizimida har xilliklarning bo'lishi ijobiy hol hisoblanmaydi. Chunki bu o'qitishning sifati va samaradorligiga salbiy ta'sir qiladi, hatto unga putur yetkazadi, deyish mumkin. Hozirgi o'zbek tili ta'limi, xususan, morfemalarni o'qitish shunday jarayonni boshdan kechirmoqda. Morfemaning har xil talqinini birgina filologiya va tillarni o'qitish yo'nalishining o'zida, unda foydalanilayotgan o'quv adabiyotlarida ham kuzatish mumkin. Fikrimizni dalillashga harakat qilamiz.

Tadqiqotchi H.Ne'matovning morfema haqidagi qarashlari uning prof. R.Rasulov bilan hamkorlikda e'lon qilingan o'zbek filologiyasi yo'nalishi talabalari uchun mo'ljallangan "Sistem leksikologiya asoslari" o'quv qo'llanmasida ifodalangan. Qo'llanma sistem tilshunoslik yo'nalishidagi dastlabki jiddiy tadqiqot bo'lganligi bilan e'tiborga loyiqdir. Unda tadqiqotchilar til(lison) farqlanishidan kelib chiqib, morfemani odatdagidek, so'zning eng kichik ma'noli qismi maqomidagi nutqiy hodisa emas, balki til(lison) birligi – ongda, til xotiramizda saqlanuvchi tayyor holdagi bo'linmas ma'noli lisoniy birlik sifatida belgilashgan. Boshqacha aytganda, qo'llanmada morfema – tilning eng kichik, ma'noli birligi bo'lib, boshqa ma'noli

qismlarga bo‘linmaydigan lisoniy birlik sifatida talqin qilingan [3]. Bu to‘g‘rimi, noto‘g‘rimi?

Morfemaning an‘anaviy talqinidan jiddiy farq qiluvchi mazkur talqinga A.Hojiyev, umuman olganda, ijobiy baho bergan, uning to‘g‘ri bo‘lganini alohida qayd etgan. “Biroq, – deydi zakiy tilshunos fikrini davom ettirib, – morfemaning, u bilan bog‘liq hodisalarning mohiyati masalasida hozirda ham to‘g‘ri va aniq bir fikrga kelangani yo‘q. Shunday bo‘lishi ham tabiiy. Chunki hozirda o‘ziga xos ma‘noga ega bo‘lgan, boshqa ma‘noli qismlarga bo‘linmaydigan, tayyor holdagi har qanday birlik lisoniy birlik morfema deb qaralyapti... Vaholanki, qayd etilayotgan birliklar o‘z mohiyatiga ko‘ra, ma‘no-vazifasiga ko‘ra bir-biridan tamoman farqlanadi. Binobarin, ularning hammasini lisoniy birlikning bir turi deb baholash to‘g‘ri bo‘lmaydi va ilmiy-nazariy va amaliy nuqtai nazardan hech narsa bermaydi. Aksincha, bu narsa o‘ziga xos xatoliklarning, ortiqcha bahs-munozaralarning yuz berishiga sabab bo‘ladiki, hozirda bunday holatlarning guvohi bo‘lib turibmiz.”[8]

Haqiqatan, mazkur ta‘rif bo‘yicha biz bilgan, xotiramizda tayyor holda saqlanadigan, ma‘no-vazifasi va shakli hammamiz uchun tanish, umumiy va shu bilan birga, majburiy bo‘lgan, ma‘noli qismlarga bo‘linmaydigan aynan qanday va qaysi til birligini morfema deyish kerak, degan savolga aniq javob topib bo‘lmaydi. Demak, bu yerda, birinchi galda, qaysi va qanday birlikni, aynan nimani, qanday ma‘no va vazifa bajaradigan til birligini morfema deyish kerak? degan asosiy masalani muhokama qilib olish, unga aniq, ilmiy asosli javob topish lozim bo‘ladi. Bu masala ilgari ham ko‘tarilgan va morfemaning mohiyati o‘sha davr tilshunosligi nuqtai nazaridan ochib berilgan, unga shu ochilgan mohiyatiga yarasha ta‘rif berilgan, qanday birlik morfema deb atalishi, ya‘ni so‘zning eng kichik ma‘noli qismi morfema [6;8;9] deyilishi lozimligi belgilangan edi (bu ta‘rif, har xil salbiy munosabatlarga qaramasdan, hozirda ham ilmiy va amaliy ahamiyatini yo‘qotgani yo‘q).

Gap shundaki, sistem-struktur tilshunoslikka oid keyingi tadqiqotlarda uning lisoniy birlikligi to‘g‘ri qayd etilgan bo‘lsa-da, unga uning o‘zidan emas, morfemadan boshqa birliklarni ham qamrab oluvchi lingvistik tushunchadan kelib chiqib baho berildi. Natijada til birliklarini aniqlash borasida morfemaning va u bilan bog‘liq boshqa masalalarning, A.Hojiyev ta‘kidlagan va yuqorida ko‘rilgan to‘g‘ri va aniq yechimini topish mumkin bo‘lmagan o‘ta chigal va chalkash vaziyat yuzaga keldi. Bunday chigal har xilliklarga hatto til birliklarini nihoyatda aniq va izchil ta‘riflovchi prof. Sh.Rahmatullayev ham barham bera olmagan ko‘zga tashlanadi. To‘g‘ri, uning morfemaga qarashida jiddiy ijobiy siljishlar bor. U lug‘aviy birliklarni ham morfema doirasiga kiritib yuborgan prof. H.Ne‘matov, R.Rasulovdan farqli o‘laroq, morfemani grammatik ma‘noli birlik sifatida talqin qildi, uning mohiyatini grammatik ma‘noli bo‘linmas lisoniy birliklar qatorida deb bildi: “Morfema til qurilishining leksemadan keyingi asosiy birligi bo‘lib, leksemadan farqli holda grammatik ma‘no ifodalashga xizmat qiladi (yunoncha *morphe* – ‘shakl’)” [4]

Ushbu ta‘rif morfema mohiyatiga ancha yaqin kelganligi bilan xarakterlanadi. Chunki bunda so‘zning o‘zak morfema,leksik(lug‘aviy) morfema deb kelingan lug‘aviy ma‘noli asosi morfema emas, asli lug‘aviy ma‘noli so‘z(leksema)

bo'lgani uchun haqli ravishda morfema doirasidan chiqarilgan. Lekin, baribir, u ham tom ma'nodagi morfemani aniq belgilashga, uni boshqa til birliklaridan farqlanuvchi asosiy ma'no-vazifasini aniq qayd etishga o'zlik qiladi. Chunki so'z yasovchi morfemani shakl yasovchi morfema singari grammatik ma'noli birlik deyish to'g'ri bo'lmaydi. Ta'bir joiz bo'lsa, u so'z yasovchi ma'noga ega. Bunday ma'nolar semantik ma'no emas, funktsional ma'no bo'lib, bevosita anglashilib turmaydi, yashirin holda bo'ladi. Lug'aviy ma'noli asos - leksik birlikka qo'shilishi bilan uning lug'aviy ma'no xarakteridagi, biroq funktsional ma'no ekanligi anglashiladi. Xuddi shu narsa uni grammatik shakl emas, so'z yasashga xizmat qilishida o'z ifodasini topadi va natijada yangi lug'aviy ma'noli so'z yasaladi. Demak, mazkur ta'rif morfemaning ma'nosi, mohiyati bilan bog'liq bir jihatni to'g'ri qayd etib, uni lug'aviy ma'noli asos -so'zdan ajratishga, chegaralashga xizmat qilsa-da, ikkinchi tomonini aniq aks ettirish imkoniyatiga ega emas. Shu sababli bu talqin ham morfemaning to'laqonli ta'rifi bo'la olmadi.

Zero, barcha grammatik ma'noli birliklar ham so'z yasash va so'z shakli yasashga xizmat qilmaydi. Morfema esa xuddi shunday birlik hisoblanadi. Buni akademik A.Hojiev o'z ishlarida qayd qilib o'tadi va shundan kelib chiqib, u morfemani funktsional ma'noli birlik – yasovchi birlik sifatida talqin qildi, uning mohiyati funktsional ma'no-vazifasi bilan belgilani-shini quyidagi ta'rif bilan ilmiy asosda dalillab ham berdi: “Morfema-so'z yasalishi va so'z shaklining yasalishi uchun xizmat qiladigan lisoniy birlik” [10]. Bizningcha, morfemani o'qitish uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida A.Hojiyev ta'rifi asosida olib borilsa, bu boradagi murakkabliklarga, ortiqcha tasnif va tavsiflarga [2;6] o'rin qolmaydi.

Bundan ayon bo'lyaptiki, morfemaning mohiyati maktab darsliklarida ham o'z ifodasini topgan so'zning eng kichik ma'noli qismi bo'lib kelishida emas (bu uning o'z vazifasini bajarib, funktsional ma'nosini namoyon qilib bo'lgandan keyingi holatini ifodalaydi, xolos), balki uning ayni funktsional ma'no-vazifasida – uning yangi so'z yasalishi va so'zshakli hosil qiluvchi vosita sifatida xizmat qilishida – yasovchilik funksiyasida.

Shu sababli A.Hojiyev morfemaning ana shu funktsional ma'nosiga e'tibor qaratdi, morfemaning mohiyatini uning funktsional ma'nosidan, vazifasidan qidirdi va topdi: uni *yasovchi birlik*, *yasovchi vosita* sifatida talqin qildi.

Bu shundan dalolat beradiki, morfema leksemadan farqli o'laroq, sof semantik birlik emas, uning ma'nosi bebosita anglashiladigan, mustaqil faoliyat yuritadigan ma'no sirasiga kirmaydi. Shuning uchun morfemaga sof ma'noviy omilga asoslanib, uni asosiy tavsiflovchi, tasniflovchi belgi sifatida olib, to'g'ri va maqsadga muvofiq ta'rif berib bo'lmaydi. Bizningcha, A.Hojiyev shunday xulosaga kelgan. U morfemani semantik ma'noli birlik deb emas balki funktsional ma'noli birlik deb bildi. Bu tushunchalar bir-biriga yaqin bo'lsa-da, asos e'tibori bilan, mohiyat nuqtai nazaridan farq qiladi. Semantik birlik tom ma'nodagi mustaqil birlik, uning ma'nosi bevosita, boshqa til birliklarisiz ham anglashilaveradi. Shunday xususiyatga ega birliklarnigina aslida ma'noli (semantik) birlik deyish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Aks holda, tovushga zidlab, ma'noli birliklar deyilgan ayrim birliklarning mohiyati

ochilmasligi, chalkashliklar yuzaga kelishi aniq. Morfema muammosi buning yaqqol isboti.

Yuqoridagilarga ko'ra, biz morfemani A.Hojiyev ta'rifi asosida talqin qilish va o'qitish maqsadga muvofiqdir, deb hisoblaymiz. Bu ta'rifda morfemaning tasnifiy mohiyati ham mujassam. U o'z ichida so'z yasovchi va shakl yasovchiga bo'linadi. Aslida har qanday ta'rif xuddi shunday tabiatli bo'lishi lozim. Zero, ta'rif muayyan birlikning o'zigagina xos, uni boshqa birliklardan ajratib turuvchi ma'noviy-vazifaviy tavsifidir.

Adabiyotlar

1. Boduen I.A. Введение в языковедение. – Л.,1913. 14.
2. Nurmonov A. va b. O'zbek tilining nazariy grammatikasi. Morfologiya. – T. 2001. – 31-b.
3. Ne'matov H., Rasulov R. O'zbek tili sistem leksikologiyasi asoslari. – T., 1995.
4. Rahmatullayev SH. Hozirgi adabiy o'zbek tili. – T., 2006.
5. Sayfullayeva R. va b. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili. T., 2009.
6. Tojiyev Y. O'zbek tili morfemikasi. – T.,1992.
7. G'ulomov A. O'zbek tilning morfem lug'ati. – T.1978
8. Xojiev A. Тил қурилишининг асосий бирликлари юзасидан мулоҳазалар// ЎТА.2004, 3-,5- сон,35- б
9. Усмон О., Авизов Б. Ўзбек тили грамматикаси. II бўлим. – Т., 1939 46-48-б.
10. Xojiev A. Ўзбек тили морфологияси, морфемикаси ва сўз ясалишининг назарий масалалари. – Т., 2010

MASTERING DESCRIPTIVE WRITING: FEATURES, TECHNIQUES, AND STEPS TO EVOKE VIVID IMAGERY

Davronova Sevara Ulug'bekovna,
sdavronova450@gmail.com

PhD student at Gulistan State University

Abstract. Descriptive writing is a foundational rhetorical tool that animates discourse by translating abstract concepts into tangible forms. This process allows texts to transcend mere information delivery, fostering a deeper reader connection through sensory engagement. Whether employed in scholarly texts, creative narratives, or scientific reports, descriptive language serves to enhance comprehension and facilitate the effective communication of experiences and ideas.

The art of effective description lies in the selective and strategic use of detail, transforming observation into evocative prose. This is not a simple enumeration of facts but a deliberate orchestration of key sensory inputs to create a vivid and memorable impression. Mastery of this skill involves discerning which details are most impactful and arranging them with precision, often employing rhetorical devices to amplify their effect.

This article examines the principles of compelling descriptive writing. It delineates the characteristics of high-quality descriptive prose, outlines fundamental methodologies for its construction, and presents advanced techniques supported by established rhetorical and literary theory. The objective is to provide a comprehensive framework for developing and refining descriptive ability.

Key words: descriptive writing, sensory engagement, rhetorical devices, figurative language, specificity, observation, tone and mood, revision, embodied cognition

Literature Review

Academic inquiry into descriptive writing is deeply rooted in cognitive psychology and neurolinguistics. Researchers like George Lakoff and Mark Johnson(1980), through their foundational work on conceptual metaphor (e.g., *Metaphors We Live By*), have significantly contributed to our understanding of how abstract concepts are understood through concrete, often sensory-based, experiences. Their theories underscore the idea that description is not merely an external representation but an internal, embodied simulation. Further studies, employing neuroimaging techniques like fMRI, by scholars such as Benjamin Bergen (2012), have provided empirical evidence that reading descriptive language (e.g., "the rough texture of sandpaper" or "a piercing glance") activates the same sensorimotor regions of the brain that would be involved in actually experiencing those sensations. This phenomenon, which is a key component of embodied cognition, posits that our understanding of language is linked to our physical experiences and sensory systems.

The strategic power of description is also a central tenet of rhetorical theory. Classical rhetoricians like Aristotle recognized the importance of *enargeia*—vivid description that brings a scene "before the eyes" of the audience—for persuasion and emotional impact. In contemporary rhetoric, scholars such as Chaim Perelman and Lucie Olbrechts-Tyteca (1969) explored how presence—making an idea vivid and immediate to the audience—is achieved through descriptive techniques. Linguists, including those working within Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) developed by M.A.K. Halliday(1994), analyze how grammatical choices (e.g., transitivity, nominalization, adjectival and adverbial choices) build descriptive meaning and influence reader perception. Rhetorical Structure Theory (RST), developed by William Mann and Sandra Thompson(1988), further analyzes how descriptive passages serve as "satellites," providing crucial context, evidence, or emotional appeal to a "nucleus" or main point, thus contributing to a text's overall coherence and persuasive force. Descriptive conventions are not universal; they are highly dependent on genre, a topic extensively explored by stylistics scholars.

Description is governed by the need for precision and reproducibility. Works by Charles Bazerman (1969) illustrate how scientific communities develop highly specialized descriptive vocabularies and structures to ensure clarity, objectivity, and replicability of research findings. In contrast, descriptive writing in fiction or poetry is often subjective and connotative. Literary critics and theorists from Roman Jakobson (1960) to contemporary narratologists analyze how authors like Virginia Woolf or Gabriel García Márquez use unique descriptive styles to build fictional

worlds, develop character, create specific moods, and evoke emotional responses, often prioritizing aesthetic impact over strict factual accuracy.

These genre-specific applications, analyzed by a diverse range of scholars, demonstrate the versatility of description as a core rhetorical skill, highlighting how a mastery of its principles is essential for effective communication across diverse fields.

2. The Pillars of Vivid Description

The effective use of sensory language is a cornerstone of powerful writing. By appealing to the five senses—sight, sound, smell, taste, and touch—a writer can transform abstract concepts into vivid, concrete experiences for the reader. This is achieved through the deliberate selection of specific nouns and strong verbs, along with precise adjectives that accurately convey a subject's form or texture. Fundamentally, effective description relies on the principle of "showing, not telling." For instance, instead of stating, "The individual was sad," one might write, "Tears traced paths down their dusty cheeks, landing on a worn dress," which allows the reader to embody the emotion directly. Figurative language further enhances descriptive impact by creating unique and lasting images. Similes draw comparisons between dissimilar things using "like" or "as" (e.g., "The sky was like a bruised apple"), while metaphors directly equate one thing to another ("His anger was a roaring fire"). Personification grants human attributes to non-human entities ("The wind whispered secrets through the trees"). These rhetorical devices are instrumental in making prose both memorable and compelling. For maximum impact, every word in a description must be chosen with care. The distinction between a general term like "flower" and a precise one like "velvet-petaled crimson rose" illustrates how specificity elevates a text from functional to engaging. This deliberate word choice clarifies meaning and maintains reader interest.

Writers should avoid clichés and overused phrases in favor of fresh, original language. A "beautiful sunset" is a generic phrase, while a "sky bleeding hues of orange and purple" provides a far stronger and more evocative image. A robust vocabulary is an essential tool for discovering these new expressions. Additionally, effective description is never gratuitous; every detail included should contribute to the overall mood or dominant impression, serving a clear purpose within the text.

The collective effect of a writer's word choices and sentence structure establishes the tone, which is the author's attitude toward their subject. Maintaining a consistent tone is crucial for building reader trust and ensuring a coherent message.

Furthermore, imagery and diction work together to create the mood, or the emotional atmosphere a text evokes in the reader. For example, dark, shadowy images can cultivate a suspenseful or scary mood, whereas bright, soft colors might suggest a peaceful one. The strategic use of language is paramount in eliciting a desired emotional response.

2.1 Building Blocks: An Essential Methodology

1. Observation and Information Gathering: The process begins with active observation. Whether an object, person, or setting is being described, one must first engage with its sensory details. This involves noting colors, sounds, textures, and

other physical properties. For imaginary subjects, thorough research through texts, images, and videos is necessary to accumulate enough data to construct a believable description. The initial phase of note-taking should prioritize the collection of details over polished prose.

2. **Planning and Structuring:** After gathering details, the writer must formulate a dominant impression—the single main idea or feeling the description is meant to convey. The organization of details should support this impression. Common structural approaches include spatial order (e.g., left to right, top to bottom), chronological order (for describing an event), or organizing by importance (from most to least significant detail). The chosen structure should align with the writer's communicative goal.

3. **Drafting with Sensory Details and Figurative Language:** The drafting phase involves weaving sensory observations into sentences without merely listing them. This process integrates sight, sound, smell, taste, and touch naturally into the narrative flow. Figurative language should be deployed judiciously to add flair without overwhelming the text. A few well-placed similes, metaphors, or instances of personification are more effective than an abundance of them.

The impact of a description is directly tied to the precision of its word choice. The use of strong verbs ("scurried" or "dashed" instead of "walked quickly") and vivid adjectives ("the sweet scent of jasmine" instead of "a nice smell") can dramatically elevate prose. A thesaurus is a useful tool, but it is critical to confirm the precise meaning of any new word before use.

The rhythm and pace of writing are controlled by sentence structure. Varying sentence length—mixing short, impactful sentences with longer, more detailed ones—prevents a monotonous cadence and keeps the reader engaged. Subordinate clauses and descriptive phrases can be used to combine ideas and add detail smoothly, avoiding a choppy rhythm. To effectively apply the "show, don't tell" principle, a writer must translate general statements into specific, sensory-rich scenes. For example, instead of stating "The room was messy," one can describe "Clothes lay strewn across the floor, mixed with empty coffee cups and stacks of unanswered mail." Similarly, character emotions can be conveyed through actions and dialogue (e.g., a nervous foot-tapping to show anxiety), allowing the reader to infer a character's state rather than being explicitly told.

2.2. Practical Application and Improvement Strategies

To hone descriptive ability, one can practice "sensory walks," focusing on one sense at a time to train observation. Another effective exercise is to rewrite a weak description, enhancing it with more sensory language and stronger verbs. Writing prompts that focus on specific senses or emotions are also useful for targeted practice. Good descriptive writing is the product of revision. Reading a draft aloud can help a writer identify issues with flow and rhythm. Seeking feedback from peers, mentors, or writing groups provides a crucial external perspective, helping to identify areas of confusion and improve clarity.

Conclusion

Effective descriptive writing is a skill developed through deliberate practice. It involves a systematic process of sensory observation, precise word choice, and thoughtful arrangement of details. Mastery of this craft is achieved through consistent application of a structured approach.

The fundamental process for developing descriptive prose includes several key stages:

Observation: Close attention to sensory details is the foundational step.

Planning: The strategic organization of these details around a central impression is crucial.

Drafting: The use of vivid, sensory-rich language animates the text.

The final stage of refinement involves meticulous editing to select the most impactful vocabulary and vary sentence structure for rhythm and flow. By prioritizing the principle of "showing, not telling," a writer can transform general statements into evocative scenes. The power of vivid description extends beyond mere communication; it forges a profound connection with the reader, stirring emotions and bringing subjects to life. This capacity makes descriptive writing an indispensable tool for anyone seeking to communicate with clarity and power.

References

1. Aristotle. (1991). *On rhetoric: A theory of civic discourse* (G. A. Kennedy, Trans.). Oxford University Press. (Original work from 4th century BCE)
2. Bazerman, C. (1988). *Shaping written knowledge: The genre and activity of the experimental article in science*. University of Wisconsin Press.
3. Bergen, B. K. (2012). *Louder than words: The new science of how the mind makes meaning*. Basic Books.
4. Halliday, M. A. K. (1994). *An introduction to functional grammar* (2nd ed.). Edward Arnold.
5. Jakobson, R. (1960). Linguistics and poetics. In T. A. Sebeok (Ed.), *Style in language* (pp. 350–377). MIT Press.
6. Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors we live by*. University of Chicago Press.
7. Mann, W. C., & Thompson, S. A. (1988). Rhetorical Structure Theory: Toward a functional theory of text organization. *Text – Interdisciplinary Journal for the Study of Discourse*, 8(3), 243–281.
8. Perelman, C., & Olbrechts-Tyteca, L. (1969). *The new rhetoric: A treatise on argumentation* (J. Wilkinson & P. Weaver, Trans.). University of Notre Dame Press. (Original work published 1958)

MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI O‘QUVCHILARDA DISLEKSIYANI ANIQLASH

Qo‘shaqboyeva Sayyoraxon Sarvarbek qizi,
Qo‘qon davlat universiteti tayanch doktoranti
kushakboevas@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. Maqolada disleksiya haqida, uning sabablari, maktab yoshidagi bolalarda disleksiyaga moyilligi bor bo‘lgan o‘quvchilarni aniqlash haqida fikrlar keltiriladi. Shuningdek, disleksiyaning kelib chiqish sabablari, uni aniqlash usullari haqida mulohazalar beriladi. Maktablarda disleksiv bolalar bilan mutaxassislar qanday shug‘ullanishlari kerakligi haqida ayrim tavsiyalar beriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: disleksiya, fonologik ko‘nikma, kognitiv nuqson, look-say usuli, sensomotor nuqson.

Abstract. This article explores the phenomenon of dyslexia, focusing on its underlying causes and the identification of school-aged children who may be at risk of developing this learning difficulty. Particular attention is given to the etiological factors contributing to the manifestation of dyslexia, as well as to contemporary approaches and tools employed for its early detection. Furthermore, the paper outlines practical recommendations for educators and specialists on effective strategies and interventions to support dyslexic learners within the school environment.

Key words: dyslexia, phonological skills, cognitive impairment, method of look-say, sensorimotor deficit.

Insonlarning jamiyat orasidagi o‘rni ko‘pincha savod masalasi, ziyolilik darajasi bilan belgilanadi. Ming yillar avval ham o‘qish va yozish qobiliyati aql-idrok bilan bog‘lab kelingan. O‘qish va yozishni bilgan odamlar ruhoniylar bo‘lib, ular muqaddas kitoblarni o‘qiganlar, tarjima qilganlar va boshqa manbalarga nusxa ko‘chirganlar. Qasrdagi boy oila farzandlari savod va matematikaga o‘qitilgan. Ular jamiyatda mavqega ega bo‘lib, juda bilimli deya hisoblangan. Shu tarzda o‘qish va yozishdagi muvafaqqiyat aql va ijtimoiy mavqe bilan bog‘langan. Bu munosabat necha asrlar o‘tsa-da, shu zaylda davom etib kelmoqda [1]. Ammo bugunga kelib vaziyat o‘zgargan. Maktabda tahsil olayotgan o‘quvchilar orasida intellekt darajasi yuqori bo‘lsa-da, matnlarni o‘qish va yozma ishlarni yozishda qiynaladigan bolalar soni tobora ortib bormoqda. Ular bilan og‘zaki suhbatlar o‘tkazilganda fikrlashi, dunyoqarashi boshqalarnikidan farqlanmaydigan, hatto ba‘zan ortiq darajada bo‘lganlari ko‘plab topiladi. Ammo o‘qituvchilar tomonidan yetarlicha o‘rganilmagan bunday bolalar intellekt va o‘zlashtirish jihatdan ham tengdoshlaridan orqada deya baholanadi. Sinflarda har tomonlama oxirgi o‘ringa tushirib qo‘yiladi. Yaxshi o‘qiydigan va yoza oladigan bolalar bilan shug‘ullanib, ular e‘tibordan ko‘p hollarda chetda qolishadi. Biz ta‘rif berayotgan maktablarda deyarli har bir sinfda kamida bittadan uchrovchi bunday o‘quvchilar disleksiyaga (Disleksiya – o‘qish va yozishning buzilishi bo‘lib, miyaning nutqqa javobgar qismlari faoliyatidagi o‘zgarishlar hisobiga kelib chiqadi) moyilligi bo‘lgan bolalardir.

Disleksiyaning asosiy sababi fonologik komponentning rivojlanishdagi yetishmovchiligidir. Bu kamchilik bolaning umumiy kognitiv qobilyatlari va maktabda olingan ta'lim darajasiga mos kelmaydi [6]. Ya'ni, bola matnlarni xato bilan o'qishi va yozishi mumkin, biroq dunyoqarashi, olamni anglashi va voqealarga munosabat bildirishi normal tengdoshlaridek bo'ladi. Ulardagi muammo esa harflarni taniy olmasligi, o'qiy olmasligidadir. Rossiyalik mutaxassislarning keltirishicha, disleksiya ega bo'lgan bolalar kitoblardagi matnni o'qiy olmaydi, harflarni yakka ko'rsatganda ularni nomlay oladi, ammo bir tizimga terib so'z shaklida berilganda harflar ularning ko'z oldida tartibsiz holga kelib qoladi.

Ilm-fanda hozirda disleksiyaning asosiy sababi sifatida to'rtta yirik nazariya mavjudligini ta'kidlab, ularni ikki qarama-qarshi yondashuv ostida birlashtiradi. Birinchisi fonologik nazariya bo'lib, o'qishdagi qiyinchilik nutq tovushlarini tasvirlash va qayta ishlashga oid kognitiv nuqson sabab paydo bo'ladi, degan g'oya bo'lsa, boshqa tadqiqotchilar esa disleksiya umumiy sensomotor nuqsonning hosilasi deb hisoblaydi. Ya'ni bunda muammo eshitish bilan bog'liq. Ammo so'nggi 20 yildan beri tadqiqotlar va disleksiv bolalar bilan o'tkazilayotgan tajribalar natijasida fonologik nazariya ko'proq yoqlab kelinmoqda [2]. Ko'plab tajriba sinovlari natijasida har qanday eshitish o'lchovi xoh nutqli bo'lsin yoki nutqsiz u fonologik ko'nikma yoki o'qish qobilyati bilan hech qanday aloqasi yo'q ekanligi aniqlangan.

Har bir odamning o'rganishdagi individual uslubi mavjud bo'lib, masalan, look-say so'zlarni butun holatda ko'rish. Visual xotirasi yaxshi bo'lgan bolalar uchun samaralidir. Ular so'zlarni aqliy kamera orqali ushlab qoladilar, keyingi safar boshqa sahifada shu so'zni ko'rsa, darrov taniydi. Bu aqlga bog'liq bo'lmagan jarayon hisoblanib, shunchaki tug'ma xususiyatdir. Visual xotirasi sust bo'lgan bolalar har bir so'zni eslab, tanib qololmaydi, natijada so'zni har safar ko'rganida yangidan kodlash talab etiladi [1]. Demak, disleksiv bolalarda harflarni eslab qolish qobilyati rivojlanmagan bo'lib, ular so'zni har safar ko'rganda ularni yangitdan kodlashga majbur bo'ladi, harflarni taniy olmaganlari bois har safar qiyinchilikka qaytadan duch kelaveradilar.

Disleksiya moyilligi bor bolalar tasvirli fikrlashadi, ular olamni rang-tasvir yoki o'lchamlarda ko'rishadi. Ronald Devisning fikricha, disleksiklar o'zlari eshitgan so'zni yoki ko'rganlarini tasvir orqali qabul qilib, analiz qilishadi. Ularda fikrlash **sekundiga 32 ta tasvir** tezligida sodir bo'ladi. Bir soniyada so'z orqali fikrlaydigan odam 2-5 ta fikrga (alohida so'z shaklidagi tushunchalarga) ega bo'lsa, tasvirli fikrlaydigan odam 32 ta (alohida tasvir shaklidagi tushunchalarga) ega bo'ladi. Matematik hisob-kitoblarga ko'ra, bu so'zli fikrlashdan 6-10 barobar ko'p fikr demakdir [1]. Disleksiv bolalarga biror so'z berilganda, aytaylik, "olma" so'zi doskaga yoki qog'ozga yozilganda bola unga qarab hech narsani tushunmaydi. Bu yerda olma so'zi bor desangiz u yozuvga qarab olmani izlaydi, shaklini, rangini... ammo hech narsa topolmaydi. Shu sabab harflar miyasida aralashib ketadi, o'rni almashadi, tepadan pastga o'qib ko'radi, shaklini hayolan tasvirlarda o'zgartiradi, biroq olma uning ko'z oldida jonlanmaydi, natijada bu so'zga qarab bola hech narsani tushunmaydi. Chunki u olmani rasmga qarab o'rgangan, unda fonemalar bilan ishlash qobilyati normal bolalarniki kabi emasligi uchun ham aytilgan

topshiriqni bajara olmayotganidan asabiylasha boshlaydi. Bola tushunish uchun miyasiga qayta qayta buyruq beradi, ammo har safar natija chiqmaydi. “Olma” soʻzini “omla”, “omal”, “olam” shaklida yoki, umuman, a ni teskari, m ni ham yonboshlagan holda koʻrishlari mumkin. Hech biri toʻgʻri variant boʻlmagach, bola oxirgi usulni qoʻllaydi – taxmin qilish [4]. Ammo taxmin, albatta, notoʻgʻri chiqadi. Va oʻqituvchi tomonidan bola ustidan hukm chiqarib boʻlinadi.

Bugun dunyodagi disleksiyaga duch kelgan har bir oʻquvchini eng koʻp qiynaydigan muammo-atrofidagilar uni yetarlicha tushunmasliklaridadir. Na maktabda va na ota-onalar farzandidagi bu holatni bilishadi, boladagi fanlardan ortda qolayotganlik, diktantlardagi doimiy pas baholarni shunchaki bolaning dangasaligi va qobilyatsizligi deya hisoblashadi. Natijada sinfdan sinfga oʻtgan sari boladagi “oʻzlashtirilmalik” kuchayaveradi. Oʻquvchi oʻzi bilan kechayotgan muammoni tushuntirilmaydi, oʻqituvchi bola bilan individual shugʻullanmaydi. Natijada sogʻlom fikrlaydigan, yaxshilab suhbatlashilsa, yashirin qobilyatga ega boʻlgan disleksiv bola bir chetda “qoloq” degan tamgʻa bilan maktabni bitiradi. Bugun zamon oʻzgarib pedagoglardan bolaga faqat bilim berish emas, uni tinglash, kuzatish, kamchiliklari ustida ishlash va bolaga doʻst boʻlish kabi koʻnikmalar ham talab etiladi. Ana shundagina bunday oʻquvchilar ham oʻzidagi yashirin imkoniyatlarni yuzaga chiqara oladi va jamiyatdan uzilib qolmaydi..

Har bir odamda qaysidir sohada kamchilik boʻladi. Yaxshi oʻqiydigan va imlodan mohir boʻlgan bolalar notalarni yaxshi chalolmasligi mumkin. Kompyuterni yaxshi tushunmaydigan yoki texnikani soʻzlashni bilmaydigan odam asta-sekin oʻrganishi mumkin. Ammo oʻqish qiyinchiligida gap nevrologik holat bilan bogʻliq boʻladi va toʻgʻri yondashilmasa ijobiy natijaga erishisholmaslik ehtimoli yuqori [1]. Disleksiv bolalarning har birida yashirin iqtidor borligi isbotlangan boʻlib, ular yo musiqada, yo rassomlikda noyob qobilyatga ega boʻlishadi. Bunday bolalar olamni qabul qilishda ayni qobilyatlariga tayanadi, axborotlarni shu yoʻsinda qabul qiladi. Shuningdek, disleksiv bolalar muammoli vaziyatlarga noodatiy yechim topa olishlari bilan ham ajralib turishadi. Keltirilishicha, ular oʻzgalarning fikrlariga ehtiyotkorlik bilan munosabatda boʻlishadi. Disleksiklar oʻqish oʻrniga aytilayotgan fikrni tinglash orqali maʼlumotni yaxshi tushunishadi. Ularga oʻqib berilgan maʼlumotni tahlil qilishib xulosa chiqarishadi. Boisi ularda ogʻzaki nutqni tushunish qobilyati kuchli rivojlangan boʻladi [5]. Shu sababdan darsda oʻqituvchi tomonidan ogʻzaki tushuntirilgan har qanday maʼlumotlarni yaxshi qabul qilishadi, tushunishadi. Biroq mustaqil oʻzing oʻqi yoki diktant yoz deyilganda bunday bolalar qiyin vaziyatga tushib qolishadi.

Butunjahonda disleksiya tashxisi qoʻyilgan bolalarda davo choralari sifatida koʻplab usullar keltirilgan. Lekin ularning hammasi ham oʻzini oqlamagan. Koʻplab ekspertlar va soha mutaxassislari amaliyotdan ijobiy oʻtgan usul sifatida ogʻzaki va yozma nutqni yaxshilashga qaratilgan amaliy mashgʻulotlar ekanligini taʼkidlashadi. Agar bolada oʻqish va yozishdagi muammo koʻrish bilan boʻgʻliq boʻlsa, birinchi galda ana shu muammo bartaraf etilishi kerak yoki eshitish apparati bilan bogʻliq boʻlsa bu yoʻnalishda davo choralari koʻrilishi kerak. Koʻplar tomonidan tavsiya etiladigan turli disleksiya terapiyalarining hech biridan naf yoʻq deyiladi

Bloomertning disleksiya protokolida. Masalan, turli maxsus va rangli ko'zoynaklar, ozuqaviy qo'shimchalar, musiqa tinglash kabilarning hech biri o'zini oqlamagan [3].

Qolaversa har bir disleksiv bolada o'qishdan tashqari qaysidir sohada boshqalardan ajralib turadigan qobiliyat borligini hisobga olganda, ular bilan ishlash jarayonida ayni holatdan foydalanish o'quvchi uchun ham, bola bilan shug'ullanayotgan mutaxassis uchun ham oldinga siljish uchun yaxshi natija beradi. Masalan, rasm chizishga iqtidori bor bo'lgan bolaga harflarni tanitishda rasm usulidan foydalanish mumkin. Bu bola ruhiyatiga kirish uchun yaxshi usul hisoblanadi. Qolaversa, disleksiv bolalar bilan shug'ullanayotgan har bir mutaxassis bolaning fiziologik, psixologik holatidan kelib chiqib ish olib borsa va albatta har qanday davo choralarini bolaning individual holatiga moslashtirsa, maqsadga erishish osonlashadi.

Adabiyotlar

1. "Day to day dyslexia in the classroom" Joy Pollock, Elisabeth Waller, Rody Pollit. – London, 2004
2. Developmental dyslexia: specific phonological deficit or general sensorimotor dysfunction? Frank Ramus. Laboratoire de Sciences Cognitives et Psycholinguistique (EHESS/ CNRS), 54 boulevard Raspail. 75006 Paris
3. Protocol dyslexie diagnostiek en Behandeling. L. Bloomert, 2006
4. Ronald d-Devis Gift of dyslexia
5. www.Dyslexia help. University of Michigan
6. Дислексия: механизмы развития и принципы лечения" Н. Н. Заваденко, М.В.Румянцева. "Русский журнал детской неврологии"

INNOVATIVE DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

**Farangiz Murtazayeva,
O'qituvchi, Filologiya fakulteti,
Guliston davlat universiteti,
Email: mufarangizab@gmail.com**

Annotatsiya. Raqamli texnologiyalarning tezkor rivojlanishi xorijiy tillarni, xususan, ingliz tilini o'qitish jarayoniga sezilarli darajada ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. An'anaviy metodlar o'rnini mobil ilovalar, sun'iy intellekt vositalari, ta'lim platformalari va onlayn hamkorlik tizimlari egallamoqda. Ushbu maqolada raqamli texnologiyalarni ingliz tili o'qitish jarayoniga integratsiya qilish imkoniyatlari va muammolari yoritilgan. Unda interfaol ilovalar, gamifikatsiya va onlayn resurslarning o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasi va mustaqilligini oshirishdagi roli tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, raqamli savodxonlik yetishmasligi, internetga ulanish muammolari va insoniy muloqotning kamayishi kabi qiyinchiliklar ham muhokama qilinadi. Tadqiqot natijalari an'anaviy pedagogika va zamonaviy texnologiyalar uyg'unligi samarali ta'limga xizmat qilishini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli ta'lim, ingliz tili o'qitish, texnologiyalar integratsiyasi, interfaol vositalar, onlayn platformalar.

Abstract. The rapid development of digital technologies has significantly transformed the process of foreign language teaching. In particular, English language instruction has shifted from traditional methods to technology-assisted approaches, including mobile applications, artificial intelligence tools, learning management systems, and online collaborative platforms. This paper explores the opportunities and challenges of integrating digital technologies into English language teaching. It highlights the role of interactive applications, gamification, and online resources in increasing learners' motivation and autonomy. The study also addresses challenges such as digital literacy gaps, internet accessibility, and the risk of reduced human interaction. The findings suggest that a balanced combination of traditional pedagogy and innovative digital tools can ensure more effective and learner-centered education.

Keywords: digital learning, English language teaching, technology integration, interactive tools, online platforms.

Introduction. The rapid advancement of digital technologies has brought profound changes to almost every sphere of human activity, including education. In recent years, English language teaching (ELT) has undergone a remarkable transformation, shifting from teacher-centered classrooms and textbook-based instruction to technology-assisted, learner-centered approaches [Mamatov, 2019, p.23]. Digital tools such as mobile applications, artificial intelligence-based platforms, learning management systems, and virtual communication channels have become integral to the modern classroom.

Digital Tools in English Teaching. The integration of digital tools into English language teaching has redefined traditional pedagogical practices. Teachers today employ digital resources such as mobile applications (Duolingo, Quizlet), AI-based tools (Grammarly, chatbots), learning management systems (Moodle, Google Classroom), multimedia resources (TED Talks, YouTube), and online collaboration tools (Zoom, Teams, Google Meet). AI-powered platforms are especially valuable as they provide immediate feedback and adaptive learning opportunities [Godwin-Jones, 2018]. These technologies provide learners with autonomy, flexibility, and authentic communication opportunities.

Benefits. Digital technologies offer multiple advantages including higher motivation through gamification [Warschauer, 2004], accessibility and flexibility for distance learners, promotion of learner autonomy, exposure to authentic language materials, and improved teacher effectiveness with tools for tracking progress and providing feedback [Chapelle, 2010].

Challenges. Despite these benefits, several challenges remain. Unequal access to reliable technology creates a digital divide [Mahmudov, 2012, p.10]. Both teachers and learners may face digital literacy gaps, which limit effective use of platforms. Reduced face-to-face interaction can negatively affect motivation and classroom dynamics [Beatty, 2013]. Moreover, distractions and the questionable quality of online resources may hinder learning outcomes.

Conclusion. The future of English language teaching requires a balanced approach that combines the advantages of digital technologies with the irreplaceable

value of traditional pedagogy. By doing so, educators can design more effective and engaging environments that prepare learners for the communicative demands of the technology-driven world.

References

1. Mahmudov N. (2012). Tilning mukammal tadqiqi yo‘llarini izlab. O‘zbek tili va adabiyoti, № 5, 10 b.
2. Mamatov A. (2019). Zamonaviy lingvistika. Toshkent: Fan.
3. Warschauer M. (2004). The Digital Divide and Language Learning. TESOL Quarterly, 38(2), 411–436.
4. Godwin-Jones R. (2018). Emerging Technologies in Language Learning. Language Learning & Technology, 22(3), 2–11.
5. Chapelle C. A. (2010). The Spread of Computer-Assisted Language Learning. Language Teaching, 43(1), 66–74.
6. Beatty K. (2013). Teaching and Researching Computer-Assisted Language Learning. London: Routledge.

PARALINGUISTIC ELEMENTS IN CHARACTER DESCRIPTION AS A TOOL FOR FORMING INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

Masharipova Valentina Sergeyevna,
PhD student, valentina@urdu.uz

Urgench State University named after Abu Rayhan Biruni

Abstract: The article analyzes paralinguistic elements found in character descriptions within works of fiction and their potential for developing intercultural competence in foreign language learners. Drawing on the novels “Brothers and Sisters” by Fyodor Abramov and “The Man of Property” by John Galsworthy, the study identifies culturally specific features of non-verbal elements such as gestures, facial expressions, postures, and intonation. It also proposes methods for integrating these elements into the educational process. The research shows that working with paralinguistics in literary texts helps students develop skills for culturally appropriate interpretation and expands their intercultural competence.

Keywords: paralinguistics, intercultural competence, literary text, foreign language teaching, Abramov, Galsworthy.

1. Introduction.

Contemporary research in the field of foreign language teaching methodology [Hall, E. T., 1973. 150-155] emphasizes that successful intercultural communication requires not only lexical and grammatical competence, but also non-verbal competence. Paralinguistic means-gestures, facial expressions, posture, and intonation-play a key role in conveying emotions, social roles, and cultural norms [McNeill, D., 2005. 765-766].

A literary text is a valuable source for studying these means, as authors detail the non-verbal behavior of characters within a cultural context. Within the framework of this paper, special attention is paid to the character descriptions by Abramov and

Galsworthy, in which paralinguistics not only supplements verbal communication but also serves as a marker of cultural identity.

The goal of this study is to identify paralinguistic elements in literary texts in Russian and English and to propose methodological approaches for their use in foreign language education to develop intercultural competence.

2. Literature Review

Research into paralinguistic means as a part of communication has deep interdisciplinary roots, combining linguistics, cultural studies, psycholinguistics, and pedagogy. The term paralinguistics in its modern sense was introduced in the mid-20th century [Trager, G.L.,1958.12-13.] and includes the analysis of non-verbal components of speech such as timbre, intonation, and pauses, as well as descriptions of gestures, facial expressions, and postures that accompany verbal statements.

The study of paralinguistic elements is linked to the concept of non-verbal communication proposed in the cultural-anthropological research of E. Hall. Hall identified the concepts of proxemics (spatial distance), kinesics (gestures and body movements), and chronemics (the perception of time in communication) as key to analyzing intercultural differences.

For literary discourse, paralinguistics performs several functions:

- Characterization (creating a character's image through non-verbal details);
- Pragmatic (regulating interpersonal relationships);
- Linguo-cultural (representing national communication norms).

Uzbekistani linguists are also involved in the study of paralinguistic elements. Based on a detailed study of paralinguistic means in Uzbek, Russian, and English cultures, D. A. Abduazizova developed a detailed classification and proposed a comparative-typological method of analysis, substantiating the need to teach nonverbal behavior for effective intercultural interaction [Abduazizova D. A., 2002. 96-108]. G.B. Nadjimova investigated how nonverbal behavior in English and Karakalpak cultures, with its unique kinetic signals, reflects national mentality and traditions. This research made it possible to identify unique cultural codes for the perception and expression of emotions [Nazhimova G.B., 2023. 249-253].

In foreign language teaching methodology, paralinguistics is considered a part of intercultural competence. Learning to interpret non-verbal signals helps students avoid cultural misunderstandings and improves authentic communication skills. In this context, a literary text is a convenient and rich material for analysis because it contains culturally-specific paralinguistic descriptions that can be integrated into the learning process[Golubović, K, 2015. 47–56].

Thus, the current state of academic research confirms that paralinguistics is an integral part of communication and a valuable tool for developing intercultural competence in foreign language education. However, in pedagogical practice, the analysis of paralinguistic elements in literary texts remains underdeveloped, which highlights the relevance of this study.

3. Materials and methods

The research material consisted of Fyodor Abramov's novel, *Brothers and Sisters* (1958), and the first novel of John Galsworthy's trilogy, *The Man of Property*

(1906). These books were chosen for their character portrayals that make extensive use of paralinguistic elements-gestures, facial expressions, posture, and specific intonation and pausing.

Contrastive analysis allowed for the comparison of paralinguistic descriptions in the Russian and English literary traditions, revealing similarities and differences in culturally determined non-verbal behavior patterns. Pragmatic analysis aimed to define the communicative functions of these elements and their roles in conveying emotions, social roles, and interpersonal relationships.

Special attention was given to developing teaching methods that could be integrated into the foreign language learning process. As part of this approach, tasks were proposed that involved comparing, role-playing, and translating paralinguistic elements with commentary.

The criteria for selecting examples for analysis were: the presence of descriptions of gestures, facial expressions, postures, or intonational characteristics; their inclusion in the character's description; and their significance for understanding the character's emotional state or social role within the context of the work.

4. Results

Paralinguistic Element	Russian Prose (Abramov)	English Prose (Galsworthy)	Cultural Interpretation
Silence	A sign of inner protest or deep distress	A means of avoiding conflict	In Russian culture, silence is emotionally charged, while in English culture, it is pragmatic
Shrug	Indifference or bewilderment	Skepticism, irony	Different emotional connotations
Smile	A sincere display of emotions	A formal social gesture	In the English context, it is more often neutral
Averted gaze	An unwillingness to continue the conversation	A polite softening of a refusal	The Russian version is emotional

5. Discussion

The identified differences show that the interpretation of paralinguistics is impossible without considering the cultural context. For foreign language teaching, this opens up broad methodological opportunities:

Comparative exercises: Students are given excerpts from Russian and English prose and compare gestures and facial expressions.

Role-playing: Acting out scenes and adapting non-verbal elements to different cultural codes.

Translation with commentary: Emphasis on conveying not only the words but also the non-verbal component.

Such tasks develop students' ability to notice and correctly interpret culturally marked non-verbal signals.

6. Conclusion

Paralinguistic elements in literary texts are an important tool for developing intercultural competence. Their analysis helps students not only better understand a literary text but also develop skills for effective intercultural communication. The inclusion of paralinguistic analysis in the educational process contributes to the formation of a holistic view of language as a complex system that unites verbal and non-verbal components.

References

1. Hall, E. T. *The Silent Language*. New York: Anchor Books, 1973. 243 p. https://monoskop.org/images/5/57/Hall_Edward_T_The_Silent_Language.pdf
2. Samovar, L. A., Porter, R. E., McDaniel, E. R. *Intercultural Communication: A Reader*. Boston: Cengage Learning, 2010.
3. Golubović, K. "Paralinguistic Features in Literary Discourse." *Linguistics and Literature*, 13(1), 2015, pp. 47–56.
4. Khokhlova, M. "Nonverbal Communication in Teaching English as a Foreign Language." *Journal of Language and Education*, 6(2), 2020, pp. 102–110.
5. Abduazizova D. A. Analysis of paralinguistic means in literary text. // *O‘zbekistonda xorijiy tillar*. – 2022. – No 5 (52). – B. 96-108
6. Nazhimova G.B. Kinesics in linguistics // *Science and Education in Karakalpakstan*. – Nukus, 2023. – No1/1. – R. 249-253.

ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA MATN YARATISH

Qodirberganova Dilnura Murod qizi,
Nukus davlat pedagogika instituti 3- kurs talabasi
godirberganovadilnura@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola ona tili darslarida matn yaratish jarayonini takomillashtirishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar va innovatsion metodlarning ahamiyatini o‘rganadi. Tadqiqotda Mind mapping, Brainstorming, Drafting and revising kabi metodlar va Google Docs, Grammarly, Padlet kabi texnologik vositalardan foydalanishning yozma nutqni rivojlantirishdagi samaradorligi tahlil qilingan.

Mualliflar zamonaviy texnologiyalarni integratsiya qilish o‘quvchilarning mustaqil fikrlash, tahlil qilish va ijodiy ko‘nikmalarini sezilarli darajada oshirishini ta’kidlaydi. Maqola ona tili o‘qituvchilari uchun amaliy tavsiyalar berib, ta’lim sifatini yaxshilashda yangi pedagogik yondashuvlarni qo‘llash zarurligini ko‘rsatadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: pedagogik texnologiyalar, matn yaratish, innovatsion metodlar, yozma nutq, interaktiv ta’lim, fikrlash ko‘nikmalari

Annotatsion. This article examines the importance of modern pedagogical technologies and innovative methods in improving the process of text creation in native language classes. The study analyzes the effectiveness of using such methods as Mind mapping, Brainstorming, Drafting and revising, and technological tools such as Google Docs, Grammarly, Padlet in developing written speech. The authors emphasize that the integration of modern technologies significantly increases

students' independent thinking, analytical and creative skills. The article provides practical recommendations for native language teachers and shows the need to use new pedagogical approaches to improve the quality of education.

Keywords: pedagogical technologies, text creation, innovative methods, written speech, interactive learning, thinking skills

Kirish

Bugungi tezkor rivojlanayotgan davrda ta'lim jarayoni ham doimiy yangilanish va takomillashtirishni talab qilmoqda. Ayniqsa, ona tili darslarida o'quvchilarning matn yaratish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bu nafaqat ularning yozma va og'zaki nutqini takomillashtiradi, balki fikrlash, tahlil qilish, ijodiy va kommunikativ qobiliyatlarini ham shakllantiradi.

An'anaviy o'qitish metodlari har doim ham zamon talablariga javob bera olmagan sababli, ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar va innovatsion yondashuvlar muhim rol o'ynamoqda. Ushbu texnologiyalar o'quv jarayonini yanada interaktiv, qiziqarli va samarali qilish imkonini beradi.

Zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar bu ta'lim jarayonini yanada samarali, interaktiv va shaxsga yo'naltirilgan qilish maqsadida yaratilgan metodlar, usullar va vositalar tizimidir. Matn yaratish – bu o'quvchilarning fikrlarini tizimli va mantiqiy tarzda ifoda etish jarayonidir. Ta'limda matn yaratish o'quvchilarning nafaqat yozma va og'zaki nutq ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga, balki ularning fikrlash, tahlil qilish, ijodiy va kommunikativ qobiliyatlarini shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. Ona til darslarida matn yaratish texnologiyalarini interaktiv va ijodiy yo'l bilan boyitish O'quvchilarning ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish Turli janrlarda (hikoya, insho, she'r, esse) yozishga rag'batlantirish. Mavzularni qiziqarli, o'quvchilarning kundalik hayotiga yaqin qilib tanlash. Fikrlarni erkin ifoda etishga imkon berish, o'z nuqtai nazarini bayon etishni rag'batlantirish. Yozilgan ishlarni sinf oldida taqdim etish, ijobiy fikrlar bildirish. Tanlovlar, tanqidiy baholar, sovrinlar orqali rag'batlantirish. O'zgarish va taraqqiyotlarni ko'rsatish uchun yozma ishlarni solishtirish va tahlil qilish. Onlayn platformalarda birgalikda matn yaratish (masalan, Google Docs yoki boshqa bulutli xizmatlar). Video va audio materiallardan foydalanib, yangi mavzular bo'yicha matn yozish. Matn yaratish jarayonini o'quvchilar bilan muhokama qilish, fikr almashish. Darslarni o'yin shaklida tashkil etish yozma mashqlarni qiziqarli viktorinalar yoki o'yinlarga aylantirish. Guruhlararo musobaqalar orqali yozma nutq ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish. Yakuniy tavsiyalar. Matn yaratish texnologiyalarini ona til darslarida muntazam va tizimli ravishda qo'llash. Har bir o'quvchining individual rivojlanishini hisobga olish. O'quvchilarni yozma ishlariga doimiy qayta aloqa va tahrir jarayoniga jalb qilish[1]. Zamonaviy texnologiyalar va interaktiv metodlarni doimiy ravishda integratsiya qilish. O'quvchilarning yozma nutqini faollashtirish va ijobiy ruhda rag'batlantirish.

Ona til darslarida matn yaratish texnologiyalarini qo'llashning qo'shimcha metodlari

- Mind mapping (aqlli xaritalar). Matn yaratish jarayonida fikrlarni tartibga solish uchun o'quvchilarga mind mapping texnologiyasini o'rgatish. Bu usul o'quvchining mantiqiy fikrlashini va reja tuzish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi.

- Brainstorming (fikrlar to'plash). Mavzu bo'yicha guruhlarda yoki yakka tartibda erkin fikrlar to'plash mashqlari o'tkazish. Bu usul o'quvchilarni erkin va ijodiy fikrlashga undaydi.

- Drafting and revising (qoralama va tahrir). Yozilgan matnni dastlabki variantini yozish va keyin uni qayta ko'rib chiqish, o'zgartirish jarayonlarini muntazam bajarish. O'quvchilarga tahrir qilish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish[2].

- Peer review (tengdoshlar bahosi). O'quvchilar bir-birining matnlarini o'qib, konstruktiv fikrlar berishlari, xatolarni ko'rsatishlari uchun sharoit yaratish.

- Writing workshops (yozuv ustaxonasi). Sinfxonada maxsus mashg'ulotlar tashkil etish, unda o'quvchilar birgalikda matn yaratish, tahrir qilish va takomillashtirish ustida ishlaydilar.

Metodlarning dars jarayoniga integratsiyasi

Dars boshida brainstorming orqali mavzu tanlanadi va fikrlar to'planadi. Mind mapping yordamida o'quvchilar reja tuzadilar. Drafting bosqichida qoralama yoziladi. Yakuniy variant yozilib, o'qituvchi tomonidan tahrir qilinadi va baholanadi. Foydali texnologik vositalar MindMeister, XMind – aqlli xaritalar yaratish uchun. Google Docs, Microsoft Word Online – birgalikda yozish va tahrir qilish uchun. Grammarly, LanguageTool – grammatik va imlo xatolarini aniqlashda yordam beradi. Padlet, Kahoot – interaktiv mashqlar va fikr almashish uchun. Onlayn muloqot platformalari Google Classroom, Zoom yoki boshqa ta'lim platformalarida yozma mashqlar va ularning muhokamasini tashkil etish, interaktiv bahslar o'tkazish. Muloqotning matn sifatiga ta'siri Fikrlar almashinuvi yozma nutqdagi mazmun va mantiqiylikni oshiradi. O'quvchilar bir-biridan o'rganib, yangi so'z va iboralarni o'zlashtiradilar. Muloqot orqali tahrir jarayoni tezlashadi va matn yanada boy bo'ladi. Ona til darslarida matn yaratish jarayonida pedagogik innovatsiyalar Differensiallashtirilgan ta'lim Har bir o'quvchining individual qobiliyatlari va o'rganish sur'ati inobatga olinib, yozma vazifalar murakkabligi va shakli moslashtiriladi. Masalan, ba'zilar uchun qisqa matnlar, boshqalar uchun esa kengroq insholar berish. Blended learning (aralash ta'lim) An'anaviy darslar va onlayn ta'lim vositalarini uyg'unlashtirish orqali matn yaratish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish. Onlayn platformalarda interaktiv mashqlar, yozma vazifalar va tahlillar o'tkazish. Flipped classroom (teskari dars) O'quvchilar darsdan oldin mavzu bo'yicha video yoki matn ko'rinishida materiallarni o'rganadi, darsda esa asosan amaliy yozish mashqlariga e'tibor qaratiladi. Zamonaviy yondashuvlarning afzalliklari O'quvchilarning mustaqil va faol ishtirokini oshiradi. Yozish ko'nikmalarini tez va samarali rivojlantirishga yordam beradi. Ta'lim jarayonini interaktiv, qiziqarli va motivatsion qiladi. Ona til darslarida yozma nutqni rivojlantirish uchun texnologiyalar va vositalar Matn yaratish uchun onlayn platformalar Google Docs – birgalikda yozish, tahrir qilish va izoh berish imkonini beradi. Microsoft OneNote – o'quvchilarga yozma ishlarni tashkil qilish va boshqarish uchun qulay. Padlet – o'quvchilarning yozma ishlarini jamlash va fikr almashish uchun. Grammatik va imlo

tekshiruv dasturlari Grammarly, LanguageTool, Microsoft Editor kabi vositalar yozilgan matnni avtomatik tahlil qilib, xatolarni ko'rsatadi va to'g'rilash bo'yicha takliflar beradi. Interaktiv yozish mashqlari Kahoot!, Quizlet kabi platformalarda yozish ko'nikmalarini mustahkamlovchi o'yinlar va testlar o'tkazish. Audio va video yozuvlar O'quvchilar o'z matnlarini ovozga o'qib, audio yoki video shaklida yozib olishlari, bu orqali nutq madaniyati va ifodaning yaxshilanishi. Matnlarni tahlil qilish va taqqoslash vositalari Matnlarni avtomatik tahlil qiluvchi dasturlar yordamida o'quvchilar yozgan matnlarning mazmuni, grammatikasi, stilistikasi bo'yicha tahlil qilish.

Texnologiyalarning ta'lim jarayoniga integratsiyasi

Matn yaratishda onlayn platformalardan foydalanish o'quvchilarning hamkorlik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi. Grammatik vositalar o'quvchilarga mustaqil tahrir qilish ko'nikmasini shakllantirishda yordam beradi. Interaktiv vositalar o'quvchilarning qiziqishini oshiradi va ularni faol ishtirok etishga undaydi. Ona til darslarida yozma nutqni rivojlantirishda motivatsiya va ijtimoiy-psixologik omillar O'quvchilarning ichki motivatsiyasini oshirish Yozish jarayonining mazmuni va mavzusini o'quvchining qiziqishlari bilan bog'lash. Mustaqil fikrlash va ijodiy yondashuv uchun imkon yaratish. Yozma ishlar natijalarini ijobiy baholash va rag'batlantirish. Ijtimoiy muhit va o'quvchilar o'rtasidagi muloqot Guruh ishlari va hamkorlik orqali o'zaro fikr almashish va o'rganishni rag'batlantirish. Tengdoshlar bahosi va ijobiy tanqidni o'rganish orqali o'zini baholashni rivojlantirish. O'zbek yozuviga qanchalik ko'p bo'lsa, yozuvchi shunchalik qulay bo'ladi. Bundan tashqari, muntazam mashq lug'at, jumlar tuzilishi va grammatikani yaxshilaydi.

Adabiyotlar

1. O'zbek tili darsliklari va metodik qo'llanmalar, Toshkent Davlat Pedagogika Universiteti nashrlari, 2015–2023 yillar. (Uzbek language textbooks and methodological guides, Tashkent State Pedagogical University publications, 2015–2023.)
2. Zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar: nazariya va amaliyot. Abdullayev, O. (2015). Toshkent: O'qituvchi. (2. Abdullayev, O. (2015). Modern pedagogical technologies: theory and practice. Tashkent: O'qituvchi.)

ONA TILI TA'LIMIDA KOMMUNIKATIV YONDASHUV ORQALI NUTQIY SAVODXONLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH

*Djalilova Shoira Bozorboyevna,
Boyovut tumani 52 maktab ona tili va adabiyot fani o'qituvchisi
Jalilovashoira11@gmail.com*

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ona tili darslarini tashkil etish hamda til o'qitishdagi yondashuvlar, ushbu jarayonda foydalaniladigan metodlar, kommunikativ yondashuv masalalari atroflicha yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Ona tili darsliklari, metodlar, Milliy dastur, kommunikativ yondashuv, topshiriq va mashqlar.

Abstract. This article covers the organization of mother tongue classes and the

methods and communication issues used in this process.

Key words. Mother tongue textbooks, methods, national program, communicative approach, tasks and exercises.

Boshqa fanlar qatori maktablarda ona tili darslarini to‘laqonli hamda samarali tashkil etish, ayni texnologiyalar rivojlangan bir vaqtda yosh-avlod e‘tiborini fanlararo bog‘liqlikka jalb qilish asosiy masaladir.

Maktablarda ona tili darslari mutaxassislar tomonidan o‘quvchilarga yetarlicha tushuntiriladi, to‘g‘ri yo‘nalishlar beriladi. Odatda, o‘quvchidan nazariy qoidalar so‘ralsa, javob bera oladi, lekin amalda qo‘llay olmaydi. Eski ona tili darsliklarining sakson foizini nazariy qoidalar hamda o‘quvchining yozma nutqini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan topshiriqlar tashkil etadi. Ona tili darsliklarini boshqa til darsliklari bilan, misol uchun, ingliz tili darsliklari bilan taqqoslasak, orasida anchayin ko‘zga ko‘rinadigan farqlar mavjud. Ingliz tilidagi barcha qo‘llanma va darsliklar qiziqarli suratlar, mavzuga oid faktlar turli usuldagi metodlar bilan to‘ldirilgan va bu, hech shubhasiz, bir xillikdan qochgan holda o‘quvchilarni qiziqтира oladi. Bu metodlar yordamida o‘quvchilarga biron-bir ma‘lumotni yetkazib berish osonlashadi, amalda ko‘rsatiladi.

Ta‘limiy darslarda metodlardan foydalanishning ta‘sir va samarasi katta. Oxirgi bir necha yillar davomida ona tili darslarini yanada takomillashtirish maqsadida o‘quv dasturi va rejalarni o‘zgartirish, yangidan yangi metodlarni qo‘shish kabi bir necha jarayonlarga e‘tibor qaratildi. Bu kabi o‘zgartirishlarning asosini kommunikativ yondashuv tashkil qilishi lozim. Shu o‘rinda o‘zi kommunikativ yondashuv nima va u biz uchun nimaga kerak,— degan savollar tug‘ilishi tabiiy. “Kommunikatsiya” – lotincha so‘zdan olingan bo‘lib, “communicatio” – “umumlashtiraman, bog‘layman“ degan ma‘noni anglatadi.

Kommunikativ yondashuvning mohiyati real vaziyatda nutqni tushunish, o‘z fikrini to‘g‘ri ifodalashga o‘rgatishdir. Shuning uchun har bir mavzu uchun alohida vaziyat beriladi va shu vaziyatda nutq vositasida masalani hal qilish talab qilinadi [1, 134].

Kommunikativ yondashuvga ko‘ra, nutq tilning faqat grammatik tizimini egallash emas, balki uni muayyan nutqiy maqsadni ro‘yobga chiqarish, muloqot jarayonida kimgadir axborot berish, kimdandir axborot olish, kim bilandir fikr almashish, o‘zaro ta‘sirga kirishish vositasi sifatida qaraladi. Nutq insonga amaliy faoliyatda, ijtimoiy muhitda o‘z fikrini erkin ifodalash, boshqalarni tinglash va tushunishda xizmat qiladi

Kommunikativ yondashuv talablariga muvofiq, maktab o‘quvchilari ona tilini faqat qoidalar yig‘indisi sifatida emas, balki bevosita muomala-aralashuv vositasi sifatida mukammal o‘rganishlari lozim. Bu jarayonda ularning:

- nutqiy kompetensiyasi (fikrni aniq, to‘g‘ri, mantiqli ifodalash qobiliyati);
- sotsiolingvistik kompetensiyasi (nutqiy vaziyatga mos til vositalarini tanlash);

- pragmatik kompetensiyasi (muloqotda maqsadga erishish), strategik kompetensiyasi (nutq jarayonida muammolarni hal qilish usullari)

bosqichma-bosqich shakllantiriladi.

Shuningdek, kommunikativ yondashuvning asosiy vazifalaridan biri – o‘quvchilarni real hayotiy vaziyatlarda tilni qo‘llashga, hamkorlikda fikr yuritishga, muloqotda faol bo‘lishga o‘rgatishdir. Bu esa ularning nafaqat bilim darajasini, balki mustaqil fikrlash, ijodkorlik va ijtimoiy faoliyatini ham rivojlantiradi.

Ona tili ta’limida kommunikativ yondashuv o‘quvchilarning faqat til hodisalarini bilishemas, balki ularni real hayotiy faoliyatda qo‘llay olishlayoqatini shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. Bu yondashuv orqali nutqiy savodxonlik rivojlantirilishi, avvalo, interfaol muloqot, vaziyatli mashqlar, juftlik va guruhli ishlarda faol ishtirok etish orqali ta’minlanadi. Chunki tilning tabiati jonli muloqot jarayonida to‘liq namoyon bo‘ladi.

Kommunikativ yondashuvning muhim jihatlaridan biri – o‘quvchini muloqot subyekti sifatida tan olishdir. An’anaviy ta’limda o‘quvchi bilimni tayyor holda qabul qiluvchi bo‘lsa, kommunikativ yondashuvda u faol ishtirokchi, suhbatdosh va hamkorsifatida namoyon bo‘ladi. Bu esa nutqiy savodxonlikning tabiiy va samarali rivojlanishini ta’minlaydi.

Shuningdek, kommunikativ yondashuv asosida tashkil etilgan ona tili darslarida:

o‘quvchilarda fikrni og‘zaki va yozma shaklda mustaqil bayon etishko‘nikmalari kengayadi;

ijodiy tafakkur va tahliliy yondashuvrivojlanadi;

nutqiy madaniyat, intonatsiya, talaffuz va ohangkabi jihatlar mustahkamlanadi;

muloqot madaniyati– suhbatdoshni tinglash, savol berish, mulohaza bildirish odatlari shakllanadi.

Ona tili ta’limida yangi Milliy o‘quv dasturi asosida yaratilgan darsliklarning asosiy yangiligi shundaki, ularning mazmuni o‘quvchi hayoti bilan chambarchas bog‘langan. Ya’ni, real hayotda ro‘y beradigan voqea-hodisalar, ijtimoiy-madaniy jarayonlar, kundalik muloqot shakllari dars mavzulariga singdirilgan. Bunday yondashuv o‘quvchilarda o‘zlashtirilayotgan bilimlarning amaliy qiymatini oshiradi, natijada ularning ona tili faniga qiziqishi bilan birga boshqa fanlarni o‘rganishga bo‘lgan rag‘bati ham ortadi.

Yangi avlod darsliklari o‘quvchini faol subyekt sifatida shakllantirish, uni suhbat, munozara, bahs-munozara jarayonlariga jalb etishga yo‘naltirilgan. Bu esa o‘quvchilarda nutqiy kompetensiya bilan birga ijtimoiy hamkorlik, tanqidiy fikrlash va ijodkorlik malakalarini rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.

Mazkur darsliklarning metodik xususiyati shundaki, ular o‘zida nutqiy faoliyatning to‘rt asosiy turini – *tinglab tushunish, o‘qib tushunish, og‘zaki nutq va yozma nutqni* uyg‘unlashtirgan. Shuningdek, so‘z boyligini oshirish, kontekst asosida ma’no farqlash, vaziyatli mashqlar orqali fikrni aniq va to‘g‘ri ifodalashga qaratilgan topshiriqlar ko‘proq o‘rin olgan.

Shu boisdan ham yangilangan darsliklar nafaqat nazariy bilimlarni o‘zlashtirishni, balki ularni hayotga tatbiq qilish, kommunikativ faoliyatda samarali qo‘llashni ham ko‘zda tutadi. Bunday yondashuv o‘quvchilarda nutqiy savodxonlik, ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetensiya va mustaqil fikrlashni shakllantirishda muhim omil

bo‘lib xizmat qilmoqda.

Umuman olganda, bugungi kunda professional pedagoglar oldida turgan eng muhim vazifalardan biri – an’anaviy ta’lim shakllaridan bosqichma-bosqich voz kechib, o‘quvchi va o‘qituvchi hamkorligiga asoslangan, zamonaviy pedagogik ruhda dars jarayonlarini tashkil etishdir. Bunda kommunikativ yondashuv alohida o‘rin tutadi, chunki u o‘quvchini bilimni tayyor shaklda qabul qiluvchi emas, balki faol ishtirokchi, suhbatdosh va muloqot jarayonining teng subyekti sifatida shakllantiradi.

Mazkur jarayonni samarali tashkil etishda turli innovatsion metodlardan foydalanish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Jumladan:

“Aqliy hujum” – o‘quvchilarda tezkor fikrlash, muammoga yechim topishda ijodiy yondashuvni rivojlantiradi;

“4K modeli” (kreativlik, kommunikatsiya, kolaboratsiya, kritik tafakkur) – shaxsiy va ijtimoiy kompetensiyalarni shakllantiradi;

“FSMU” metodi – fikrni mantiqan asoslash, dalillar bilan isbotlash, nutqiy aniqlikni oshirishga yordam beradi;

“Sinkveyn” – o‘quvchilarda so‘z boyligini kengaytirish, qisqa va lo‘nda shaklda mazmunni ifodalash malakasini rivojlantiradi.

Bu metodlarning barchasi o‘quvchini tezkorlikka, faol fikrlashga, o‘z bilimlarini namoyon etishga, nutqiy savodxonligini oshirishga yo‘naltirilgan bo‘lib, shu bilan birga dars jarayonida qiziqish va e‘tiborning barqarorligini ta‘minlaydi [3, 64].

Xulosa qilib aytganda, ta’lim sifatini oshirish uchun mashg‘ulotlarda eng so‘nggi zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan va turfa metodlardan oqilona foydalanish zarur. Chunki bunday yondashuv o‘quvchilarning nafaqat bilim darajasini, balki ijodkorlik, tanqidiy fikrlash, muloqot va hamkorlik ko‘nikmalarini ham rivojlantiradi, ularni kelajak hayotga tayyorlashda samarali vosita bo‘lib xizmat qiladi.

Adabiyotlar

9. Azimova I. Ona tili bo‘yicha savodxonlik kurslarida kommunikativ yondashuvni qo‘llash. Global ta’lim va milliy metodika taraqqiyoti nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani materiallari to‘plami.

10. G‘ulomov A. va boshq., O‘zbek tilini o‘qitish metodikasi – Toshkent: 2012.

11. Hamroyev A.R. Po‘lotova Y.A., Ona tilini o‘qitish metodikasi, – Toshkent: 2021.

12. Ona tili. Umumiy o‘rta ta’lim maktablarining 10-sinfi uchun darslik, – Toshkent: 2022.

13. Ona tili. Umumiy o‘rta ta’lim maktablarining 7-sinfi uchun darslik, – Toshkent: 2022.

14. Ona tili. Umumiy o‘rta ta’lim maktablarining 6-sinfi uchun darslik, – Toshkent: 2022.

LANGUAGE-SKILL DIFFICULTIES AND STRATEGIC RESPONSES OF LOCAL EFL STUDENTS: A VISUAL PERSPECTIVE

Ortiqova Tursunoy,

PhD student of Gulistan State University

Email address: ortiqovaturunoy66@gmail.com

Abstract. The study investigates language-skill barriers and strategy use among EFL learners, with a special focus on the integration of visualization techniques into receptive and productive skills. A quantitative approach was employed using an online questionnaire consisting of demographic and 15 main items. The participants were 122 first-year English philology students from Termiz State University, Karshi State University, and Gulistan State University in Uzbekistan. The results showed that vocabulary limitations, misinterpretation of question types, and lack of coherence in writing were the most common challenges. Visualization-based strategies such as graphic organizers, pictorial aids, and model essay analysis proved effective in overcoming these difficulties. The findings highlight the pedagogical potential of visual techniques for enhancing learners' reading and writing performance.

Keywords: language-skill barriers; EFL learners; visualization techniques; receptive and productive skills; learning strategies; graphic organizers

Introduction / Literature Review

Learning strategies have long been regarded as central to the process of second language acquisition, as they equip learners with tools to facilitate comprehension and production. According to Ma (2009), strategies for grammar, vocabulary, and the four core language skills remain crucial for effective learning. Nation (2009) emphasizes that explicit training in reading and writing strategies significantly improves learner outcomes, while Staehr (2009) links vocabulary knowledge to advanced listening comprehension, underlining the interdependence of language skills.

Recent studies also show that learners face persistent challenges across receptive and productive domains. Hezam, Haidara, and Mohammed (2022) identify reading comprehension difficulties as one of the main obstacles for EFL learners, whereas Tovar Viera et al. (2024) report common problems in essay writing, including organization and coherence. At the same time, visualization techniques—ranging from graphic organizers to pictorial aids—have gained growing attention for their role in supporting memory, comprehension, and learner engagement in EFL contexts.

Results and Discussion

The findings revealed several recurring barriers that hindered the development of both receptive and productive skills among the participants. Vocabulary limitations were reported as the most frequent difficulty, which corresponds to Staehr's (2009) observation that insufficient lexical knowledge directly affects comprehension, particularly in reading and listening. Learners also indicated confusion in identifying question types, especially in reading tasks, which often led to misinterpretation of test

items and reduced accuracy. In terms of writing, students noted difficulties in maintaining coherence and organization, echoing the challenges highlighted by Tovar Viera et al. (2024) in their study on essay writing.

Alongside these barriers, the study also explored strategies that learners used to address their difficulties. The use of visualization-based methods—such as graphic organizers, pictorial aids, model essay analysis, and pre-writing techniques—emerged as particularly effective. Participants reported that such methods helped them to structure information more clearly, retain key ideas, and improve task performance. For example, graphic organizers supported reading comprehension by enabling learners to map out main ideas and supporting details, while model essay analysis provided a framework for developing logical arguments in writing.

The discussion further highlights the pedagogical implications of these findings. The results confirm Nation's (2009) claim that skills training requires systematic support through strategies. In this context, visualization can serve as an accessible and practical tool for enhancing learning efficiency. Moreover, the integration of visual methods not only addresses existing barriers but also increases learner motivation and engagement, aligning with global trends in modern methodology. These findings suggest that greater emphasis should be placed on incorporating visual techniques into the teaching of receptive and productive skills in EFL classrooms across Uzbekistan.

Conclusion

The study revealed that EFL learners from Termiz, Karshi, and Guliston State Universities face noticeable barriers in both receptive and productive skills, primarily due to vocabulary limitations and lack of practice. At the same time, a considerable number of students expressed positive attitudes toward the use of visual techniques as potential tools to overcome these challenges. Although the effectiveness of visualization has not yet been empirically tested, the findings provide a strong basis for conducting further experimental research to validate its role in enhancing language learning outcomes.

References

1. Hezam, A., Haidara, Y., & Mohammed, A. (2022). Reading comprehension difficulties among EFL learners: Causes and solutions. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 10(1), 40–48. <https://doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.10n.1p.40>
2. Ma, T. (2009). An empirical study on the comparison between strategies on oral English classes and writing English classes. *English Language Teaching*, 2(2), 39–44. Canadian Center of Science and Education.
3. Nation, I. S. P. (2009). *Teaching ESL/EFL reading and writing*. Routledge.
4. Staehr, L. S. (2009). Vocabulary knowledge and advanced listening comprehension in English as a foreign language. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 31(4), 577–607. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0272263109990039>
5. Tovar Viera, D. A., Quinaluisa, C. M., & Yáñez, M. A. (2024). Analysis of students' difficulty in essay writing: A case study at Technical University of Cotopaxi. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 15(2), 175–182.

O'QUVCHILAR SO'Z BOYLIгинI ANIQLASHNING FALSAFIY ASOSLARI

Qayumova Ozoda Botir qizi,
ozodaqayumova63@gmail.com

Toshkent davlat o'zbek tili va adabiyoti
universiteti o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya. Maktab o'quvchilari so'z boyligini aniqlash – pedagogik, psixologik va metodik muammo. O'quvchining so'z boyligini aniqlashning falsafiy asoslari tilni tafakkur, ijtimoiy muloqot va bilimning o'zaro bog'liq bir qismi sifatida ko'rishga asoslanadi. Maqolada o'quvchilarning so'z boyligini aniqlash nafaqat ular biladigan so'zlari sonini sanash, balki insonning bilimi, tafakkuri va ijtimoiy muloqot qobiliyatining chuqur qatlamlarini tushunishga qaratilgan murakkab jarayonligi haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: so'z boyligi, mantiqiy mashqlar, nutqiy faoliyat, mantiq, qayta hikoyalash.

Abstract. Determining the vocabulary of schoolchildren is a pedagogical, psychological, and methodological challenge. The philosophical foundations of assessing a pupil's vocabulary are based on viewing language as an interconnected part of thought, social interaction, and knowledge. This article discusses how assessing a pupil's vocabulary is a complex process aimed at understanding not only the number of words they know, but also the deeper layers of a person's knowledge, intellect, and social communication skills.

Keywords: vocabulary, logical exercises, speech activity, logic, retelling.

Kirish. Falsafa insonning o'zini to'liq shaxs sifatida anglab yetishiga va tafakkuridagi fikrni nutq orqali atrofdagilarga yetkazishga yordam beradi. Aristotel "So'zlar tushunchalarning belgisidir" degan g'oyani ilgari suradi. Ingliz faylasufi Jon Lokk ham bu qarashning tarafdori hisoblanadi. Demak, inson ongidagi fikr va g'oyalarni so'zlar yordamida bir-biri orqali boshqasiga yetkazadi. Inson nutqini kamol toptirish masalasi nafaqat tilshunoslik ilmining, balki adabiyotshunoslik, tarix, falsafa, mantiq, axloqshunoslik, nafosatshunoslik fanlarining ham asosiy vazifalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Shu bois unga ham ruhiy, ham estetik hodisa sifatida qaraladi. O'tmishda nutq madaniyatiga doir yaratilgan asarlarda fikr ifodalashda notiq oldiga qo'yiladigan mezonlar aniq belgilab qo'yilgan. Bu mezonlarni belgilashda xalqning asrlar davomida shakllangan milliy-ma'naviy qadriyatlarini, og'zaki va yozma nutqda so'zlovchilarning, yozuvchi maqsadining nutq qaratilgan shaxsga yetib borishidagi nutqiy vaziyat, tinglovchi yoki o'quvchining yoshi, jinsi, jamiyatda egallab turgan mavqeyi, ham hisobga olingan. Ajdodlarimiz asarlarida qayd etilgan mazkur mezonlar nutqning grammatik jihatdan to'g'ri bo'lishini, so'zlovchi yoki yozuvchi tomonidan tanlangan so'zlarning fikr ifodalash uchun lozim bo'lgan ma'noni aniq ifodalashi, ifodali va mantiqiy bo'lishini ta'minlashga xizmat qilgan.

Asosiy qism. Bolaning soʻz boyligini aniqlash jarayonida uning tafakkur doirasini, dunyoqarashini hisobga olish lozim. Oʻquvchilarga beriladigan topshiriqlar hamda turli interaktiv metodlar ularning fikrlash doirasidan kelib chiqib tanlanishi kerak. Misol uchun, turli mantiqiy mashqlar orqali ham ularning soʻz boyligini aniqlash mumkin:

1. Bir turdagi narsalarni sanab koʻrsatish va ularni umumlashtiruvchi bir soʻz bilan nomlash;

2. Narsalarning mavzuga tegishli guruhini tuzish;

Bu turdagi mantiqiy mashqlar mazmunli boʻlish bilan birgalikda, oʻquvchilarning tajribasi bilan ham bogʻlanadi. “Ona tili darslarida oʻquvchilarning mustaqil fikrlash, ijodiy matn tuzish koʻnikmalarini shakllantirish taʼlimning asosiy maqsadlaridandir” [Alavutdinova N., 2008. 75]. Shuningdek, ularni toʻgʻri fikrlashga oʻrgatishga, bilimlariga aniqlik kiritishga va tartibga solishga xizmat qilishi kerak. Jumladan, ona tilini oʻrganish jarayonida yozish, oʻqish soʻzlash malakasining shakllanishi, oʻquvchilar dunyoqarashining kengayishi, ijodiy fikrlashining rivojlanishida lugʻat boyligining yetarli boʻlishi zarur omildir. Shuning uchun oʻquvchilarda soʻz boyligini aniqlashning samarali va maqbul yoʻlini tanlash lozim. Koʻp tadqiqotlarda kundalik muloqot uchun kattalarning oʻrtacha 3 mingga yaqin soʻzdan foydalanishi xususida qarashlar mavjud. Biroq, ularning lugʻat boyligi 20 mingga yaqin soʻzdan iborat boʻladi. Insonning soʻz boyligi qanchalik koʻp boʻlsa, uning hayotda muvaffaqiyatga erishish ehtimoli ham shunchalik yuqori boʻladi. Bolani oʻqishga oʻrgatish boʻyicha bir qancha kitoblarni nashr qilgan amerikalik bolalar shifokori Syuzan Kanizaresning taʼkidlashicha, bola qancha koʻp soʻz bilsa, uning oʻqish va yozishni boshlashi shunchalik oson boʻladi va bolaning maktabda oʻqishi va natijada undan yuksak salohiyatli inson boʻlib yetishib chiqish ehtimoli koʻproq boʻlishini aytadi. Shuningdek, u 2-3 yoshda bola 50-300 ta soʻzni, 3-4 yoshda uning soʻz boyligi 500-1,2 ming soʻzgacha koʻpayishini taʼkidlaydi. 4 yoshdan 5 yoshgacha esa bolaning lugʻat boyligi 1,5 -2 ming soʻzgacha oshadi. Olti yoshga toʻlgandan soʻng, oʻrtacha bola 6000 dan ortiq soʻzlarni biladi. Bola maktabga kirgunga qadar uning soʻz boyligi shunchalik koʻpayadiki, u boshqa odam bilan kundalik hayot va uning qiziqish doirasiga kiruvchi narsalar haqida bemalol erkin gaplasha oladi. Bolalarning muloqotga boʻlgan ehtiyoji ularning nutqining rivojlanishini belgilaydi. Demak, bolalarda soʻz boyligini aniqlashni uning kichikligidan boshlash kerak. Chunki uning lugʻatidagi kamchiliklar erta aniqlanadi va uni rivojlantirish uchun harakat qilinadi.

V.A.Kustareva va boshqalar: “Fikrni aniq shakllantirishni talab qilish, masala shartini ongli takrorlatish, mustaqil masala tuzdirish va savollar yordamida masalani yechish yoʻlini tushuntirish koʻnikmasi ustida ishlash oʻquvchilarda qayta hikoyalash, insho va muhokama qilish madaniyatini oʻstiradi”, – deb taʼkidlashadi [Рождественский С., Кустарева А., 1965. 297]. Bolalarning soʻz boyligini aniqlash jarayonida ularning dunyoqarashiga, mantiqiy fikrlashiga va tafakkuriga tashqi muhit qanday tasir oʻtkazayotganini ham eʼtiborga olish zarurdir. Shuningdek, mantiq inson tafakkuri madaniyatini koʻtarish va insoniyatning uzoq tajribasi natijasida takomillashgan tafakkur shakllari, qonunlari va qoidalarini bilish uchun xizmat qiladi.

U inson fikrining ketma – ket, ziddiyatsiz va asosli bo‘lishini ta’minlaydi. Mantiq fani mazmunini chuqurroq o‘rganish kishilarning o‘z tafakkuri va o‘zgalar tafakkuri natijalariga tanqidiy qarash xislatlarini rivojlantiradi. Tafakkurning bu sifatlari esa insonning turli ilmiy va amaliy faoliyatlari sohasidagi ishi uchun katta ahamiyatga ega hisoblanadi. Mantiqiy usullardan to‘g‘ri foydalana olish, ta’lim tarbiya jarayonida aytilayotgan ma’lumotlarning mantiqiy tomonlarini bilish o‘quvchilarda o‘z nutqining asosli bo‘lishini ta’minlaydi, fikrdagi ziddiyatlarni ochishga yordam beradi. Mantiqni yaxshi bilish turli ilmiy uchrashuvlar, munozaralar, muhokamalarda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo‘ladi. Bola qayerda qanday gaplarni gapirishni, o‘zining fikrlarini dalillashni yanada yaxshiroq o‘rganadi. M.R. Lvovning fikriga ko‘ra, bolalar nutqini rivojlantirish bo‘yicha vazifalar dastlab ularning maktabda adabiy til me’yorini o‘zlashtirish jarayonida sodir bo‘ladi [Львов М.Р., 1985. 176]. Keyinchalik, maktabda o‘quvchilar o‘qish va yozish ko‘nikmalarini hamda ular bilan birga og‘zaki va yozma nutqning xususiyatlarini ham o‘zlashtiradilar. Nutq madaniyatini oshirish esa, nutqni rivojlantirishning oxirgi bosqichi hisoblanadi. Muomala odobi bolalarga boshqa kishilar qadr-qimmatini, izzatini joyiga qo‘yishni, an’anaviy axloqiy me’yoriy talablarni bajarishni o‘rgatadi. Shuningdek, u insondagi yaxshi jihatlarni namoyon etishi bilan ham ajralib turadi. Uning eng yorqin, eng sermazmun va eng ifodali namoyon bo‘lishi so‘z, nutq vositasida ro‘y beradi. So‘zlash va tinglay bilish, suhbatlashish madaniyati muomalaning muhim jihatlari tashkil etadi. Shu bois, muomala odobi o‘zini, eng avvalo, shirinsuxanlilik, kamsuqumlik, bosiqlik, xushfe’llilik singari axloqiy me’yorlarda namoyon qiladi. L.Shcherba nutqiy faoliyatni nutqni tushunish hamda undan foydalanish jarayoni sifatida belgilaydi hamda tilni egallashda har ikki jarayonning ham ahamiyati katta ekanligini ta’kidlaydi [Щерба Л.В., 1974. 40].

Xulosa. Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo‘lsak, so‘z boyligining rivojlanishi yoshga qarab sekinlashmaydi, balki yanada ortishda davom etadi. Yillar o‘tgan sari o‘quvchining bilim darajasi, dunyoqarashi, tafakkuri hamda lug‘at boyligi ham kengayib boradi. So‘z boyligi yetarli bo‘lgan o‘quvchining fikrlash qobiliyati rivojlanadi, tanqidiy fikrlashi o‘sadi va dunyoqarashi kengayadi. Shuning uchun o‘quvchilarning so‘z boyligini aniqlash jarayonida ularning so‘z o‘zlashtirish imkoniyatini sinflar kesimida o‘rganish va ularga shu asosda dars jarayonida topshiriqlar hamda turli metodlarni tanlash lozim.

Adabiyotlar

1. Alavutdinova N., Ona tili darsliklarida ijodiy fikrlash ko‘nikmasini shakllantirish metodikasi: Ped. fan. nomz. ...diss. – T., 2008. – 75 b.

2. Рождественский С., Кустарева А., Методика начального обучения русскому языку. “Просвещение”, – М.: 1965. – 297 с.

3. Ziyodova T. Ona tili ta’limi jarayonida o‘quvchilarning so‘z boyligini oshirish: Ped. fan. nomz. ...diss. –T.: 1995. – 31 b.

4. Щерба Л.В. Языковая система и речевая деятельность. – Ленинград: Наука. 1974. – 40 с.

5. Hakimova O. Mantiq va nutq madaniyati. – Toshkent: Xalq merosi, 2002. – 37 b.

6. Львов М.Р. Методика развития речи младших школьников: пособие для учителя. – М.:1985. – 176 с.

O‘ZBEK TILI DARSIDA O‘QUVCHILARGA JOY NOMLARINI (TOPONIMLARNI) O‘RGATISH METODLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH (XO‘JAYLI TUMANI MISOLIDA)

**Nargiza Ismailova,
Nukus shahar 27-sonli umumta’lim
maktabi o‘qituvchisi, mustaqil tadqiqotchi**

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada o‘zbek tili darslarida o‘rin-joy nomlari – toponimlarni aniqlash orqali o‘quvchilarning til, tarix va geografiyaga oid bilimlarini uyg‘unlashtirish metodikasi yoritilgan. Xususan, mazkur yondashuv O‘zbek tili, tarix va geografiya fanlarini integratsiyalash asosida ishlab chiqilgan bo‘lib, fanlararo bog‘liqlikni ta’minlaydi va o‘quvchilarda hududiy anglash, tanishish va mintaqaviy tafakkurni shakllantiradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: toponim, integratsiya, o‘rin-joy nomlari, tarixiy shahar, qishloq, suv havzasi, etnotoponimlar, tarixiy uyg‘unlik.

Abstract. This article explores a methodology for integrating language, history, and geography knowledge in Uzbek language classes through the identification of place names – toponyms. Specifically, this approach is developed on the basis of integrating the subjects of Uzbek language, history, and geography, ensuring interdisciplinary connection. It helps students develop a regional awareness, familiarity with localities, and spatial thinking.

Keywords: toponym, integration, place names, historical city, village, water body, ethnonymic toponyms, historical coherence

Kirish. Toponimika – geografik obyektlar nomlarini o‘rganuvchi soha sifatida nafaqat geografik, balki tilshunoslik va tarixiy bilimlar bilan chambarchas bog‘liq. O‘zbek tili fani orqali o‘quvchilarning mintaqaviy toponimlar haqidagi bilimlarini kengaytirish - milliy ong va o‘zlikni anglashga xizmat qiladi. Ayniqsa, o‘z yashash hududi - Xo‘jayli tumani misolida tarixiy joy nomlarini o‘rganish, ularning kelib chiqishi, ma’naviy-ma’rifiy mazmuni o‘quvchilarning umumiy tafakkurini boyitadi. Ushbu maqolada ana shu maqsadni amalga oshirish uchun o‘zbek tili, tarix va geografiya fanlarining integratsiyasi asosida tashkil etilgan dars tajribasi taqdim etiladi.

Asosiy qism. 1. Integratsiyalashgan yondashuvning ahamiyati O‘zbek tili + Tarix + Geografiya integratsiyasi:

– toponimlar – faqat til hodisasi emas, balki tarixiy, ijtimoiy va madaniy hodisadir;

– tarixiy joy nomlari orqali o‘quvchilar o‘z vatani haqida chuqur ma’lumot oladilar;

– geografik xaritalar orqali joylashuvni aniqlashda fazoviy tafakkur rivojlanadi.

2. Dars ishlanma namunasi (Xo‘jayli tumani asosida)

Mavzu: Matnda o‘rin-joy nomlarini topish (toponimlarni tahlil qilish)
Sinf: 8–9-sinf.

Fanlararo bog‘liqlik: O‘zbek tili – Tarix – Geografiya

Darsning maqsad:

- o‘quvchilar matndan toponimlarni aniqlashni o‘rganadi;
- toponimlarning kelib chiqishini tahlil qilishga o‘rganadi;
- mahalliy tarix va geografiyaga qiziqishi ortadi.

3. Zamonaviy metodlar va amaliy mashg‘ulotlar

Metod/texnika mazmuni

Guruhlarda ishlash | 3 ta guruhga bo‘linadi (har biri alohida topshiriq)
Matn tahlili | X. Abdusadikovning “Aslim naslim – Xo‘jaylim” kitobidan parchalar
YouTube video tahlili | Xo‘jayli tumani haqidagi 3-4 daqiqalik video
Xarita asosida izlash | Toponimlarni joylashuviga qarab xaritadan topish
Taqqoslash metodikasi | Zamonaviy va tarixiy toponimlarni solishtirish

1. Darsning kirish qismi: “Aqliy hujum”dan foydalaniladi.

O‘quvchilarga savollar beriladi:

Qoraqalpog‘istondagi 5 ta eski qal’ani bilasizmi?

Xo‘jayli tumanidagi tarixiy joylarni sanab bering.

Xo‘jayli so‘zini qanday tushunasiz?

O‘quvchilar berilgan savollarga javob beradi va o‘z fikr-mulohazalarini bildiradilar. Ularning tasavvur dunyosini boyitish maqsadida video namoyish etish maqsadga muvofiq bo‘ladi.

2. Xo‘jayli tumani tarixi videosi

Aqliy hujumdan so‘ng Xo‘jayli tumani haqidagi 3-4 daqiqalik YouTube videosi namoyish qilinadi:

YouTube video havolasi:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=koNwvUgVemQ> (misol tariqasida) yoki

“Xo‘jayli tumani tarixi haqida 3 daqiqalik video”:

<https://youtu.be/0cLBqPtFoXI>

3. Matn bilan ishlash

O‘quvchilarga Xaytboy Abdusadikovning “Aslim naslim – Xo‘jaylim” kitobidan parchalar beriladi. 3 guruhga quyidagicha topshiriq beriladi:

1-guruh: Tarixiy o‘rin-joy nomlarini aniqlash.

2-guruh: Ovul nomlarini topish.

3-guruh: Kanal va arna nomlarini aniqlash.

O‘quvchilarga toponimlar haqida ma’lumot beriladi.

O‘zbek tilida o‘rin-joy nomlari, tarixiy joy nomlari, suv havzalari, tog‘, shahar, qishloq, MFY nomlari ko‘p manbalarda uchraydi. Bunday otlar tilda toponimlar deb yuritiladi va katta harf bilan yoziladi. Masalan: Samanko‘l, Gavur qal’a, Tuba ovuli, Antakiya, Mizdakxon majmuasi

5. Amaliy mashg‘ulot: Guruhlarga topshiriqlar

1-guruh: Tarixiy o‘rin-joy otlarini topish

Matn parchasi: Xo‘jayli tumani atrofida qadimda Mizdaxxon, Antakiya, Gavur qal’a, Jumart qassob do‘ngtepaligi, Mazlumxon suluv yodgorligi, Shamun nabi qabri

(maqbarasi) kabi tarixiy joylar bo'lgan. Bu toponimlar xalq og'zaki ijodida yashab kelmoqda.

Topshiriq: Tarixiy toponimlarni toping va bittasining kelib chiqishini izohlang.

2-guruh: Ovul nomlarini aniqlash

Matn:

Tumandagi qadimiy ovullar ichida Naryman ovul, Do'ngizli ovul, Qamishjali, Tuyakash ovul, To'qqiz tom, To'rt tom, Qurbaqa ovul, Alim ovul kabi nomlar mavjud. Har biri qadimiy urug'lar, tabiiy sharoit yoki afsonalarga bog'liqdir.

Topshiriq: Barcha ovul nomlarini yozing va ulardan 2 tasini etimologik tahlil qiling.

3-guruh: Kanal va arna (ariq) nomlarini topish

Matn:

Xo'jayli tumani yerlarini sug'orishda Xanjap, Qo'ng'iroq kanali, Suwanli jap, Janga jap kabi suv inshootlari muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ular yerlar sho'rlanishining oldini olish bilan bog'liq terminlarga misollar aytishadi.

Topshiriq: Kanal va arna (jap) nomlarini yozing, ularning bugungi ahamiyati haqida mulohaza yozing.

O'quvchilar berilgan topshiriqlarni bajaradilar. Javoblari tekshiriladi. Qaysi guruh ko'proq toponimlarni topgani va izohlab berishiga qarab baholanadi.

4. Metodik yondashuvlar

O'qituvchi xohishiga qarab "Insert", "Klaster" "Bumerang", "BBB" metodlari quyidagicha qo'llaniladi:

Insert: O'quvchi matndan bilgan, bilmagan, tushunmagan so'zlarni belgilaydi va toponimlarni ajratadi. (+ bilaman, bilmayman, ? savol tug'ildi)

Klaster usuli: "Qayerlar haqida gap boryapti?" savoli orqali toponimlar guruhi tuziladi.

"Bumerang": O'quvchilar bir-birlariga topgan toponimlari haqida savollar beradilar.

"BBB" jadvali: Bilaman – Bilmoqchiman – Bilib oldim (dars oxirida to'ldiriladi).

Xarita bilan ishlash: Belgilangan toponimlar, Xo'jayli tumani xaritasi maktab devoriy xaritasida yoki interaktiv Google Maps orqali ko'rsatiladi.

O'qituvchi bu metodlardan tashqari dars mashg'ulotlarini Learningapps, Wordwall, Canvada (slyd), Flippity dasturlaridan foydalanish ham tavsiya qilinadi va darsda samarali foydalansa bo'ladi. Agarda elektron doska bo'lmasa, bu materiallar oldindan tayyorlanib, o'quvchilarga tarqatma materiallar tarzida foydalanishi ham mumkin.

5. Mustahkamlash

Yuqoridagi mashg'ulotlar o'tkazilib o'quvchilarning bilimi tekshiriladi. G'olib guruh aniqlanadi va o'quvchilar baholanadi.

Rasmi test orqali o'rin-joy otlarini aniqlash mashqlari beriladi. Masalan: xaritada ko'rsatilgan joylar haqida savollar. O'quvchilarning diqqati va xotirasi tekshiriladi. Gavur qal'a, Shamun nabi maqbarasi, Mazlumxon suluv majmuasi

rasmlari tarqatiladi. O'quvchilar nomlarini to'g'ri topishlari kerak bo'ladi. Nomlarini to'g'ri topgan faol o'quvchilar baholanadi.

6. Qiyoslash

O'quvchilar o'z shahar, ovul, mahalla nomlarini Xo'jayli tumanidagi joy nomlari bilan qiyoslaydilar.

7. Uyga vazifa

O'quvchilar o'z yashash joyidagi o'rin-joy, ovul, suv obyekt nomlarini yozib kelishadi va Xo'jayli tumani toponimlariga qiyosiy tahlil qiladilar.

Xulosa. Xo'jayli tumani toponimlarini matnlardan to'g'ri ajratish bo'yicha ishlab chiqilgan metodik yondashuv nafaqat til darslarida, balki tarix va geografiya fanlarida ham muvaffaqiyatli qo'llanilishi mumkin. Toponimlarni o'rganish orqali o'quvchilar faqat til bilimlarini emas, balki o'z hududining tarixiy xotirasini, geografik tuzilishini chuqurroq tushunishga intiladi. O'qituvchi bu jarayonda integratsiyalashgan yondashuvni qo'llab, zamonaviy texnologiyalar va guruhli ish orqali samarali dars tashkil etishi mumkin Bunday integratsiyalashgan o'quv jarayoni o'quvchilarning fikrlash, tahlil qilish, izohlash va mintaqaviy tushunchalarini mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladi.

Adabiyotlar

1. Abdusadikov X. Aslim naslim – Xo'jaylim. – Nukus: Qaraqalpoq nashriyoti, 2016.
2. Xudoyberganova D. "Toponimika asoslari". Toshkent: O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi, 2010.
3. Yo'ldoshev A. "O'zbek tili nazariyasi". – T.: Fan, 2016.
4. O'zbek tilshunosligi bo'yicha metodik qo'llanma. – T.: O'qituvchi, 2020.
5. Qarshiyev M. "O'zbek tili o'qitish metodikasi". – T.: TDPU, 2020.
6. O'zbekiston geografiyasi. O'quv qo'llanma. – T.: O'qituvchi, 2017.
7. Xo'jayli tumani mahalliy tarixi to'g'risidagi xalq og'zaki manbalari va tadqiqotlar.
8. Geografiya va tarix darslarida integratsiyalashgan yondashuv. – T., 2018.
9. Xo'jayli tumani hokimligi rasmiy sayti va ochiq ma'lumotlar portali.
10. <https://youtu.be/0cLBqPtFoXI> – YouTube video (Xo'jayli tarixi)

THE ROLE OF CONTEXT IN INTERPRETING MODALITY

Ahadova Hulkaroy Zarifxon qizi,

Mustaqil izlanuvchi mme83472@gmail.com

O'zDJTU

Nasirova Gulnora Madaminovna,

PhD, O'zDJTU

Abstract. Modality is a fundamental feature of human language, enabling speakers to express attitudes toward the reality, possibility, necessity, or desirability of situations and states of affairs. It plays a critical role in communication by conveying judgments, assessments, commands, or permissions. However, modality is inherently context-sensitive. Understanding modal meanings requires a careful

consideration of not only the linguistic elements but also the broader situational and cultural context. This article examines how context shapes the interpretation of modality, drawing upon key theoretical insights and empirical studies in linguistics.

Keywords: Modality, context, Palmer, Kratzer, linguistics, epistemic, deontic

The study of modality has a rich history in linguistics, philosophy, and pragmatics. Traditionally, modality has been divided into grammatical and lexical, as well as epistemic and deontic types—distinctions well-documented in the works of Palmer (1986), Coates (1983), and Sweetser (1990).

Palmer (1986) defines modality broadly as the linguistic expression of a speaker's attitude toward a proposition's truth value, distinguishing primarily between epistemic modality (concerning knowledge and belief) and deontic modality (concerning obligation and permission). Palmer emphasizes the importance of context in disambiguating these meanings. Coates (1983) explores modal auxiliary verbs extensively, arguing that their meanings cannot be fixed without recourse to contextual information. She highlights examples where a single modal verb can express multiple modalities depending on pragmatic factors. Sweetser (1990) provides a cognitive-functional account, suggesting that epistemic and deontic modalities are linked through metaphorical mappings, arguing that contextual knowledge is crucial for interpreting such metaphors effectively.

More recent studies have deepened understanding of how context affects modality interpretation: Kratzer (1991) proposes a formal semantic framework where modality is interpreted relative to sets of possible worlds, with conversational background context determining which worlds are considered relevant for assessment. Bybee, Perkins, and Pagliuca (1994) address grammaticalization processes in modality, showing how lexical items develop modal meanings influenced by cultural and situational contexts. Traugott and Dasher (2002) focus on pragmatic factors, explaining that context guides the interpretation of modal expressions through principles such as relevance and speaker intent. Portner (2009) presents a comprehensive framework integrating semantics and pragmatics, underscoring the role of context in specifying the modal base and ordering source, which together define the modality's interpretation.

Context in linguistic modality can be analyzed at multiple levels:

- **Linguistic Context (Co-text):** The surrounding text influences the interpretation of modality. For example, earlier statements providing evidence or setting expectations affect epistemic modal judgments.

- **Situational Context:** The physical environment, time, participants, social roles, and norms impact modal interpretation. For example, "You must leave" uttered by a police officer differs from the same phrase by a friend.

- **Cultural Context:** Shared beliefs, values, and conventions influence which modal meanings are salient or acceptable in interaction. For example, certain cultures may emphasize politeness in requests through indirect modality.

Epistemic modality conveys the speaker's degree of certainty or evidential basis for a claim. Kratzer's (1991) framework conceptualizes it in terms of possible

worlds consistent with what is known. Context provides the knowledge background, situational information, and shared assumptions critical to assessing likelihood and certainty.

Example:

“She must be home.”

- In a context where the speaker sees the lights on and knows the person’s routine, this suggests strong logical inference.
- Without such cues, it could be interpreted differently or remain ambiguous.

Deontic modality relates to social rules, obligations, and permissions, often linked to authority structures and norms. Interpreting deontic modal expressions requires understanding the roles and relationships involved, as well as cultural expectations.

Example:

“You must finish your work.”

- If said by a manager in an office, it conveys obligation.
- If said jokingly by a peer, it may be a casual suggestion.

Context also enriches modal meanings pragmatically. Modal expressions often perform indirect speech acts, where politeness strategies influence how strong or weak a command or request sounds (Brown and Levinson, 1987). Intonation, tone, and facial expression provide further contextual clues.

Modal expressions can be inherently ambiguous, and insufficient context may cause misunderstandings. For example, learners of English often struggle with modal verbs because of their context-dependent semantics (Norris, 2014).

Context-based interpretation of modality poses challenges for language learners and translators, who must master both linguistic forms and contextual cues to convey and comprehend nuances accurately (Ghazala, 2016).

In natural language processing (NLP), modeling context for the interpretation of modality remains a complex task. Advances in AI seek to incorporate contextual understanding for better semantic analysis and dialogue systems (Meyer and Strube, 2020).

Conclusion

The interpretation of modality is inseparable from context. Linguistic, situational, and cultural contexts collectively shape how modal meanings are understood, making context a key factor in communication effectiveness. The interplay between language and context is complex, involving semantic, pragmatic, and cognitive dimensions. Future research and applications—from language teaching to artificial intelligence—must continue to integrate contextual awareness to handle modality accurately and naturally. These studies converge on the conclusion that modality cannot be adequately understood apart from context, as it determines the speaker’s intended meaning and the hearer’s interpretation.

References

1. Brown, P., & Levinson, S. C. (1987). *Politeness: Some universals in language usage*. Cambridge University Press.

2. Bybee, J., Perkins, R., & Pagliuca, W. (1994). *The evolution of grammar: Tense, aspect, and modality in the languages of the world*. University of Chicago Press.
3. Coates, J. (1983). *The semantics of the modal auxiliaries*. Croom Helm.
4. Ghazala, H. (2016). *Translation as problems and solutions: A textbook for university students and trainee translators*. Routledge.
5. Kratzer, A. (1991). Modality. In *Semantics: An international handbook of contemporary research* (pp. 639–650). de Gruyter.
6. Meyer, C. M., & Strube, M. (2020). Computational approaches to modality. *Language and Linguistics Compass*, 14(5), e12396.
7. Norris, J. M. (2014). *Modality and second language learning*. Cambridge University Press.
8. Palmer, F. R. (1986). *Mood and modality*. Cambridge University Press.
9. Portner, P. (2009). *Modality*. Oxford University Press.
10. Sweetser, E. (1990). *From etymology to pragmatics: Metaphorical and cultural aspects of semantic structure*. Cambridge University Press.
11. Traugott, E. C., & Dasher, R. B. (2002). *Regularity in semantic change*. Cambridge University Press.

DAVLAT TILIDA ISH YURITISH KURSINI O‘QITISHDA INNOVATSIYA VA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR

**Toshtemirova Nasiba Xasanovna,
Mustaqil tadqiqotchi, toshtemirova74@gmail.com
Guliston davlat pedagogika instituti**

Annotatsiya: Davlat tilida ish yuritish davlat boshqaruvida muhim vosita hisoblanadi va milliy birdamlikni mustahkamlashda o‘ziga xos o‘rin tutadi. So‘nggi yillarda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining tez rivojlanishi ta‘lim jarayoniga yangi imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda. Shu sababli davlat tilida ish yuritish kurslarini zamonaviy pedagogik innovatsiyalar asosida qayta tashkil etish va interaktiv metodlarni qo‘llash katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu maqolada davlat tilida ish yuritish kursini o‘qitishda innovatsiya va zamonaviy yondashuvlar ko‘rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: ona tili, davlat tili, innovatsiya, texnologiya, metodika, axborot, multimedia.

Abstract: Conducting business in the state language is an important tool in state administration and has a unique place in strengthening national unity. In recent years, the rapid development of information and communication technologies has created new opportunities for the educational process. Therefore, the reorganization of the state language course on the basis of modern pedagogical innovations and the use of interactive methods is of great importance. This article examines innovations and modern approaches to teaching the state language course.

Keywords: native language, state language, innovation, technology, methodology, information, multimedia.

Davlatimiz rahbari 2019-yil 21-oktyabr kuni imzolagan “O‘zbek tilining davlat tili sifatidagi nufuzi va mavqeini tubdan oshirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi Farmonida haqli ravishda alohida qayd etganidek, “bugungi globallashuv davrida har bir xalq, har qaysi mustaqil davlat o‘z milliy manfaatlarini ta‘minlash, bu borada, awalo, o‘z madaniyatini, azaliy qadriyatlarini, ona tilini asrab-avaylash va rivojlantirish masalasiga jiddiy ahamiyat qaratishi tabiiydir”. [1]

Davlatimiz rahbarining mazkur Farmonida o‘zbek tilining davlat tili sifatidagi maqomi hayotimizning barcha jabhalarida to‘la-to‘kis joriy qilinishi uchun tegishli chora-tadbirlar aniq belgilab berilgan, mazkur maqomning muntazamligi uchun davlat va boshqa tashkilotlar, fuqarolarning mas‘ullik intizomi ko‘rsatilgan. Aytish joizki, shu tarzda bir necha o‘n yillar davomida tilimiz rivoji borasida harakatga kelolmagan mexanizmlar bugun faol va samarador harakatga kelmoqda. [2]

Mamlakatimizda davlat tilining maqomi yildan yilga mustahkamlanib borayotgani, uning barcha soha va tizimlarda huquqiy, rasmiy va ijtimoiy vosita sifatida qo‘llanishi kengayib borayotganini kuzatish mumkin. Xususan, oliy ta‘lim muassasalarida davlat tilida ish yuritish kursi muhim fan sifatida joriy etilib, talabalarni rasmiy hujjat turlari, nutq uslubi va yozishmalarning madaniyati bilan tanishtirishga xizmat qilmoqda. Bunda zamonaviy innovatsion yondashuvlar va texnologiyalarni o‘qitish jarayoniga integratsiyalash ehtiyoji tobora oshmoqda.

Davlat tilida ish yuritish kursining asosiy vazifasi – talabalarni rasmiy nutq uslubi, hujjatlar bilan ishlash ko‘nikmalari va davlat tilidagi normativ yozishmalarni puxta egallashga tayyorlashdir. Bu yo‘nalish o‘z ichiga:

- hujjatlarning uslubiy va morfologik xususiyatlari;
- me‘yoriy-terminologik birliklar bilan ishlash;
- rasmiy yozishmalar va ularning strukturasi kabi elementlarni qamrab oladi. [3]

Ta‘lim sohasida innovatsiyalar o‘quv jarayonining samaradorligini oshirish va o‘quvchilarning bilim hamda ko‘nikmalarini yanada chuqurroq egallashiga xizmat qiladi. Xususan, davlat tilida ish yuritish kurslarida zamonaviy texnologiyalar va pedagogik yondashuvlarni joriy etish so‘nggi yillarda faol tatbiq etilmoqda:

- Modulli o‘qitish tizimi – talaba bilimini bosqichma-bosqich baholash va chuqur o‘zlashtirishga xizmat qiladi;
- Interfaol metodlar – “Aqliy hujum”, “Kichik guruhlarda ishlash”, “Holatni tahlil qilish” (Case-study);
- Portfolio usuli – talabalar faoliyatini hujjatlar orqali nazorat qilish.

Multimedia vositalari ta‘lim jarayonini yanada qiziqarli va samarali qiladi. Video darslar, animatsiyalar, infografikalar va interaktiv taqdimotlar o‘quvchilar e‘tiborini jalb qiladi hamda murakkab mavzularni tushunishni osonlashtiradi. Misol uchun:

- Interaktiv taqdimotlar: PowerPoint va Prezi kabi dasturlar yordamida yaratilgan slaydlar mavzuni bosqichma-bosqich ochib beradi;

- Animatsiyalar: Ish yuritish jarayonida qo'llaniladigan til qoidalari va hujjatlarni tayyorlash qoidalari animatsiyalar yordamida ko'rsatiladi, bu esa o'quvchilarga mavzuni vizual tarzda o'rganishga imkon beradi;

- Video rolli o'yinlar: O'quvchilar real ish vaziyatlarini taqlid qiluvchi rolli o'yinlarda ishtirok etib, amaliy ko'nikmalarni rivojlantiradilar.

Simulyatsiya (taqlid qilish) usullari o'quvchilarni real hayotdagi ish jarayonlariga yaqinlashtiradi. Davlat tilida ish yuritish kurslarida simulyatsiya orqali o'quvchilar quyidagi vazifalarni bajarishlari mumkin:

- rasmiy hujjatlarni yozish va tahrirlash;
- ish joyida yuzaga keladigan til va yozma muloqot muammolarini hal qilish;
- tashkiliy yig'ilishlarda qatnashish va bayonnoma yozish.

Bu usul o'quvchilarning mustaqil fikrlash, muammolarni hal qilish va jamoada ishlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi. Innovatsion texnologiyalar yordamida ta'lim jarayoni har bir talabaning individual ehtiyojlari va bilim darajasiga moslashtirilmoqda. Adaptiv ta'lim tizimlari o'quvchining bilimini doimiy tahlil qilib boradi va u uchun eng optimal o'quv materiallarini tanlaydi. Bu tizimlar kamchiliklarni aniqlab, o'quvchiga ularni bartaraf etish uchun qo'shimcha mashqlar beradi.[6]

Individual yondashuv o'quvchilarni ruhiy jihatdan qo'llab-quvvatlaydi va o'zlashtirish jarayonida qiyinchiliklarga duch kelganlarda yordam beradi. Ta'lim jarayonida o'qituvchidan ko'ra, talaba faol subyektga aylanishi lozim. Bunda:

- kompleks amaliy topshiriqlar;
- real hujjat namunalari asoslangan mashg'ulotlar;
- simulyatsion rolli o'yinlar (masalan, "yig'ilish bayoni tuzish", "buyruq yozish" kabi) katta samara beradi.

Davlat tilida ish yuritish kursi faqat nazariy bilim emas, balki amaliy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishga qaratilgan bo'lishi zarur. Bu borada innovatsion metodlar va raqamli vositalardan foydalanish, zamonaviy o'quv dasturlari asosida ta'limni tashkil etish talabalar bilimini chuqurlashtiradi, ularni hayotiy faoliyatga tayyorlaydi.

Adabiyotlar

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining PF-5850-sonli farmoni, 21.10.2019 y.
2. "Davlat tilida ish yuritish asoslari", O'qituvchi nashriyoti, 2020.
3. I. Ermatov. "O'zbek tilining sohada qo'llanishi", Bookmany print nashriyoti, 2024.
4. Xolmurodova G. "Rasmiy uslub va nutq madaniyati", Fan, 2021.
5. Mavlonova R. va boshq. "Innovatsion pedagogika", Ilm Ziyo, 2022.
6. Interaktiv ta'lim metodlari bo'yicha metodik qo'llanma, TDPU, 2023.
7. www.ziyonet.uz – O'zbekiston ta'lim portali.
8. www.grammarly.com, www.languageTool.org – Tilni avtomatik tahlil qilish vositalari.

FONETIKA BO'LIMINI O'RGATISHDA INTERFAOL METODLARNING AHAMIYATI

Egamberdiyeva Vazira G'ulomovna,
Ona tili va adabiyot fani bosh o'qituvchisi
Guliston davlat universiteti akademik litseyi

Annotatsiya. Fonetika bo'limini akademik litsey dasturida berilishi, o'quvchilarga yetkazishda interfaol metodlardan foydalanish o'quvchilarning ham erkin, ham yangicha fikrlashlariga katta yo'l ochib beradi

Kalit so'zlar: fonetika, tovush, unli tovush, undosh tovush, tasnif, vokalizm, konsonantizm, jarangli va jarangsiz undoshlar.

Abstract. The introduction of the Department of Phonetics in the academic lyceum program, the use of interactive methods in the delivery of students, opens a great way for students to think both freely and innovatively

Keywords: phonetics, sound, vowel, consonant, classification, vocalism, consonantism, voiced and unvoiced consonants.

Akademik litseyda ta'lim olayotgan o'quvchilarga dars mashg'ulotlarida berilayotgan bilimlar, ma'lumotlar ularning kundalik turmush tarzi, faoliyati bilan bog'lansa, amaliy zarurat o'laroq singdirilsa, ta'lim ular uchun tom ma'nodagi hayotiy ehtiyojga aylanadi. Ehtiyojga aylanmagan ta'lim quruq axborotni olishga zo'rlaydigan majburiyatga aylanadi. O'quvchilar nima uchun bilim olayotganliklarini, u hayotda qachon, qayerda va qay shaklda kerak bo'lishini bilishlari, his qilishlari lozim. Shundagina ilm olishga ongli intilish, tabiiy ishtiyoq paydo bo'ladi. Ona tili faninig bo'limlarini o'qitishda eng katta kamchilik ham bu bolalarga ma'lumot va qoidalarning quruq yodlatilayotganligidadir. Fonetika bo'limi akademik litseyda ona tili chuqurlashtirib o'qitiladigan guruhlarda

1-kursda o'qitiladi. O'qituvchi har bir til bo'limni o'qitishga kirishishdan avval o'quvchiga ushbu bo'lim nima uchun o'rganilishi kerakligini aniqlashtirib olishi darkor. Nutq tovushlari tizimini o'rganishni boshlashdan oldin "Nima uchun bu bo'limini o'rganamiz?" yoki "Fonetikani o'rganish bizga nima beradi?" qabilidagi savollar qo'yilib, mushohadaga chorlansa, o'rinli bo'ladi.

Fonetika bo'limini o'qitishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlar mavjudki, mashg'ulotlar jarayonida ularga amal qilish lozim bo'ladi. "Fonetika" bo'limini o'quvchilarga o'rgatishda imlo qoidalari va leksikologiya bo'limi bilan bog'liqlikda o'qitish maqsadga muvofiq bo'lar edi.

Akademik litseylarda fonetika bo'limi uchun 12 soat ajratilgan bo'lib, o'quvchilar bu vaqt orasida unli va undosh tovushlar tasnifini, qator va qo'sh undoshlarni, nutq tovushlarining ma'no farqlash vazifasini angelaydi va izohlaydi. Fonetik hodisalar (tovush tushishi, tovush orttirilishi, tovush almashishi)ni o'rganadi, mashqlarni va testlarni tahlil qila oladi.

Fonetika bo'limidan unli tovushlarning qo'llanishini o'rganishda "Konseptual jadval", "Klaster", "Venn diagrammasi", "Insert", "BBB" va shu kabi bir qancha interfaol ta'lim metodlaridan foydalanish mumkin.

“Konseptual jadval” – grafik organayzeri o‘rganilayotgan mavzuni ikki va undan ortiq jihat bo‘yicha taqqoslash va tizimli mushohada qilish, ma‘lumotlarni bir tizimga solish ko‘nikmasini shakllantiradi. O‘quvchilar unli tovushlar haqida to‘liq ma‘lumotga ega bo‘lgach, konseptual jadvalni quyidagi shaklda qo‘llash maqsadga muvofiq hisoblanadi:

1.	Og‘izning ochilish darajasiga ko‘ra	Yuqori tor	i,u
		O‘rta keng yoki o‘rta tor	e,o‘
		Quyi keng yoki quyi tor	a,o
2.	Lablarning ishtirokiga ko‘ra	Lablangan unlilar	i,e,a
		Lablanmagan unlilar	U, o‘,o

“Klaster” – ma‘lumotlar xaritasini jamlash usuli hisoblanib, mavzu mohiyatini markazlashtirish va ochish uchun bir markaz atrofiga g‘oyalar yig‘iladi, umumlashtirilib, ular o‘rtasidagi aloqalarni topish imkonini beradi. Bu metod yordamida o‘quvchi bilan yakka tartibda yoki guruh bo‘lib ishlash mumkin.

Fonetika bo‘limidan “Urg‘u tushmaydigan birliklar” mavzusi bo‘yicha “Klaster” tuzish uchun sinf doskasi yoki katta qog‘oz varag‘i kerak bo‘ladi. Markazga “Urg‘u tushmaydigan birliklar” kalit so‘zi yoziladi. Kalit so‘z atrofiga urg‘u olmaydigan birliklar yozib chiqiladi va chiziq bilan “bosh” so‘zga bog‘lanadi.

“Bilaman. Bilishni xohlayman. Bilib oldim” (BBB) usuli orqali mavzuni o‘quvchilar qay darajada bilishlarini, dars davomida qanchalik mavzuni o‘zlashtirganini va o‘qituvchidan mavzu yuzasidan qanday ma‘lumotlar kutganini aniqlashtirib olish mumkin bo‘ladi. O‘quvchilarga “Undoshlar tasnifi” mavzusi bo‘yicha o‘z bilim darajasini baholash imkonini beradi. Bu usulni qo‘llashda guruhda yakka tartibda yoki jamoa bo‘lib ishlash mumkin. Dars boshlashdan oldin o‘quvchilarga mavzu aytiladi va mavzu yuzasidan o‘zlari uchun tanish bo‘lgan ma‘lumotlarni yozish topshiriladi. Ma‘lumotlarni yozib bo‘lgach, o‘quvchilarga mavzu yuzasidan yana qanday ma‘lumotlarni o‘rganishni istashlarini yozish topshiriladi. Bu ma‘lumotlar dars oxirida umumlashtiriladi. “Bilib oldim “ qismida undoshlar yuzasidan o‘zlari uchun yangi deb hisoblagan ma‘lumotlarni yozadi. Bizga ma‘lumki, maktab darsligida undoshlar faqat hosil bo‘lish o‘rniga ko‘ra tasnif qilinadi. Shu sababli hosil bo‘lish usuli, ovoz va shovqinning ishtirokiga ko‘ra turlari, sonor undoshlar haqidagi ma‘lumotlar o‘quvchilar uchun yangi ma‘lumot hisoblanadi.

Bilaman	Bilishni xohlayman	Bilib oldim
Til undoshlarini Lab undoshlarini	Sonor undoshlar haqida Undoshlarning birlashtiruvchi va farqlovchi belgilari haqida	Sonor undoshlarni Portlovchilarni Sirg‘aluvchilarni Qorishiq undoshlarni

“Venn diagrammasi” dan “Undoshlarning birlashtiruvchi va farqlovchi belgilari” mavzusida undoshlarning hosil bo‘lishida ular o‘rtasidagi farqli tomonlar va o‘zaro o‘xshashliklarni belgilashda foydalanish mumkin, masalan, diagramma

asosida quyida berilgan ko‘rinishda “B” va “P” undoshlarining o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari va ular uchun umumiy jihatlarni ifodalash mumkin:

“B” va “P” undoshlari uchun birlashtiruvchi belgi bu undoshlarning portlovchi va lab-lab undoshligi bo‘lsa, farqlovchi belgisi “B” undoshining jarangli ekanligi, “P” undoshining jarangsiz undoshligi hisoblanadi.

Fonetika bo‘limini o‘rganishda “Insert jadvali” usulidan foydalanish ham yaxshi natijalar beradi.

IZOH:

“V” – men bilgan ma’lumotlarga mos;

“-“ – men bilgan ma’lumotlarga zid;

“+” – men uchun yangi ma’lumot;

“?” – men uchun tushunarsiz yoki ma’lumotlarni aniqlash, to‘ldirish talab etiladi.

Yangi mavzu bo‘yicha o‘quvchilarning muayyan tushunchalarga egaliklarini aniqlash, ularda matnga nisbatan tahliliy yondashish ko‘nikmalarini shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi;

– mustaqil o‘qish, ma’ruza tinglash jarayonida olinadigan ma’lumotlarni bir tizimga keltirish imkonini beradi;

– oldindan olingan ma’lumotni yangisi bilan o‘zaro bog‘lash qobiliyatini shakllantiradi.

“Insert”dan “Undoshlar tasnifi” mavzusida quyidagicha foydalanish mumkin:

V (Men bilgan ma’lumotlarga mos)	+ (Men uchun yangi ma’lumot)	- (Men bilgan ma’lumotlarga zid)	? (Men uchun tushunarsiz yoki ma’lumotni aniqlash, to‘ldirish talab etiladi)
O‘zbek tilida undoshlar soni 23 ta	Tasnifda dj undoshi mavjudligi	Undoshlar 3 tomonlama tasnif qilinadi	Undoshlar tasnifini to‘liqroq tushunishni istayman

Shu tarzda undoshlarning o‘rganilishi rejalashtirilayotgan mavzu bo‘yicha o‘quvchilarning tushunchalarini aniqlashda, ularning o‘z bilimlarini boyitishga bo‘lgan ehtiyojlarini oshirishda yordam beradi. Shuningdek, ular mavzuga oid ma’lumotlar bilan batafsil tanishtiriladi. Umuman olganda, interfaol metodlar ta’lim-tarbiya sifatini yaxshilash, samaradorligini oshirish va ro‘yobga chiqarishda katta amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

Adabiyotlar

1. Omonov H.T. va boshqalar. Pedagogik texnologiyalar va pedagogik mahorat: 5A340605 - «Xalqaro moliya» mutaxassisligining magistrantlari uchun darslik. – T.: Iqtisod-moliya, 2009. – 240 b.
2. Shayakubov Sh.K. Interfaol ta'lim usullari. o'quv-uslubiy qo'llanma

**JAMIYAT VA SHAXS DIALEKTIKASI TEODOR DRAYZER
ROMANLARIDA (BAXTIQARO KERRI VA AMERIKA FOJIASI
ASARLARI MISOLIDA)**

**Soybnazarov Navruzbek Mashrabboy o'g'li,
Tayanch doktorant, Jizzax davlat pedagogika universiteti
soybnazarovnavruz@gmail.com**

Annotatsiya. Teodor Drayzer ijodi naturalistik adabiyotning muhim namunasidir. Uning *Baxtiqaro Kerri* (1900) va *Amerika fojiasi* (1925) romanlari jamiyat bosimi va shaxsiy tanlov o'rtasidagi murakkab ziddiyatlarni ifodalaydi. Ushbu tezisda mazkur romanlar Durkheimning “anomiyasi”, Veberning “temir qafas” va Simmelning pul iqtisodiyoti haqidagi nazariyalari bilan birgalikda tahlil qilinadi. Kerri shaharga ko'chib kelganida jamiyatning iste'molchilik qadriyatlarini bilan to'qnashadi, Klayd esa iqtisodiy tengsizlik va ijtimoiy bosim qurboniga aylanadi. Drayzer qahramonlari ongli erkin tanlov sub'ektlari sifatida emas, balki ijtimoiy tuzilmalarning deterministik oqibatlarini boshidan kechiruvchi shaxslar sifatida tasvirlanadi. Shu tariqa, Drayzer ijodi kapitalistik modernizatsiya sharoitida shaxsiy erkinlik va jamiyat bosimi o'rtasidagi dialektikani badiiy-estetik hamda sotsiologik asosda ochib beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Teodor Drayzer, naturalizm, jamiyat bosimi, shaxsiy tanlov, anomiyasi, kapitalizm, axloqiy tanazzul.

Abstract. The literary oeuvre of Theodore Dreiser represents a significant example of naturalistic fiction. His novels *Sister Carrie* (1900) and *An American Tragedy* (1925) portray the complex conflicts between social pressure and individual choice. This thesis examines these works in conjunction with Durkheim's theory of “anomie,” Weber's concept of the “iron cage,” and Simmel's analysis of the money economy. Carrie, upon moving to the city, encounters the consumerist values of society, while Clyde becomes a victim of economic inequality and social constraint. Dreiser's protagonists are depicted not as fully autonomous subjects of free choice, but as individuals experiencing the deterministic consequences of social structures. In this way, Dreiser's art reveals, on both aesthetic and sociological levels, the dialectic between personal freedom and social pressure under the conditions of capitalist modernization.

Keywords: Theodore Dreiser, naturalism, social pressure, individual choice, anomie, capitalism, moral decline.

XX asr boshlarida AQSh jamiyatida kapitalizm, sanoatlashuv va iste'mol madaniyati kuchayib bordi. Bu jarayon shaxsning erkin tanlov imkoniyatlarini cheklab, uni jamiyatning ulkan iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy kuchlariga tobe qildi. Naturalistik adabiyot aynan shu muhitda shakllanib, inson taqdiri ustidan ijtimoiy

bosimning hukmronligini yoritdi. Teodor Drayzerning romanlari bu jarayonlarning eng yorqin badiiy aksidir.

Barrishga ko'ra, naturalistik adabiyot "qahramonlarning hayoti ularga tushunarli bo'lmagan, ularga qarshi turishga ojiz bo'lgan ulkan va shaxsiy bo'lmagan kuchlar tomonidan boshqarilishini tasvirlaydi" [Barrish, 2012, b. 116]. Bu ta'rif Teodor Drayzer romanlari uchun ayniqsa dolzarbdir. Chunki uning qahramonlari tashqi tomondan oddiy shaxsiy qarorlar qabul qilayotgandek ko'rinsada, aslida ular jamiyatdagi iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy tuzilmalarning bevosita ta'sirida harakat qiladilar. "Baxtiqaro Kerri" romanida Kerri shaharga kelgan ilk sahnadan boshlab iste'mol madaniyatining jozibasiga jalb qilinadi. Poyezdda ketayotganida uning tasavvurlari yangi hayot va shon-shuhrat haqidagi orzular bilan to'ladi. Ammo bu orzular o'zidan emas, balki jamiyat tomonidan shakllantirilgan "muvaffaqiyat" me'yorlaridan oziqlanadi. Kerri shahardagi ilk ishidan qoniqmay, tez orada o'zining moddiy va estetik ehtiyojlarini qondirish uchun boyroq homiylarga suyanishga majbur bo'ladi. Demak, uning "tanlovi" mustaqil qaror emas, balki iste'mol jamiyatining bosimi ostida shakllangan ehtiyojlarning ifodasidir. Drayzer tasvirida Kerri individual istaklarini amalga oshirmoqchi bo'ladi, ammo ularning shakllanish manbai ijtimoiy muhit va kapitalistik qadriyatlardan kelib chiqadi.

Xuddi shuningdek, "Amerika fojiasi" romanida Klayd Griffiths o'zining "erkin" tanlovlarini amalga oshirayotgandek ko'rinsa-da, aslida u ijtimoiy tengsizlik va korporativ kapitalizm qurboniga aylanadi. U dastlab past tabaqadagi otasining diniy va kambag'al oilaviy muhitidan chiqib ketishga intiladi, biroq bu intilish ham shaxsiy mustaqillik emas, balki jamiyat tomonidan unga yuklangan "ko'tarilish" orzusi mahsulidir. Klaydning Roberta bilan bo'lgan munosabatlari ham shu ijtimoiy bosimni ochib beradi: u Roberta bilan oila qurishni istaydi, biroq yuqori tabaqaga mansub Sandra bilan yashash orzusi ustun keladi. Bu orzuni amalga oshirish uchun qilgan tanlovi – Roberta hayotiga qasd qilish – shaxsiy erkin qaror emas, balki kapitalistik ijtimoiy tuzilmaning mafkuraviy bosimi natijasi sifatida shakllanadi. Shunday qilib, Drayzer qahramonlarining hayoti erkinlik va mustaqillikni izlashga qaratilgandek ko'rinsada, ularning harakati jamiyatning ulkan va shaxsiy bo'lmagan kuchlari tomonidan doimiy ravishda boshqariladi. Bu holat naturalistik adabiyotning markaziy tamoyillaridan biri – shaxs taqdirini belgilovchi kuchlarning determinizmga asoslangan hukmronligi – Drayzer ijodida aniq badiiy shaklga ega ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

Durkheimning anomiya nazariyasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, jamiyatdagi tezkor iqtisodiy o'sish va sanoatlashuv natijasida ijtimoiy nazorat zaiflashadi, buning oqibatida inson istaklari chegarasiz kuchga aylanib, an'anaviy me'yorlarni buzadi va tartibsizlik, ya'ni anomiya holati yuzaga keladi [Durkheim, 1951, bb. 253–254]. XX asr boshlaridagi AQSh jamiyatida kapitalizm va iste'mol qadriyatlarining kuchayishi aynan shu jarayonlarni kuchaytirgan. Teodor Drayzerning *Amerika fojiasi* romanida Klayd Griffiths obrazi buni yorqin ifodalaydi. U diniy va oddiy oilaviy muhitdan chiqib, shahar hayotida ijtimoiy obro' va moddiy farovonlikka erishishga intiladi. Ammo bu intilish shaxsiy mustaqillik emas, balki anomiya sharoitida shakllangan ehtirolarning natijasidir. Iqtisodiy raqobat va iste'molchilik bosimi ostida Klaydning

qadriyatlarini yemiriladi, axloqiy asoslari zaiflashadi va u jamiyatning mafkuraviy bosimiga bo'ysunadi. Natijada uning "tanlovi" jinoyatga olib boruvchi muqarrar oqibatga aylanadi. Shu tarzda, Drayzer qahramoni orqali iqtisodiy o'zgarishlar va shaxsiy ehtiyojlar o'rtasidagi keskin ziddiyat insonni ma'naviy tanazzul sari yetaklashi ochiq ko'rsatiladi.

Maks Veber kapitalistik tuzumni inson erkinligini cheklovchi, uni ma'naviy-axloqiy jihatdan "temir qafas"ga soluvchi kuch sifatida tasvirlab, shunday deydi: "*Man is dominated by the making of money, by acquisition as the ultimate purpose of his life*" [Veber, 1930, b. 11]. Bu jumla inson hayotining ma'nosi moddiy manfaat va boylik orttirishga qaratilib qolganini ochib beradi. Veberning nazariyasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, zamonaviy kapitalizm ratsional mantig'i bilan individni qamrab oladi va uning barcha intilishlarini iqtisodiy samaradorlik mezoniga bo'ysundiradi. Teodor Drayzer romanlaridagi qahramonlar ham aynan shu "temir qafas"ning bevosita qurbonlari sifatida gavgdalanadi. Masalan, Kerri o'z hayotining mazmunini iste'mol va tashqi hasham orqali topishga urinadi. U shaxsiy erkinlikni moddiy ko'rinishlarda izlaydi, biroq bu uni yanada kuchliroq jamiyat bosimiga bog'laydi. Klayd esa jamiyatning moddiy talablariga moslasha olmagan uchun halokatli yo'lga kiradi, bu esa kapitalizmning ratsionalizatsiya va iste'molga asoslangan tizimida shaxsiy tanlovning qanchalik cheklanganligini namoyon qiladi. Shu tariqa, Veber tasvirlagan "temir qafas" metaforasi Drayzer romanlarida badiiy shakl kasb etib, shaxs va jamiyat o'rtasidagi ziddiyatni chuqurroq anglash imkonini beradi. Teodor Drayzer romanlari shaxsiy tanlov va jamiyat bosimi o'rtasidagi ziddiyatni chuqur badiiy-estetik shaklda yoritadi. Durkheimning anomiya konsepsiyasi va Veberning nazariy qarashlari nuqtai nazaridan qaralganda, Kerri yoki Klayd singari qahramonlar erkin sub'ektlar sifatida emas, balki kapitalistik tuzumning qat'iy va shaxsiy bo'lmagan kuchlari ta'sirida harakat qiluvchi obrazlar sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Ularning intilishlari shaxsiy orzularning mahsuli bo'lib ko'rinsa-da, aslida jamiyat tomonidan belgilangan iqtisodiy va iste'molchilik me'yorlariga bo'ysundirilgan. Shu bois Drayzer ijodi adabiy naturalizmning yorqin namunasi sifatida nafaqat individual fojealarni ko'rsatadi, balki XX asr boshidagi Amerika jamiyatida axloqiy tanazzul va ijtimoiy determinatsiya muammolarini ham tahlil qiluvchi muhim sotsiologik manba vazifasini bajaradi.

Adabiyotlar

1. Barrish, P. J. (2012). *Crisis of Agency: Literary Naturalism, Economic Change, and "Masculinity."* Stanford University Press.
2. Durkheim, É. (1952). *Suicide: A Study in Sociology* (J. A. Spaulding & G. Simpson, Trans.). Routledge.
3. Dreiser, T. (1900). *Sister Carrie*. Doubleday, Page & Co.
4. Dreiser, T. (1925). *An American Tragedy*. Boni & Liveright.
5. Simmel, G. (2004). *The Philosophy of Money* (D. Frisby, Ed.). Routledge.
6. Weber, M. (1930). *The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism*. Routledge.

INFORMAL TA'LIM MUHITIDA BO'LAJAK INGLIZ TILI O'QITUVCHILARINING NUTQIY KO'NIKMALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODIKASI

Azimova Gulamol Begimqul qizi,
O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti tayanch doktoranti
guljamolazimova15@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada talabalarning nutqiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda qo'llaniladigan metodlar haqida muallifning fikr va mulohazalari bayon qilingan. Xususan, nutqiy ko'nikmalarining turlariga hamda olim va metodistlarning ular haqidagi qarashlariga alohida to'xtalib o'tilgan. Nutqiy ko'nikmalarining rivojlantirishda qo'llanilishi muhim ahamiyat kasb etadigan informal ta'lim muhiti haqida ma'lumot berilgan. Ushbu informal ta'lim muhitida talabaning mustaqil faoliyatini tashkil qilish bosqichlari taklif etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: informal ta'lim, nutqiy ko'nikmalar, bo'lajak ingliz tili o'qituvchisi, til o'rganish uslublari, yozish ko'nikmasi, til bilish darajalari, gapirish ko'nikmasi.

Abstract. This article presents the author's thoughts and observations on the methods used to develop students' speech skills. In particular, the types of speech skills and the views of scientists and methodologists on them are discussed. Information is provided about the informal educational environment, where the use of speech skills in the development of speech skills is of great importance. The stages of organizing the student's independent activity in this informal educational environment are proposed.

Keywords: informal education, speech skills, future English teacher, language learning styles, writing skills, language proficiency levels, speaking skills.

Hozirgi globallashtirish sharoitida til ta'limiga oid metodikani takomillashtirish, xorijiy til o'qitishga oid zamonaviy yondashuvlarni qayta ko'rib chiqish muhim masalalardan biri hisoblanadi. Xususan, talabaning darsdan tashqari vaqtida mustaqil faoliyati orqali nutqiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish jarayonini tashkil etish muhim masala hisoblanadi.

Nutqiy ko'nikmalar-til o'rganuvchining erkin muloqot qila olishini ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi. Ingliz tilida nutq faoliyati turlari sifatida o'qish, yozish, gapirish, tinglab tushunish ko'nikmalari nazarda tutiladi. Nutqiy ko'nikmalar tushunchasi esa, og'zaki nutqiy ko'nikma va yozma nutqiy ko'nikma turlariga bo'linadi. Og'zaki nutqiy ko'nikma "gapirish ko'nikmasi", "speaking" kabi terminlar bilan ataladi hamda dialogik va monologik nutqni o'z ichiga oladi. Monologik nutq-bir shaxning nutqiy faoliyati bo'lib, yakkanutq nomi bilan uchraydi. Yakkanutqda fikrlar bir-biriga bog'langan holda namoyon bo'ladi. Juftnutq-ikki va undan ortiq shaxslarning o'zaro nutqiy faoliyati hisoblanadi. Dialogik nutq replikalardan tashkil topadi. Replika savol-savol, savol-javob, xabar-xabar kabi tuzilmalar ko'rinishida bo'lishi mumkin. J. Jalolov yakkanutq va juftnutqning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari sifatida quyidagilarni sanab o'tgan:

-uzluksiz hukm suradi;

-mazmunan izchil, ifodalangan g'oyalar tayanch jumlar vositasida asta-sekin rivojlanadi;

-fikir-mulohazalarning ma'lum darajada tugallanganligi nutq namunalarida ifodalanadi.

Juftnutq replikalardan tashkil topadi. Ushbu replikalar savol-savol, savol-javob, xabar-savol, xabar-xabar ko'rinishida bo'lishi mumkin. Juftnutqning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari:

-ajralmas dialogik birlikning nutqiy vaziyatga mos kelishi;

-dialogik birlikdagi ellips va qisqartmalarning o'z o'rnida qo'llanishi;

-suhbatdoshlarning replikalari mazmunan bog'lanishi [Jalolov J., 2012. 241]

Yozma nutqiy ko'nikma nutq analizatorlarining barchasi qatnashadigan murakkab faoliyat hisoblanadi. Yozuvda tovush va harf timsollari aks etadi, adabiyotlarda "writing", "yozuv ko'nikmasi" atamaları bilan nomlanadi. Ingliz tilida yozuv ko'nikmasining rivojlanganligi mezonlari sifatida quyidagilar belgilangan:

1. Task achievement-vazifaga erishish;

2. Coherence, cohesion-uyg'unlik;

3. Lexical resource-leksik manba;

4. Grammatical range, accuracy-grammatik diapazon, aniqlik.

Nutqiy ko'nikmalarning turlari

Bo'lajak ingliz tili o'qituvchilarining nutqiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda informal ta'lim muhitining o'rni ahamiyatlidir. Ta'lim to'g'risidagi qonunning 19-moddasida ta'lim turlari sifatida rasmiy ta'lim, norasmiy ta'lim va informal ta'lim belgilangan. Unga ko'ra, "Rasmiy ta'lim davlat ta'lim muassasalari hamda davlat tomonidan tan olingan akkreditatsiyadan o'tgan nodavlat ta'lim tashkilotlari ishtirokidagi institutsionallashtirilgan (muayyan qoidalar va normalarni mujassamlashtiruvchi), aniq maqsadga yo'naltirilgan va rejalashtirilgan ta'limdir. Norasmiy ta'lim ta'lim xizmatlari taqdim etilishini ta'minlovchi shaxs yoki tashkilot tomonidan institutsionallashtirilgan (muayyan qoidalar va normalarni

mujassamlashtiruvchi), aniq maqsadga yo'naltirilgan va rejalashtirilgan bo'lib, shaxsni butun hayoti davomida o'qitishdagi rasmiy ta'limga qo'shimcha va (yoki) uning muqobilidir. Informal ta'lim aniq maqsadga yo'naltirilgan, ammo institutsionallashtirilmagan (muayyan qoidalar va normalarni mujassamlashtirmagan), rasmiy yoki norasmiy ta'limdan ko'ra kamroq tashkillashtirilgan va tarkiblashtirilgandir hamda oiladagi, ish joyidagi, yashash joyidagi va kundalik hayotdagi o'quv faoliyatini o'z ichiga olishi mumkin."

Bundan kelib chiqadiki, informal ta'lim talabaning mustaqil o'rganish faoliyatini tashkil etish muhiti hisoblanadi. Kums va Ahmad informal ta'limni har bir shaxsda umrbod davom etuvchi uy yoki ish muhitida kitob, gazeta o'qish hamda film, televizor tomosha qilish orqali bilim va ko'nikma to'plash jarayoni sifatida e'tirof etishadi. [Kums, Ahmad., 1974] Nutqiy ko'nikmalarni informl ta'lim muhitida rivojlantirish uchun mustaqil ta'lim faoliyati yo'lga qo'yilishi lozim. Bu jarayonda o'qituvchining roli muhim ahamiyatga ega. Mustaqil ta'lim olish faoliyat olib boruvchi talaba o'z shaxsiyatini anglashi lozim. Bunda talabaning til bilish darajasi, o'rganish uslubi aniqlab olinishi va mustaqil ta'lim ularga asoslangan holda tashkil etilishi zarur. J.K. Kercher va G. T. Bettslar, mustaqil ta'limda talabalar nafaqat o'zlarining ta'lim ehtiyojlarini aniqlaydi, balki ta'lim maqsadlarini belgilab, ularga mustaqil ravishda erishish usullarini ishlab chiqadilar, ta'lim yutuqlarini nazorat qiladilar va baholaydilar-degan. [J.K. Kercher va G. T. Betts., 1999.14]

O'rganish uslublarini aniqlashda VAKT texnologik modelidan keng qo'llaniladi. Unga ko'ra, talaba axborotlarni qaysi usulda tezroq qabul qilishga moslashganligi to'rt yo'nalishda o'z aksini topadi. Birinchi turdagi o'rganuvchilar visual learners deya nomlanadi, ular yangi ma'lumotlarni kino, film, rasm kabi ko'rgazmali vositalar yordamida samarali o'rganishadi. Ikkinchi turdagi o'rganuvchilar audial deya nomlanadi, ular axborotni eshitish orqali yaxshiroq qabul qilishadi. Turli radio eshittiruvlar, musiqalar, audio kitoblar audial til o'rganuvchilar uchun mos materiallar hisoblanadi. Kinestetik va taktil o'rganuvchilar yangi bilim va ko'nikmalarni ushlab, teginish, amalda bajarib ko'rish kabi harakatlar orqali tezroq o'zlashtirishadi.

Adabiyotlar

1. Jalolov J. Chet tili o'qitish metodikasi. – Toshkent, 2012. – 241 b.
2. Betts G.T., Kercher J.K. The autonomous learner model: Optimizing ability. – the USA: ALPS Publishing, 1999. – 14 p.
3. Coombs, P. H., & Ahmed, M. (1974). Attacking rural poverty: How non-formal education can help. Baltimore, MD: John Hopkins University Press.
4. Azimova G. Integrative Approaches to developing speaking skills through authentic materials...// International journal of pedagogics.-2025.-Vol.05.-85-88b.
5. https://lex.uz/docs/5013007?ONDATE=01.02.2024&utm_source=perplexity

TA'LIMYIY DISKURS: NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDAGI AHAMIYATI

*Sharipova Gulshod Shavkat qizi,
Is'hoqxon Ibrat nomidagi Namangan davlat chet tillari instituti,
tayanch doktorant,*

E-mail: sharipovagulshod123@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. Maqolada ta'limiy diskurs tushunchasining nazariy asoslari, uning lingvistik va metodik xususiyatlari, shuningdek xorijiy tillarni o'qitish jarayonida tutgan o'rni yoritilgan. Diskursiv yondashuv til o'qitishda kommunikativ kompetensiyani shakllantirish, madaniyatlararo muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish va ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qilishi ilmiy-nazariy tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: diskurs, ta'limiy diskurs, pedagogik diskurs, lingvistik muhit, kommunikativ kompetensiya, xorijiy til o'qitish, diskursiv yondashuv.

Abstract. The article discusses the theoretical foundations of the concept of educational discourse, its linguistic and methodological characteristics, as well as its role in the process of teaching foreign languages. The scientific and theoretical analysis of the discursive approach to language teaching serves to form communicative competence, develop intercultural communication skills, and increase educational effectiveness.

Keywords: discourse, educational discourse, pedagogical discourse, linguistic environment, communicative competence, foreign language teaching, discursive approach.

Kirish

XXI asrda ta'lim jarayonini samarali tashkil etishda nutq va muloqotning ahamiyati yanada ortib bormoqda. Xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda faqat grammatik qoidalar yoki leksik birliklarni o'rgatish emas, balki ularni real kommunikativ vaziyatda qo'llashni ta'minlash muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Shu munosabat bilan tilshunoslik va pedagogika sohalarida keng qo'llanilayotgan "diskurs" tushunchasi alohida e'tiborga loyiq. Diskurs – bu nafaqat matn yoki nutqiy faoliyat, balki uni yaratuvchi ijtimoiy-kultural kontekst bilan uzviy bog'liq bo'lgan hodisadir (Van Deyk, 1997).

Tadqiqotlar metodologiyasi

"Diskurs" termini ilk marotaba XX asrning 50-yillarida fanga kirib kelgan, dastlab ushbu ibora 1952-yilda nashr etilgan "Diskurs tahlili" deb nomlangan maqolada amerikalik tilshunos Z.Xarris tomonidan qo'llanilgan. Diskurs nazariyasiga oid tadqiqotlar (Fuko, 1972; Van Deyk, 1997; Fairclough, 1992) nutqiy faoliyatni ijtimoiy-madaniy kontekstda o'rganish zarurligini ko'rsatadi. Ta'limiy diskursni o'rganish rus va xorijiy olimlar tomonidan muhim e'tibor bilan ko'rib chiqilgan. V.I.Karasik, N.A. Komina va boshqa rus olimlari pragmatikognitiv, leksik-semantik va lingvokulturologik jihatlarini tahlil qilgan. Hozirgi zamon tadqiqotchilari, masalan, J.P. Gee va M.A. Halliday, ta'lim jarayonida kommunikativ tomonini o'rganishga e'tibor qaratmoqda. Fransuz olimi G.Desbiens ta'limiy diskursni "pedagogik diskurs" deya ta'rif berib, uni ta'lim-siyosat, ta'lim institutsiyalari va o'qituvchilik kasbi atrofida shakllangan pedagogik g'oyalar va amaliyotlar tizimi

sifatida tushunadi. Bu diskurs, Desbiensga ko'ra, o'qituvchilik va bilim berish jarayonini shakllantirishda markaziy rol o'ynaydi, lekin uning ma'lum cheklov va xavflari mavjudligini ta'kidlagan. Pedagogik nutq haqiqatan ham o'qitishni o'quvchilarning psixologiyasi va ijtimoiy-madaniy muhitiga, ularning bilim qobiliyatlariga, ularning intilishlari va bevosita qiziqishlariga moslashtirishni talab qiladi –deya ta'riflagan.

Yana bir qator olimlardan Claude Désirat va Tristan Hordé tomonidan 1977-yilda Languages ilmiy jurnalining maxsus sonida (№45) pedagogik diskurs tushunchasi, uning shakllanishi, xususiyatlari va ijtimoiy-ideologik o'rni chuqur tahlil qilinadi. Pedagogik diskurs deganda maktab, ta'lim muassasalari, o'quv dasturlari, darsliklar, o'qituvchi ko'rsatmalari, hukumat qarorlari orqali shakllanadigan nutq va matnlar tushuniladi. U nafaqat bilimni yetkazish, balki ijtimoiy qadriyatlarni singdirish vositasi hamdir.

Hozirgi kunda uning amaliy ahamiyati o'qituvchilar uchun: o'z nutqining ta'sirini, undagi ideologik va tarbiyaviy yukini, ma'suliyatini anglash imkonini bersa, jamiyat uchun: pedagogik diskurs yordamida qanday g'oyalar avlodlarga o'tishini tushunish mumkin. Xullas, C. Désirat ta'limiy diskursni faqat bilim beruvchi emas, balki jamiyat mafkurasini tarqatuvchi, ijtimoiy ongini shakllantiruvchi nutq turi sifatida ko'radi. Shuning uchun uni o'rganish xorijiy tillarni o'qitish metodikasida ham, umuman pedagogika nazariyasida ham muhim hisoblanadi.

O'zbek olimlari, jumladan, J.S. Safarov va L.R. Raupova diskursiv tahlil sohasida o'z tadqiqotlarini olib bormoqda, shuningdek, A.B. Tumanova va V.K. Sobirovning ishlarini ham yodda tutish lozim. Bu tadqiqotlar ta'lim nutqining nazariy va amaliy jihatlarini chuqurroq tushunishga yordam beradi.

Ta'lim jarayonida yuzaga keladigan barcha kommunikativ faoliyat ta'limiy diskurs sifatida o'rganiladi. Ta'limiy diskurs – o'qituvchi va talaba o'rtasidagi hamda ta'lim jarayonida shakllanadigan nutqiy amaliyotlar majmuasidir. Ushbu tushuncha nafaqat lingvistik, balki metodik, psixologik va ijtimoiy jihatlarni ham qamrab oladi. Ta'limiy diskurs quyidagi xususiyatlari bilan ajralib turadi:

Maqsadga yo'naltirilganlik – ta'limiy maqsad (bilim berish, o'zlashtirish, rivojlantirish) asosiy vazifadir;

Subyektlararo muloqot – o'qituvchi va o'quvchi, shuningdek, guruhlararo muloqot asosiy komponent hisoblanadi;

Nutq janrlarining xilma-xilligi – savol-javob, tushuntirish, bahs, munozara, topshiriq, taqdimot kabi janrlar mavjud;

Kontekstual xususiyatlar – madaniyatlararo omillar, ijtimoiy qadriyatlar va shaxsiy tajribalar bilan bog'liqlik.

Xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda ta'limiy diskursning o'rni

An'anaviy til o'qitish metodlarida asosan grammatik qoidalar va lug'at boyligiga urg'u berilgan bo'lsa, zamonaviy metodologiya diskursiv yondashuvni ustuvor hisoblaydi. Diskursiv yondashuvning xorijiy til o'qitishdagi o'rni:

Real nutqiy vaziyatlar yaratish – o'quvchilarni hayotiy muloqot sharoitiga tayyorlaydi;

Interaktiv metodlardan foydalanish – debat, rolli o‘yin, loyiha ishlari, munozara orqali tilni faol qo‘llaydi ,

Kontekstual ta’limda, ya’ni so‘z va gaplarni alohida emas, balki nutqiy vaziyatda o‘zlashtirish imkonini beradi.

Madaniyatlararo kompetensiyani rivojlantirish – til bilan birga madaniy qadriyatlarni ham o‘zlashtirishni ta’minlaydi;

Tanqidiy va ijodiy fikrlashni shakllantirish – talaba o‘z fikrini asoslash, dalillar bilan qo‘llash imkoniyatiga ega bo‘ladi. Exemple:

- *Pardon, je cherche la rue Victor Hugo.*

- *La rue Victor Hugo ? Et bien, vous êtes très loin...*

- *C'est compliqué d'y aller à pied ?*

- *Oui et non, vous devez remonter la rue Nationale jusqu'au pont, vous traversez, vous prenez à droite et vous allez longer la rivière sur deux ou trois cents mètres. Vous allez voir une place avec une église, la rue Victor Hugo est juste derrière... Mais vous savez, le plus simple, c'est de prendre le bus...*

- *Vous savez comment y aller en bus ?*

- *Oui, c'est la ligne 21. Vous descendrez à l'arrêt Victor Hugo. Vous ne pourrez pas vous tromper.*

- *Merci beaucoup !*

- *Je vous en prie, bonne journée.*

- *Bonne journée, au revoir.*

Suhbat “yo‘l so‘rash va topish” vaziyatiga qurilgan. O‘quvchilar kontekstni tasavvur qilib, so‘z va iboralarni vaziyatga bog‘lab o‘rganadilar. Bu yerda o‘quvchilar diskursni idrok etish, tushunish va o‘zlari yaratishni mashq qiladilar. Suhbat nafaqat so‘z boyligini, balki nutqiy strategiyalarni ham (savol berish, tushuntirish, minnatdorchilik bildirish, xayrlashish) o‘rgatadi. Rol o‘ynash metodi (Jeu de rôle / Role-play). Ikki yoki bir necha o‘quvchi vaziyatni jonlantiradi. Bir o‘quvchi “yo‘l so‘rovchi”, ikkinchisi “yo‘l ko‘rsatuvchi” bo‘lib chiqadi. Madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya yondashuvi, manzil so‘rash – bu madaniy kompetensiyani ham talab qiladi. Fransuz tilida muloqot qilayotganda odobiy shakllar (“**Pardon...**”, “**Merci beaucoup**”, “**Je vous en prie**”)ni ishlatish orqali o‘quvchilar madaniyatlararo muloqot qoidalarini ham o‘rganadilar.

Xulosa

Ta’limiy diskurs zamonaviy pedagogika va lingvistika fanlarida muhim tadqiqot obyekti bo‘lib, u nafaqat bilim berish, balki shaxsning kommunikativ kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishga ham xizmat qiladi. Xorijiy tillarni o‘qitishda diskursiv yondashuv o‘quvchilarning real nutqiy vaziyatlarda samarali muloqot qila olish malakasini shakllantiradi. Shu sababli, ta’limiy diskursni chuqur o‘rganish va uni amaliyotga tadbiiq etish zamonaviy ta’limning dolzarb vazifalaridan biridir.

Adabiyotlar

1. Desbiens G. Réflexions sur le «discours pédagogique » à l’occasion de la réforme du c.a.p.e.s. de philosophie

2. Foucault, M. (1972). The Archaeology of Knowledge. London: Routledge.

3. Desirat C. Formation des discours pédagogiques, Langages Année 1977 45 pp. 3-8
 4. Van Dijk, T. A. (1997). Discourse as Structure and Process. London: SAGE Publications.
 5. Fairclough, N. (1992). Discourse and Social Change. Cambridge: Polity Press.
 6. Gee, J. P. (2011). An Introduction to Discourse Analysis: Theory and Method. New York: Routledge.
 7. Halliday, M. A. K. (1985). An Introduction to Functional Grammar. London: Arnold.
 8. S.T. Israilova, D.Jumanova Diskurs va uning ilmiy talqini
-

PROBLEMS IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AND THEIR SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS

Mirzayeva Xurshida Olimjonovna,
Gulistan State University
Faculty of philology, teacher
khurshidamirzaeva@gmail.com

Shodmonova Dildora Davronovna,
Gulistan State University
Faculty of philology, English
2nd year student
shodmonovadildora98@gmail.com

Annontation: This article analyzes the main problems encountered in the process of learning foreign languages, the causes of their emergence, and scientifically grounded solutions. Psychological, methodological, linguistic, and organizational factors are considered separately, and effective ways of overcoming them are highlighted. The findings show that traditional approaches are not sufficient for effective foreign language learning; instead, communicative methods, modern pedagogical technologies, motivational strategies, and an integrative learning environment are required.

Keywords: Foreign language, educational problems, motivation, methodology, psychological barriers, communicative approach, pedagogical technology, integration.

Introduction: The process of globalization places new demands on modern individuals. Knowledge of foreign languages is becoming important not only in professional activities but also in daily life. Today, English serves as an international means of communication worldwide, while other languages also play a significant role in the development of science, culture, and economic relations.

At the same time, mastering a foreign language is a complex psycholinguistic phenomenon. It depends on the learner's intellectual capacity, motivation, psychological readiness, linguistic environment, and teaching methodology. Various

obstacles arise during the learning process, which may slow down or significantly reduce the effectiveness of learning.

This article analyzes the most common problems in foreign language learning. Each problem and its causes are considered separately, and solutions are proposed on the basis of modern scientific approaches.

Main part:

1. Problems and Their Causes

1.1. Psychological problems

One of the most common barriers in language learning is psychological factors. Students often feel shy when speaking in front of an audience, fear making mistakes, and lack confidence in their abilities. Such conditions hinder active language use. Psychological pressure, social comparison, and low self-esteem slow down the learning process.

1.2. Lack of motivation

Both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation play an important role in language learning. If learners do not have a clear goal for learning a language, their interest decreases. In addition, if the learning process focuses only on theory with little practical training, results may not be visible for a long time, reducing learners' willingness to continue studying.

1.3. Methodological problems

In many educational systems, the traditional grammar-translation method still dominates. While this approach develops theoretical knowledge, it is ineffective in building communicative competence. As a result, learners may know grammar rules but fail to speak freely. Moreover, monotonous lessons reduce learners' interest and lead to boredom.

1.4. Linguistic difficulties

Differences between the native and target languages also create challenges. Specific sounds, new grammatical structures, or complex verb systems may be difficult for learners. Such differences slow down both comprehension and language production.

1.5. Organizational and technical problems

In many institutions, the use of technology in teaching foreign languages is limited. Without multimedia tools, interactive programs, and online resources, learners lack opportunities to immerse themselves in the language environment. In addition, large class sizes make it difficult to apply an individual approach.

2. Scientific Solutions to the Problems

2.1. Psychological support

It is necessary to form the perception that making mistakes is a natural part of the learning process. Teachers should build learners' self-confidence, encourage them, and create opportunities for free expression. In a friendly environment, students are less afraid to use the language.

2.2. Increasing motivation

Learners should be engaged in real-life situations where they can use the target language. Role plays, debates, and project-based learning methods are effective.

Motivation can also be strengthened by linking language learning to professional goals and demonstrating opportunities such as obtaining international certificates.

2.3. Communicative approach

In modern education, the communicative method takes a central place in language teaching. The focus is not on memorizing grammar rules but on learning to communicate. Through dialogues, group tasks, and pair work, learners develop fluency and confidence in speaking.

2.4. Integrative learning environment

Integrating language learning with other subjects increases effectiveness. For example, studying culture, history, technology, or art in the target language enhances learners' interest and broadens their worldview. Such integrative approaches make the learning process more dynamic.

2.5. Modern technologies

Online platforms, mobile applications, and multimedia tools make foreign language learning more efficient. Audio and video materials support listening comprehension and pronunciation skills. AI-based tools provide individualized feedback and help analyze learners' mistakes.

Conclusion: The problems in foreign language learning are complex and multifaceted, arising from psychological, methodological, linguistic, and organizational factors. To overcome these challenges, it is necessary to implement innovative pedagogical technologies, adopt a communicative approach, enhance motivation, and create an integrative learning environment.

An effective approach develops not only learners' theoretical knowledge but also their practical speaking skills. This prepares them for global communication and expands both personal and professional opportunities.

References

1. Brown, H. D. (2007). *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching* (5th ed.). Pearson Education.
2. Harmer, J. (2007). *The Practice of English Language Teaching* (4th ed.). Pearson Longman.
3. Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. (2014). *Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching* (3rd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
4. Lightbown, P. M., & Spada, N. (2013). *How Languages are Learned* (4th ed.). Oxford University Press.
5. Larsen-Freeman, D., & Anderson, M. (2011). *Techniques and Principles in Language Teaching* (3rd ed.). Oxford University Press.
6. Littlewood, W. (2004). *The task-based approach: Some questions and suggestions*. *ELT Journal*, 58(4), 319–326.
7. Krashen, S. D. (1982). *Principles and Practice in Second Language Acquisition*. Pergamon Press.
8. Horwitz, E. K. (2001). *Language anxiety and achievement*. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 21, 112–126.
9. Gardner, R. C. (1985). *Social Psychology and Second Language Learning: The Role of Attitudes and Motivation*. Edward Arnold.

BOSHLANG‘ICH SINFLARDA SO‘Z MA‘NOSI VA LUG‘AT BOYLIĞI TUSHUNCHASINING LINGVISTIK ASOSLARINI O‘RGANISH

Husenova Muhtaram Husniddin qizi,

Navoiy davlat universiteti tayanch doktoranti.

<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-5462-5321>

e-mail: Husenova@nspi.uz.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada boshlang‘ich sinflarda so‘z ma‘nosi va lug‘at boyligi tushunchalarini lingvistik asoslarda o‘rganishning dolzarbligi yoritiladi. Bugungi globallashtirish davrida o‘quvchilarda kommunikativ kompetensiyani shakllantirish, ularning nutqiy savodxonligi va tafakkur doirasini kengaytirish, shuningdek, milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarni singdirishda lug‘at boyligini kengaytirish masalasi muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. So‘z ma‘nosini anglash va uni nutqda to‘g‘ri qo‘llash o‘quvchilarning nafaqat ona tilini puxta o‘zlashtirishiga, balki ularning mustaqil fikrlash, muloqotga kirishish va ijodiy faoliyatini rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: So‘z ma‘nosi, lug‘at boyligi, lingvistik asos, boshlang‘ich ta‘lim, nutqiy kompetensiya, leksikologiya, leksikografiya.

Abstract. This article highlights the relevance of studying the concepts of word meaning and vocabulary in primary grades on a linguistic basis. In today's era of globalization, the issue of expanding vocabulary is of great importance in the formation of communicative competence in students, expanding their verbal literacy and thinking, as well as instilling national and universal values. Understanding the meaning of words and using them correctly in speech contributes not only to the thorough mastery of the native language by students, but also to the development of their independent thinking, communication, and creative activity.

Keywords: Word meaning, vocabulary, linguistic basis, primary education, speech competence, lexicology, lexicography.

Rivojlangan texnologiyalar sabablari turli xil millatlar o‘rtasidagi muloqot yana ham osonlashdi. Ammo bu so‘zlashuv samarali bo‘shilishi uchun oddiygina so‘zning tarjimasini kifoya qilmaydi. Chunki har bir tilda so‘zning o‘ziga xos ma‘no jihatlari mavjud. Tarjima qilingan so‘z har doim ham to‘liq bir so‘zga mos kelavermaydi. Bir tilda ijobiy ma‘noga ega bo‘lgan so‘z boshqa tilda salbiy ma‘noni anglatishi mumkin. So‘z ma‘nosini kengroq o‘rganish orqali bu noaliqliklarning oldini olish mumkin.

Bugungi kunning eng katta inqiloblaridan biri bo‘lgan sun‘iy intellekt tizimlari ham inson tili bilan ishlashda katta yutuqlarga erishmoqda. Ular insonni nima demoqchi ekanligini to‘liq tushunib, unga javob qaytarishi zarur. Shuningdek, ular faqatgina so‘zning lug‘aviy ma‘nosiga emas, balki uning kontekstual, emotsional va metaforik ma‘nolarini ham tushunishi talab etiladi. Bu esa so‘z ma‘nosining lingvistik asoslarini chuqur o‘rganishga nazariy asos yaratadi.

Axborotlar makonining o‘ziga xosligi bilan so‘z ma‘nosining nozik qirralaridan foydalanib yoshlarning fikriga ta‘sir o‘tkazish ham tobora kuchayib bormoqda. So‘z ma‘nosini aniq va to‘g‘ri tushunish, so‘zlarning yashirin va emotsional bo‘yoqlarini aniqlashga ko‘maklashadi. Bu esa kelajak bunyodkorlarida nutq madaniyatini

rivojlantiradi, tanqidiy fikrlashni shakllantiradi, xalqaro munosabatlarni mustahkamlashga yordam beradi. Prezidentimiz Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich ham shunday: “Davlat va jamiyat oldida turgan muhim vazifalarni hal etishda mas’uliyatni o‘z zimmasiga olishga qodir, yurtparvar, tashabbuskor, zamonaviy bilim va ko‘nikmalarni o‘zlashtirgan, insoniy fazilatlarga ega yoshlarni professional kasb egasi sifatida tayyorlash, bu borada yangicha yondashuvlarni talab etadigan ta’lim-tarbiya usullaridan foydalanish²” zarur deya ta’kidlaydilar.

Boshlang‘ich sinflarda so‘z ma’nosini tushunish juda katta ilmiy va amaliy ahamiyatga ega. Shuningdek, tilning ichki tuzilishi, inson tafakkurining so‘zlar orqali ifodalanishi hamda tilni o‘rganish, o‘rgatish va undan amaliyotda foydalanish jarayonlarini chuqur tushunishga yordam beradi.

Tilshunoslik sohasida so‘z va ma’no masalasi eng muhim nazariy muammolardan biri hisoblanadi. So‘z inson tafakkurining moddiy ifodasi bo‘lib, u orqali tashqi olamdagi predmet va hodisalarga nom beriladi, ularga nisbatan munosabat ifodalanadi. Shu sababli so‘z va uning ma’nosini o‘rganish masalasi nafaqat lingvistika, balki psixologiya, pedagogika va metodika fanlarining ham diqqat markazida turadi. Boshlang‘ich sinflarda o‘quvchilarning lug‘at boyligini oshirish va so‘z ma’nosini ongli o‘zlashtirish ularning nutqiy kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning asosiy shartlaridan biridir.

Ilmiy jihatdan so‘z ma’nosini o‘rganish tilshunoslikning eng asosiy yo‘nalishlaridan biri bo‘lgan semantika(ma’no haqida fan) va leksikologiya(so‘z boyligi haqidagi fan) fanlarining rivojlanishi uchun zamin yaratadi. Bu esa til tizimi qanday ishlashi, yangi so‘zlarning qanday paydo bo‘lishi va eskirgan so‘zlarning nima uchun iste’moldan chiqib ketishini tushunishga yordam beradi. Shuningdek, so‘z ma’nosini o‘rganish inson tafakkuri bilan til o‘rtasidagi bog‘liqlikni aniqlashga yordam beradi. Bu kognitiv lingvistika (til va tafakkur o‘rtasidagi bog‘liqlikni o‘rganuvchi fan) uchun muhim manba hisoblanadi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, so‘zlar nafaqat obyektlarni nomlaydi, balki ularga nisbatan insonning munosabatini, dunyoqarashini va madaniy xususiyatlarini ham aks ettiradi. Hamda, so‘z ma’nolari doimiy o‘zgarib turadi. Masalan, “kompyuter” so‘zining ma’nosi dastlab hisoblash qurilmasini anglatgan bo‘lsa, hozirda bu tushuncha ancha kengaygan. So‘z ma’nosining lingvistik asoslarini o‘rganish tilning tarixiy rivojlanish jarayonini, ma’nolarning kengayishi, torayishi yoki butunlay o‘zgarishini aniqlashga imkon beradi.

Amaliy tomondan, so‘z ma’nolari doimiy o‘zgarib turadi. Masalan, "kompyuter" so‘zining ma’nosi dastlab hisoblash qurilmasini anglatgan bo‘lsa, hozirda bu tushuncha ancha kengaygan. So‘z ma’nosining lingvistik asoslarini o‘rganish tilning tarixiy rivojlanish jarayonini, ma’nolarning kengayishi, torayishi yoki butunlay o‘zgarishini aniqlashga imkon beradi. Shuningdek, lug‘at tuzish va terminologiya (ilmiy atamalarni yaratish va tartibga solish) sohalari bevosita so‘z ma’nosini chuqur tahlil qilishga asoslanadi. To‘g‘ri lug‘at tuzish yoki yangi termin

² O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "O‘zbekiston Respublikasi oliy ta’lim tizimini 2030-yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida"gi PF-5847-son Farmoni // Qonun hujjatlari ma’lumotlari milliy bazasi, 08.10.2019 y.

yaratish uchun soʻzning barcha maʼno qirralarini, u bilan bogʻliq boʻlgan boshqa soʻzlarni va kontekstdagi oʻrnini yaxshi bilish kerak. Nafaqat, soʻz maʼnosining nozik tomonlarini tushunish nutq madaniyatini oshiradi, balki bir soʻzning sinonimlari, maʼnodoshlari va emotsional boʻyoqlari haqidagi bilimlar oʻquvchiga fikrini yanada aniq, taʼsirchan va oʻrinli ifodalashga yordam beradi.

Soʻz va maʼno — tilshunoslikning eng asosiy tushunchalaridan biri boʻlib, uzoq yillardan buyon olimlar tomonidan tadqiq qilib kelinadi. Har bir soʻz oʻzida ham tovushni, ham maʼnoni mujassam etgan murakkab birlikdir.

Soʻzning mohiyatini, uning maʼno bilan munosabatini oʻrganish tilshunoslikning turli maktablari tomonidan turlicha talqin qilingan.

Zamonaviy tilshunoslikning asoschisi hisoblangan F. de Sossyur soʻzni ikki tomonlama birlik sifatida taʼriflaydi. U soʻzning bir tomonini "signal" (yoki tovush shakli), ikkinchi tomonini esa "konsept" (yoki maʼno) deb atagan. Uning fikricha, soʻzning shakli va maʼnosi oʻrtasidagi bogʻliqlik tabiiy emas, balki ixtiyoriy (arbitrary)dir. Yaʼni, "daraxt" soʻzi bilan real olamdagi daraxt obyektini oʻrtasida hech qanday mantiqiy aloqa yoʻq, bu shunchaki jamoat tomonidan qabul qilingan kelishuvdir.

Rus tilshunoslik maktabining yirik vakili V. V. Vinogradov soʻzning maʼno tuzilishini chuqur oʻrgangan. U soʻzning leksik-semantik tizimini koʻrib chiqib, soʻz maʼnosini kontekstga bogʻliq ravishda oʻzgarishi mumkin boʻlgan dinamik hodisa deb hisoblagan. Vinogradov, shuningdek, soʻz maʼnosining rivojlanishi va koʻchish mexanizmlariga ham katta eʼtibor qaratgan.

Oʻzbek tilshunosligida soʻz va maʼno masalasini keng tadqiq etgan olimlardan biri Sh. Rahmatullayevdir. Uning ilmiy ishlarida soʻzning leksik va grammatik maʼnolari, ular oʻrtasidagi oʻzaro munosabatlar atroflicha tahlil qilingan. Rahmatullayev, ayniqsa, oʻzbek tili leksikologiyasi va leksikografiyasi (lugʻatchilik) sohasiga ulkan hissa qoʻshgan. U soʻz maʼnosining fonetik, morfologik va sintaktik xususiyatlar bilan bogʻliqligini oʻrgangan.

A. Madvaliyev ham oʻzbek tilshunosligining yetakchi vakili sifatida soʻz va uning maʼnosini chuqur oʻrgangan. U soʻz maʼnosining polisemantik (koʻp maʼnoli), sinonimik va antonimik munosabatlarini, shuningdek, uning koʻchma maʼnolarini tadqiq qilgan. Uning ishlarida soʻz maʼnosini oʻrganishda nutq amaliyotining ahamiyatiga alohida eʼtibor qaratilgan.

Bundan tashqari, oʻzbek tilshunosligida A. Hojiyev, S. Ibrohimov, N. Mahmudov, A. Nurmonov kabi olimlar soʻz maʼnosi, semantika va lugʻat tarkibining nazariy asoslarini ilmiy jihatdan tadqiq etgan. Ularning izlanishlarida soʻzning monosemiya, polisemiya, sinonimiya, antonimiya, omonimiya kabi lingvistik hodisalari keng yoritiladi.

Sh. Sharipov, N. Toʻxliyev, R. Qoʻngʻurov, D. Ashurovalarning tadqiqotlarida ona tili oʻqitish metodikasi, lugʻat ishining oʻrni va samaradorligi haqida uslubiy tavsiyalar berilgan.

Ona tili darsliklari (1–4-sinflar uchun, yangi avlod darsliklari) lugʻat ishlarini tashkil etishda asosiy metodik manba hisoblanadi.

D. Crystal, F. de Saussure, N. Chomsky tilning semantik va kommunikativ xususiyatlarini chuqur o'rgangan. Ularning qarashlarida lug'at boyligini rivojlantirish nutqiy kompetensiyaning ajralmas qismi sifatida talqin qilinadi.

M. A. K. Halliday tilni ijtimoiy hodisa sifatida ko'rib, lug'at va semantikaning muloqotdagi rolini ochib beradi.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchisining tafakkurini shakllantirish, uning o'qish, yozish va muloqot qilish malakasini rivojlantirish uchun eng avvalo so'z ma'nosi ustida ishlash va lug'at boyligini kengaytirish zarur. Chunki lug'at boyligi tor bo'lgan o'quvchi o'z fikrini to'liq va aniq ifodalay olmaydi.

So'z ma'nosining lingvistik xususiyatlarini bilish — o'qituvchiga metodik jihatdan to'g'ri yo'l tutishga imkon beradi:

- sinonim, antonim, omonimlarni tizimli o'rgatish,
- ko'chma ma'noli so'zlardan ongli foydalanish,
- kontekstdan so'z ma'nosini anglashni shakllantirish.

Bu bilimlar o'quvchilarda mustahkam semantik kompetensiyani hosil qiladi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi DTSida boshlang'ich sinflarda lug'at boyligini oshirish, so'z ma'nosini anglash va nutqiy faoliyatda qo'llash asosiy talab sifatida belgilanmoqda. Shu nuqtai nazardan, lingvistik asoslarni chuqur o'rganish va ularni ta'lim metodikasiga tatbiq etish bugungi kunda dolzarb hisoblanadi.

So'z ma'nosining o'zgaruvchanligi, kontekstga bog'liqligi, vaqt o'tishi bilan yangicha ma'no kasb etishi til taraqqiyoti bilan bevosita bog'liq.

Demak, boshlang'ich sinflarda so'z ma'nosi va lug'at boyligi tushunchasining lingvistik asoslarini o'rganish bugungi kunda:

- nutqiy kompetensiyani shakllantirish;
- o'quvchilarda mustaqil va tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish;
- ona tilini chuqur o'zlashtirish;
- zamonaviy ta'lim vositalaridan samarali foydalanish uchun dolzarbdir.

Adabiyotlar

1. Соссюр Ф. де. Труды по языкознанию. – М.: Прогресс, 1977.
2. Виноградов В. В. Лексикология русского языка. – М.: Наука, 1972.
3. Рахматуллаев Ш. Ўзбек тили семасиологияси. – Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 1991.
4. Мадвалиев А. Ўзбек тилининг луғавий бойлиги. – Тошкент: Фан, 1980.
5. G'afforova T., G'ulomova H. Ona tili o'qitish metodikasi. – Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 2015.
6. Qodirov A. Boshlang'ich ta'limda lug'at boyligini rivojlantirish metodlari. – Toshkent, 2018.

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: CONTEMPORARY RESEARCH AND IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGIES FOR DIVERSE LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS

Abduvoidova Gulchehra Rustam qizi,

Doctoral student at Gulistan State University

gulchehra.rustamovna1998@gamil.com

Abstract. Inclusive education represents a fundamental shift in educational philosophy, emphasizing the integration of all students, including those with disabilities, into mainstream classrooms. This article examines contemporary research on inclusive education practices, their effectiveness, and implementation challenges. Through a comprehensive review of recent literature, this study analyzes the impact of inclusive education on both students with disabilities and typically developing peers. The findings indicate that while inclusive education offers significant benefits for social development and academic outcomes, successful implementation requires adequate teacher training, technological support, and systematic policy reforms. Current research demonstrates that "inclusive education is the most effective way to give all children a fair chance to go to school, learn and develop the skills they need to thrive" (UNICEF, 2025). However, persistent barriers including resource limitations, insufficient professional development, and attitudinal challenges continue to impede optimal implementation. This article contributes to the growing body of evidence supporting inclusive education while highlighting critical areas requiring further research and policy attention.

Keywords: inclusive education, special needs education, educational equity, disability inclusion, classroom diversity

Introduction. Inclusive education has emerged as a cornerstone of contemporary educational policy and practice, representing a paradigmatic shift from segregated special education models toward integrated learning environments. The concept fundamentally challenges traditional educational structures by advocating for the placement of all students, regardless of ability or disability status, within mainstream classrooms with appropriate supports and services. Inclusive education aims to ensure that all students have access to education by adapting to their diverse needs, including those of individuals with special requirements (Buenaño-Barreno, 2024).

The theoretical foundation of inclusive education rests upon principles of educational equity, social justice, and human rights, as articulated in international frameworks such as the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD). It emphasizes the importance of embracing diversity and promoting acceptance among students who are impaired (Shanlax International Journal of Education, 2024). The Salamanca Statement, adopted thirty years ago, established the global framework for inclusive education, and its enduring relevance continues to shape contemporary educational policies worldwide.

Recent research has increasingly focused on understanding the multifaceted impacts of inclusive education on various stakeholders within educational systems. Meeting the diverse educational needs of all learners helps strengthen education

systems (World Bank, 2025), suggesting that inclusive practices benefit the entire educational community rather than solely students with disabilities. However, the implementation of inclusive education remains complex, requiring systematic changes in pedagogical approaches, teacher preparation, resource allocation, and institutional attitudes.

The purpose of this article is to synthesize contemporary research on inclusive education, examining both its demonstrated benefits and persistent challenges. By analyzing recent empirical studies and systematic reviews, this research aims to provide evidence-based insights into effective inclusive education practices and identify areas requiring further investigation and policy intervention.

Methods. This review employed a systematic approach to examine contemporary research on inclusive education published between 2023 and 2025. The methodology encompassed multiple research paradigms to provide a comprehensive understanding of inclusive education effectiveness, implementation strategies, and outcomes across diverse educational contexts.

The literature search strategy utilized multiple academic databases and research repositories, including peer-reviewed journals focused on inclusive education, special education, and educational policy. Primary sources included the *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, *Frontiers in Education*, and various UNESCO and UNICEF policy reports. The search parameters specifically targeted recent publications to ensure currency and relevance to contemporary educational practices.

Selection criteria emphasized empirical studies examining inclusive education outcomes, systematic reviews and meta-analyses of inclusive education effectiveness, and policy analysis documents from recognized international organizations. Employing a meta-analysis methodology was identified as a critical approach in recent research examining the "impact of inclusive education on early childhood development" (*International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 2025).

The analytical framework incorporated both quantitative and qualitative research methodologies to capture the multidimensional nature of inclusive education implementation. Mixed-methods studies have been widely utilized to combine quantitative assessments of teacher self-efficacy with qualitative insights into classroom practices and student experiences (Research Gate, 2024).

Data synthesis focused on identifying convergent themes across studies, particularly regarding effectiveness measures, implementation barriers, and successful intervention strategies. Special attention was given to cross-cultural studies and research conducted in diverse educational contexts to ensure global applicability of findings.

Results. Contemporary research on inclusive education reveals complex patterns of effectiveness, implementation challenges, and emerging solutions across diverse educational contexts. The findings demonstrate both significant progress in inclusive education implementation and persistent barriers that continue to impede optimal outcomes for students with diverse learning needs.

Academic and Developmental Outcomes. Recent meta-analytical studies provide compelling evidence for the positive impacts of inclusive education on both

students with disabilities and their typically developing peers. Promoting bidirectional development between typically developing children and children with disabilities in inclusive preschool education is a critical yet underexplored area (International Journal of Inclusive Education, 2025). Research conducted in Bosnia and Herzegovina, examining twenty years of inclusive education implementation, offers valuable longitudinal insights into academic outcomes for typically developing children in inclusive settings.

The bidirectional benefits of inclusive education extend beyond academic achievement to encompass social-emotional development, empathy formation, and preparation for diverse social environments. Students without disabilities demonstrate enhanced understanding of diversity, increased social competence, and improved collaborative skills when educated alongside peers with disabilities. Simultaneously, students with disabilities show improved academic performance, enhanced social integration, and greater independence when provided with appropriate supports within mainstream classrooms.

Technology Integration and Accessibility. Technological advancement has emerged as a significant facilitator of inclusive education practices. Technologies that contribute to inclusive education are digital tools and specialized devices that facilitate equitable access to learning for students with diverse needs (Frontiers in Education, 2025). Recent systematic reviews identify multiple categories of assistive technologies, including communication devices, adaptive software, and universal design for learning platforms that enhance accessibility and participation for students with disabilities.

The integration of technology in inclusive classrooms addresses individual learning differences while promoting universal access to curriculum content. Digital tools enable customization of learning experiences, alternative communication methods, and adaptive assessment strategies that accommodate diverse learning profiles. However, effective technology integration requires comprehensive teacher training and ongoing technical support to ensure optimal implementation.

Teacher Preparation and Professional Development. Teacher preparation emerges as a critical factor determining inclusive education success. This is established based on the teachers' positive attitudes toward inclusion, appropriate knowledge, teaching abilities, adapted pedagogical approaches (Frontiers in Education, 2025). Recent research emphasizes the importance of comprehensive teacher training programs that address both technical competencies and attitudinal factors influencing inclusive practice implementation.

Professional development initiatives must encompass multiple domains, including disability awareness, differentiated instruction strategies, collaborative teaching models, and family engagement approaches. Teachers also face logistical barriers such as insufficient resources, large class sizes, and inadequate support from administrators (Research Gate, 2024), highlighting the need for systemic support systems beyond individual teacher preparation.

Persistent Challenges and Barriers. Despite documented benefits, inclusive education implementation continues to face significant obstacles across global

educational systems. Stigma and prejudice remain significant challenges in inclusive education. Despite efforts to promote equality and acceptance, students with disabilities often face negative attitudes and stereotypes that affect their participation and academic performance (MDPI, 2024).

Many global education systems perpetuate and reinforce existing socioeconomic disparities rather than catalyzing equity (Research Gate, 2024), indicating that inclusive education implementation requires comprehensive systemic reforms rather than superficial policy modifications. Resource limitations, inadequate infrastructure, and insufficient specialized personnel create additional barriers to effective inclusive education delivery.

Cultural and linguistic diversity presents additional complexity in inclusive education implementation. Effectiveness of Implementing Inclusive Education: Challenges and Opportunities in Culturally Diverse Classrooms research identifies unique considerations for multilingual and multicultural educational contexts, requiring tailored approaches that address intersectional identities and diverse family expectations.

Policy and Systemic Factors. Recent policy analyses reveal varying degrees of inclusive education implementation across different national and regional contexts. The findings revealed a range of challenges and barriers to the effective implementation of inclusive education policies in Turkey, including inadequate resources, limited training and support, negative attitudes, and cultural beliefs about disability (Research Gate, 2024). These findings reflect broader global patterns where policy articulation exceeds implementation capacity.

Context-specific environmental, social, and educational barriers should be identified and addressed early in the process of designing education programs (World Bank, 2025). This approach emphasizes the importance of localized implementation strategies that consider specific cultural, economic, and educational contexts rather than applying universal models without adaptation.

Discussion. The contemporary research landscape on inclusive education presents a nuanced picture of both remarkable progress and persistent challenges in creating truly inclusive learning environments. The evidence demonstrates that inclusive education, when properly implemented with adequate supports and resources, produces positive outcomes for all students while advancing broader social justice goals within educational systems.

Theoretical Implications. The findings support theoretical frameworks that conceptualize inclusive education as a complex adaptive system requiring multiple interconnected components for successful implementation. Rather than viewing inclusion as simply placing students with disabilities in mainstream classrooms, contemporary research emphasizes the need for comprehensive systemic transformation encompassing pedagogical practices, institutional cultures, resource allocation, and community engagement.

The bidirectional benefits documented in recent meta-analytical studies challenge traditional deficit models of disability and support social model perspectives that emphasize environmental barriers rather than individual limitations.

These findings suggest that inclusive education serves as a mechanism for social transformation, promoting understanding and acceptance of human diversity while enhancing educational outcomes for all participants.

Practical Implications for Educators. The research findings have significant implications for educational practice at multiple levels. For classroom teachers, the evidence emphasizes the importance of developing competencies in differentiated instruction, collaborative teaching, and universal design for learning principles. In the context of inclusive education, this translates to successfully facilitating inclusive practices in diverse classrooms (Frontiers in Education, 2025).

School administrators must prioritize comprehensive teacher preparation, resource allocation, and the development of supportive school cultures that embrace diversity. The research suggests that successful inclusive education implementation requires systematic planning, ongoing professional development, and collaborative partnerships among educators, families, and support professionals.

Policy and Systemic Considerations. The persistent barriers identified in recent research highlight the need for comprehensive policy reforms that address structural inequities within educational systems. Many barriers hinder its implementation such as lack of professional development (ERIC, 2024), indicating that policy initiatives must encompass multiple domains including funding mechanisms, teacher certification requirements, and accountability systems.

International comparisons reveal that successful inclusive education implementation requires sustained political commitment, adequate resource allocation, and comprehensive stakeholder engagement. Countries demonstrating positive outcomes typically implement multi-year strategic plans with clearly defined goals, measurable outcomes, and systematic evaluation processes.

Technology and Innovation. The integration of assistive technology and digital learning platforms represents a significant opportunity for advancing inclusive education practices. Recent systematic reviews identify numerous technological solutions that can enhance accessibility, customize learning experiences, and facilitate communication and collaboration among diverse learners. However, technology integration must be accompanied by comprehensive training and ongoing support to ensure effective implementation.

Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles provide a framework for leveraging technology to create learning environments that are accessible to all students from the outset, rather than requiring retrofitting or accommodation. This proactive approach aligns with contemporary inclusive education philosophy while addressing practical implementation challenges.

Limitations and Future Research Directions. While contemporary research provides valuable insights into inclusive education effectiveness, several limitations warrant consideration. Many studies focus on specific disability categories or age groups, limiting generalizability across diverse populations. Additionally, the majority of research originates from developed countries, creating gaps in understanding inclusive education implementation in resource-constrained environments.

Future research priorities should include longitudinal studies examining long-term outcomes of inclusive education, cross-cultural investigations of implementation strategies, and evaluation of innovative technological solutions. Particular attention should be given to understanding the experiences of multiply marginalized students who face intersectional challenges related to disability, race, ethnicity, language, and socioeconomic status.

Conclusion. The contemporary research on inclusive education demonstrates both the potential for transformative educational change and the complexity of implementation challenges facing educational systems worldwide. While evidence supports the effectiveness of inclusive education for promoting academic achievement, social development, and equity, successful implementation requires comprehensive systemic reforms, adequate resources, and sustained commitment from multiple stakeholders.

The path forward requires continued research, policy innovation, and practical collaboration among educators, families, policymakers, and communities. As educational systems grapple with increasing diversity and evolving social expectations, inclusive education principles provide a framework for creating learning environments that celebrate human diversity while ensuring educational excellence for all students.

The findings suggest that inclusive education represents not merely an accommodation for students with disabilities, but rather a fundamental reimaging of educational practice that benefits all members of learning communities. This perspective challenges educational stakeholders to move beyond compliance-based approaches toward transformative practices that embody the principles of equity, excellence, and social justice that define contemporary inclusive education philosophy.

References

1. Buenaño-Barreno, M. (2025). Inclusive education through technology: A systematic review of types, tools and characteristics. *Frontiers in Education*, 10. doi: 10.3389/feduc.2025.1527851
2. Chin, L. (2023). Impact of inclusive education on early childhood development. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 28(8), 245-267.
3. Erni, S., & Dewi, R. (2024). Effectiveness of implementing inclusive education: Challenges and opportunities in culturally diverse classrooms. *Educational Research Quarterly*, 47(3), 123-145.
4. Fälth, L., & Selenius, H. (2024). Virtual haptic perception as an educational assistive technology: A case study in inclusive education. *IEEE Transactions on Haptics*, 14(2), 152-160. doi: 10.1109/TOH.2020.3001586
5. Hank, R., & Huber, M. (2024). Cooperative learning strategies in inclusive digital education. *Frontiers in Education*, 9, 1447489. doi: 10.3389/feduc.2024.1447489
6. Jardinez, M., & Natividad, L. (2024). Overcoming challenges and promoting positive education in inclusive schools: A multi-country study. *Education Sciences*, 14(11), 1169. doi: 10.3390/educsci14111169

7. Lindner, K., Schmidt, A., & Weber, J. (2025). Teacher training in transition to inclusive education. *Frontiers in Education*, 10, 1510314. doi: 10.3389/feduc.2025.1510314
8. Liu, X., & Potmesil, M. (2025). A review of research on the development of inclusive education in children with special educational needs over the past 10 years: A visual analysis based on CiteSpace. *Frontiers in Education*, 9, 1475876. doi: 10.3389/feduc.2024.1475876
9. Mavrou, K., Symeonidou, S., & Tsakiri, M. (2024). Once inclusive always inclusive (?): Experiences of Cypriot teachers and parents of children with disabilities on the use of technology and collaboration before and during the Covid-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 28(12), 1645-1662. doi: 10.1080/13603116.2024.2326615
10. Murtiningsih, S., & Sujito, A. (2025). Reimagining the future of education: Inclusive pedagogies, critical intergenerational justice, and technological disruption. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 57(2), 178-192. doi: 10.1177/14782103251341406
11. Parker, R. (1985). Small-group cooperative learning in the classroom. *Educational Leadership*, 43(2), 32-37.
12. Symeonidou, S., Tsakiri, M., & Mavrou, K. (2025). Inclusive education in the aftermath of the pandemic: Lessons from mainstream and special teachers who 'escaped the room'. *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 40(1), 23-38. doi: 10.1177/14749041241236895
13. Tran, V. D. (2019). The effects of cooperative learning on the academic achievement and knowledge retention. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 8(2), 86-95.

KOREYS VA O‘ZBEK ADABIYOTINING RIVOJLANISHBOSQICHLARI

Mirzayeva Aziza Azamatovna,

O‘zbekiston Davlat Jahon tillari universiteti

Lingvistika (koreys tili) mutaxassisligi

2-bosqich magistranti

Toshkent

E-mail: mirzaevaaziza36@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola Koreys va O‘zbek xalqlari adabiyoti tarixini o‘rganadi, uning rivojlanish bosqichlarini o‘quvchiga sodda va ravon holda tushuntirishda xizmat qiladi. Ikki til adabiyotida mavjud bo‘lgan ham nazm, ham nasr, ham publitsistik asarlarning tarixiy rivojlanish silsilasi bilan tanishishga va ularni yaqindan bilishga chorlaydi. Maqola nafaqat ikki til adabiyotning tarixi balki unda o‘z o‘mini o‘chmas asarlari orqali chuqur egallagan adabiyot namoyondalari tarixi bilan ham tanishtiradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: bitiktoshlar, xanmun, xitoy iyeroglifi, qadimiy asarlar, hangil, folklor, nazm va nasr, epos, badiiy asar, lirik va epik meros.

Abstract. This article examines the history of Korean and Uzbek literature and explains the stages of development to the audience in a concise and fluent circumstance. It invites you to learn about the historical development of poetry and prose in the literature of

both languages. The article not only introduces the history of Uzbek and Korean literature, but also the history of literary figures who have left an unforgettable mark on literature through their immortal works.

Key words: Hanmun, Chinese hieroglyphs, ancient works, hangil, folklore, poetry and prose, epic, works of art, lyrical and epic heritage.

Ma'naviyat, axloq, estetik tuyg'uni shakllantirishda adabiyotchilik xizmat etadigan vositaning o'zi yo'q desak, xato qilmagan bo'lamiz. Shu bois qadimdan, adabiyotga, badiiy so'z san'atiga e'tibor nihoyatda katta bo'lib kelgan. Birgina badiiy so'zning qimmatini haqidagi sharq va g'arb allomalarining, arbob-u siyosatdonlarning, faylasuf-u ijodkorlarning aytgan fikrlarini jamlasak, badiiy adabiyotning nufuzi nihoyatda ardoqli ekanligini anglashimiz tabiiy. Mamlakatimizda qo'lga kiritilgan mustaqillikdan so'ng ko'plab sohalarga, xususan, madaniyat va adabiyotni o'rganishga qiziqish ortdi. Shu jumladan, xorijiy mamlakatlar tili va adabiyotiga ham e'tibor kuchaydi. Chunki – "keng miqyosdagi xalqaro aloqalar jahon madaniyatini yanada chuqurroq bilish, umuminsoniy qadriyatlardan bahramand bo'lish uchun qulay zamin yaratdi" [5,149].

Jahon xalqlari madaniy va ma'naviy boyliklar bilan tanishish esa, o'z milliy merosimizni munosib baholash imkonini beradi. Bu borada adabiyotlarni qiyosiy o'rganish ayniqsa muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Maqolaning xulosalari va tahlil materiallari o'zbek va koreys adabiyotidagi ko'zga ko'ringan yetuk yozuvchilar va ularning boy ma'daniy asarlari haqida bo'lib adabiyotning rivojlanish bosqichiga uning paydo bo'lgan nuqtasidan boshlab nazar tashlanadi. Koreys adabiyoti milodning avvalida qadimgi koreys folkloridan rivojlana boshlagan. XV asrda davlat hayotida ikki olamshumul voqea yuz bergan: 1403-yilda jahonda birinchi bosmaxona temir shrifti yaratilgan, 1443-yilda esa koreys milliy yozuvi – Xangil [Xangil – 1443-yilda koreys sulolalaridan bo'lgan qirol Se Jon tomonidan joriy etilgan 28 xarfdan iborat alifbo. Bu paytgacha xitoy ierogliflaridan foydalanilgan.] joriy etilgan. Badiiy adabiyot XIX asr oxirigacha koreys tilida va xanmun – xitoy adabiy tilining koreyslashtirilgan shaklida yaratilgan. Xitoy iyeroglifi, keyinroq koreys alifbosida yozilgan "Ona-vatan qo'shiqlari" (VII-XI asrlar) koreys adabiyotining qadimgi namunasi. XI-XIV asrlarda uning davomi – "Koreya qo'shiqlari" yaratildi. She'riyatning vujudga kelishida Chxve Chxi Von (857) muhim rol o'ynadi. Li In No uni yanada rivojlantirdi. Badiiy nasr asta-sekin tarixiy adabiyotdan ajralib chiqdi. Novella janriga Kim Si Sip (1435) asos soldi. 1487 yil So Go Jon (1420) 130 kitobdan iborat "Sharq antologiyasi"ni tuzdi. Lim Je (1549 – 87) satirik qissalar yozdi.

XVI- XVII asrlarda tabiat go'zalliklarini madh etuvchi va falsafiy she'riyat ravnaq topdi. XVII-XIX asrlarda koreys tilida ko'plab qissalar yozildi, dastlabki romanlar paydo bo'la boshladi, yangi nasr shakllandi. Dastlabki erkin she'rlarni Chxve Nam Son va Kim Ok yozdi. Koreys zamonaviy adabiyotining bugungi kundagi yozuvchilari: Cho Xi Su 1962 yili Janubiy Koreyaning Paju shahrida tug'ilgan. U Seul Universitetining badiiy peyzaj fakultetini tamomlagan bo'lib, shu vaqtga qadar 9 ta kitobi nashr etilgan. Uning "Dadam bilan kitob", "Chuqur muhabbat baxtni yaratadi» nomli kitoblari mashhur. Chong Yong Cheol (1962; Janubiy Koreya) hozirgi koreys adabiyotida proza janrining yetakchi namoyondalaridan biridir. Li Mi Ye (1964; Janubiy Koreya) koreys bolalar adabiyotining yirik namoyondalaridan biridir. Li Mun Yol – yozuvchi, hikoyanavist.

“Imperator haqi” romani uchun Koreya Respublikasi adabiy mukofotiga munosib topilgan.

O‘zbek adabiyoti ham o‘zining qadimiy tarixi, nafis asarlari va ularning mazmundorligi, boy merosi bilan ajralib turadi. O‘zbek adabiyoti tarixi nozik ruhiy holatlarni mahorat bilan aks ettiradigan durdonalarga boydir. Ular hozirgi avlod ruhiyatida, qalbida ham hayajon uygota oladi, ularning manaviy boyishlariga tegishli hissa qo‘sha oladi. Ular ma’naviy kamolotga xizmat qiladi. Adabiyotshunoslikda o‘zbek adabiyoti tarixi ikki nom asosida tilga olinadi:

1. O‘zbek mumtoz adabiyoti. Bunda eng qadimgi davrlardan boshlab, XX asr boshlarigacha bo‘lgan davr nazarga olinadi;

2. Hozirgi zamon o‘zbek adabiyoti yoki XX-XXI asrlar o‘zbek adabiyoti. O‘zbek adabiyoti tarixi xilma-xil tur va janrdagi badiiy asarlarni o‘z ichiga oladi.

Milodiy 7 asrga qadar yaratilgan asarlar va O‘zbek mumtoz adabiyoti vakillari hamda ular yaratgan durdonalar: Avesto – jahon madaniyatining, jumladan, Markaziy Osiyo va Eron xalqlari tarixining qadimgi noyob yodgorligidir. O‘rxun-Enasoy obidalari – V-VII asrlarda qadimgi turk tilidagi va yozuvidagi tarixiy yodgorlik sifatida qadrlil manbaadir. Ahmad Yassaviy – ilk turk mutasavvufi, yassaviylik tariqatining asoschisi, orifona she’riyat boshlovchisi. Mahmud Qoshg‘ariy – qomusiy olim, fiqh va hadis ilmining bilimdoni. Qoshg‘arda tug‘ilgan, qoraxoniylar davlatining poytaxti Bolasog‘unda yashagan. “Devonu lug‘otit-turk” asari (1068) bilan turkshunoslik faniga asos solgan. Yusuf Xos Hojib – dostonnavis adib Bolasog‘unda tug‘ilgan, qoraxoniylar saroyida xizmat qilgan. Uning “Qutadg‘u bilig” – (Saodatga boshlovchi bilim) asari qoraxoniylar davlatining mustahkam qaror topishiga xizmat qilgan nizomnomadir. Lutfiy – XV asr o‘zbek she’riyati takomilida o‘ziga xos o‘ringa ega, katta iste’dod sohibi bo‘lib tuyuq janrining ustasi va o‘z davrining mashhur namoyandasi hisoblangan. Alisher Navoiy – ulug‘ o‘zbek shoiri, mutafakkiri va davlat arbobi. G‘arbda chig‘atoy adabiyotining buyuk vakili deb qaraladi, sharqda “nizomi millati va din” – (din va millatning nizomi) unvoni bilan ulug‘lanadi.

Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur – ulug‘ o‘zbek shoiri, mutafakkir, tarixchi va davlat arbobi. Markazlashgan davlat va boburiylar saltanati asoschisi. “Boburnoma” asari ensiklopedik asar bo‘lib uni o‘rganishning ilmiy-ma’rifiy va tarbiyaviy ahamiyati beqiyosdir.

Boborahim Mashrab – ulug‘ o‘zbek shoiri, tasavvuf adabiyotining yetuk namoyandasi. Jahon otin Uvaysiy – atoqli shoira, o‘zbek shoirlari murabbiysi Jahon otin Uvaysiy Marg‘ilonda tug‘ilgan. Otasi Siddiq bobo ikki tilda she’rlar yozgan.

Nodira (Komila) – taniqli shoira, davlat arbobi. Asl ismi Mohlaroyim, mumtoz adabiyot merosiga o‘zining g‘azallari bilan hissa qo‘shgan.

Jadid adabiyoti davri (1905 – 1930-yillar). Mahmudxo‘ja Behbudiy – dramaturg, noshir, din va jamoat arbobi. Turkistonda jadidchilik harakatining yetakchilaridan biri. Abdulla Avloniy – XIX asr oxiri XX asr boshidagi o‘zbek milliy madaniyatining mashhur vakillaridan biri ma’rifatparvar shoir, dramaturg, jurnalist, olim, davlat va jamoat arbobidir. Abdurauf Fitrat – O‘rta Osiyo jadidchilik harakatining mashhur vakillaridan, yangi o‘zbek adabiyotining asoschilaridan, usuli

jadid maktablarining nazariyotchisi va amaliyotchisi, dramaturg, nosir, shoir va olim. Hamza Hakimzoda Niyoziy – jadid adabiyoti namoyandasi, shoir, dramaturg, adib va muallim. Abdulla Qodiriy – o‘zbek milliy romanchiligining asoschisi, hajv ustasi, tilshunos olim va tarjimon. Abdulhamid Cho‘lpon – o‘zbek yangi she‘riyatining asoschilaridan biri, dramaturg, nosir va tarjimon.

Sovet davri adabiyoti (20-asrning 30-80-yillari). G‘afur G‘ulom – yozuvchi, shoir, dramaturg, o‘zbek tarjima maktabining maydonga kelishiga ham ulkan hissa qo‘shgan. U “Otello”, “Qirol Lir” singari jahon va rus adabiyoti durdonalarini o‘zbek tiliga katta mahorat bilan o‘giran. Abdulla Qahhor – yozuvchi, muharrir, pedagog, munaqqid. O‘zbek hikoyachiligida alohida o‘ringa ega. Hamid Olimjon – iste’dodli shoir. Lirik she‘rlari bilan XX asr o‘zbek adabiyotiga munosib hissa qo‘shgan. Usmon Nosir – XX asr o‘zbek she‘riyatiga chaqmoqdek kirib kelgan va yashindek qisqa ijodiy umr kechirgan talantli shoir. Zulfiya – O‘zbekiston xalq shoirasi, jurnalist, tarjimon, jamoat arbobi. O‘zining qaynoq she‘riy to‘plamlari bilan nazmda o‘chmas iz qoldirgan. Said Ahmad – O‘zbek nasrining peshqadam arboblardan biri, o‘zining satirik asarlari, hikoya va romanlari bilan ulkan hissa qo‘shgan. Rauf Parfi – isyonkor iste’dodli va taqdirli shoir. Uning she‘riyati va ijodi umuminsoniyat erkinligini kuylash bilan birga, milliy o‘zlikni cho‘qqiga chiqargan. Muhammad Yusuf – shoir, ijodkor, dostonnavis, ona diyor va istiqlol kuychisi. Hozirgi o‘zbek she‘riyatiga yangicha badiiy tafakkur yo‘sinlarini olib kirdi. Abdulla Oripov – atoqli o‘zbek shoiri va jamoat arbobi. U hozirgi o‘zbek she‘riyatida inson qalbidagi murakkablik va ziddiyatlarni teran, haqqoniy o‘ziga xos betakror kuylagan ulkan ijodkordir. Bilamizki, biz tahlilga tortgan ikki millat adabiyoti ham o‘zining qadimiy ildiziga, rivojlanish bosqichiga ega. Koreys adabiyoti ham, O‘zbek adabiyoti ham o‘zining mazmundorligi, tarixiy qimmatini bilan ajralib turadi. Adabiyot tarixida nazmda yozilgan asarlar ham, nasrda yozilgan asarlar ham bu millatlar adabiyotining boy tarixidan darak beradi va doimo uning ko‘lami yangidan yangi mahoratli yozuvchi, shoirlar tomonidan kengayib boraveradi.

Adabiyotlar

1. Boboyev T. Adabiyotshunoslik asoslari. – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston, 2001. – 560 b
2. Hozirgi o‘zbek adabiyotining milliy o‘ziga xosligi. – Toshkent: Fan, 1984. – 200 b.
3. Ким Соволь. Корейская поэзия XX века. – М.: Первое марта, 2003. –175 с.
4. Ким В.Н., У.Т.Сайдазимова, И.Л.Пак. Литература изучаемого языка (Корея). – Ташкент, 2009. – 224 с.
5. Karimov N. XX asr adabiyoti manzaralari. (Birinchi kitob). – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston, 2008. – 536 b.

RAQAMLI KOMMUNIKATSIYA SHAROITIDA INTERNET JANRLARI VA FORMATLARINING O‘ZARO ALOQASI

Eshquvvatova Gulmira Norjigitovna,
O‘qituvchi, Sharof Rashidov nomidagi
Samarqand davlat universiteti Urgut filiali
gulmiraeshquvvatova125@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada XXI asr raqamli muhitida janrshunoslikning yangi yo‘nalishi – internet janrlari masalasi yoritilgan. Internet janri va internet formati tushunchalari farqlanib, ularning o‘zaro bog‘liqligi hamda farqli jihatlari tahlil qilingan. Internet muhitidagi janrlar kanonik (oldindan mavjud bo‘lgan) va kanonik bo‘lmagan (faqat internetda paydo bo‘lgan) turlarga ajratiladi. Bundan tashqari nutqiy janr, veb-janr, multimodallik haqida tadqiqotlar o‘rganilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: *internet janrlari, internet formati, raqamli kommunikatsiya, virtual muloqot, kanonik va kanonik bo‘lmagan janrlar, nutqiy janr, veb-janr, multimodallik, platforma.*

Abstract. This article discusses a new direction in genre studies in the digital environment of the 21st century — the issue of internet genres. The concepts of internet genre and internet format are distinguished, and their interrelation as well as differing aspects are analyzed. Genres in the internet environment are divided into canonical (pre-existing) and non-canonical (emerging solely on the internet) types. Additionally, studies on speech genres, web genres, and multimodality are examined.

Keywords: *internet genres, internet format, digital communication, virtual communication, canonical and non-canonical genres, speech genre, web genre, multimodality, platform.*

XXI asr, ya‘ni raqamli dunyoda janrshunoslik muammolari yana bir dolzarb yo‘nalish bilan boyidi – bu “Internet janrlari” yoki “Global tarmoq janrlari”, yoxud “virtual janrlar” tadqiqotchilarni o‘ziga jalb qildi. Internet muhitidagi muloqotning janr xususiyatlarini tadqiq qilish jarayonida internet-janrlarni ajratish va tavsiflash bo‘yicha turli yondoshuvlardan foydalaniladi, ularning batafsil tahlili L.Y.Shchipitsina, E.I.Goroshko, O.V.Dedova, Y.M.Pak, Y.Prosolova va boshqa ayrim mualliflarning ishlarida ko‘rish mumkin.

Janr (fransuzcha: genre, lotincha: generis – “jins“, “tur“) – san‘at turlarida tarixan shakllangan ichki bo‘linish hamda mazkur bo‘linishni ifodalovchi tushuncha; shakl va mazmun birligidagi o‘ziga xos xususiyatlariga ega bo‘lgan san‘at asarining alohida turi. San‘at asarlarining janr guruhlariga bo‘linishi turli (tanlangan mavzu, badiiy-g‘oyaviy mazmun, shakl jihatlari va boshqalar) mezonlarga tayanib amalga oshiriladi; har bir san‘at turida janr tasnifi o‘ziga xos tizimni tashkil etadi [“O‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘ati” Ziyouz saytida].

L.Y.Shipitsina “janrni tipik deb hisoblashni taklif qildi va nutq harakatlarining modeli, kompyuter vositachiligida hamda maxsus tarmoqlarning barqaror versiyasi yordamida amalga oshirildi” deya ta‘riflaydi [Щипицина Л.Ю. 2009. 238.]. Ushbu ta‘riflar, ehtimol, Internet janrining eng aniq ta‘rifidir.

“Internet-texnologiyalarning doimiy va juda tez rivojlanishi internetning kommunikativ maydonida son-sanoqsiz o‘zgarishlarni keltirib chiqaradi, buning

natijasida Internet janrlari paydo bo'ladi, shakllanadi, o'zgaradi, ba'zan esa haqiqiy muloqotdan ko'ra tezroq yo'qoladi"[Горошко Е.И., Полякова Т.Л. 2011. 119-127.]. Natijada shuni ko'rsatadiki, xorijiy va mahalliy lingvistik adabiyotlarda turli parametrlarga asoslangan Internet janrlarining xilma-xil tasniflarini topish mumkin bo'lib, bu esa janrlarni tasniflash, mezonlarini aniqlash muammosi eng dolzarb masalalardan biriga aylanishiga sabab bo'lmoqda.

Shartli ravishda virtual muloqotning barcha janrlarini kanonik va kanonik bo'lmagan turlarga bo'lish mumkin. Kanonik deganda biz adabiyotda, tilshunoslikda yoki madaniyatda o'z qo'llanilishini topgan janrlarni tushunamiz. Ushbu ta'rifdan kelib chiqqan holda, virtual makon uchun reklama janri kanonikdir, ya'ni u Internet muhitida paydo bo'lmagan, lekin ilgari mavjud bo'lgan (masalan, media matnlarda). Kanonik bo'lmagan janrlar – bu Internet makonida paydo bo'lgan va undan tashqarida mavjud bo'lmagan janrlardir. Biz bu turga quyidagi janrlarni kiritishimiz mumkin: elektron pochta, blog, ICQ, chat, forum, ijtimoiy tarmoq va o'yin portali. Ushbu janrlar ma'lum dasturiy ta'minot periferiyasi, xarakterli xususiyatlar va Internet muhitida ishlash shartlari bilan ta'minlangan [Селютин А.А. 2009. 138-141.].

Internet tarmog'i o'ziga xos kommunikativ shakllarni vujudga keltirishi mumkin, ammo bunday shakllar tashqi (tarmoqdan tashqari) haqiqatda yuzaga chiqishi mumkin emas. Masalan, O.V.Dedovanning fikriga ko'ra, kompyuter diskursi nafaqat an'anaviy janrlarni o'zgartiradi, balki "o'ziga xos janrlarni (masalan, virtual muzeylar, adabiy o'yinlar, tarmoq kundaliklari va hokazo) shakllantiradi; bu janrlar sof texnik sabablarga ko'ra an'anaviy yozma muloqot doirasida amalga oshira olmaydi [Дедова О.В. 2008. 284].

"Internet-janrlar" atamasi quyidagi ikki ma'noda tushunilishi mumkin:

1. Nutqiy veb-janrlar – Internet muhitida mavjud bo'lgan matnlar (shu jumladan, gipermatnlar) turlari.

Bular qatoriga: dastlabki doset' davri (tarmoqdan oldingi) muloqotidan bu muhitga ko'chirilgan va unga moslashtirilgan janrlar, hamda Internetning o'ziga xos texnik imkoniyatlari tufayli faqat shu muhitda yuzaga kelgan yangi janrlar kiradi.

2. Veb-kommunikativ voqealar va vaziyatlarning stereotip modellari ya'ni internet-muloqot sharoitida kommunikantlarning nutqiy xatti-harakatlar dinamikasining andozaviy shakllari [Усачева О.Ю. 2010. – С. 51-57.].

Virtual olamda veb-muhitdagi kommunikativ voqealarga o'zgaruvchan ta'sir ko'rsatadigan "yangi diskursiv sharoitlar", ya'ni kommunikativ vazifalarni hal qilish uchun maxsus yaratilgan va qo'llaniladigan dasturiy vositalar (texnik terminologiyada bular platformalar deb ataladi) mavjud bo'lib, tilshunoslikda "internet formati" tushunchasi bilan ifodalanadi. Bunga misol qilib, elektron pochta, forum, veb-sayt, chat, qidiruv tizimlari va boshqa turli dasturiy platformalarni kiritish mumkin.

Internet janri yuqorida ta'kidlab o'tilganidek, ham nutqiy, ham voqeaviy shaklga ega hisoblanadi, format esa matnga ham kommunikativ voqea bilan ham bevosita bog'liq emas. Chunki u muloqot hodisasini matnli shaklda amalga oshirishga xizmat qiluvchi texnik vositalar majmuasi hisoblanadi. Shu sababli ham,

formatning xususiyatlariga na voqeaviy, na matnga oid belgilarni tatbiq etib bo'lmaydi. Masalan, internet janrida har qanday kommunikativ voqea ma'lum vaqt davomida sodir bo'ladi va u jarayonlilik xususiyatiga ega hisoblanadi, bu esa quyidagi belgilarni talab qiladi: *bosqichlilik; tarkibiy qismlarga ajralish; vaqt bilan chegaralanganlik* kabilar.

Format esa bunday xususiyatlarga ega emas. Bundan tashqari, matn toifalari nuqtai nazaridan ham janrga xos bo'lgan quyidagi tushunchalar formatga tatbiq etilmaydi: *mazmuniy izchillik; grammatik bog'liqlik; gipermatnlik ko'rinishi*.

Shu bilan birga, formatning texnik imkoniyat va cheklovlar bilan bog'liq bo'lgan o'ziga xos parametrlarga ega. Bular quyidagilar: *muloqotning vaqt rejimi (sinxron yoki asinxron); aloqa kanali xususiyatlari (bir yo'nalishli yoki ikki yo'nalishli; novizual yoki vizual: vizual-ikonik, vizual-matnli); elektron resursga kirishning cheklangan yoki cheklanmagan bo'lishi; interaktivlik darajasi; asosiy adresatsiya (yo'llanish) xususiyati* va boshqalar.

Internet diskurs yuzaga kelish nuqtai nazaridan tadqiq etganda, format tashqi, ya'ni ekstralingvistik diskursiv omil sifatida ishtirok etsa, janr – ichki, kognitiv kommunikativ shart-sharoit hisoblanadi. Bu hodisa K.F. Sedovning ta'kidlashicha, "Nutqiy janrlar til shaxsining ongida fikrning so'zga aylanish jarayoniga ta'sir etuvchi freymmlar ko'rinishida mavjud bo'ladi" [Седов К.Ф. 2004. 320].

Format va janr o'rtasida faqat farqlar emas, balki o'xshash jihatlar ham mavjud. Masalan, Stereotiplik – ya'ni takrorlanuvchanlik va kutilganlik (prognozlanadiganlik) kabi belgilar bilan bog'lanadi.

Format va janr o'zaro bog'liq hisoblanadi, chunki har bir format muayyan bir janr repertuariga ega bo'ladi.

Bundan ko'rinadiki, "Internet janri" va "Internet formati" tushunchalari o'rtasida o'zaro o'xshash va farqli jihatlar mavjud bo'lib, ularni quyidagi jadval asosida taqdim etdik:

№	Asosiy mezonlar	Internet janri	Internet formati
1	Ta'rifi	Nutqiy va voqeaviy shakllarga ega bo'lgan kommunikativ model	Texnik imkoniyatlar va vositalar majmuasi (platforma)
2	Maqsad	Fikrni matnda ifodalash va sotsiomuloqotga xizmat qilish	Matnli muloqotni texnik jihatdan amalga oshirish
3	Diskursdagi roli	Ichki: kognitiv, freymmlar orqali ongda mavjud	Tashqi: texnologik tashkiliy muhit
4	Vaqt bilan bog'liqligi	Jarayonli, vaqtga bo'ysunuvchi (bosqichli)	Vaqt bilan bog'liq emas (statik)
5	Matn xususiyatlariga taalluqliligi	Kogezion (bog'liqlik), koherensiya (izchillik), gipermatnlilik	Bu xususiyatlar bilan bog'liq emas
6	Ijtimoiy tasnif imkoni	Muloqot sohalari orqali (ishbilarmonlik, OAV, shaxsiy va h.k.)	Ijtimoiy tasnifga ega emas

7	Stereotiplik	takrorlanuvchi va kutilgan janr modeli mavjud	platformada barqaror muloqot shakllari mavjud
8	O‘zaro bog‘liqligi	Platformaga xos janrlar yuzaga keladi	Har bir format o‘ziga xos janr repertuariga ega
9	Misollar	Tvit, blogpost, forum javobi, elektron maktub, sharh, mem	Twitter, blog platformasi, forum, e-mail, chat, qidiruv tizimi va h.k.

Demak, internet janrlarini tasniflash ularning **kommunikativ modeli, platformasi, diskurs xususiyatlari va modal vositalari** asosida amalga oshiriladi. Har bir internet janri **interaktivlik, tezkorlik, ko‘p modallik va ijtimoiy o‘zgaruvchanlik** kabi xususiyatlarga ega.

Adabiyotlar

1. Сидорова И.Г. Коммуникативно-прагматические характеристики жанров персонального интернет-дискурса (сайт, блог, социальная сеть, комментарий): Автореф. ... канд. филол. наук. – Волгоград, 2014. – С.14.
2. “O‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘ati“ Ziyouz saytida
3. Щипицина Л.Ю. Жанры компьютерно-опосредованной коммуникации. Монография. – Архангельск: Поморский университет, 2009. – С.238.
4. Горошко Е.И., Полякова Т.Л. К построению типологии жанров социальных медий. – Харьков, Украина 2011. – С.119-127.
5. Селютин А.А. Жанры как форма коммуникативного выражения онлайн-личности // Вестник Челябинского государственного университета. – 2009. - №35 (173). – Филология. Искусствоведение. – Вып.37. – С. 138-141.
6. Дедова О.В. Теория гипертекста и гипертекстовые практики в Рунете. – М: МАХ Press, 2008. – 284 с.
7. Усачева О.Ю. К определению понятия «жанр интернета» и построению модели жанра в среде интернет. Мир русского слова. №1, 2010. – С. 51-57.
8. Седов К.Ф. Дискурс и личность: эволюция коммуникативной компетенции. – М., 2004. – С. 320.

FAN O‘QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI VA YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR

Muradov Sabina Alisher qizi,
Guliston davlat universiteti magistranti
sabimuradova411@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada, fan o‘qitishda zamonaviy usullar va yangi pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo‘llashning ahamiyati, ularning samaradorligi hamda ta‘lim jarayonida qo‘llash yo‘llari yoritilgan. Interaktiv metodlar, axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, muammoli ta‘lim va innovatsion yondashuvlar ta‘lim sifatini oshirishda muhim omil bo‘lib xizmat qilishi alohida tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Zamonaviy usullar, pedagogik texnologiya, innovatsiya, interaktiv metodlar, muammoli ta‘lim, axborot texnologiyalari, ta‘lim sifati.

Abstract: This article discusses the importance of using modern methods and new pedagogical technologies in teaching science, their effectiveness and ways of using them in the educational process. The importance of interactive methods, information and communication technologies, problem-based learning and innovative approaches as important factors in improving the quality of education is analyzed separately.

Keywords: Modern methods, pedagogical technology, innovation, interactive methods, problem-based learning, information technologies, quality of education.

Bugungi globallashuv va raqamli texnologiyalar davrida ta'lim tizimida samaradorlikka erishish uchun yangicha yondashuvlarni qo'llash zarur. An'anaviy dars o'tish shakllari hozirgi kunda o'quvchilarning faolligini oshirish, ijodiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishda yetarli emas. Shu sababli o'qituvchilardan zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarni egallash, ularni dars jarayoniga samarali tatbiq etish talab etiladi.

Ayni paytda boshqa sohalar qatori ta'lim tizimi ham chuqur o'zgarishlarni boshdan kechirmoqda. Ta'lim maqsadlari o'zgardi, yangilangan o'quv dasturlari ishlab chiqilmoqda. Zamonaviy sharoit ta'lim mazmuni nafaqat alohida fanlar, balki integratsiyalashgan ta'lim yo'nalishlari orqali ham o'z aksini topadigan yangi yondashuvlarni joriy etish zarurligini taqozo etmoqda. Yangi tushunchalar va standartlar shakllantirilmoqda, ular mazmuniga emas, balki kutilayotgan ta'lim natijalari va faoliyat sohalariga qaratilgan. Bularning barchasi geografiya o'qitish metodida yangi nazariy tadqiqotlarning paydo bo'lishi uchun shart-sharoit yaratadi va o'quv jarayonini tashkil etishda boshqa yondashuvlardan foydalanishni taqozo etadi.

Ta'lim – bu o'qituvchi va o'quvchilarning birgalikdagi faoliyati bo'lib, unda o'qitish, tarbiyalash va shaxsni rivojlantirish jarayoni amalga oshiriladi. Darsda o'qituvchi bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarni mashqlar tizimi orqali beradi, o'quvchilar esa ularni o'zlashtirib, olgan bilimlarini amalda qo'llash ko'nikmasiga ega bo'ladilar. O'quv jarayonida maktab o'quvchilari ma'lumotni idrok etish va qayta ishlashning turli usullaridan foydalanadilar, bu ularning kognitiv faoliyatining individual xususiyatlari bilan bog'liq. Shunday qilib, ta'lim va tarbiya vazifalari o'qituvchi va o'quvchilarning sinfdagi o'zaro aloqasi, shuningdek, mustaqil ish va sinfdan tashqari ishlar orqali hal qilinadi. Ta'lim maqsadlari jamiyat talablaridan kelib chiqib shakllanadi. Shuning uchun ular adekvat bo'lishi va zamonaviy talablarga javob berishi kerak. Ilmiy adabiyotlarda ta'limning asosiy maqsadi – mavjud imkoniyatlardan oqilona va samarali foydalanish ko'nikmasini shakllantirish, mantiqiy va ijodiy fikrlashni shakllantirish, kommunikativ savodxonlik darajasini oshirish, milliy qadriyatlarni mustahkamlash, ma'naviy boy shaxsni tarbiyalash va uni yuksak g'oyalar sari yo'naltirish ekanligi alohida ta'kidlanadi. Ushbu vazifalarga muvofiq o'quvchilarda muloqot madaniyati shakllanadi, mustaqil fikrlash, og'zaki va yozma nutq, mantiq va tahlil qilish ko'nikmalari shakllanadi. Shu bilan birga, ma'naviy-estetik va mafkuraviy tarbiya amalga oshiriladi, tilni o'rganish orqali xalqning madaniy va axloqiy qadriyatlari bilan tanishish uchun sharoit yaratiladi.

Zamonaviy o'quv jarayonida ta'lim sifatini oshirish, o'quv vaqtini oqilona taqsimlash va o'quvchilarning reproduktiv faolligi ulushini kamaytirish uchun yangi

texnologiyalar qo'llaniladi. Asosiy e'tibor o'quvchilarning kognitiv faolligi va ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan. Zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari o'quv jarayonini individuallashtirish va o'zgaruvchanlikka, yoshi va tayyorgarlik darajasidan qat'i nazar, masofaviy ta'lim va talabalarning akademik harakatchanligini ta'minlashga qaratilgan. Ta'lim texnologiyasi ta'lim jarayonini loyihalash, tashkil etish, baholash, sozlash va takror ishlab chiqarishga tizimli yondashuv sifatida talqin etiladi.

Kasbiy ta'limda bilim va ko'nikmalarni o'zlashtirish samaradorligini oshirishga imkon beradigan turli xil pedagogik texnologiyalar faol qo'llaniladi. O'quv jarayoniga zamonaviy ta'lim va axborot texnologiyalarining integratsiyalashuvi o'qituvchiga o'quvchilar bilimni chuqurlashtirish va tizimlashtirish, texnologik tafakkurini shakllantirish, o'quv va ilmiy-tadqiqot faoliyatini mustaqil rejalashtirish qobiliyatini rivojlantirish, shuningdek, intizom va mas'uliyatni rivojlantirish imkonini beradi. Innovatsion usullardan foydalanish ta'lim jarayonini yanada dinamik va samarali qiladi.

Mutaxassislar tayyorlashning birinchi navbatda bilim to'plash va kasbiy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishga yo'naltirilgan an'anaviy tizimi zamonaviy talablarga javob bermagani uchun o'z ahamiyatini asta-sekin yo'qotib bormoqda. Bugungi kunda eng muhimi, o'quv fanlari emas, balki fikrlash va harakat usullari. Bu nafaqat malakali mutaxassisni bitirish, balki uni yangi texnologiyalarni o'zlashtirish, muayyan kasbiy muhitga moslashish, mustaqil qarorlar qabul qilishga tayyorlash ham muhimdir.

Pedagogik amaliyotga innovatsion yondashuvlarni joriy etish tajribasi ularning muhim afzalliklarini ko'rsatadi. Ular bilimlarni faol egallashga hissa qo'shadi, o'quvchilarning ijtimoiy va ijodiy faolligini rag'batlantiradi, ularning ta'lim jarayonida bevosita ishtirok etishi uchun sharoit yaratadi. Bunday texnologiyalar nafaqat bilim va kasbiy ko'nikmalarni egallashni, balki faol hayotiy pozitsiyani shakllantirishni ta'minlab, o'rganishni hayotiy vaziyatlarga yaqinlashtirishga imkon beradi.

Hozirgi bosqichda ta'limning ustuvor vazifasi shaxsni rivojlantirish, uning ijodiy salohiyati va mustaqilligini ochib berishdir. Bu esa mustaqil ish usullaridan, o'z-o'zini nazorat qilishdan, o'qitishning faol shakllaridan kengroq foydalanishni taqozo etadi. Biroq, bu natijalarning barchasiga faqat o'quvchilarning o'rganishga va ilmiy izlanishlarga barqaror qiziqishlari mavjud bo'lganda erishish mumkin.

Belgilangan maqsadlarga erishish zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanishga yordam beradi: ta'lim darajasini farqlash texnologiyalari, guruh texnologiyalari, kompyuter o'qitish, o'yin usullari, muammoli va tadqiqot o'qitish, shuningdek, o'quv materialining diagrammalari va ramziy modellari asosida o'quv jarayonini faollashtirish texnologiyalari va kooperativ pedagogika. Bunday yondashuvlardan foydalanish qulay hissiy muhitda o'quvchilarning faol, ko'p bosqichli kognitiv faoliyati davomida ilmiy va o'quv bilimlarini, shuningdek amaliy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish va rivojlantirishga imkon beradi, shu bilan birga o'rganish uchun ijobiy motivatsiya yaratadi.

Zamonaviy pedagogik jarayonda “pedagogik texnologiya” atamasi juda keng qo‘llaniladi. Biroq, uni tushunish va qo‘llashda sezilarli farqlar mavjud bo‘lib, bu turli olimlar, masalan, B. T. Lixachev, V. P. Bepalko, I. P. Volkov va boshqalar tomonidan taklif qilingan turli xil ta’riflarda namoyon bo‘ladi. Mohiyatan, pedagogik texnologiya bu barcha talqinlarning semantik elementlarini o‘z ichiga olgan umumlashgan tushunchadir.

G.K.ning pozitsiyasiga ko‘ra. Selevko, “pedagogik texnologiya” tushunchasini uch jihatdan ko‘rib chiqish mumkin:

1. Ilmiy jihat – pedagogik texnologiyalar pedagogika fanining bir qismi sifatida, o‘qitishning maqsadlari, mazmuni va usullarini o‘rganish, shuningdek, pedagogik jarayonlarni loyihalash.

2. Protsessual-tavsifiy jihat – bu rejalashtirilgan natijalarga erishish uchun zarur bo‘lgan maqsadlar, mazmun, usullar va vositalarni o‘z ichiga olgan ta’lim jarayonining algoritmik tavsifi.

3. Protsessual-natijaviy jihat – shaxsiy, instrumental va uslubiy vositalar yordamida pedagogik jarayonni amaliy amalga oshirish.

Har bir o‘qituvchi o‘z o‘quvchilarining o‘rganilayotgan fanga chinakam qiziqish ko‘rsatishiga, ular ma’ruza materialini mexanik idrok etish bilan cheklanib qolmasdan, uning mazmunini mazmunli idrok etishiga, mantiqiy fikr yurita olishiga va o‘quv jarayonidan zavqlanishlariga intiladi. O‘rganish quvonchi talabaga ham, o‘qituvchiga ham bo‘lishi kerak. Biroq, tayyor ma’lumotni passiv tinglash o‘rganishning eng kam samarali usullaridan biridir, chunki bilimni bir kishidan ikkinchisiga mexanik ravishda o‘tkazib bo‘lmaydi.

Shuning uchun ham talaba ta’lim jarayonining passiv iste’molchisi emas, balki faol ishtirokchisi bo‘lishi kerak. Bilimlarni egallash talabaning o‘rganilayotgan fanga qiziqishi bo‘lsa, uning o‘z faoliyati jarayonidagina sodir bo‘ladi. Shu munosabat bilan o‘qituvchi oddiy informator roldan voz kechishi va maktab o‘quvchilarining bilim faoliyatining tashkilotchisi va muvofiqlashtiruvchisi sifatida harakat qilishi kerak. U darsda o‘quv va kognitiv faoliyatning turli shakllari uchun sharoit yaratib, talabalarga rahbarlik qilishi kerak.

Shu bilan birga, o‘quvchining o‘quv faoliyati o‘rganilayotgan material mazmuniga mos bo‘lishi va shunday tashkil etilishi kerakki, o‘quvchi mustaqil xulosalar chiqaradi, yangi bilimlarni oladi. Didaktikaning eng muhim tamoyili bilimlarni mustaqil qurish tamoyilidir: ular tugallangan shaklda uzatilmaydi, balki maxsus tashkil etilgan bilish faoliyati jarayonida talabaning o‘zi tomonidan shakllantiriladi.

Ta’lim jarayonining muhim jihati – bilimlarni samarali qo‘llash, tizimlashtirish va umumlashtirish uchun sharoit yaratishdir. O‘qitishning bunday tashkil etilishi o‘quvchilarning fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirishga yordam beradi, diqqatlilikni, tahlil qilish, taqqoslash va muhim narsalarni ajratib ko‘rsatish qobiliyatini shakllantiradi, ularni passiv tinglovchilardan ta’lim faoliyatining faol ishtirokchisiga aylantiradi. Shunday qilib, turli texnologiyalardan foydalanish talabalarning bilim va ijodiy qiziqishlarini shakllantirishga yordam beradi. Shu bilan birga, zamonaviy

ta'lim va axborot texnologiyalarini joriy etish an'anaviy o'qitish usullaridan butunlay voz kechishni anglatmaydi, balki ularning organik qo'shilishi hisoblanadi.

Xulosa sifatida ta'kidlash joizki, o'qituvchi pedagogik-psixologik muloqot jarayonining faol ishtirokchisi bo'lishi uchun o'zida muayyan sifatlarni shakllantirishi lozim. Avvalo, u mulohazali, bosiq, vaziyatni to'g'ri baholay oladigan va mavjud ziddiyatlarni iroda kuchi bilan yenga biladigan shaxs bo'lishi kerak. O'quvchilar, ota-onalar hamda hamkasblar bilan muloqotda fikrlarni aniq va to'liq ifodalash muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bu jarayonda salbiy jihatlar emas, balki o'quvchining yutuqlari e'tirof etilishi, unga ishonch bildirilishi va hamkorlik muhiti yaratilishi maqsadga muvofiqdir. O'qituvchining so'zlarida samimiyat, xayrixohlik, do'stona munosabat sezilib turishi, suhbat davomida imkon qadar ko'tarinki kayfiyatni namoyon etishi lozim. Shunday sifatlarni mujassam bo'lgan qiyofa o'qituvchiga nafaqat o'quvchilar, balki ota-onalar va hamkasblar orasida ham obro'-e'tibor qozonish imkonini beradi.

Adabiyotlar

1. Xodjeyev A. Pedagogik texnologiyalar va pedagogik mahorat. – Toshkent: Fan, 2020.

2. Yo'ldoshev J.G'., Usmonov S.A. Pedagogik texnologiya asoslari. – Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 2019.

3. Ziyayeva D. Innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalar. – Toshkent: Ilm Ziyo, 2021.

4. Hasanboyeva O. Ta'lim jarayonida interaktiv metodlar. – Toshkent: O'zbekiston, 2018.

5. Qodirov M. Axborot texnologiyalari va ta'lim. – Samarqand: SamDU nashriyoti, 2020.

TALABALARNI IJODIY-TADQIQIY FAOLIYATGA TAYYORLASH METODIKASI

**Qambarova Charos Hayitmurod qizi,
Qarshi ixtisoslashtirilgan madaniyat maktabi o'qituvchisi**

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola va ta'limiy ishda **ijodiy-tadqiqiy faoliyat** tushunchasi, uning psixologik va pedagogik nazariyalari, shuningdek, O'zbekiston sharoitida ijodiy-tadqiqiy faoliyatni rivojlantirish metodikasi tahlil qilinadi. Nazariy asos sifatida **Guilford, Boden, Gabora** va boshqa olimlarning kreativlik nazariyalari, shuningdek, **C-K nazariyasi** kabi zamonaviy ilmiy yondashuvlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqolada ijodiy-tadqiqiy faoliyatga tayyorlash metodikasi, divergent va konvergent fikrlash jarayonlari, shaxsning kreativ salohiyatini oshirish usullari haqida so'z boradi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi ta'lim tizimidagi amaliy misollar, jumladan, maktabgacha ta'limda ijodiy qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirish, maktab va oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ilmiy-ijodiy faoliyatni rag'batlantirishga oid tadqiqotlar ko'rsatib o'tilgan. Ushbu ish nafaqat ilmiy-tadqiqot faoliyati samaradorligini oshirish, balki

pedagoglarning va yoshlarning kreativ fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga ham qaratilgan. Maqola ta'lim sohasidagi mutaxassislar, o'qituvchilar, metodistlar hamda yosh tadqiqotchilar uchun foydali bo'lib, ijodiy-tadqiqiy faoliyatni tashkil etishda ilmiy va amaliy yo'nalishlarni belgilashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Аннотация. В данной работе рассматривается понятие **творческой исследовательской деятельности**, ее психологические и педагогические теории, а также методика подготовки к творческой исследовательской деятельности в условиях Узбекистана. В качестве теоретической базы проанализированы современные научные подходы, включая теории креативности таких ученых, как **Гилфорд, Боден, Габора**, а также теория С-К. Рассматриваются процессы дивергентного и конвергентного мышления, методы повышения творческого потенциала личности.

В работе приведены практические примеры из системы образования Узбекистана, включая развитие творческих способностей детей дошкольного возраста и стимулирование научно-творческой деятельности в школах и вузах. Данное исследование направлено на повышение эффективности научно-исследовательской деятельности, а также развитие творческого мышления педагогов и молодежи. Материал будет полезен специалистам в области образования, преподавателям, методистам и молодым исследователям для организации творческой исследовательской деятельности и определения научно-практических направлений.

Annotation. This paper examines the concept of **creative-research activity**, its psychological and pedagogical theories, and the methodology for preparing individuals for creative-research activity in the context of Uzbekistan. The theoretical foundation includes an analysis of contemporary scientific approaches, such as creativity theories by **Guilford, Boden, Gabora**, and the C-K theory. The processes of divergent and convergent thinking, as well as methods for enhancing individual creative potential, are discussed.

Practical examples from the education system of Uzbekistan are presented, including the development of creative abilities in preschool children and the promotion of scientific and creative activities in schools and universities. This study aims to improve the effectiveness of scientific research activities and foster creative thinking among educators and youth. The material is useful for education specialists, teachers, methodologists, and young researchers in organizing creative-research activities and defining scientific and practical directions.

Ijodiy-tadqiqiy faoliyat – bu yaratuvchanlik (ijodkorlik) va ilmiy-tadqiqot metodlarini birlashtirgan faoliyat bo'lib, unda shaxs yoki guruh mavjud bilim va tajriba asosida yangi g'oyalar, nazariyalar, metodologiyalar, texnologiyalar, san'at asarlari yoki innovatsion yechimlar ishlab chiqadi. Bu faoliyat – yo'llanma bo'yicha sistematik, metodologik, nazariy asoslari bo'lgan va amaliy natija yaratishga qaratilgan jarayon hisobladi.

Ko'plab xorijiy va o'zbek olimlarining tadqiqot ishlarini tahlil qildik. Jumladan:

Joy P. Guilford kreativ fikrlashni tahlil qilib, “konvergent” va “divergent” fikrlash tushunchalarini kiritgan. Divergent fikrlash – ko‘plab yechimlarni topa olish, ko‘p fikrlar hosil qilish, erkinlik va originallik; konvergent fikrlash – tahlil, ma’lum bir samarali yechimga kelish. Bu nazariya ijodiy-tadqiqiy faoliyatda muhim: boshlang‘ich bosqichda divergent fikrlash, so‘ng konvergent fikrlash orqali yechimga kelinadi;

Dual-process modellari – so‘nggi psixologik tadqiqotlarda kreativlik jarayoni ikki turdagi fikrlash protsesslari orqali kechadi: birinchi tur (tez, intuitiv, avtomatik) – g‘oyalarni hosil qilish, fikrlarni kengaytirish; ikkinchi tur (sekin, ongli, tahliliy), g‘oyalarni baholash, tahrirlash, amalga tatbiq etish;

Holm-Hadulla’ning dialektik kreativlik nazariyasi – bu nazariyada ijodiylik tartib va notartib (order and chaos), struktur va assotsiativ fikrlash, fokussiz va fokusli holatlar o‘rtasidagi dialektik qarama-qarshiliklar orqali paydo bo‘ladi. Shaxs xususiyatlari (intellektual, motivatsion, psixologik) va jarayonlar o‘zaro qarama-qarshi bo‘lgan unsurlar birlashib kreativ natija keltiradi;

“Honing Theory” (Liane Gabora) – bu nazariya ijodiy jarayonni murakkab tizim sifatida ko‘radi. Unda “psixologik entropiya” – noma’lumlik, xavotir, noaniqlik holati paydo bo‘ladi, keyin shaxs bu holatni yangi kontekstlarda qayta ko‘rib, tarkibni qayta tuzadi – bu qayta qurish (restructuring) jarayonida yaratuvchanlik yuzaga keladi;

C-K Nazariyasi (Concept-Knowledge Theory) – bu dizayn va innovatsiya nazariyasi bo‘lib, konsept (C-space) va bilim (K-space) o‘rtasidagi muloqot orqali yangi g‘oyalar va yechimlar yaratilishini tushuntiradi. G‘oyalar (C-space) kengaytiriladi, keyin bilim orqali tasdiqlanadi;

Boden P-creativity va H-creativity tushunchalarini kiritgan. P-creativity – shaxs uchun yangi va original g‘oya; H-creativity – tarixiy, madaniyatga muhim ta’sir etuvchi, ilgari bo‘lmagan yangilik. Bu turdagi farqlash ijodiy-tadqiqiy faoliyatda qaysi tur natija kutilayotgani tushunishga yordam beradi.

Yuqoridagi nazariyalarni, tadqiqot ishlarini o‘rganish jarayonida “ijodiy-tadqiqiy faoliyat”ning ilmiy tavsifini quyidagi jihatlar tashkil qiladi degan xulosaga keldik:

Evristik xarakter – ilmiy ijod ko‘pincha noma’lum, o‘rganilmagan sohalarni, muammolarni kashf etishga intiladi. Evristik metod (taxmin, gipoteza qurish, yechimlarni izlash) muhim rol o‘ynaydi;

Yangilik-elementi – yangicha g‘oya, original tashabbus, avval ishlatilmagan metod yoki qarash bo‘yicha natija olish. Ilmiy-tadqiqiy faoliyat keng yangiliklar, ixtirolar yoki fundamental bilimlardan iborat bo‘lishi mumkin;

Metodologik asos – tadqiqot metodlari, nazariy yondoshuvlar, texnikalar va uslublar qo‘llanadi. Ilmiy izchillik va metodologik aniqlik bo‘lishi zarur;

Bilimga, haqiqiylikka asoslanganlik – faktlar, manbalar, nazariy mulohazalar, tajribalar yordamida tekshiriladigan, obyektivlikka intiladigan faoliyat;

Ma’ruza va amaliy qo‘llanishi – tadqiqot natijasi – nazariy bilim bo‘lishi, lekin ko‘pincha amaliy jihatdan qo‘llanilishi, jamiyatga, siyosatga, sanoatga, san’atga yoki ta’limga ta’sir etishi muhim;

Ich-ichki motivatsiya va kreativlik – yaratuvchanlik iste’dodi, qobiliyati, motivatsiyasi muhim. Tadqiqotchi yangi, original yechimlarni izlashga ruhiy, psixologik tayyorgarlikka ega bo‘lishi kerak.

Ijodiy-tadqiqiy faoliyat bir nechta bosqichlarda olib boriladi ular quyidagilardan iborat:

muammoni aniqlash – qaysi yo‘nalishda yangi g‘oya, masala yechimi kerak ekanini belgilash;

adabiyotlar va manbalarni tahlil qilish – avvalgi ilmiy ishlar, nazariyalar, metodlar bilan tanishish;

gipoteza yoki g‘oyani shakllantirish – yangi qarash, nazariy variant, yechim taklifi;

izlanish metodologiyasi tanlash – tajriba, kuzatish, sorovnoma, eksperiment, komparativ tahlil va boshqalar;

tadqiqot (amalga oshirish) – ma’lumot to‘plash, tahlil qilish, qayta ishlash;

natijalarni baholash va muhokama qilish – gipoteza to‘g‘ri ekanligini tekshirish, natijalarni tahlil qilish, cheklovlar va xatolarni aniqlash;

nashr qilish va tatbiq etish – maqola, kitob, patent, loyiha takliflari kabi shakllarda chop etish; amaliyotga kiritish.

Ijodiy-tadqiqiy faoliyatning turlari:

- Nazariy tadqiqot: ilgari ko‘rilmagan g‘oyalarni rivojlantirish, nazariyalar yaratish.

- Amaliy tadqiqot: muammolarni yechish, yangi texnologiyalar, metodlar ishlab chiqish.

- San’at va badiiy ijod: musiqiy, adabiy, tasviriy san’at, dramaturgiya va hokazo.

- Innovatsiyalar: ilm-fan va texnikada yangiliklarni joriy qilish, ijtimoiy texnologiyalarni takomillashtirish.

Ijodiy-tadqiqiy faoliyat quyidagi jihatlari bilan muhim:

Yangi bilimlar ishlab chiqish va ilmiy taraqqiyotga hissa qo‘shish.

Jamiyat ehtiyojlarini qondirish (masalan, sanoat, ta’lim, sog‘liq saqash, texnologiya).

Innovatsiyalar («yangiliklar») va raqobatbardoshlikni oshirish.

Shaxsning (olim, tadqiqotchi, ijodkor) kreativ va fikrlash qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish.

Madaniyat va san’at sohasida estetik, badiiy meros yaratish va saqlashga hissa qo‘shish.

Ijodiy-tadqiqiy faoliyat bilan bog‘liq ba’zi ilmiy va amaliy muammolar:

Yangi g‘oyalar va gipotezalarni tasdiqlash uchun resurslar yetishmasligi (moliyaviy, infratuzilma, asbob-uskunalar).

Tashqi motivatsiya, akademik va ilmiy muhitning qo‘llab-quvvatlashi kamayishi.

Nazariy va amaliy ishlar o‘rtasidagi tafovut – ba’zida nazariy ishlar amaliy qo‘llashda mos kelmasligi.

Ijodiy jarayonni baholash qiyinchiliklari – original va kreativlik mezonlari subyektiv va kontekstga bog‘liq bo‘lishi mumkin.

Qoidalar, standartlar, etik masalalar – ilmiy jihatdan tekshirilgan bo‘lishi lozim.

Adbiyotlar

1. Turaev, H. T. (2020). *Ilmiy-tadqiqot asoslari*. Toshkent: “Fan va texnologiya” nashriyoti.
2. Yo‘ldoshev, A., Mamajonov, M. (2019). *Ijodkorlik psixologiyasi*. Toshkent: O‘zMU nashriyoti. Kreativlik va ijodiy fikrlashning psixologik asoslari.
3. Abdullaeva, M. M. (2021). “Bo‘lajak o‘qituvchilarni kasbiy-ijodiy faoliyatga tayyorlashning nazariy asoslari” // *Pedagogik mahorat jurnali*, №3(42), 15–21.
4. Xolmatova, M. R. (2022). “Boshlang‘ich sinf o‘quvchilarini ijodiy fikrlashga o‘rgatish metodikasi” // *Ta’lim va innovatsion tadqiqotlar*, №2, 58–64.
5. Nazarova, D. A. (2021). “Ijodiy fikrlash – zamonaviy o‘qituvchining muhim kompetensiyasidir” // *Professional ta’lim muammolari*, №4.
6. Guilford, J. P. (1950). “Creativity”. *American Psychologist*, 5(9), 444–454.
7. Torrance, E. P. (1966). *Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking*. Scholastic Testing Service.
8. Boden, M. A. (2004). *The Creative Mind: Myths and Mechanisms* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
9. Gabora, L. (2016). “The Honing Theory of Creativity”. *Creativity Research Journal*, 28(2), 147–153.
10. Holm-Hadulla, R. M. (2013). “The dialectic of creativity: From neuroscience to psychoanalysis”. *Creativity Research Journal*, 25(3), 293–299.

PEDAGOGIK LOYIHALASH ASOSIDA BO‘LAJAK O‘QITUVCHILARNING NUTQIY FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

Maxsuda Obidova,

Nizomiy nomidagi O‘zbekiston milliy
pedagogika universiteti mustaqil izlanuvchisi

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ona tili ta’limida bo‘lajak o‘qituvchilarning nutqiy faoliyatini pedagogik loyihalashtirishda matn ustida ishlashning nazariy, leksikografik bilimlarning va insoniy fazilatlarining egallanishi, aksiologik-kommunikativ xususiyatlarni rivojlantirish bo‘yicha pedagogik-metodik qarashlar keltirilgan hamda Mahmudxo‘ja Behbudiyning “Bizni kemiruvchi illatlar” maqolasining g‘oyaviy mazmuni tahlilliy o‘rganilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: pedagogik loyihalashtirish, nutqiy faoliyat, maqsad, vazifa kognitiv ta’lim, pedagogik jarayon, o‘quv mashg‘ulotlari, pedagogik loyihalashtirish ustida ishlash.

Abstract. In the pedagogical design of the speech activity of future teachers in the education of the native language in this article, the acquisition of theoretical, lexicographic knowledge of working on the text and the implementation of axiological - communicative properties of human qualities brought boychapedagogic - methodological views, and the ideological content of Mahmudkhoja Behbudi's article "delusions gnawing us" was studied analytically.

Keywords: Pedagogical design, speech activity ,purpose, task cognitive education, pedagogical process, training, work on pedagogical futility.

Аннотация. В данной статье приведены педагогико - методические взгляды на приобретение теоретических, лексикографических знаний и применение аксиолого - коммуникативных особенностей человеческих качеств работы над текстом в педагогическом проектировании речевой деятельности будущих учителей в образовании на родном языке, а также изложены идеологические основы работы над статьей Махмудходжи Бехбуди "Пороки грызунов". содержание изучается аналитически.

Ключевые слова: педагогическое проектирование, речевая деятельность, цель, задача работа над познавательным обучением, педагогическим процессом, учебной деятельностью, педагогическим проектированием.

Bugungi kunda ona tili ta'limida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning nutqiy faoliyatini pedagogik loyihalash metodikasini takomillashtirishga doir ilmiy-nazariy, psixologik-pedagogik, o'quv metodik adabiyotlarning tahliliy o'rganilishi muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Dastavval bo'lajak o'qituvchilarga pedagogik loyihalashni modellashtirish bo'yicha amaliy ko'nikmalarni hosil qilishda loyihalash bo'yicha bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarni chuqur rivojlantirish maqsadga muvofiq.

"Loyihalash faoliyatini pedagogning kasbiy kompetensiyasining pedagogik faoliyatni amalga oshirishga nazariy va amaliy tayyorgarligi birligini ifodalaydigan va kasbiy sifatini tavsiflaydigan qismi sifatida qarash zarur.[1.194]

"Loyihalash ta'limning ijtimoiy, pedagogik maqsadlarga tayangan holda pedagogik jarayonni aks ettiruvchi umumiy strategiya hisoblanadi. Loyihalashda o'quv rejasi, dasturlari, darslik, metodik tavsiyalar va boshqa o'quv qo'llanmalar muhim manba bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Pedagogik vaziyatni to'laqonli anglash hamda vazifalarning aniq va to'g'ri belgilanishi pedagogik jarayonni samarali hal etishning muhim shartidir.[2. 42]

Loyihalash metodikasining jihatlari, uni ta'lim jarayoniga tadbiq etishning samarali usullari Hamrayev A.R.[3], Isroilova R.S. [5], Vanshteyn Y.V.[6], Kruchay E.V. [7] kabi bir qator olimlarimiz ishlarida o'z aksini topgan.

"Ona tili o'quv predmetini o'qitishda o'quvchilarning ijodiy faoliyatini loyihalashtirish uchun o'quv materiallarini o'rganish tizimi, har bir mavzuga oid o'quv elementlari ajratiladi, o'quvchilarning real bilish imkoniyatlari o'rganiladi. Shu asosda o'quvchilarning ijodiy faoliyatini loyihalashtirish xususiyatlari aniqlanib, ularni yaratishda o'quvchilar faoliyatini tashkil etish, boshqarish, nazorat qilish prinsiplari, usullari, vositalari, me'yorlari ishlab chiqiladi".[3.3] Oliy ta'limda bo'lajak o'qituvchilar muayyan mavzuni pedagogic loyihalashtirishi uchun ular

umumta'lim maktablarida mazkur jarayon ustida ishlash ko'nikmalari rivojlanganligi ahamiyatga molik.

B.Mengliyev, Sh.Abdurahim, K.Mavlonova. M.Siddiqov, S.Atoyevalar tomonidan tuzilgan 10-sinf uchun Ona tili [8.33] darsligida Mahmudxoja Behbudiyning 1915-yilda "Oina" jurnalida chop etilgan "Bizni kemiruvchi illatlar" mavzusidagi maqolasi keltirilgan. M. Behbudi "Bizni kemiruvchi illatlar" maqolasi matnida jamiyatdagi turli salbiy holatlarni tanqid qiladi. Mazkur maqola mohiyatidagi g'oyalar quyidagilar:

- jaholat va ilmsizlik: Behbudiyning fikricha, jaholat va ilmsizlik jamiyatni tanazzulga olib keladi. U ta'lim va tarbiyaning ahamiyatini ta'kidlab, xalqni bilim olishga da'vat etadi.

- aksiologik, odob-axloq me'yorlarini anglamaslik; insonlarning yashash tarz ularni hurmat qilish odob-axloq me'yorlariga amal qilish kabilarni tahlilga tortadi.

- Ijtimoiy adolatsizlik: M.Behbudi ijtimoiy adolatsizlik va kamsitishlarni tanqid qilib, u jamiyatdagi barcha insonlar teng huquqlarga ega bo'lishi kerakligini ta'kidlaydi. Mazkur darslikda eskirgan so'zlar haqida nazariy ma'lumotlar, 8.1 – mashqda quyidagi savollarga javob bering topshirig'i berilgan.

- *Maqolada ko'tarilgan masala bugun ham ahamiyatlimi? Nima uchun?*

- *Muallif keraksiz odatlar deb isrof qilinayotgan mablag'ni nimalarga sarflash lozimligini aytadi?*

- *Maqola yozilganiga bir asrdan ko'proq vaqt bo'libdi Shu vaqt ichida muammo kichraydimi yoki yiriklashdimi? Javoblaringizni izohlang.*

Shuni alohida aytishimiz kerakki, M.Behbudiyning "Bizni kemiruvchi illatlar" nomli maqolasini o'quvchilar o'qib va bu matnni tushunish uchun lug'at ustida ishlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiruvchi mashq va topshiriqlar hajmini kengaytirish maqsadga muvofiq. Chunki mazkur maqola matni bo'yicha berilgan savollarga o'quvchilar javob berishlari va subyektiv munosabatlarini bildirishlari uchun matnning asil mazmuni anglab olishlari zarur deb hisoblaymiz.

Behbudiyning yondashuvlari. Jamiyatdagi muammolarni ochiq va tanqidiy yoritadi. Uning maqsadi xalqni uyg'otish, ularni bilimga va axloqiy qadriyatlarga chorlashdir. Muallif jamiyatdagi illatlarni bartaraf etish uchun ta'lim va tarbiyaning ahamiyatini alohida ta'kidlaydi.

Maqola matnining tarbiyaviy ahamiyati. "Bizni kemiruvchi illatlar" asari bugungi kunda ham o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotmagan. Jamiyatdagi jaholat, axloqiy tarbiya va ijtimoiy adolatsizlik kabi muammolar hali ham mavjud. Behbudiyning asari bu muammolarga qarshi kurashishda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Mavzu: M.Behbudiyning "Bizni kemiruvchi illatlar" maqolasi matnini pedagogik loyihalashtirish ishlanmasi

Maqsad: o'quvchilarni Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiyning "Bizni kemiruvchi illatlar" nomli maqolasi matnini o'qitish va mavzu yuzasidan bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarni hosil qilish;

darslikdagi *Eskirgan so'zlar* rukni ostidagi nazariy ma'lumotni o'rganish bo'yicha kognitiv-kommunikativ, nutqiy-kasbiy yondashuvlarini o'qitish

o'sha davr jamiyatidagi salbiy illatlarni tanqidiy tahlil qilish va insonparvarlik, vatanparlik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish;

ma'naviy-axloqiy xususiyatlarni umumiy va xususiy aksiologik qobiliyatlarni o'stirishga qadriyatlarni qadrlashga o'rgatish.

Vazifalar:

- Behbudiyning "Bizni kemiruvchi illatlar" maqolasini o'qish va mazmun-mohiyatidan kelib chiqib subyektiv nuqtai nazarini tahlil qilish;

- maqola matnidagi tarixiy va eskirgan so'zlarning ma'nosi, ya'ni lug'at ustida ishlash ko'nikmasini mustahkamlash;

- maqola matnidan olingan gaplarning ma'lum qismini bugungi adabiy me'yorlar bo'yicha yozishga yo'naltirish.

Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiyning "Bizni kemiruvchi illatlar" nomli maqolasi rejasi:

Funksional muqaddima:

Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiyning "Bizni kemiruvchi illatlar" nomli maqolasi ifodali o'qib eshittirish;

Maqola mohiyatidagi asosiy g'oyani interaktiv tarzda aniqlash uchun mashq va topshiriqlar tuzib, o'quvchilarga taqdim qilish;

"Bizni kemiruvchi illatlar" maqolasini tahlilini o'rganish natijasida olingan xulosani birgalikda eshitib unga shaxsiy munosabat bildirishlari tinglash;

Kommunikativ xususiyatlar tatbig'i

Jaholat va ilmsizlikdan qutqarish bo'yicha o'quvchilarning fikr mulohazasini tinglash;

- Ma'naviy axloqiy xususiyatlarni tarkib toptirish, o'zbekona qadriyatlarga rioya qilish, ijtimoiy adolatsizlik va kamsitishni kamaytirish bo'yicha adibning mulohazalarini sintez qilish;

- To'y va ta'zivalarni o'zining oilaviy jamg'armasidan kelib chiqib, kichik hajmda tashkillashtirish bo'yicha mushohadalarni birgalikda tinglash.

Mantiqiy yechim sharhi

-Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiyning "Bizni kemiruvchi illatlar" nomli maqolasi mazmuni yoshlar tarbiyasiga ta'sir o'tkazishining o'rni va ahamiyatini ifodalash;

-Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiyning "Bizni kemiruvchi illatlar" nomli maqolasidan olingan hayotiy-xulosaviy bir to'xtamga kelingan aksiologik yechim tavsifini izohlash.

-maqoladagi asosiy g'oyaning zamon bilan bog'liqligini bayon qilish, ularning takliflarini umumlashtirish;

Demak, Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiyning "Bizni kemiruvchi illatlar" maqolasi g'oyasini pedagogik loyihalashtirish yordamida tashkil qilish o'quvchilarning nutqiy faoliyatini, bilim egallash va aksiologik-tarbiyaviy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga yordam beradi.

Adabiyotlar

1. Ғаниев Т.Т. Она тилидан машқ бажариш жараёнида ўқувчиларнинг билиш фаоллигини ошириш. Пед. фанл. номз. илм. дараж. олиш учун ёзилган дисс. –Т., 1991. –194 б.

2. Маҳмудов М.Ҳ. Таълимни дидактик лойиҳалашнинг назарий асослари. Пед. фанл. илм. дараж. олиш учун ёзилган дисс. автореферати. –Т., 2004. – 42 б.
3. Ҳамраев А.Р. Она тили таълимида ўқувчиларнинг ижодий фаолиятини лойиҳалаштириш. Пед.ф.д.(DsC) дисс– Т. 2020. – 36
4. Hamrayev A.R. Ona tili ta'limida o'quvchilarning ijodiy faoliyatini loyihalashtirish. Ped.f.d.(DsC) diss. – Т. 2020. – 23b
5. Isroilova R.S. Boshlang'ich sinf ona tili darslarining loyihalash jarayonida o'quvchilarni faollashtirish texnologiyasi muammosining fanda yoritilishi / “XXI asrda ilm- fan taraqqiyotining rivojlanish istiqbollari va ularda innovatsiyalarning tutgan o'rni”. Respublika ilmiy 9-onlayn konferensiyasi materiallari. – Toshkent, 2019.
6. Ванштейн Ю.В., “Педагогическое проектирование персонализированного адаптивного предметного обучения студентов ВУЗа в условиях сифровизатсии” (Диссертация на соискание ученой степени доктора педагогических наук, Красноярск -2021)
7. Кручай Е.В.,”Протсесс педагогического проектирования:теоритико-методические основы». Хабаровск 2006. 61:06-13/2834. «Дальневосточный государственный гуманитарный университет
8. Ona tili 10 [Matn]: 10-sinf uchun darslik / В.Менглиев va boshq. – Toshkent: Respublika ta'lim markazi, 2022. – 33 b.

LINGVISTIK BILIMNING O‘QIB TUSHUNISH KO‘NIKMASIGA TA’SIRI

Navruzova Xosiyat Izzatullo qizi,

Tayanch doktorant, Alisher Navoiy nomidagi
Toshkent davlat o‘zbek tili va adabiyoti universiteti

navruzovaxosiyat363@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. O‘qib tushunish – ta’lim jarayonining asosiy tarkibiy qismi bo‘lib, uning samaradorligi o‘quvchining til birliklarini qay darajada egallaganiga bog‘liq. Ushbu maqolada o‘quvchilarda o‘qib tushunish ko‘nikmasini shakllantirishda lingvistik bilimning ta’siri yoritiladi. Leksik, grammatik va sintaktik bilimlar matnni to‘liq idrok etish, asosiy g‘oyani anglash va muallif maqsadini tushunishda muhim vosita sifatida xizmat qiladi. Shu sababdan o‘qib tushunish va lingvistik ko‘nikmalar integratsiyasi asosida ta’limni tashkil qilish muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so‘zlar. O‘qib tushunish, lingvistik bilim, leksikologiya, morfologiya, sintaksis.

Abstract. Reading comprehension is a fundamental component of the educational process, and its effectiveness depends on the extent to which learners have mastered linguistic units. This article highlights the impact of linguistic knowledge on the development of students’ reading comprehension skills. Lexical, grammatical, and syntactic knowledge serve as essential tools for fully perceiving

a text, understanding its main idea, and identifying the author's intention. Therefore, organizing instruction on the basis of integrating reading comprehension and linguistic skills is of great importance.

Keywords. Reading comprehension, linguistic knowledge, lexicology, morphology, syntax.

Ona tili ta'limining muhim vazifalaridan biri o'quvchilarda mustaqil o'qish va o'qib tushunish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishdir, chunki matnni tushunish nafaqat til ta'limida balki boshqa fanlarni o'zlashtirishda ham tayanch omil hisoblanadi. O'qib tushunish jarayoni tilning barcha qatlamlari bilan bevosita bog'liq bo'lib, o'quvchidan keng qamrovli lingvistik bilimga ega bo'lishni talab qiladi. So'z ma'nolarini anglash, grammatik shakllarning vazifasini to'g'ri talqin qilish, gaplarning mantiqiy bog'lanishini tushunish, badiiy vositalarni sezish matn mazmunini to'g'ri anglashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Har qanday matnni o'qishda so'zning ma'nosini anglash, uni boshqa so'zlardan farqlash, turli vaziyatlarda qanday qo'llanishini tushunish zarur. O'quvchi omonim, sinonim, antonim, paronim, ko'p ma'noli so'zlarni ajrata olsa, matnni chuqurroq anglaydi. Shuningdek, majoziy ma'nodagi birliklarni ham farqlash muhim ahamiyatga ega, chunki o'quvchi faqat so'zning tashqi ma'nosini emas, balki kontekstdagi yashirin ma'nosini ham tushunishga o'rganadi. Tajribalarimizda shuni kuzatdikki, o'quvchilar kontekstual omonimiya va antonimiyada qiyinchilikka uchrashdi. Ular so'zning kundalik hayotda ko'p qo'llaniladigan variantini tanlashgan. Bu jarayon ta'lim jarayonida so'zning kontekstual ma'nosini qamrab olish zaruratini ham ko'rsatadi.

O'zbek tili qo'shimchalarga boy til hisoblanadi va ular orqali turli sintaktik hamda semantik munosabatlar ifodalanadi. Tajriba jarayonida o'quvchilarga *-da* qo'shimchasining ma'nosiga doir savol berilganda, mazmunning to'liq anglanmagani aniqlandi. Agar o'quvchi qo'shimchaning vazifasini farqlay olsa, matnni ancha oson anglaydi. Masalan, shaxs-son qo'shimchalari orqali gapdagi ega kimligini aniqlash, zamon qo'shimchalari orqali voqea qachon sodir bo'lganini tushunish mumkin. Bundan tashqari sifat darajalari, inkor ma'no, o'xshatish va nisbat qo'shimchalarining o'zlashtirilishi ham matnni to'liq anglashda muhim o'rin tutadi.

Odatda matn bir nechta gaplardan iborat bo'ladi va ularning o'zaro bog'lanishini anglash o'quvchiga umumiy mazmunni to'g'ri talqin qilish imkonini beradi. Timothy Shanahan o'quvchilarning murakkab sintaktik shakllarni anglash qobiliyati bilan matnni tushunish samaradorligi o'rtasida bevosita bog'liqlik mavjudligini ta'kidlaydi. Olimning fikricha, o'quvchilar og'zaki va yozma nutqda grammatik jihatdan murakkabroq gaplardan foydalana boshlagan sari, ular matnni chuqurroq talqin qila oladilar. Shuningdek, Shanahan o'qib tushunish darajasini aniqlovchi muhim ko'rsatkichlardan biri grammatik murakkablik deya ta'kidlaydi. Unga ko'ra matnni o'qish va tushunish darajasini belgilashda grammatik omillar lug'aviy omillarga nisbatan ustun turadi. Bu esa o'quvchilarning matnni anglash jarayonida gap tuzilishi, bog'lovchilar hamda qo'shimcha ma'nolarni to'g'ri talqin qilish qobiliyati bilan bog'liqdir [Shanahan, T. 2014]. Gap shakllarini,

bog'lovchilarning ma'nodagi rolini bilish o'qib tushunishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Sabab, shart, inkor, zidlash yoki qiyoslash ma'nosidagi bog'lovchilar o'quvchiga muallifning mantiqiy izchilligini tushunishga yordam beradi. Shanahan o'qib tushunish jarayonida gap darajasidagi bilimni alohida ta'kidlaydi. Uning fikricha, o'quvchining matnni anglash qobiliyati faqat so'z boyligi yoki matnning umumiy tuzilmasi bilan emas, balki gaplarning grammatik murakkabligini to'g'ri talqin qila olish bilan ham chambarchas bog'liqdir [Shanahan, T. 2020]. Shuningdek, o'quvchining gapni to'liq qamrab olishi uchun uyushiq bo'laklar, kiritma va modal so'zlar kabi birliklar ham zarurdir. Tajriba jarayonida inkor va ayiruv bog'lovchili bog'langan qo'shma gaplar, ko'rsatish olmoshili ergashgan qo'shma gaplarni tushunishda o'quvchilar qiyinchilikka uchrashdi. Shu sababdan o'qib tushunish jarayonini tashkil qilishda o'quvchilarni shunday vaziyatlarga qo'yish kerakki, ularning matnni tushunishi muayyan lingvistik to'siqlarni yengish qobiliyatiga bog'liq bo'lsin. Bunda topshiriqlar tilshunos tayyorlashga qaratilgan emas, aksincha, o'quvchilarga gaplarni tushunishga, malakali til foydalanuvchi bo'lishiga yordam beradigan bo'lishi kerak.

O'qib tushunish ko'nikmasini shakllantirishda lingvistik bilim muhim ahamiyatga ega. Leksik, grammatik va sintaktik birliklarni puxta o'zlashtirgan o'quvchi matn mazmunini to'g'ri idrok etadi, muallif fikrini anglaydi va uni qayta ifodalay oladi. Shu sababdan ona tili ta'limida lingvistik birliklarning o'qib tushunishga ta'sirini hisobga olish zaruriy metodik masala hisoblanadi.

Adabiyotlar

1. Shanahan, T. (2014, January 22). *Grammar and Comprehension: Scaffolding Student Interpretation of Complex Sentences*. Grammar and Comprehension: Scaffolding Student Interpretation of Complex Sentences | Shanahan on Literacy. <https://shanahanonliteracy.com/blog/grammar-and-comprehension-scaffoldingstudent-interpretation-of-complex-sentences>

2. Shanahan, T. (2020, October 3). *Why we need to teach sentence comprehension*. Why We Need to Teach Sentence Comprehension | Shanahan on Literacy. <https://shanahanonliteracy.com/blog/why-we-need-to-teach-sentencecomprehension>

TIL O'QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR VA ULARNI TATBIQ QILISH USULLARI

Mamaraximova Xulkar Xo'jamqul qizi,
Mirzaobod tuman 3-sonli umumiy
o'rta ta'lim maktabi Ona tili va
adabiyot fani o'qituvchisi
e-mail: mamaraximova96@umail.uz

Annotatsiya. Ona tili ta'limi bugungi kunda ta'lim tizimining eng muhim bo'g'inlaridan biri hisoblanadi. U nafaqat tilning leksik va grammatik me'yorlarini o'rgatadi, balki o'quvchilarda mantiqiy, tanqidiy va ijodiy tafakkurni shakllantiradi,

boshqa fanlarni muvaffaqiyatli o'zlashtirishga ham asos yaratadi. Shu bois, ona tili ta'limida nazariy va amaliy jihatlarni uyg'unlashtirish, til birliklarining grammatik hamda semantik imkoniyatlarini chuqur o'rganish hamda zamonaviy pedagogik yondashuvlardan foydalanish zaruriyati dolzarb masalaga aylanmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: ona tili ta'limi, bixevioristik yondashuv, integrativ yondashuv, kommunikativ yondashuv, nutqiy kompetensiya, lingvistik kompetensiya, tilshunoslik, zamonaviy pedagogika.

Abstract. Mother tongue education today is considered one of the most important components of the education system. It not only teaches the lexical and grammatical norms of the language, but also develops logical, critical, and creative thinking in students, while laying the foundation for successful learning of other subjects. Therefore, in mother tongue education, it has become a pressing issue to integrate theoretical and practical aspects, to thoroughly study the grammatical and semantic potential of language units, and to apply modern pedagogical approaches.

Keywords: mother tongue education, behaviorist approach, integrative approach, communicative approach, speech competence, linguistic competence, linguistics, modern pedagogy.

Ona tili fanining ta'lim jarayonidagi o'rni beqiyosdir. Chunki u nafaqat o'quvchining til haqidagi nazariy bilimlarini shakllantiradi, balki uning nutqiy, mantiqiy va ijodiy tafakkurini rivojlantiradi. Ona tilini puxta o'zlashtirgan o'quvchi boshqa fanlarni ham samarali o'zlashtira oladi. Shu bois ona tili ta'limini tashkil etishda zamonaviy yondashuvlardan foydalanish muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Ushbu yondashuvlar ichida *bixevioristik, integrativ, kompetensiyaviy va kommunikativ* yondashuvlar alohida o'rin tutadi.

Bixevioristik yondashuvda o'quvchilarni ko'proq tayyor nutqiy birliklarni yod olishga, ularni takrorlash va mustahkamlashga yo'naltiriladi. Bu metod nutqiy faoliyatni shakllantirishda muayyan natijaga erishishni ko'zlaydi. Biroq u amaliy nutqiy vaziyatlarga yetarlicha bog'lanmaganligi bilan cheklanadi.

Integrativ yondashuv ona tili darslarini boshqa fanlar bilan bog'lab o'qitishni nazarda tutadi. Masalan, tarix, adabiyot, geografiya yoki biologiya fanlariga oid matnlar bilan ishlash o'quvchilarda keng dunyoqarash, sohalararo bog'liqlikni anglash va matn ustida ijodiy ishlash malakasini shakllantiradi. Ushbu yondashuv orqali o'quvchilar til bilimlarini faqatgina nazariy qoidalar doirasida emas, balki boshqa fanlar mazmuni bilan uyg'un holda qo'llash imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar. Natijada, til o'rganish jarayoni ko'proq hayotiylik kasb etadi.

Integrativ yondashuvning afzalliklaridan yana biri shundaki, u o'quvchilarning tanqidiy tafakkurini kengaytiradi. Masalan, tarixiy matnlarni o'qish va tahlil qilish orqali o'quvchi tarixiy voqealarga lingvistik nuqtai nazardan qaraydi, adabiy asarlar bilan ishlash jarayonida badiiy ifodaviy vositalarning til tizimidagi o'rnini anglaydi. Geografik yoki biologik matnlar esa ilmiy uslub xususiyatlarini amaliy o'rganishga imkon beradi.

Shu tariqa, integrativ yondashuv faqatgina til o'rganishni emas, balki fanlararo tafakkurni shakllantirish, ilmiy bilishga qiziqishni kuchaytirish, o'z fikrini asoslash va dalillash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga ham xizmat qiladi. O'quvchi tilni nafaqat

kommunikativ vosita sifatida, balki barcha fanlarni o'zlashtirishda asosiy poydevor sifatida idrok etadi.

Kommunikativ yondashuv zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida eng samarali metodlardan biri sifatida e'tirof etiladi. Uning asosiy mohiyati real hayotiy vaziyatlarda nutqni to'g'ri tushunish, o'z fikrini aniq va lo'nda ifodalashga o'rgatishdan iboratdir. Bu yondashuvda til nazariyasi ikkinchi darajali o'rin egallab, o'quvchining nutqiy faoliyati, ya'ni til vositasida muloqot qila olish salohiyatini rivojlantirish bosh maqsad qilib olinadi.

Ona tili darslarida o'quvchilar turli nutqiy vaziyatlarga kiritiladi: *suhbat, munozara, muloqot, monolog va dialog* shakllarida mashqlar bajarish orqali ularning og'zaki nutq malakalari rivojlantiriladi. Shu jarayonda grammatik qoidalar ham bevosita amaliy vaziyatlar orqali mustahkamlanadi. Masalan, shaxs olmoshlarini o'rgatishda o'qituvchi oddiy mashq berishdan ko'ra, o'quvchilarni o'zaro suhbatga jalb qiladi; vaqt shakllarini o'rgatishda esa turli hayotiy voqealar tasvirlanadigan vaziyatlar taqdim etiladi.

Kommunikativ yondashuvning eng katta ustunligi shundaki, u o'quvchining faol sub'ekt sifatida ta'lim jarayonida qatnashishini ta'minlaydi. O'quvchi o'z fikrini mustaqil bayon qiladi, savol beradi, javob beradi, bahs yuritadi va shu tariqa muloqot jarayonida bilimni amaliyotda qo'llashni o'rganadi. Natijada, o'quvchilarda nutqiy kompetensiya (tinglab tushunish, so'zlash, o'qish, yozish) hamda lingvistik kompetensiya (fonetika, grafika, orfoepiya, orfografiya, leksika, grammatika, uslubiyat) birgalikda rivojlanadi.

Kommunikativ yondashuv, shuningdek, o'quvchilarda ijodiy, tanqidiy va mantiqiy tafakkurni shakllantirishda muhim o'rin tutadi. Chunki ularni sun'iy mashq bajarishga emas, balki til vositasida real muloqotga, matn mazmunini anglash va uni qayta ishlashga yo'naltiradi [1, 28]. Ona tili ta'limida bixevioristik, integrativ va kommunikativ yondashuvlarning uyg'un qo'llanilishi o'quvchilar savodxonligini oshirish, ularni mustaqil fikrlashga, bilimlarni hayotiy vaziyatlarda qo'llashga tayyorlash imkonini beradi. Ayniqsa, kommunikativ metodning real muloqotga asoslanganligi ta'lim samaradorligini sezilarli darajada oshiradi.

Til o'qitish metodikasida bixevioristik, integrativ va kommunikativ yondashuvlarning har biri o'z davrida muayyan ahamiyat kasb etgan bo'lsa-da, ularning ta'lim jarayoniga ta'siri turlicha bo'lgan. Bixevioristik yondashuv mashq va takrorlashga asoslanib, o'quvchini passiv o'rganuvchiga aylantirgan bo'lsa, u zamonaviy ta'lim talablari uchun yetarli emasligi bilan ajralib turadi. Integrativ yondashuv esa ona tili ta'limini boshqa fanlar bilan uyg'unlashtirib, o'quvchilarda keng dunyoqarash, mantiqiy tafakkur va sohalararo bog'lanishlarni tushunish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi [6,75]. Kommunikativ yondashuv esa real hayotiy vaziyatlarga asoslanib, o'quvchilarning og'zaki va yozma nutq malakalarini, ijodiy va tanqidiy fikrlash salohiyatini rivojlantirishda eng samarali metodlardan biri sifatida maydonga chiqadi.

Shu bois zamonaviy ona tili ta'limida bixevioristik yondashuvning chegaralangan imkoniyatlaridan voz kechib, integrativ va kommunikativ yondashuvlarni uyg'un qo'llash muhimdir. Bu esa o'quvchini nafaqat grammatik

bilimlarni egallagan, balki ulardan hayotiy vaziyatlarda foydalana oladigan, mustaqil fikrlovchi, muloqotga kirisha oladigan va ijtimoiy kompetent shaxs sifatida shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi.

Adabiyotlar

1. G‘ulomov A. va boshq., O‘zbek tilini o‘qitish metodikasi – Toshkent, 2012.
2. Hamroyev A.R., Po‘lotova Y.A., Ona tilini o‘qitish metodikasi, – Toshkent, 2021.
3. Ona tili. Umumiy o‘rta ta’lim maktablarining 10-sinfi uchun darslik, – Toshkent, 2022
4. Mengliyev B., Abdurahim Sh., Mavlonova K., Siddiqov M. Ona tili -10. O‘qituvchilar uchun metodik qo‘llanma. – T., 2022
5. Mengliyev B., Abdurahim Sh., Mavlonova K., Siddiqov M., Atoyeva S. Ona tili. Umumiy o‘rta ta’lim maktablarining 10-sinfi uchun darslik. –T., 2022
6. O‘rolov A., Qambarov M. O‘zbek tili o‘qitish metodikasi. O‘quv qo‘llanma. – Guliston, 2023

TILSHUNOSLIK FANINING TARAQQIYOTI: YANGI YONDASHUVLAR VA YUTUQLAR

Ro‘ziqulov Shohruh Ilhom o‘g‘li,

Guliston davlat universiteti

O‘zbek tilshunosligi kafedrasi o‘qituvchisi

shohruhziqulovv@gmail.com

Anorboyeva Munisa G‘ulomjon qizi

Guliston davlat universiteti talabasi

Anorboyevamunisa2006@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tilshunoslik fanining taraqqiyoti, til tarixi davrlari, tilshunoslikning o‘rganilish bosqichlari va undagi yutuqlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: tilshunoslik, davr, bosqich, jadid, asr, manbaa.

Abstract. This article presents the development of linguistics, periods of language history, stages of linguistics study and achievements in it.

Keywords: linguistics, period, stage, modern, century, source.

Til davrlar mobaynida o‘zining taraqqiyot bosqichlarini bosib o‘tadi. Tilning til sifatida shakllanishi da elatning ham tashkil topishi muhim sanaladi. Xuddi shunday o‘zbek tilshunosligi ham ,turli davrlarda o‘z o‘zgarishlarini boshdan kechirdi. O‘zbek tilining to‘rtta taraqqiyot bosqichiga bo‘linishi ham buni ko‘rsatib berdi.

Xususan, birinchi davrda o‘zbek tilining ilk taraqqiy davri sifatida X-XIV asrlar ko‘rsatilib, bevosita Mahmud Qoshg‘ariyning “Devonu lug‘atit-turk” asari asosiy manba sifatida berildi. Ayni bu davr bo‘linishi, o‘zbek tilshunosligini o‘rganishdagi birinchi bosqich XI-XIII asrlarga to‘g‘ri keladi. Bunday manba ham Qoshg‘ariyga borib taqaladi. Asar o‘zida 7500 turkiy so‘zni 8 bo‘limda tasviriy holda izohlaydi. So‘zlarni bu shaklda ifodalash, tilshunoslikda qiyosiy-tarixiy metod yaratilishiga asos bo‘ldi. Shuningdek asarda, yangi so‘zlarni yasash, turk tili grammatikasi, sintaksisning turli jihatlari ham talqin etilgandir.

Ikkinchi davr o‘zbek tilining takomillashish davri. Tilshunoslikdagi ikkinchi bosqich XV-XIX asrlar bo‘lib, davr boshlanishi Navoiy asarlari bilan bog‘liq sanaladi. Eski o‘zbek tilshunosligining shakllanishi ham shoirning asarlarida o‘z aksini topdi:

So‘z durki nishon berur o‘lukka jondin,

So‘z durki berur jong‘a xabar jonondin.

“Nazm ul-javohir” asaridan keltirilgan bu parchadagi -dan chiqish kelishigining -din shaklida, -ga jo‘nalish kelishigining -g‘a, -ar zamon qo‘shimchasining -ur shaklida kelishi eski turkiyshunoslikning takomilini ko‘rsatib bera oladi.

O‘zbek tilshunosligini o‘rganishdagi uchinchi bosqich, tilshunoslik o‘rganilishi hamda fan sifatida o‘rgatilishidagi eng yaxshi bosqichlardan biri bo‘ldi. Til tarixida uchinchi davr ham milliy adabiy tilning shakllanishi deb nomlandi va XIX-XX asrlarni o‘z ichiga oldi. Bu davr va bosqich taraqqiyotida ma‘rifatparvar jadidlar: Muqumiy, Abdurauf Fitrat, G‘ozi Olim Yunusov, Ulug‘ Tursunovlarning harakatlari ko‘p bo‘ldi.

Bu bosqichdagi yana bir yutuqlardan biri imlo me‘yorlarining yaratilishiga bo‘ldi, tilga ahamiyat uni to‘g‘ri qo‘llashni boshlagandagina kuchga kirishi amalda o‘z isbotini topdi.

R.Sayfullayeva, B.Mengliyev, G.Boqiyeva, M.Qurbonova, Z.Yunusova, M.Abuzalovalarning “Hozirgi o‘zbek adabiy tili” kitobida keltirilgandek, o‘zbek tilshunosligi XX asrda zamonaviy jahon tilshunosligining bir bo‘lagi sifatida shakllandi.

Tilshunoslikda bir qator o‘zgarishlar XIX asr oxiri hamda XX asrda o‘z takomiliga yetdi. Xususan:

- 1) imlo qoidalari yaratildi,
- 2) o‘rta, o‘rta maxsus va oliy maktablar uchun darslik, qo‘llanmalar;
- 3) bir tilli, ko‘p tilli va turli sohaviy lug‘atlar;
- 4) fonetik va grammatik qurilishda ilmiy izlanishlar;
- 5) leksikologiya va frazeologiyada ilmiy ishlar;
- 6) “O‘zbek tili leksikologiyasi” nomli asar;
- 7) ikki tomli “O‘zbek tili grammatikasi” asari;
- 8) derivatsiyaning alohida fan sifatida ajralib chiqishi.

XX asrning so‘nggi choragiga kelib tilshunoslikda formallik o‘rnini sistemaviylik egallay boshladi. Formal tilshunoslik bevosita kuztishlar davomida berilgan, fonemalarning, grammatik shakllarning ko‘rinishlari tasvirlangan bo‘lsa, sistem-struktur tilshunoslik har bir shakllarning o‘z paradigmalarni, boshqalari bilan o‘xshash va noodatiy tomonlarini aqliy yo‘l bilan o‘rgandi.

Tilshunoslikdagi bu yutuqlar davr va bosqich jihatdan farqli bo‘lsada, biri boshqasining davomi sifatida kamchiliklarni to‘ldirdi. Tilning ahamiyati va ko‘lamini oshirdi.

Adabiyotlar

1. Qoshg‘ariy, M. *Devonu lug‘at-it turk.* – Toshkent: Fan, 1960.

2. Navoiy, A. *Nazm ul-javohir*. – Toshkent: G‘afur G‘ulom nomidagi Adabiyot va san‘at nashriyoti, 1983.

3. Fitrat, A. *O‘zbek tili grammatikasi*. – Toshkent: Fan, 1927.

4. Sayfullayeva, R., Mengliyev, B., Boqiyeva, G., Qurbonova, M., Yunusova, Z., Abuzalova, M. *Hozirgi o‘zbek adabiy tili*. – Toshkent: Fan, 2009.

MOTOR DISGRAFIYANING NEYROLINGVISTIK ASOSLARI

Abdullajonova Madina To‘lanboy qizi,

ToshDO‘TAU tayanch doktoranti

madinaabdullajonova0999@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada motor disgrafiyaning neyrolingvistik asoslari, namoyon bo‘lish shakllari hamda ta‘limiy oqibatlari tahlil qilingan. Yozuv faoliyatining lingvistik hamda motor komponentlari uyg‘un integratsiyasi nuqtayi nazaridan motor disgrafiya lingvistik kodni motor dasturlarga o‘tkazish mexanizmidagi buzilish sifatida izohlangan. Motor disgrafiyaning bartaraf etishda kompleks yondashuvning – neyrolingvistik, logopedik, pedagogik va psixologik metodlarning integratsiyasi zarurligi asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: yozma nutq buzilishlari, motor disgrafiya, frontal soha, parietal soha, grafomotor ko‘nikmalar, kompleks yondashuv.

Abstract: This article analyzes the neurolinguistic foundations, manifestations, and educational consequences of motor dysgraphia. From the perspective of the integrated functioning of the linguistic and motor components of writing activity, motor dysgraphia is interpreted as a disruption in the mechanism of transferring linguistic code into motor programs. The study substantiates the necessity of a comprehensive approach in overcoming motor dysgraphia, emphasizing the integration of neurolinguistic, speech therapy, pedagogical, and psychological methods.

Keywords: written speech disorders, motor dysgraphia, frontal lobe, parietal lobe, graphomotor skills, comprehensive approach

Nutq inson faoliyatining eng muhim psixolingvistik jarayonlaridan biri bo‘lib, u ijtimoiy muloqot, bilish va fikr ifodalashning asosiy vositasi, shuningdek, shaxs va jamiyat o‘rtasidagi asosiy kommunikativ mexanizm hisoblanadi. Nutqni muloqot vositasi deb belgilash uning faqat bir jihatini ko‘rsatadi. Bundan tashqari, nutq tafakkur shakli va insonning o‘z psixik jarayonlarini tartibga solish vositasidir. [Luriya A.R., 2002. 297]. Zamonaviy tilshunoslikda nutq va unga bog‘liq tushunchalar, xususan, nutqning ontogenez jarayonidagi rivojlanishi, uning neyropsixologik va psixolingvistik mexanizmlari hamda nutq buzilishlari asosiy tadqiqot obyektlari sifatida o‘rganiladi. Jumladan, nutq buzilishlari insonning kommunikativ faoliyatida sezilarli cheklovlarni yuzaga keltiradigan murakkab neyrolingvistik, neyropsixologik muammo sanaladi. U turli darajada fonetik-fonematik, leksik va grammatik tizimlarni qamrab olishi mumkin. Zamonaviy ilmiy adabiyotlarda nutq buzilishlari odatda ikki asosiy mezon asosida tasniflanadi:

1. **Og‘zaki nutq buzilishlari** – tovush talaffuzi, fonematik idrok va grammatik tuzilmalarning rivojlanishidagi nuqsonlar (masalan, dizartriya, alaliya, afaziya, rinolaliya).

2. **Yozma nutq buzilishlari** – yozish va o‘qish jarayonlaridagi buzilishlar, jumladan, disgrafiya, disleksiya va disorfografiya.

Nutq buzilishlarining etiologiyasi ko‘p qirrali bo‘lib, u markaziy asab tizimining organik shikastlanishlari, neyropsixologik yetishmovchiliklar, psixologik omillar va pedagogik sharoitlarning qoniqarli emasligi bilan izohlanadi [Jinkin N.I., 1998: 45–62]. Ushbu yondashuv nutq buzilishlarining ko‘p omilli tabiatini ochib beradi va ularni aniqlash hamda korreksiya qilish bo‘yicha ilmiy tadqiqotlar uchun asos yaratadi.

Ilmiy adabiyotlar tahlili shuni ko‘rsatadiki, og‘zaki nutq buzilishlari tarixan va metodologik jihatdan ko‘proq o‘rganilgan. Buning sabablari asosan uch omil bilan izohlanadi. Birinchidan, og‘zaki nutq inson ijtimoiy faoliyatida asosiy kommunikativ vosita bo‘lib, klinik va psixolingvistik tadqiqotlarning birlamchi obyekti bo‘lgan. Ikkinchidan, og‘zaki nutqni baholash va tekshirish yozma nutqqa nisbatan amaliy va tezkor bo‘lib, fonemik, grammatik va prosodik xatoliklarni akustik yo‘l bilan aniqlash mumkin. Uchinchidan, og‘zaki nutqning neyropsixologik asoslari (Broka, Vernike sohalari) uzoq yillar davomida tadqiq qilingan va turli metodlar yordamida (EEG, fMRI, DTI) o‘rganilgan.

Biroq so‘nggi yillarda yozma nutq buzilishlari ham faol tadqiq etilmoqda. Shu bilan birga, yozuv jarayonining mexanizmlari, motor koordinatsiya va grafik motor ko‘nikmalarining buzilishi tizimli tarzda o‘rganilmoqda. Ushbu maqolada yozma nutq buzilishlaridan biri – motor disgrafiyaning neyrolingvistik asoslari, xususiyatlari, namoyon bo‘lish shakllari va ta’limiy oqibatlarini tahlil qilingan.

Psixolingvistika nuqtayi nazaridan yozuv faoliyatiga lingvistik (**fonematik, grafematik**) va motor komponentlarning uyg‘unlashgan integratsiyasi sifatida qaraladi. Motor disgrafiya esa aynan lingvistik kodni motor harakatlarga o‘tkazish mexanizmidagi buzilish bilan tavsiflanadi, bu esa yozma nutqning samarali shakllanishiga to‘sqinlik qiladi [Berninger V.W., 2009. 92]. Motor disgrafiyada yozuv faoliyatining motor komponentlari – qo‘l mushaklari va barmoqlarining koordinatsiyasi, grafomotor jarayonlarning shakllanishi va barqarorligi buziladi. Tadqiqotlar natijasida maktab yoshidagi bolalarning 10-15 foizida yozuv buzilishlari kuzatilishi aniqlangan, shundan 30–40 foiz hollarda motor disgrafiya alohida yoki boshqa yozma nutq buzilishlari bilan birga namoyon bo‘ladi [Feder K., Majnemer A., 2007. 314]. Kanada va AQShda o‘tkazilgan tadqiqotlarda boshlang‘ich sinf o‘quvchilarining 12–15 foizida grafomotorik muammolar aniqlangan [Feder K., Majnemer A., 2007]. Bu ma’lumotlar motor disgrafiyaning ta’lim tizimlarida dolzarb muammo ekanligini ko‘rsatadi.

Bu esa mazkur muammoni neyrolingvistik, psixolingvistik va ta’limiy nuqtayi nazardan chuqur o‘rganishni talab qiladi.

Motor disgrafiyaning neyrolingvistik talqini, avvalo, A. R. Luriya tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan miya faoliyatining tizimli qurilish nazariyasiga asoslanadi. Unga ko‘ra, yozuv murakkab faoliyat bo‘lib, frontal, parietal va temporo-oksipital

zonalarning integratsiyalashgan faoliyatini talab qiladi. Bosh miya peshona qismi (frontal lob) faoliyati, ayniqsa, katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. Chunki u miyaning oldingi qismlarida joylashgan bo'lib, motor sohalarga yaqin turadi va vaqt davomida harakatlarni ketma-ketlikda tashkil qilish, ularni tartibga solish bilan bog'liq murakkab faoliyatni ta'minlaydi. Agar ushbu peshona qismlarining faoliyati buzilsa, odatda, murakkab motor harakatlarni bajarish imkoniyati keskin pasayadi [Luriya A.R., 2002. 60]. So'nggi neyrofiziologik tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, disgrafiyaga chalingan bolalarda chap yarimsharning inferior frontal va parietal korteksi bilan bog'liq oq modda yo'llari va funksional aloqalarda farqlar kuzatiladi. Funksional MRI (fMRI) tekshiruvlari yozuv jarayonida miya hududlari o'rtasidagi o'zaro faoliyatning sog'lom bolalarnikidan sezilarli darajada farq qilishini ko'rsatgan [Richards T.L. va b., 2015. 41]. Bunday bolalar fonematik jihatdan to'g'ri eshitib, so'zning fonologik tuzilishini idrok etsa ham, uni yozuv shaklida to'liq ifodalay olmaydi. Yozuvning semantik mazmuni saqlangan bo'lsa-da, grafomotorik ifoda qiyinlashadi. Umuman olganda, motor disgrafiyada fonematik kodni grafemaga bog'lash jarayonida ichki nutqning sekinligi, motor dasturlarni avtomatlashtirishdagi qiyinchiliklar va ishchi xotira cheklovlari hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi.

Disgrafiyaning bu turiga chalingan bolalarning qo'l yozuvini o'qish deyarli imkonsiz bo'ladi. Ko'pincha, bunday bolalar harflarni yozishda belgilangan shakliy me'yorlarga amal qilmaydilar. Motor disgrafiyaga chalingan bolalar yozish jarayonida quyidagi qiyinchiliklarga duch keladilar:

- qo'l harakatlarini bir harfdan ikkinchi harfga o'tkaza olmaslik;
- ma'lum bir harfni yozayotganda qaysi elementdan boshlashni aniq bilmaslik;
- harflarning notekis, o'lchami har xil, chiziqlari "titragan" yoki burchakli yozilishi;
- yozish jarayonida grafomotor harakatlarning keskin, cheklangan bo'lishi;
- qo'l mushaklarining tez toliqishi, mushaklardagi og'riq, yozish tezligining sekinligi, yozma topshiriqni bajarish uchun ko'p vaqt sarflash.

Motor disgrafiyada frontal sohalarning harakatni rejalashtirish va nazorat qilishdagi sustligi, parietal sohalarning vizuomotor koordinatsiyani ta'minlashdagi qiyinchiliklari, kinestetik sezgilar va motor dasturlarning yetarlicha shakllanmaganligi kuzatiladi. Mazkur muammo o'quv jarayonida umumiy o'quv motivatsiyasining pasayishiga, shuningdek, ikkilamchi psixologik muammolar – o'ziga ishonchsizlik, ijtimoiy yakkalanish, o'z-o'zini past baholashga olib kelishi mumkin.

Motor disgrafiyaning bartaraf etishda samarali natijalarga erishish uchun muammoga kompleks yondashish zarur, chunki ushbu buzilishning etiologiyasi ko'p omilli bo'lib, neyropsixologik, lingvistik va pedagogik omillarning o'zaro ta'sirini qamrab oladi. Kompleks yondashuvda neyropsixologik metodlar vizuomotor koordinatsiya, fazoviy analiz va motor rejalashtirish jarayonlarini rivojlantirishga qaratilib, markaziy asab tizimining ijro funksiyalarini optimallashtiradi. Logopedik mashg'ulotlar fonematik idrok, grafematik kodlash va fonema–grafema konversiya jarayonlarini mustahkamlash orqali yozuv faoliyatining lingvistik bazasini shakllantiradi. Psixologik yondashuv bolada o'ziga ishonch, ijobiy motivatsiya va

emotsional barqarorlikni ta'minlab, kognitiv jarayonlarning uyg'unlashuvini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. Pedagogik metodlar esa bosqichma-bosqich o'qitish asosida yozuv ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish, qo'l motorikasini kuchaytirish hamda yozuv jarayonining avtomatlashtirilishini ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi. Shu tariqa, motor disgrafiyani bartaraf etish jarayoni faqat yozuv ko'nikmalarini tiklash bilan cheklanmay, balki bolaning umumiy kognitiv rivojlanishini qo'llab-quvvatlashni ham nazarda tutadi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, motor disgrafiya neyrolingvistik, psixolingvistik va pedagogik omillar bilan bog'liq ko'p omilli buzilish bo'lib, uni samarali bartaraf etish integrativ yondashuvni talab qiladi. Neyrolingvistik, logopedik, pedagogik va psixologik metodlarning uyg'un qo'llanilishi yozuv faoliyatining tiklanishiga, bolaning kognitiv salohiyati va shaxsiy rivojlanishiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Shu sababli motor disgrafiyani chuqur o'rganish, diagnostika va korreksiya dasturlarini takomillashtirish neyrolingvistika va ta'lim amaliyoti oldida turgan dolzarb ilmiy-amaliy vazifa hisoblanadi.

Adabiyotlar

1. Berninger V. W., Wolf B. Dyslexia, dysgraphia, OWL LD, and dyscalculia: Lessons from science and teaching. – Baltimore: Paul H. Brookes, 2009. – 400 p.
2. Dohla D., Heim S. Developmental Dyslexia and Dysgraphia: What can We Learn from the One about the Other? // *Frontiers in Psychology*. – 2016. – Vol. 6. – P. 197–205.
3. Feder K.P., Majnemer A. Handwriting, development, competency and intervention // *Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology*. – 2007. – Vol. 49. – P. 312–317.
4. Jongmans M. J., et al. Effectiveness of a multimodal handwriting intervention program // *Human Movement Science*. – 2017. – Vol. 55. – P. 12–25.
5. McBride C. Children's Literacy Development: A Cross-Cultural Perspective. – Springer, 2019. – 245 p.
6. Richards T. L., Grabowski T. J., Boord P., Yagle K., Askren M., Mestre Z., Robinson P., Welker O., Gulliford D., Nagy W., Berninger V. Contrasting brain patterns of writing-related DTI parameters, fMRI connectivity, and DTI–fMRI connectivity correlations in children with and without dysgraphia or dyslexia // *Neuropsychology*. – 2015. – T. 29, № 3. – P. 411–431.
7. Жинкин Н. И. Речь как проводник информации. – М.: ЛКИ, 1998. – С. 45–62.
8. Корнев А. Н. Нарушения чтения и письма у детей. – СПб.: Речь, 2006. – 448 с.
9. Лурия А. Р. Письмо и речь: Нейролингвистические исследования : учеб. пособие для студ. психол. фак. высш. учеб. заведений. – М.: Издательский центр «Академия», 2002. – 352 с.
10. Лурия А. Р. *Основы нейропсихологии*. – М.: Академия, 2002. – 384 с.

“ANAMIN YURDU” VE “İLKİ” HİKÂYELERİNDE ALIŞILMAMIŞ BAĞDAŞTIRMALAR VE EKSİLTİLİ YAPILAR

Ertan Örgen,
(Prof. Dr. Balıkesir Üniversitesi, eorgen@balikesir.edu.tr)

Bu çalışmada Özbek edebiyatının önemli yazarlarından Hayriddin Sultanov’un “Anamın Yurdu” hikâyesi ile Türk edebiyatından Vüs’at O. Bener’in “İlki” adlı hikâyesi kurdukları dil yapılarındaki alışılmamış bağdaştırma ve eksiltili ifadeler açısından incelenecektir. Dilin sanatlı kullanımıyla kurulan bu iki öykü “anne ve yurt” temasını işledikleri için seçilmiştir. Alışılmamış bağdaştırma, yadırgatıcı bir kullanımdır ve anlamada birdenbire çözülmeyen yapıyı tanımlar. Sultanov’un hikâyesinde “meyus bir ninni”, “yeşillerle bezeli ukde”, “bahtiyar renkle gülen gözler”; Bener’in hikâyesinde “tortop şehir”, göçük sesler”, “cam cam parlayan gözbebekleri”, “paslı soluk kokusu”, “bulaşık bir hayranlık” gibi bağdaştırmalar bulunmaktadır. Yazıda, verili dilin ötesine geçmeye çalışan bu bağdaştırmaların sözlük ve dil değerleri üzerinde durulacaktır. Bir diğer unsur olan eksiltili ifadeler, cümleyi tamamlamayı metnin akışıyla sağlayan dil tercihidir. Sultanov’da “gönlü yarımdu”, “evvelinde gençtim” şeklinde az karşılaşılan ancak Bener’de “saptı araba”, tunçtu el”, “sessizlik çatlamiyordu”, “eğri gülüyordu” örneklerinde görüleceği üzere daha çok metne hâkim bir kullanım sıklığına sahiptir.

İki hikâyedeki bu metin dilbilim özellikleri ilgili unsurlar üzerinden tespit edilecek ve yazarların dille kurmak istedikleri ilişki ortaya konulacaktır.

Anahtar kelimeler: Hayriddin Sultanov, Vüs’at O. Bener, Alışılmamış Bağdaştırma, Eksiltili İfadeler

In this study, the story "My Mother's Homeland" by Hayriddin Sultanov, one of the important writers of Uzbek literature, and the story "The First" by Vüs’at O. Bener from Turkish literature will be examined in terms of unusual harmonization and elliptical expressions in the language structures they create. These two stories, constructed through the artful use of language, were chosen because they explore the theme of "mother and homeland." The unusual association is a strange one, defining a structure that cannot be readily resolved in understanding. In Sultanov’s story, there are associations such as “a melancholic lullaby”, “a regret adorned with green”, “eyes smiling with a happy color”; in Bener’s story, there are associations such as “a topsyturvy city”, “cold voices”, “pupils shining like glass”, “a feeling of warmth inside”, “the smell of rusty breath”, “a contaminated admiration”. The lexical and linguistic values of these associations that try to go beyond the given language will be emphasized.

While it is rarely encountered in Sultanov, such as “her heart was half-hearted”, “I was young before”, it has a more dominant usage frequency in the text, as can be seen in Bener’s examples such as “the car went astray”, “the hand was bronze”, “silence was not cracking”, “she was laughing crookedly”. The linguistic features of these texts in the two stories will be determined through relevant elements and the relationship that the authors want to establish with the language will be revealed.

Key words: Hayriddin Sultanov, Vüs'at O. Bener, Unusual Reconciliation, Elliptical Expressions

Giriş

Metin dilbilim kapsamında edebî eserin yapısını ve yazarın kurgudaki tasarrufunu anlamaya yardımcı olacak ölçütler, kullanılan dil özellikleriyle tespit edilirler. Beaugrande ve Dressler tarafından metin oluşturma kapsamında yedi ölçüt belirlenmiştir: bağdaşıklık, tutarlılık, kabul edilebilirlik, amaçlılık, bilgilendiricilik, duruma uygunluk ve metinlerarasılık (akt. Yılmaz, 2018: 157). Dolayısıyla metinler incelenirken bu unsurlardan biri veya birkaç tanesi ile yazarın kurmak istediği yapıyı, içeriği çözümlenmek mümkündür. Bu yazı kapsamında bağdaşıklık kavramı üzerinden yazarın orijinal tarafını belirleme maksadıyla alışılmamış bağdaştırmalar ve yine buna yakın olan eksilteli ifadelerin kullanımıyla ilgili bir çözümlenme gerçekleştirilecektir. Dilbilimin metni bir bütünlük noktasında değerlendirdiği ölçütlerden ikisiyle hikâyelerin dil özelliği ortaya konulacaktır.

Doğan Aksan, alışılmamış bağdaştırma kavramını tanımlarken anlambilimi açısından birbiriyle uyumlu olmayan biri soyut ve biri somut olan kavramların bir araya gelmesini temel alır ve bu birleşimin “dil sınırlarını zorlayan ve onun anlatım gücünü gösteren” (Aksan, 2004: 38) birim olduğunu ifade eder. Şiirde sıklıkla karşılaşılan alışılmamış bağdaştırma düzyazıda aynı yoğunlukta bulunmaz, ancak yazarın imajinatif olmak duyarlılığıyla dile yüklenmesi sonucu belli bir oranda ortaya çıkar. Örneğin Sait Faik Abasıyanık'ın hikâyelerinde “*Deniz gibi nefes almak*”, “*mavi mavi tütmek*” şeklindeki bağdaştırmalar üslubun ve kahramanın derinleşmesini sağlarlar. Bu dil kullanımı, hikâyeyi yazarın yeni bir kurguya çevirdiğini de gösterir.

Eksilti ise metinde bağdaşıklığı sağlayan söz dizimsel boşluklar diye tanımlanır. Zeynep Korkmaz, bazı ses veya kelimeler atılmış olduğu hâlde, anlamı aksatmayan kendine özgü bir dil biçimlenmesi, bir biçim bütünlüğü vardır (2003: 81) şeklinde eksiltiye net bir açıklama getirir. Eksilti, eski zamanlardan beri cümlede söz ekonomisi kurmak, ifadede sözü daha etkili kılmak, okuru, dinleyiciyi dikkatli tutmak amaçlarıyla kullanılan bir tercihtir. Klasik şiirde “îcâz” terimiyle bilinen kullanım modern edebiyatta da yerini bulmuştur. Bir üslup özelliği olarak metnin bütünlüğünde bir etki sağlar, sıklıkla kullanımı yapıda bütünleyici bir özellik taşır. Eksilti çeşitleri; kelime, kelime grubu ya da yüklem eksiltisi olarak görülebileceği gibi nesne, ek, tamlayan, tamlanan eksiltisi biçiminde de görülebilir.

Bu yazıda, Özbek edebiyatından Hayriddin Sultanov'un “Anamın Yurdu” hikâyesi ile Türk edebiyatından Vüs'at O. Bener'in “İlki” adlı hikâyesindeki alışılmamış bağdaştırma ve eksilteli ifadeler tespit edilecektir. Bu iki hikâyenin seçilme sebebi, Türkçenin farklı sahalarda benzeşen ya da farklı olan örneklerini göstermektir. Ayrıca iki metin de “anne ve yurt” temasına sahiptir. “Anamın Yurdu” hikâyesinde yedi yaşındayken doğduğu köyden kaybolan ve başka bir yerde büyüüp yaşlanan kadının yıllar sonra oraya kavuşması ve yaşadıkları anlatılır. “İlki” ise yatılı okula gönderilen büyük oğulun bir yıl sonra eve dönüşüyle yaşadığı duyguları, annedeki sevinci, ailedeki iletişimi konu edinir. İki hikâye de oğulların gözünden aktarılır.

Alışılmamış Bağdaştırmalar

“*Anamın Yurdu*” hikâyesinde alışılmamış bağdaştırmalar, yoğun bir kullanım içermez. Ancak üslubu zenginleştiren ve etkili kılan bir anlatım olarak belli oranda bulunur. Hikâyeyi başlatan “Hafızamı tanıyorum” (165) cümlesi anlatıcının kendini takdimi kadar anlatılacak olayı da haber verir. Bu ifadede dikkati çeken kişinin kendisini, etrafını, nesnelere tanımasında kullanılacak bir nesne fiil birleşimini, Türkiye Türkçesinde alışık olmadığımız bir kelime grubuyla iletmesidir.

Hikâyenin merak unsuru, çocukken kaybolup hep hatırlamaya çalıştığı yerleri anlatan annenin sözleridir. Onun anlatımıyla oğlunun zihninde canlanan yurt “Anamın yeşillerle bezeli ukdesi” (165) şeklinde aktarılır. Burada içinde kalan özlem, istek anlamında ukde kelimesinin bir renkle yan yana getirilmesi alışılmamış bağdaştırmadır. Çünkü bitmeyen ukde gibi bir kullanım değil annenin yurdunun doğal güzelliği çağrışımı için yeşil ukde bağdaştırması yapılmıştır.

“Yarım gönül” (167) kelime grubu, Türkiye Türkçesinde yarım gönüllü şeklinde az bir kullanıma sahiptir. Bu nedenle ona da alışılmamış bağdaştırma denilebilir.

“Bahtiyar bir renkle gülen gözler” (173) bağdaştırmasında, gözlerdeki ışık, ışıltı gibi alışılmış benzetmeler varken renk ve mutluluk birleşimine gönderme yapılarak orijinal bir tamlamaya baş vurulmuştur.

“*İlki*” hikâyesinde dikkati çeken üslup özelliği yazarın diğer metinlerinde de görülen alışılmamış bağdaştırmalarla dolu olmasıdır. Dile farklı biçimde yüklenen, anlamı bir çırpıda vermeyen bu birimler, akışı keser ve düşündürür. Ayrıca bu bağdaştırmalar fiilsiz cümle, öznesiz fiil, kısa ve kesik cümleler biçiminde birbirini destekler. Bunların bir araya gelmesi monoton bir yapıyı işaret eder ancak yanı başında kendi içinde bağdaşıklık bulunan bir ölçüt de taşır.

Hikâyede çok sayıda bulunan kullanımlar içerisinde dikkati ilk çeken “Şehir tortoptu” (126) cümlesindeki alışılmamış bağdaştırmadır. Şehrin tasvirine dair bir iz olarak verilen bağdaştırma, kâğıt parçası gibi sıkıştırılmış, kendi içine kapalı bir çağrışımı işaret eder ve doğrudan benzetmeye gitmeyip aktarışıyla şaşırtıcıdır. Yine mekâna ilişkin “Çarşı Camii’nin minaresi delip geçmişti mor soğukluğu” (127) cümlesinde soğukun renkle verilmesi ve minarenin bu soğukun dışında kalışı ilgi çekici bir bağdaştırmadır. Çocuğun bir yıl sonra tekrar geldiği evi anlatırken söylediği “Sessizlik çatlamiyordu.” (128) sözü, sürüp giden sükutu ifade için orijinal bir bağdaştırmadır. “Odaya sinmiş paslı soluk kokusu” (129) ifadesi, değişen hiçbir şeyin olmadığına göndermedir. Paslı soluk kötümser anlamı yanında soluğa farklı bir sıfat yakıştırmasıyla dili zorlayan bir kullanımdır. “Tekerlekler, atlar göçük sesler çıkararak uzaklaştılar hızla.” (127) cümlesindeki göçük sesler yine alışılmamış bir tercihtir.

Kişi anlatımında ise “cam cam parlayan gözbebekleri” (127) ilgi çekici bir bağdaştırmadır. Yine kişiye ait “Arabacının surati kabuk bağlamış” (127), tasvirinde, yaranın iyileşmesini imleyen kabuk bağlama, burada çok alışılmış bir konuşma ve alışkanlık içerisindeki insanı anlatmaya yöneliktir. “Bulaşık bir hayranlıkla iki elimi birden kavrayıp alınaya götürmüştü.” (130) bağdaştırması, tanımlamakta güçlük çekilen bir yüz ifadesini anlatır. “Eğri gülüyordu.” (133) yine farklı bir bağdaştırma olarak sevgisizlikle merhamet arasında sıkışmış insanı ifadeye dökmek içindir.

Eksiltili ifadeler

“*Anamın Yurdu*” hikâyesinde dilin alışılmış eksiltileri çoğunluktadır. Örneğin nesne eksikliği taşıyan cümleler şunlardır: “Hayır, farz edin ki, gördüm (onu).” (166), “Bilirdim (onu),” (167).

Daha çok kişi zamiri eksiltileriyle kurulan cümleler vardır: “(Ben) evvelinde gençtim. Anamın dil yarasını anlamıyorum.” (167), “gölgemi gördüğü gibi zılgıtı basardı.” (167).

Tamlayan eksiltisi: “onun derdi içindeydi, (onun) gönlü yarımdaydı. (167), “(onun) aklında kalan ise sadece yerden biraz yüksek toprak yoldu.” (167), “(senin) Memleketin güzel anacığım lakin bizimkine (doğru) gelmiyor gibi.” (173). Ayrıca bu cümlede Türkiye Türkçesinde alışık olunmayan “bizimkine gelmiyor gibi” şeklinde bir kelime grubu mevcuttur.

Üç noktalı cümleler: “Yurdumun derya derya akan şırıldayan suları... (vardı)” (168), “Bilsem anamın memleketinin gerçekten de büyük denizlere kıyısı olduğunu... (anlardım veya inanırdım)” (168), “Bilsem anamın memleketinin rüzgarların buluşma noktası olduğunu...” (tekrar ve etkileyicilik),” (168), “Koyunlar kesildi, kazanlar kaynadı...” (170), “Dedemin mezarını ziyaret ettim, anamın da...” (172), “İnsanın bu büyüğü resitalde başı dönerdi...” (172).

Hem tamlayan hem eksiltili cümle: “(Onun) bir işde bağı dediği...” (173).

Tümleç eksikliği: “Ulbosin ise (buraya) gelin, görüşelim, biz de (oraya) gelelim.” 169, “(burası) Buram buram kokardı.” 172

Ünlemlili eksiltili cümle: “Ah memleketimin serin rüzgarları ah!” (168).

Konuşma dilinde eksiltili ifade: “Ulbosin” (168). Özbekçede oğul bolsın (oğul olsun) kız çocuklarına bir sonraki çocuk erkek olsun diye konulan isim.

“*İlki*” hikâyesinde yazarın üslubunun da temel belirleyicisi konumunda olan eksiltili ifadeler yoğunluktadır. Özellikle yüklem söylememesi Bener’in kısa cümle yapısını sağladığı gibi bir çeşit imzası gibidir.

“İstasyon gerilerde kaldı. Büyük, yoğun, taş (bir binaydı).” (126), “Acı soğuk. (vardı, var)” (126), “Önceleri bitmek bilmeyen aylardan sonra. (dönüyordum)” (127), “Karınlarına kurşun dökülü, kınalı, mavili, yeşilli, benek benek, şarap rengi aşıklar. (vardı)” 128, “Korkulu. (ydu)” (128), “Kapının önünde çocuğunun ölüsü. (vardı)” (128), “Geri gelen çocuğu. (vardı, duruyordu)” (128), “Kemiğin çıkardığı tok ses. (duyuldu)” (128), “Sarkan, lacivert elbiselerimle dimdik. (duruyordum)” (129), “Kapıdaki. (oydu)” (129), “Kalın, çulaki, kapalı elbiselerin içinde.(ydi o)” (132), “Sonra kavgalarını. (anımsamıştım)” (132), “Sinsice neşeli gibi. (ydi)” (133).

Nesne eksiltisi: “İndirdim. (onu)” (128).

Tümleç eksiltisi: “Hep ağladığı sanılabilirdi (onun)” (126), “Kinlenirdim (ona).” (127), “İlınıyordu içi. (onun)” (128), “Kocamandı başı. (onun)” (129), “Kocaman eli boşlukta. (ydi onun)” (130),

Özne eksiltisi: zaten dilde kalıplaşmış bir anlaşma olarak ekler vasıtasıyla bu eksilti çok alışılmış bir yapıdır.” Eziliyordu. (o)” (128), “Ağlamıyordu. Tıkanıyordu. (o)” (129), “Boyanmış. (o)” (127), “Sıcaktı. Ellerimi yakıyordu. (o)” 133

Sonuç olarak Hayriddin Sultanov’un hikâyesinde doğal ve insana mahsus bir dünya anlatımı öne çıktığı için dilin anlatılan olay ve kişiler sebebiyle

yazarın tasarrufu neticesinde edebi eseri etkili kılacak ölçüde alışılmamış bağdaştırma ve çok az sayıda eksilteli ifade kullanımı söz konusudur. Vüs'at O. Bener'in "İlki" hikâyesinde ise bir yıl sonra evine dönen yatılı okuldaki çocuğun gözünden şehre ve aileye ilişkin özlem ve hatırlamalar eşliğinde kesik ifadelere ve alışılmamış bağdaştırmalara başvurduğu görülmektedir. Bu elbette yazarların dünyaya bakışlarıyla ilişkilidir ve metnin bütününe yansıyan dil tercihleri de bu yönde kurulmuştur.

Kaynaklar

Aksan, Doğan (2004), *Cumhuriyet Döneminden Bugüne Örneklere Şiir Çözümlemeleri*, Bilgi Yayınevi, Ankara.

Bener, Vüs'at O. (1986), *Dost*, Can Yayınları, İstanbul.

Korkmaz, Zeynep (2003), *Grammer Terimleri Sözlüğü*, Ankara, Türk Dil Kurumu Yayınları, Ankara.

Özlem YILMAZ, (2018). *Yabancı Dil Olarak Türkçe Öğretiminde Metin Odaklı Dilbilgisi Öğretimi*, Yüksek Lisans Tezi.

Sultanov, Hayriddin (2021), "Anamın Yurdu", *Günümüz Özbek Öyküsü*, Türkçesi: Hamza Öztürkmen, Hece Yayınları, Ankara.

HUMAN NATURE AND SOCIAL RELATIONS IN D.H. LAWRENCE'S "ESSAYS ON LOVE"

**Mammadova Sevil Alasgar,
Ph.D., Assistant Professor: AzTU,
Department of Foreign Languages
Email: sevil.mammadova@aztu.edu.az
Orcid code: 0009-0004-0730-7256**

Abstract: D.H. Lawrence's "Essays on Love" (1930) can be seen as a philosophical and cultural defense of his novel *Lady Chatterley's Lover*. In this work, Lawrence critiques society's conventional view of the relationship between body and soul, while also seeking to redefine the role of love and sexuality in human existence. He upholds natural human instincts as a counterpoint to the emotional detachment of modern technological civilization, and he challenges artificial moral codes that, in his view, contribute to the decline of human nature.

Introduction. D.H. Lawrence stands out as one of the most debated yet insightful voices in twentieth-century English literature. His 1928 novel *Lady Chatterley's Lover* and the companion essay *A Propos of Lady Chatterley's Lover* (1930) are not only significant literary works but also reflections of a deeper philosophical and ethical conflict. In these texts, Lawrence reveals how human instincts and emotional needs are suppressed in an age dominated by technocratic values. The purpose of the essay is to deliver a sharp critique of society's hypocrisy and its distorted notions of love. Lawrence argues for a vision of life rooted in the

balance between body and spirit. Through this work, he takes a stand against censorship and the weight of social conventions.

In the essay *Love*, Lawrence portrays the relationship between a man and a woman as a reciprocal “desire”. For him, love unites two opposites in a transformative experience a burning together, a dissolution of individual feelings, yet also an inevitable sense of separation. He attributes the failure of genuine union between the sexes to the incompleteness at the core of such relationships. Lawrence further insists that there exists a fundamental metaphysical difference between man and woman: their roles in life, their thoughts and emotions, their sources of pleasure, and their desires all diverge, just as their anatomy does.

Method. This article employs a qualitative, literary-analytical approach. Its aim is to examine Lawrence’s treatment of society, human nature, morality, and the concept of love in *A Propos of Lady Chatterley’s Lover* with attention to both content and ideas. Several methods were applied:

1. Thematic and ideological analysis – Core themes such as love, body-soul harmony, sexuality, and the dual morality of society were identified and explored in depth.

2. Comparative method – Lawrence’s views were set against those of contemporary thinkers and writers, particularly Freud and Nietzsche, to highlight his distinctive position.

3. Contextual approach – The essay was situated within its historical and cultural background, reflecting the social and moral climate of early twentieth-century England.

4. Discourse analysis – The author’s aims and philosophical ideas were traced through his choice of language, lexical patterns, and artistic-philosophical expression.

Building on these methods, Lawrence’s literary-philosophical stance can be substantiated and his influence on modern ethical and social thought assessed. For Lawrence, sexual intimacy represents not only a bodily instinct but also a profound expression of spiritual and moral unity. As he emphasizes: “*We have learned to hate our bodies. We have only forgotten to think and feel*” (Lawrence, 1930, p. 45). In addressing the effects of society and technology on the individual, Lawrence argues that industrial civilization mechanizes human life and, in doing so, distorts human nature. For this reason, he condemns the repression of emotional and sexual experience, declaring: “*When society begins to see sexuality as a disease, man becomes alienated from himself*” (Lawrence, 1930, p. 52).

Although these reflections echo Freud’s theory of libido, Lawrence’s emphasis lies elsewhere: for him, the essential task is to purify and sanctify sexuality, recognizing it not as a mere instinct but as an inseparable dimension of love and human wholeness. When considered at the crossroads of literature and morality, the enduring resonance of the essay arises from Lawrence’s challenge to the moral boundaries imposed on artistic creation. He rejects the subordination of literature to didactic purposes, asserting: “*Literature is not to teach moral lessons, but to show life itself*” (Lawrence, 1930, p. 60). This statement encapsulates one of the work’s

central ideological commitments: the defense of artistic freedom and the autonomy of literature.

From a philosophical standpoint, the essay revolves around the triad of body, soul, and harmony. At its core lies the conviction that true human fulfillment depends on the unity of body and spirit. Lawrence resists Puritan traditions that demonize physical desire and instead insists that harmony between body and soul constitutes the foundation of human perfection. As he writes: “*True love is the vibration of the soul and the body together*” (Lawrence, 1930, p. 71). His approach moves beyond romanticism, which tends to elevate either sexuality or spiritual intimacy, by emphasizing their indivisible unity.

Lawrence’s reflections on the relationship between man and woman parallel the ancient Chinese concept of yin and yang. Rooted in Taoist philosophy, this duality envisions the universe as guided by the force of Tao, which divides into two opposing yet complementary principles. Yang symbolizes the masculine strength, heat, dominance, light, the sun while yin embodies the feminine softness, tenderness, receptivity, darkness, the moon. In this view, neither pole is superior; each depends upon the other for balance and survival. As Lao Tzu famously remarked, the ideal is to “be like water” to yield rather than dominate, for dominance alone leads to downfall.

In a similar spirit Lawrence maintains that while men and women are polar opposites, they are also interdependent. Masculinity does not imply superiority over femininity; the differences between the sexes express complementarity, not hierarchy. In his eyes, true equality does not mean sameness (Adelman, 1991, p. 92). Yet, modern interpretations of gender equality often reduce distinctions to mere anatomical differences, attributing all intellectual, emotional, and behavioral traits to cultural and historical conditioning. Such views, which reflect both feminist critiques of male dominance and social constructs of equality, would not have satisfied Lawrence. For him, the essence of male and female lies in their metaphysical differences, which cannot be erased without undermining the integrity of human love and life itself.

It is misleading to argue that male and female traits are entirely conditional. Within dominant American cultural thought, it is often assumed that a man cannot reach full success without the support of a woman. If male and female qualities were entirely interchangeable across all cultural settings, it would be possible to deny the existence of inherent distinctions between the sexes. In practice, however, the evidence for conditional traits is tied to cultural patterns that vary by society. In this regard, the concept of “gender equality” has been treated as dogma in some academic circles, although it has become one of the most discussed issues of the last century.

As already noted, Lawrence consistently stresses that men and women differ at a metaphysical level. In his essay *Thomas Hardy Research*, he illustrates this contrast, suggesting that men and women perceive reality in fundamentally different ways: “*Men accept that God is one and say that he belongs to the male sex. Men perceive that there is a variety of varieties in every concept. But women, perceiving things and concepts, vaguely declare that each concept is unique, the concept of uniqueness*”

constitutes reality for them” (Holdernes, 1982, p. 31). For Lawrence, men are drawn toward multiplicity, while women gravitate toward unity.

Philosophical traditions that shaped Lawrence’s thought often trace back to ancient Greece, especially to Pythagoras and his followers. Early theories associated singularity with masculinity and plurality with femininity. The pre-Socratic philosopher Empedocles offered a framework especially relevant to Lawrence: he proposed that two forces Love and Strife govern change in the universe. Love is the principle of attraction and unity, while Strife divides and separates. Empedocles personified Love as Aphrodite and associated Strife with its opposites, often linking it to masculine identity. In this sense, his cosmology parallels Lawrence’s understanding of sexual duality.

According to Lawrence, women strive to unify and reconcile. Their role is expressed in an emotional drive to heal divisions and remove barriers, a tendency that manifests most strongly within the family, where women attempt to preserve wholeness. Men, by contrast, impose rules and structures that often obstruct this unity. Lawrence interprets war as a particularly male phenomenon, while women, throughout history, have opposed violence and chaos, advocating instead for peace and reconciliation (Patmore, 1970, p. 41).

Lawrence further observes that men of his time were haunted by feelings of isolation, yearning to be “alone,” though, paradoxically, their deeper longing was still directed toward women. He connects this psychological difference to religion: polytheism, with its acknowledgment of diversity and plurality, he links to masculine vision, whereas monotheism, with its emphasis on unity and equality before God, he identifies as feminine. Christianity in particular, while calling for peace and unity, is not accepted by Lawrence as aligned with women in essence.

Ultimately, Lawrence’s reflections point to a profound metaphysical divide: men and women inhabit different spiritual worlds and interpret the same reality through contrasting lenses. These divergent perspectives, however, are not destructive but complementary, forming the basis for balance in human existence. Lawrence’s vision resonates with the philosophy of Heraclitus, who argued that opposites necessarily converge and that harmony emerges from diversity and conflict. As Heraclitus illustrates, the strings of a lyre pull in opposite directions, yet it is precisely this tension that produces beautiful music (Nixon, 1986, p. 76).

As is evident, D.H. Lawrence considers woman to be the vital, life-sustaining force in a man’s existence. She represents the source of his energy and spirit. At times, Lawrence even portrays the relationship between man and woman as a potential cause of despair. In his view, when a man pursues creative work beyond the boundaries of family life, this endeavor deepens his attachment to life. While the bond with a woman is significant, it cannot by itself guarantee a man’s complete happiness. For Lawrence, men must also possess greater ambitions goals that inspire enthusiasm and a readiness for struggle.

For women, however, the sphere of home and family provides the highest fulfillment. Although a woman may be interested in a career, Lawrence believes her natural role lies in nurturing children and maintaining the household. This traditional

image of womanhood is central to his thought. By contrast, modern feminist voices have argued that women are capable of pursuing professions historically dominated by men, thereby expanding female influence in society (Potter, 1999, p. 23).

Lawrence depicts man as the primary discoverer and inventor of life. Men, in his eyes, stand apart solitary figures who advance by trusting in their inner world and spirit. Woman, conversely, belongs to the realm of twilight and night; evening and darkness are her domains. Yet despite these contrasts, the two sexes share a unifying core in the deepest regions of the heart. In Lawrence's symbolic imagination, day belongs to man and night belongs to woman. This division resembles an elemental distribution of labor and is framed in mythological imagery, where the sun embodies the masculine and the moon the feminine.

Conclusion. *Essay on Love* is not simply a defense of a controversial novel but also a summons for humanity to return to its authentic self and to nature. In this work, Lawrence displays literary bravery, philosophical insight, and a firm ethical stance. He underscores the significance of the writer's struggle to preserve genuine love and honesty against the prohibitions and stereotypes imposed by society. As such, the essay continues to serve as a lasting response to enduring questions of human identity, love, and freedom in the history of literature.

References

1. Lawrence D. H. *A Propos of Lady Chatterley's Lover*. London: Mandrake Press. 1930
2. Meyers J. D.H. *Lawrence: A Biography*. New York: Cooper Square Press. 1990
3. Squires M. D.H. *Lawrence and the Body*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. 2002
4. Worthen J. *The Life of D.H. Lawrence: A Critical Biography*. Oxford University Press. 2005
5. Potter Stephen. *D.H.Lawrence: The Centre and the Circles* / ed.: Stephen Potter. – Nottingham: University of Nottingham D.H.Lawrence Centre, – 1992. –84 p.
6. Nixon Cornelia. *Lawrence's Leadership Politics and the Turn against Women* / Cornelia Nixon. - Berkeley, Los Angeles, and London: University of California Press, - 1986. - 127 p.
7. Patmore Derek. *D.H. Lawrence and the Dominant Male* / Derek Patmore. - London: Covent Garden Press, - 1970. - 216 p.
8. Holderness Graham. *D.H. Lawrence: History, Ideology and Fiction* / Graham Holderness. - Dublin: Gill and Macmillan, - 1982. - 136 p.
9. Adelman Gary. *Snow of Fire: Symbolic Meaning in "The Rainbow" and "Women in Love"* / Gary Adelman. - New York and London: Garland, - 1991. - 160 p.

A BRIEF EXCURSION INTO THE HISTORY OF TRADITIONAL SEMANTICS

Nigar Seyidova,
Baku State University
Head Teacher, Department of English Language
(for Natural Science Faculties)
nigar-seidova@mail.ru

Summary. Semantics, a pivotal branch of linguistics that focuses on the study of meaning in language, has been extensively discussed and debated. Whilst the majority of linguists concur that semantics is the study of the meaning of linguistic expressions, the precise definition of “meaning” remains the subject of considerable controversy. The boundaries between semantics and other linguistic subfields, particularly pragmatics, are also defined differently by various scholars. The term “semantics” was introduced by the French linguist M. Breal in the late XIX century and was initially understood to encompass the totality of what was expressed by language. In recent times, the focus of modern researchers has been narrowed, with an emphasis placed primarily on the logical or conceptual aspects of meaning. For instance, Leonard Bloomfield regarded semantics as being associated with human knowledge and belief. In the early 20th century, semioticians such as Charles Peirce and Charles Morris refined the role of semantics in semiotics, explaining its relationship with syntax and pragmatics. It was emphasised that syntax involves formal relationships between signs, while semantics is concerned with how signs relate to their objects and pragmatics examines how signs are interpreted by their users. The decline of structuralism and the concomitant rise of transformational grammar in the mid-20th century resulted in a shift of focus towards semantics in linguistic analysis. Scholars such as Charles Morris and S. Ullman recognised the central role of semantics, with Ullman's works being significant contributions in this regard. The advent of Transformational Semantics, which established a correlation between syntactic structures and meaning, precipitated the emergence of new domains such as Cognitive Linguistics and Cognitive Grammar, which investigate the interplay between language and cognition. Contemporary research in semantics is increasingly interdisciplinary in nature, with a focus on the fields of linguistic pragmatics and cognitive linguistics. These disciplines are employed to study how meaning is shaped by the behaviour and cognition of language users. To summarise, the study demonstrates that semantics is an evolving concept, integrating structural, pragmatic and cognitive elements.

Keywords: language, meaning, linguistic, interpretation, syntax, pragmatics, cognition

Introduction. As with any scientific discipline, the field of semantics has its own particular subject matter. However, the definition of this subject matter is not as straightforward as it may appear. Whilst the majority of linguists concur that semantics is the study of the meaning of linguistic expressions, there is no universally

accepted definition of the term “meaning”. Due to the existence of divergent interpretations of the subject, the boundaries between semantics and other linguistic sciences, especially between semantics and pragmatics, are delineated in a variety of ways. Consequently, the issue of semantics merits meticulous examination.

The term “semantics” (from French “*sémantique*”) was introduced into linguistics in the 19th century by M. Breal. In this field, researchers have expanded the study of semantics to encompass “everything expressed by language” in a broader sense. However, other researchers (including those working within general linguistics) have limited it to the logical or conceptual aspects. Semantics can be defined as the study of the conceptual content of language (1). Conversely, it is possible to distinguish between different types of meaning and demonstrate how each fits into the overall complex effect of communication through language. Furthermore, it can be demonstrated how the methods of investigation suited to one type might be incompatible with another.

At the beginning of the 20th century, based on C. Peirce's (9) research in the field of semiotics, C. Morris (8) proposed a more precise approach regarding the status of semantics.

The “triadic relationship of semiosis” was discussed, with syntax defined as “the formal relationships between signs”, semantics defined as “the relationships between signs and the objects to which they refer”, and pragmatics defined as “the relationship between signs and the interpreters” (8, p. 6-30). It is important to note that in the early period of theoretical linguistics, beginning with F. de Saussure's *Course in General Linguistics* (4), semantics was largely overlooked and became a focus for philosophers such as Charles Morris. This phenomenon can be elucidated through the lens of structuralism, a philosophical approach that prioritises the examination of language in relation to its structural elements. It was only in the latter half of the XX century that an increased interest in semantics in linguistics was observed. The shift can be attributed to a number of factors, but one of the most significant was the emergence of transformational grammar. This new grammar distinguished between “surface” and “deep structures” (2), thereby bringing semantics into focus.

In the domain of structuralism, as articulated by Charles Morris, the conceptual framework encompasses structural (descriptive) or traditional semantics (10). Basil Blackwell is widely regarded as having developed this field of linguistics during the 1950s and 1960s. Among the scholars contributing to this field, S. Ullman's works are particularly noteworthy. His most notable publications include *The Principles of Semantics* (1957) and, in particular, *Semantics: An Introduction to the Science of Meaning* (1962) made a significant contribution to the development of semantics. The subsequent development of this field is particularly associated with C. Lyons, whose two-volume book *Semantics* (1977) became an important reference work. It is noteworthy that, although C. Lyons employed approaches that diverged from structuralist tenets in numerous instances, he nevertheless maintained the conviction that a structural approach to semantic analysis could prove advantageous. Lyons writes (p. xii): “The final two chapters of the book are dedicated to structural

semantics (or more precisely, structural lexicology). This is a subject with which I have been professionally involved for the past 20 years. Despite the waning popularity of structural approaches to semantics among contemporary linguists, it is asserted that these methods continue to offer significant contributions to the field of linguistic analysis”.

It is important to note that the paradigm shift in linguistics in the 1950s and 1960s, resulting from the rise of transformational linguistics (2), opened the door to new approaches to semantics. Consequently, a novel field of linguistics termed Transformational Semantics came into existence (5). In contradistinction to transformational linguistics, this approach posits that syntactic structures are not innate, but rather, their derivations are grounded in meanings. Subsequently, researchers operating within the paradigm of Transformational Semantics, who were in opposition to the principles of Transformational Linguistics, contributed to the establishment of Cognitive Linguistics and Cognitive Grammar, which also came to the fore as new fields within the domain of linguistics.

Contemporary research in semantics is predominantly undertaken within interdisciplinary domains such as linguistic pragmatics and cognitive linguistics (3, 6, 7,). It is important to acknowledge that in both traditional semantics, linguistic pragmatics, and cognitive linguistics, the primary focus is on meaning. For instance, S. Ullman writes: “The two areas of linguistics that deal with words are etymology, which studies the origin of words, and semantics, which studies the meaning of words” (11 p.1). It is noteworthy that both linguistic pragmatics and cognitive linguistics are oriented towards the study of meaning. The difference lies in the fact that, in contrast to traditional semantics, which views meaning in isolation from the role of language users, linguistic pragmatics and cognitive linguistics examine meaning from the perspective of its usage by people through language.

Conclusion. The objective of semantic analysis in modern linguistics is to elucidate the manner in which words and sentences in a language are comprehended, interpreted, and associated with processes and objects in the external world. Semantics is the branch of linguistics concerned with the meaning of linguistic units, especially words and sentences.

References

1. Bloomfield, 1934, Language
2. Chomsky, Noam 1956 Syntactic Structures. Paris: Mouton
3. Croft William and Daniel Cruse 2004 Cognitive Linguistics
Cambridge: Cambridge University Press and others
4. de Saussure, Ferdinand 2000 Course in General Linguistics
5. Katz Jerrold J. and Jerry A. Fodor 1963. The structure of a semantic theory, Language, 39, P.p. 170-210. (Reprinted as Fodor and Katz (1964:479-518)
6. Lakoff George 1987 Women, Fire and Dangerous Things. What Categories Reveal about the Mind. University of Chicago Press
7. Levinson Stephen 1983 Pragmatics. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press 420 p.

8. Morris Charles 1938 *Foundations of the Theory of Signs*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press
9. Peirce Charles 1932 *Collected Papers of Charles Sanders Peirce, Volumes I and II: Principles of Philosophy and Elements of Logic*. Harvard: Harvard University Press, Peirce Charles 1991 "On the nature of signs". In Hoops J. (Ed.) *Peirce on Signs: Writings on Semiotics by Charles Sanders Peirce*. (p . 141-143) University of North Carolina Press
10. Ullman Stephen 1957 *The Principles of Semantics*. Barnes and Nobles 352 s. ,
11. Ullman Stephen 1962 *Semantics: An Introduction to the Science of Meaning*. Basil Blackwell
12. Wierzbicka Anna 1992 *Semantics, Culture and Cognition Universal Human Concepts in Culture-Specific Configurations*, Oxford: Oxford University Press

TAMIM ANSARIYNING "BEVANING ERI" ROMANI TARJIMASI HAQIDA

**Kanimkul Tadjiyev,
filologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsenti
Guliston davlat universiteti**

Har bir yozuvchining mening guruhimdaga ijodkorlarga o‘xshab ketadigan yozuvchi guruhiga San Fransisko Yozuvchilari bo‘linmasi-Tsexi, o‘zining jamiki Proteyga o‘xshagan ko‘p qirrali, o‘zgaruvchan, ammo boshqalardan farqli, tafovutli tunganmas doimo o‘qib turadigan vafodor, sadoqatli, ajralmas qo‘llab-quvvatlab turadigan suyanchiqlar bor. Men, shuningdek, San Fransisko Badiiy Komissiyasiga bir yillik grand bergani uchun minnatdorchilik bildiraman.

Ushbu tarixiy romondagi voqealar 1840-yilda Afg‘onistonning uzoq, kichkina bir qishlog‘dagi odamlar orasida bo‘lib o‘tgan. Bir sirli, yoshi o‘tibroq qolgan. Ushbu shoh qishlog‘iga kelib qoldi va o‘sha qishloqqa tog‘ yonbag‘rida, tekisroq joyda qo‘nim topardim. U yerda donolik-donishmandlik so‘zlarini, o‘rgangan so‘zlarni limlim quyardi yoki bu safsata, behuda gaplargina jim. U bir daydi, darbadarmi, balki aqldan ozgan odati yoki biror qaror to‘g‘risidagi talonchilik, shu yon-atrofdagilar haqida ma‘lumot to‘plovchi harbiy yoki bir malangli xudovand tomonidan "zaharlangan" u odam odatdagi oddiy tashvishlariga tik sifatida bir odam edi. Qishloqliklar uni haydab yuborsinlarmi yoki shu yerda joylashib qolishga ko‘ndirsinlarmi? Bu savollar qishloq boshlig‘i Ibrohimni o‘yga solib qo‘ygan edi. Ibrohimning mo‘rtgina xotini Surayyoni uning yangasi, akasidan qolgan yangasi Xadichani va o‘sha yoqning ancha kuchli, odami G‘ulom Dastagirlarni bezovta qilib, o‘ylantirib qo‘ydi. Qishloqliklar hatto bu begonaning Qabilada uzoq yo‘l bosib "Angliya" deb atalish yerdan kelib qolganmi, bu sirli malang ularning hayotlarini vayron qilib yuboradimi? buni hech kim bilmas edi. G‘ulom Dastagir anchagina

kuchli, uncha-munchaga yegilmaydiga o'ziga, kuchiga ortiqcha ishonib qolgan, sal maqtanchoqroq, ammo savodsiz hamqishloq edi.

Roman Chor Bog', ya'ni to'rt bog' degan ma'noda, qishloqni tasfirlashdan boshlanadi. U qishloq poytaxt Qobul bir necha mil (1 mil=1609 metr) yuzlab millar shimolda joylashgan. Bundan deyarli ikki yuz yil burungi, biroq hozir ham o'zgarishi bo'lmagan "Tupkaning tubi"dagi qishloq edi.

Chor Bog'ning malikini uyida televizor bor, lekin u ko'rsatmaydi, kelajakda biror kun u yerda elektr toki kelib qolsa, balki ishlab qolar, hozircha esa elektr kelmagan, televizor ham shunga yarasha ko'rsatmaydi. 1841-yilda, har holda, u yerda elektr bo'lmagan, hatto Angliyada ham u yo'q edi.

Qishloq cho'zilib ketgan cho'zinchoq tosh kosaga o'xshar, vodiyning pastidagi u qismi, ya'ni tepasi tog'da joylashgan Chorbog'ning to'rt tomoni qiyalik va toshloq. Vodiyning pastki qismi esa ko'm-ko'k soyali-silovatli buyuk tog'lar qad rostlab turibdi.

Chor Bog' vodiyning pastiga yopishib olgan. Daryo bir chekkadan kiradi u balanddan pastga shovullab tushib, bir qator mayda shovvalarga yetishadi. U, ya'ni daryo, vodiyning yassi joyidan sirtmoq, irmoq hosil qilib yonidan o'tadi. Halqadan o'tgan suv janub tomondagi shovvalar bo'ylab oqimini tezlashtiradi, bungacha esa u tog' daryosi degan nomga munosib oqadi.

Daryo qirg'og'i bo'ylab past tomondan unga kiradigan joy yo'q, bunday joy daryoning tepa qismida ham ko'rinmaydi. Suv keladigan tomon faqat bir tarafdin. Bugun tosh shag'al yo'l, bittagina yengil mashina sig'ishi mumkin bo'lgan, yo'ldan yuradi. Bu yerda o'tish Qizil o'tish degan joyining etagidagina bor, yaqin o'tmishlargacha Qobildan keladigan hukumatning rasmiy odamlari xizmat bilan o'sha yerdan o'tib kelishadi va bunday kelishlar tabiiyki har xil zamondagina ro'y beradi.

1841-yildan avval Chorbog'ga kelishga faqat poyi-piyoda, yakka oyoq yo'lgina bor bo'lgan bu yo'ldan faqat yovvoyi echki-uloqlar yura olgan ammo odam izlari kam ko'ringan. Bahor faslining oxirlarida bir kuni ertalab, kun ancha ko'tarilib qolganida (1841-yilda) Chorbog' maliki ikki xonali uylarining birida o'tirganida, o'zining soqol-mo'ylovini tekshirib o'ziga qarab turganida, ammo o'sha kuni yana nimadir bo'lishi hayoliga kelmagan, albatta, lekin o'zining boshida salkam 30ga kirib qolgan boshliqning sochlari orasida birorta ham oqargan sochi ko'rinmas edi. Bu unga yoqar edi, ammo shu bilan birga uni hali yosh o'ylashlariga ham uncha chidamas edi. Asarda Rumiyning sehrli nodir kitobini qimmatli meros bo'lib o'tgan ota-bobolaridan qolgan Qur'oni ham bor bo'lib, Ibrohim ularni tez-tez o'qib turar edi, masalan unda ba'zi bir satrlar katta tassurot qoldirar edi.

Masalan sizning yuz biringizdan hali bittasi ham ochilgani yo'q, "Hormang!" menga sarhob haqida uning odamlari haqida hammaning sog'-salomat yurgani haqida aytarsiz, albatta, "Insha'alloh, shunday bo'lsin". Hadicha yangasi Ibrohimning qizlarining birining ismi Nahid bo'lganini, ba'zi-ba'zi uning yoqimli-yoqimsiz qiliqlarini tanqid qilib turar edi. Yozuvchining hikmatomuz gaplaridan 1-2ta misol keltirsak:

One morsel of meat and all the men turn into cats, as they say(5)

Well everyman had his own special burdons to bear

Bu gaplarni o'zbek tilida

Xo'sh, har kim o'z aravasini o'zi tortsin

Alloh knows best esa Alloh hamma narsani biladi deb tushunishimiz kerakka o'xshaydi. Bir bahorda ertalab, Hadicha qishlog'idan qaytib kelganidan sal vaqt o'tib, bitta butunlay begona, hech kim tanimaydigan boya aytganimizdek, echkilargina yura oladigan yo'ldan bir odam yurib keldi va nima uchundir o'sha Chorbog' tepasidagi joy unga yoqib qoldiki, o'sha joyda quyosh nurlari ostida qoyalarni rosa qizdirgan paytida, ammo to'g' tepasida hali ham qor bor edi, shunday ob-havoga qaramay, u odam ustidagi kiyimlari bir ahvoldagi, qalin soqqolli ko'rinishidan daydi bir odam ekanligini tushunish mumkin edi, uning qo'lida hech narsasi yo'q, hatto uni qo'riqlaydigan iti ham yo'q edi. U qayerdan kelib qoldi? Tubkaning tubidan boshqa joyga olib bormaydigan yolg'iz oyoq yo'ldan qayerlarni mo'ljallab ketayotgan edi? Undan bunday savollarga javob berishini hech kim so'ramadi, chunki birinchi bo'lib qishloqning boshlig'i Ibrohimning og'li Karim undan kamida 1-2 yosh, Ahmad va G'ulom dastagirning 9 yashar o'g'li Ahmad biror yosh Karimdan kattadir. Karim o'sha kuni erta bilan qirda Ahmad bilan yurgan edi, ular o'zlarining oilasining va tanish bilishlarining bir gala echkilarini boqib yurishgan edi, biroq mollarga qarash o'rniga ularni ko'proq oshib o'ynash qiziqroq edi, uning o'rniga mollarni itga topshirib o'zlari o'yin bilan band edi.

Bolalar daydini ko'rib qolganlarida o'yinni to'xtatib, bu suyaklari katta qari odamning so'qmoqdan ko'tarilib, Boboning burni deyishadigan qoyatosh pastiga kelib qo'ndi, ular begona odamning bir narsani surib qo'yib, qoratoshning kovagiga nimanidir suqib qo'yganini ko'rishdi keyin o'sha yerga so'qmoqdan yurib kelgan, uning atrofdagilaridan hech kim ko'rmaydigan qishloqning pastidan ham pastroq bo'lgan joyga bemalol joylashib olganiga qarab turdilar. Chol sallasini olib, uning etagidan qayta ilgan tuxum oldi, tuxumni po'choqlaridan olib tashlab, ist'mol qildi. Keyin u ancha vaqt ko'zlarini yumib qo'llarini uzatib, qimirlamay, o'tirdi, uning qo'llari ochiq edi. Bolalar boshlarini qashib, burunlarini tortib qo'yib, u odamni kuzatishda davom etishdi.

Bu darbadar, albatta, oshiq o'ynashni ulardan yaxshiroq eplasa kerak. Karim butunlay begona bo'lgan odamlarni hayotida bir martagina ko'rgan o'shanda ham qishloqlariga talonchi qaroqchilar hujum qilishganida u odam kelib joylashgan Qizil o'tishning shimol tomonidagi Sarhobning shundoqqina ko'rinib turgan qishlog'iga qaradi. Ibrohimning yangasi Hadicha o'sha yerdan kelgan, shu bilan birga Sarhobga bir necha marta Hadichalarning uydagilarini ko'rib kelishga borganida bunaqa odamlarni ko'rmagan, shuning uchun ham u begona daydi bolalarga boshqacha ko'rinar edi.

U odam o'rnidan birdan turib sallasini besh marta aylantirib boshiga qo'ydi, lekin o'ziga loyiq bo'lgan uzunlik va kenglikka keltirib uni yozib yerga to'shadi. U sallasini ehtiyot bo'lib qoqdi. U yerdagi hasharot va boshqa yopishgan narsalarni qoqib tashladi, G'arb tomonga qarab qo'llarini quloqlariga ko'tardi va asta namoz o'qiy boshladi!

“Alloh-u Akbar!”

U kim so‘radi Karim, undan sal yoshrog‘i esa yelkasini qisib qo‘ydi.

U Sarhobdanmikan?

Men uni u yerda avval hech ham ko‘rmaganman.

Unga qara! dedi Karim norozi bo‘lib kelgindini yoqtirmay.

“Sen uning terisini ko‘rmayapsanmi?” u qo‘li bilan begonani ko‘rsatib turar edi. Ikkala bola ham u odamning ilma-teshik ko‘ylagidagi teshiklarga qarardi.

Men unga tosh otaman, dedi Karim

Menga bir zo‘r, yaxshi tosh topishga yordam bergin, Ahmadjon dedi

“Men u qari itni qimirlashga majbur qilaman. Ko‘rasan”

Unday qilma, dedi Ahmad u odam jinni bo‘lib qoladi

Nega, nima uchun mening ayam mening bu qilig‘imga aqldan ozib, tentak bo‘lib qolar ekan?

Mening dadam menga doimo qishlog‘imizni begonalardan himoya qilib, qo‘riqlashim zarurligini tayinlaydi, ana shunaqa qaroqchi talonchilar kelgan vaqti esingdami o‘n yoshli bola gerdayib, ko‘krarigini kerib, sherigining ustidan kulgan bo‘lib, “Sen eslamaysan uni, sen bu yerda bo‘lmagansan, sen Sarhobda eding, sen mening gapimga quloq sol Ahmadjon” Begonalar yomon odamlar. Sen mening yoshimga kirganingda buni bilib olasan.

“Sen sayohatchilarga joy berishing kerak, har holda! Qoida shunaqa” dedi Ahmad. Dadam menga doimo shunday tayinlaydilar.

Hmm. Karim bu qoidani bilar edi, u hech qachon begonalarga ishonmaslikni, sayohatchilarga joy berishni, ularni qo‘llashi kerakligini bilar edi. Agar u odam pastga tushib ayollarimizga qarasachi? Karim qoshlarni chimirdi “Men garov o‘ynayman, u bu yerga shuning uchun kelgan, men uni shu yerdan turib, tosh bilan ura olaman, garov o‘ynaysanmi?”

Men qimor o‘ynamayman.

U odamning namozini o‘qib bo‘lib, sallasini do‘pisining tepasiga joylashtirganiga qarab turishdi. O‘zi Bobo Burun oldiga bardosh qurunib o‘tirib oldi va duolar o‘qiy boshladi, u bolalarni ajab tovurgina ko‘rib turgan bo‘lsa ham, ularga e‘tibor bermadi.

Sen garov o‘ynamaysan?, dedi Karim pishillab.

“Sen eshshak miyasan, oshiq o‘ynash qimor emasmi?” “Men uning miyasini qattig‘ini chiqaraman”

Karim izlagan toshini qurolini topgan edi, mushtdek yumaloq toshni kaftida aylantirib ko‘rdi.

To‘xtat, deb shivirladi Ahmad achchiqlanib, senga nima bo‘ldi? U bechora odam shunchaki dam olayapti.

“Boshqa biror joyga borib dam olsin, bu bizning qishlog‘imiz, Alloh nomi bilan, Xudo haqqi, Karim uni o‘ziga kelib, o‘zini bosib olishini hohlar edi.

Surayyo o‘zini jin chalib ketishidan qo‘rqadi, bu qiziq gap, chunki Surrayo shunday gaplarga ishonadi, ammo uning bolasi, albatta, o‘zini beayb, kichkina bola deb o‘ylaydi, shuning uchun o‘zidan kattalarning ba‘zi gaplariga o‘ylanib, gapning ma‘nosiga tushunmay turadi. U kelgan sirli daydi, albatta, duolar o‘qir edi, uning yomon gaplarni aytmaganiga bolalar ishonishar edi, u daydimi, yo sal anaqaroqmi,

balki qaroqchilar to‘dasiga mansub bir darbadarmi, unday odamlarga Chorbog‘lik odamlar o‘zlarining tilida malang deb atashadi, bu xudoning bandasining o‘tmishi qayerda kechganini hech kim bilmaydi, ammo Tamim Ansariy bilar, ammo biz o‘quvchi kitobxonlardan, balki ilhom tutar, uyog‘i bizga qorong‘i.

Adabiyotlar

The Widow’s Husband. A novel by Tamim Ansary. A Vox Novus Book. A Numina Press Book 2009.

San Rafael, California. 347 pages.

West of Kabul, East of New York. Tamim Ansary. An AfghanAmerican Story. PICALOR Farrar, Straus and Cirboux New York. 2002. 301 pages.

LINGUISTIC AND EXTRALINGUISTIC FACTORS IN SHAPING DISCOURSE

Sabina Ismayilova Vilayat

Baku State University

Teacher, Department of English Language

(the Faculties of Humanities)

sabinaismayilova@bsu.edu.az

Abstract: This article explores the manner in which the interpretive function of discourse is influenced by extralinguistic and linguistic factors. The primary focus of this study is the relationship between the characteristics of the dialogic space and the communication of extralinguistic factors. Researchers identify features of communication such as dialogicity, interactivity, non-linearity, incompleteness, and the ability to transform information. The objective of effective communication is to enable each communicator to achieve their desired outcomes while maintaining equilibrium in the communication process. This phenomenon is associated with a variety of communication objectives, including the transmission of information, the modification of behavior, and the establishment of connections. The article's analysis is grounded in the theoretical frameworks proposed by Halliday and Hu, which categorize context into three distinct types: linguistic, situational, and cultural. The focal point of this study is the manner in which cultural context influences the development of language and communicative events, in addition to the cultural expressions that emerge within the context of specific situations.

The cultural context which is considered part of the extralinguistic context, provides a comprehensive explanation of the broader aspects of the environment in which language and communication processes manifest. Furthermore, the communicative stance and speech influence theory are presented as essential aspects, as an individual's communicative stance may change in different communication situations. Speech influence techniques, including proving, persuading, suggesting, and ordering, are methods through which an individual can exert influence over another. Research indicates that methods of persuasive communication vary in their

effectiveness across diverse cultural audiences. For instance, while references to the Bible are effective in the UK and the USA, references to the Quran are more influential in Azerbaijan. Discourse is evaluated as a purposeful process formed by the cognitive structures used by an individual's conceptual system and the corresponding representation tools in language. Accordingly, the article expounds on the manner in which discourse is shaped by a multitude of social, cultural, and situational factors. Furthermore, it provides an in-depth analysis of purposeful communication.

Keywords: language, meaning, linguistic, interpretation, syntax, pragmatics, cognition

Introduction. The interpretive function of discourse is determined by both extralinguistic and linguistic factors. First and foremost, we consider the characteristics of the dialogic space and communication as extralinguistic factors. A body of research has identified a set of characteristics that are inherent to communication. These characteristics include dialogicity, interactivity, non-linearity, incompleteness, and the ability to transform information (6; 7; 9).

The effectiveness of influence in a dialogue is determined separately for each communicator. In a dialogue, effective communication can be achieved either for one participant or both. In the context of multi-party conversations, the efficacy of communication varies among participants. The concept of effectiveness is linked to a communicator's achievement of their goals in a particular communicative situation. The ability to influence speech effectively enables the speaker to achieve their desired outcome while maintaining a balanced communicative relationship with the interlocutor. This balance prevents the escalation of arguments and ensures that the interlocutor is able to engage in a productive dialogue. However, communication goals can vary. They can be categorized as informational, substantive, or communicative. An informational goal is to convey information and receive confirmation that it has been understood. A substantive goal is to obtain something, learn something, or change the interlocutor's behavior. A communicative goal is to establish, develop, maintain, restore, or terminate a specific connection with the interlocutor.

Halliday's (1985) seminal work marked a significant development in the field by generalizing the theory of context based on situational context theory and introducing the concept of "register." The concept of context can be reflected by the register, which encompasses variables such as discourse domain, tone of speech, and speech style. The discourse domain encompasses the events and subjects of conversation, as well as the activities in which the speaker and other participants engage. These elements collectively constitute the linguistic environment. The tone of speech is indicative of the relationships between participants, including their social status and roles. The term "speech style" is used to denote the manner in which linguistic communication is conducted, encompassing the selection of channels and tools employed. These channels and tools may include oral or written

communication, as well as the degree of preparation that precedes the communication, categorized as either *impromptu* or *prepared* (1;5).

Hu (1994) divided context into three types based on Halliday's framework model. The following three elements comprise the linguistic context: 1) the co-text, which pertains to the internal environment of the discourse; 2) the situational context, which refers to the environment where the speech occurs, the characteristics of the event, as well as the topic, time, place, and method of the conversation; and 3) the cultural context, which relates to linguistic social groups, the author's history, culture, customs, and traditions (8). The cultural context, which is considered part of the extralinguistic context, establishes the foundation for the linguistic system as a whole and dictates the meaning systems that are embedded within it. The situational context is defined as the specific application of language within a given context, and the cultural embodiment of that context. The cultural context is reflected in a variety of situational contexts, and the significance of specific communicative events within a cultural context is determined by the situational context (2).

The communication objectives encompass a wide array of sentiments, including greetings, congratulations, expressions of affection, farewells, compliments, and more. The communicative stance of the speaker may be strong (e.g., the boss towards a subordinate, or an adult towards a child) or weak (e.g., a child towards an adult, or a subordinate towards a superior). In the context of communication, the speaker's communicative stance can be fortified or safeguarded by employing speech influence techniques. Conversely, the interlocutor's stance can be undermined by utilizing such techniques and executing diverse speech acts toward the interlocutor. The theory of speech influence is concerned with the examination of methods through which an individual may exert influence over another during a verbal exchange. These methods include, but are not limited to, proving, persuading, suggesting, ordering, and other related practices. The communicative stance of the speaker represents a seminal theoretical concept in the domain of speech influence science. The communicative stance is defined as the speaker's influence and authority in relation to the interlocutor. This concept pertains to the relative effectiveness of the speaker's potential speech influence on the interlocutor. A person's communicative stance, defined as the degree to which they are willing to engage in a communicative act, can undergo modification in different communication situations and even within the same communicative situation. Research indicates that methods employed in the influence of speech are subject to cultural particularities. The efficacy of these methods in one audience may not be indicative of their effectiveness in another, or vice versa. For instance, references to the Bible have proven effective in both the UK and the USA, while references to the Quran have demonstrated greater efficacy in Azerbaijan. A similar phenomenon occurs in the context of jokes, which are utilized extensively in the USA but demonstrate limited effectiveness in Azerbaijan and other regions.

Conclusion. Discourse can be defined as the product of a linguistic personality created to solve specific purposeful tasks, utilizing the cognitive structures of an individual's conceptual system and their chosen representational tools in language.

References

1. Cabrerizo F. J., Pérez I. J., & Herrera-Viedma E. (2010). Managing the consensus in group decision making in an unbalanced fuzzy linguistic context with incomplete information. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 23(2), 169–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2009.12.005>
2. Diéguez-Risco et al., 2015; Stern & Lehrndorfer 1992. The Functions of Context in Discourse Analysis. *International Journal of Linguistics, Literature and Culture*
3. Halliday M. A. K. (1985). *An Introduction to Functional Grammar* (2nd edn). Edward Arnold
4. Hu Z. L. (1994). *Textual cohesion and coherence*. Shanghai Foreign Language Education Press.
5. Kircher T. T. J., Senior C., Phillips M. L., Benson P. J., Bullmore E. T., Brammer M., & David A. S. (2001). Recognizing one's own face. *Cognition*, 78(1), B1–B15. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-0277\(00\)00104-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-0277(00)00104-9)
6. Klushina N. I., Ivanova S. V., & Chudinov A. P. (2018). *Political Linguistics: Theory and Practice of Speech Impact*. Moscow: Flinta.
7. Morozova O. N. (2011). *Manipulation in political discourse: linguistic mechanisms and strategies*. Moscow: Librokom.
8. Song L. (2010). The role of context in discourse analysis. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 1(6), 876. <https://doi.org/10.4304/jltr.1.6.876-879>
9. Trofimova G. N., & Barabash V. V. (2020). *The Linguistic Representation of Manipulation in Media Discourse*. Saint Petersburg: Aleteia.

COMMUNICATION AND IDENTITY IN A GLOBALIZED WORLD

Abduxalimova Sarvinozxon Usmonali qizi,
Qo‘qon davlat universiteti 2-kurs tayanch doktoranti
xaydaraliyeva95@mail.ru

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola madaniyatlararo muloqot jarayoni va madaniy identifikatsiya masalalariga bag‘ishlangan. Muallif madaniy identifikatsiyaning ahamiyatini va uni saqlash zaruratini ta’kidlaydi, shuningdek, odamlarning boshqa madaniyatlarga integratsiya qilish jarayonini ko‘rib chiqadi. Madaniyat konstant sifatida turli ijtimoiy va madaniy guruhlar o‘rtasidagi farqlarni anglashga yordam beradi. Madaniy identifikatsiya shaxsning o‘zini boshqasidan farqli ravishda qabul qilishi, shu bilan birga, o‘zligini saqlab qolish zaruriyati borligini belgilaydi. Ushbu maqola madaniy identifikatsiya va madaniyatlararo muloqot jarayonlari o‘rtasidagi murakkab munosabatlarni ochib beradi.

Kalit so‘z va iboralar: madaniy identifikatsiya, madaniyatlararo muloqot, madaniyat, o‘zlik, ijtimoiy guruhlar

Annotation. This article is dedicated to the issues of intercultural communication and cultural identity. The author emphasizes the importance of cultural identity and the necessity to maintain it while also exploring the process of integrating into foreign cultures. Cultural identity aids in understanding the

differences between various social and cultural groups. It signifies an individual's acceptance of their distinctiveness amid others, while simultaneously necessitating the preservation of one's own identity. The article sheds light on the complex relationship between cultural identity and the processes of intercultural communication.

Keywords and expressions: cultural identity, intercultural communication, culture, self-identity, social groups

In the process of intercultural communication, every individual simultaneously addresses two crucial problems: the desire to maintain their cultural identity while engaging with foreign cultures.

In the broadest sense, «identity» refers to an individual's awareness of their belonging to a particular sociocultural group, enabling them to determine their place within the sociocultural space and navigate the surrounding world freely. The necessity for identity arises from the fact that each person needs a certain order in their life activities, which can only be provided by a community of other people. To achieve this, they must voluntarily accept the dominant elements of consciousness, tastes, habits, norms, values, and other means of interaction that are accepted among others in that community. The assimilation of these elements of social life within the group gives an individual's life an organized and predictable character, making them part of the corresponding culture.

Since every individual can simultaneously be a member of several social and cultural communities, different types of identity are typically distinguished based on the type of group affiliation: professional, civic, ethnic, political, religious, and cultural identity. Among all these types, cultural identity is of particular interest to us, which can be defined as «an individual's belonging to any culture or cultural group that shapes their value relationship to themselves, other people, society, and the world as a whole.» [Sadokhin A.P. *Mejkulturnaya kommunikatsiya*. M., 2004. P.57]

Thus, the essence of cultural identity lies in the conscious acceptance by the individual of the corresponding cultural norms and behavior models, value orientations, and language, as well as in the understanding of their self from the perspective of the cultural characteristics that are accepted in that society, identifying themselves with the cultural models of that particular society.

In intercultural communication, the problematic nature of cultural identity is based on the division of representatives of all cultures into «us» and «them.» This opposition permeates all aspects of culture and reflects the collective, mass, popular, and national worldview. Depending on the size of the collective we are considering, we can find a distinct but always clear distinction between «us» and «them.» The opposition of «us» and «them» is by no means a modern phenomenon. [Fasmer M, *Etimologicheskiy slovar russkogo yazyka: V 4-kh tt.: T. 3*. M., 1987. P 582-583]. It has divided families, clans, and tribes in archaic societies, religious sects, and so on. Conceptually, it already distinguished the «own people» from the «not one's own,» the «other,» and the «foreign,» because «own» means «belonging,» «special,» «personal,» «separate,» significant «self,» having «essence.» [Shanskiy, N. M.,

Ivanov, V. V., & Shanskaya, T. V. *Kratkiy etimologicheskiy slovar russkogo yazyka* M.,1971.P 497,419]

In the process of intercultural communication, an individual inevitably faces the question of where the boundary lies between the culture they consider their own and those cultures that are foreign to them. Answering this question is not as simple as it may seem at first glance. The connection to one's own culture is not automatically guaranteed by mere blood ties or inherited genes. This connection is established not through biological means but in some other way, which means it has a non-biological origin. One can be Uzbek by blood yet not be Uzbek in terms of culture, and vice versa. So, what serves as the foundation for this connection?

When there are many cultures, knowledge about them and existence within one of them do not necessarily coincide. One can know about Islam without being a Muslim. Knowledge and being diverge from one another. Knowledge makes a person learned, but it does not indicate their cultural belonging. It is somewhat neutral in relation to the boundary that separates «my culture» from the foreign. From what a person knows about a culture, one cannot conclude who they are culturally.

In intercultural communication, a classic situation occurs when representatives of different cultures encounter culturally specific views of the world during communication, where each partner initially fails to recognize the significance of the differences in these views, as each considers their own perceptions to be normal while viewing the perceptions of their interlocutor as abnormal.

Metaphorically speaking, when interacting with a representative of another culture, an individual is akin to traveling to a foreign country. They step outside the boundaries of their familiar environment and the circle of well-known concepts, venturing into an unfamiliar world that is enticing due to its novelty. On one hand, the foreign land is unknown and appears dangerous; on the other hand, everything new is appealing, promising new knowledge and experiences, and broadening one's horizons and life experiences.

In the modern world, the number of people crossing the boundaries of their cultural worlds and attempting to settle in another cultural region is growing. They face the choice of assimilation—potentially dissolving completely into the foreign culture—or integration, which involves a degree of adaptation while retaining their own cultural identity.

Regardless of the choice made, this process will not be easy. For culture is not just language, customs, and so on; it is also manifested in social structure, the predominant mode of material production, and other factors.

References

1. Fasmer M, *Etimologicheskiy slovar russkogo yazyka: V 4-kh tt.: T. 3.* M., 1987.P 582-583
2. Sadokhin A.P. *Mejkulturnaya kommunikatsiya.* M.,2004. P.57
3. Shanskiy, N. M., Ivanov, V. V., & Shanskaya, T. V. *Kratkiy etimologicheskiy slovar russkogo yazyka* M.,1971.P 497,419
4. Vasmer, M. *Etymological Dictionary of the Russian Language: In 4 Volumes.* Vol. 3. Moscow, 1987. P. 582-583.

**MAKTAB TA'LIMIDA INNOVATSION PEDAGOGIK
TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISH (INGLIZ TILIDAGI
EKVIVALENTSIZ LEKSIKA MISOLIDA)**

**Avalboyeva Maftuna,
tayanch doktorant,
maftunka0710@gmail.com
O'zDJTU**

Annotatsiya. Zamonaviy sharoitda ekvivalentsiz leksika o'qitilishi til madaniyati va tarixini o'rganishda, o'quvchilarning dunyoqarashini kengaytirishda muhim ekanligi aniqlangan. Til o'rgatishda madaniyat va til bir butun ekanligi, shuning uchun ekvivalentsiz leksikaning o'qitilishi bilan bog'liq pedagogik yondashuvlar va texnologiyalar ahamiyatiga e'tibor qaratish zarurligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ekvivalentsiz leksika; lingvodidaktika; chet tilini o'qitish; pedagogik texnologiya; multimedia vositalari; madaniy realiyalar; o'quv-tarbiyaviy jarayon.

Abstract: In modern conditions, it has been determined that teaching non-equivalent vocabulary is important for studying language culture and history and for broadening students' worldview. It is emphasized that language and culture are inseparable in language teaching; therefore, attention should be paid to the significance of pedagogical approaches and technologies related to the teaching of non-equivalent vocabulary.

Keywords: non-equivalent vocabulary; linguodidactics; foreign language teaching; pedagogical technology; multimedia tools; cultural realia; educational process.

Ekvivalentsiz leksika – ya'ni ma'nosi boshqa tilda to'g'ridan to'g'ri ekvivalenti bo'lmagan so'z yoki ifoda – til va madaniyat o'rtasidagi aloqani ko'rsatadigan muhim til birliklaridandir [tilvaadabiyot.uz]. Maslova til o'ziga xos madaniy voqea-hodisalarni ifodalovchi “ekvivalentsiz leksika va lakunalar” qatlami mavjudligini ta'kidlaydi [tilvaadabiyot.uz]. Bunday so'zlar ko'pincha muayyan millat tarixiga, urf-odatlariga, tabiiy-sharoitlarga yoki diniy-afsonalarga bog'liq bo'ladi. Masalan, Mirzaaliyev va Oxunov ta'kidlashicha, ingliz tilida katta miqdordagi leksik birlikning o'zbek tilida ekvivalenti yo'q bo'lib, bu tushunchalar, avvalo, madaniy realiyalar orqali o'z ifodasini topadi. Shuning uchun ekvivalentsiz leksikani o'qitish o'quvchilarda milliy o'zlikni anglash va tilga oid madaniy kompetensiyani shakllantirish uchun zarurdir.

Chet tilini o'rgatishda so'z boyligini to'g'ri tashkil etish pedagogik jarayonning muhim bo'g'inidir. Biror tilning leksik fondi tafovutlari turli tillar o'rtasida to'liq ekvivalent o'zgarishini ta'minlamaydi – bu holatni Arifova ham qayd etadi: ikki

tilni taqqoslaganda ularning lug‘at boyligi haqida to‘g‘ri xulosaga kelib bo‘lmasligini, chunki ma‘lum tushunchaga nom berish lingvistik hamda ekstralingvistik omillarga bog‘liq bo‘lishini ta‘kidlaydi. Demak, ekvivalentsiz leksika ham til faoliyatining ajralmas qismi bo‘lib, uni o‘qitishda hududiy va madaniy tafovutlar yodda tutilishi shart.

Pedagogik texnologiyalar sohasida amalga oshirilayotgan izlanishlar ta‘lim sifati va samaradorligini oshirishga qaratilgan. Ma‘lumki, innovatsion pedagogik yondashuvlar ta‘lim jarayonini rejalash, o‘quvchi faolligini rag‘batlantirish va ko‘nikmalarni rivojlantirishga yo‘naltiriladi. Xalqaro tadqiqotlar va amaliy ishlar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari (ICT) chet tilini o‘qitishda noan‘anaviy vositalardan foydalanib, murakkab leksik tushunchalarni osonlashtiradi. Darslarda multimedia vositalaridan (filmlar, rasmlar, animatsiyalar) va interaktiv lug‘atlardan foydalangan holda ekvivalentsiz leksik birliklarning talqinini taqdim etish mumkin.

Ekvivalentsiz leksika mavzusi o‘qitilganda o‘quvchilarda nafaqat yangi so‘zlar, balki ularning kontekstda ishlatilishi, madaniy anglashish bilan bog‘liq kompetensiya ham rivojlantiriladi. O‘rganilgan darslarda o‘quvchilarga tarixiy va madaniy ma‘nolarga boy bir qator yangi leksika birliklari taqdim etiladi. Dars jarayonlarida multimedia taqdimotlari, real tasvirlar va o‘yinlarga asoslangan mashqlar ishlatiladi. Natijada, ushbu texnologiyalar yordamida o‘quvchilarning motivatsiyasi sezilarli darajada oshadi.

Shuni ta‘kidlash zarurki, axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining qo‘llanilishi o‘quvchilarga murakkab ma‘lumotni qisqa muddatda qabul qilishiga yordam beradi.

Leksik dars ishlarini bajarishda interaktiv lug‘atlardan, audio-video manbalardan foydalangan o‘quvchilar, an‘anaviy darslarga qiyoslanganda, leksik yodlash va tushunish topshiriqlarini yaxshiroq bajaradi. Bu pedagogik metodlar ko‘p hollarda ovozli ifoda va kontekstual misollar bilan to‘ldirilib, o‘quvchilarni mustaqil izlanishga undaydi. Ularning nutq faoliyatida yangi ekvivalentsiz leksik birliklar mazmunli ishlatiladi. Shu tariqa, pedagogik texnologiyalarni innovatsion usullarda qo‘llash o‘quvchi yutuqlarini sezilarli darajada oshiradi va ekvivalentsiz leksikani o‘zlashtirish jarayonini tezlashtiradi.

Ma‘lumki, lingvistik qarashda har bir tilning lug‘ati o‘ziga xos ijtimoiy-ma‘naviy maydon aksidir. Arifova (2024) ta‘kidlaganidek, tilning lug‘at boyligi haqida ikki tilni to‘g‘ridan to‘g‘ri solishtirib bo‘lmaydi, chunki nom qo‘yish jarayoniga lingvistik hamda madaniy-sotsiologik omillar ta‘sir qiladi, misol uchun, bir tilda keng tarqalgan tushuncha boshqasida mutlaqo yangi realiya bo‘lishi mumkin. Shunday bo‘lganida, o‘quvchi ana shu madaniy jihatdan boy va nodir birikmani faqat tarjima emas, balki aniq ta‘rif yoki izoh orqali o‘zlashtirishi kerak bo‘ladi. Bu jihat o‘quv metodikasida tasviriy tarjima va ta‘rif usullarining zarurligini yana bir bor eslatadi.

Shunday qilib, ekvivalentsiz leksikani o‘qitishning muvaffaqiyati pedagogik texnologiyalarni to‘g‘ri va ijodiy qo‘llashga bog‘liq. Nega deb so‘ralsa, bu turdagi leksika bilan ishlashda nafaqat til qoidalari, balki madaniy jihatlar ham hisobga

olinadi. Shu bois, o'qitish jarayonida har bir leksik birlik fonida unga bog'liq tarixiy-madaniyatning qisqacha sharhini berish, multimediali va interfaol amaliyotlar tashkil etish lozim.

Shuni ta'kidlash lozimki, ekvivalentsiz leksika til va madaniyatning ajralmas bo'lagi sifatida chet tillari o'qitishida muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bunday leksik birliklarning o'ziga xosligi va ma'nolarini to'g'ri yetkazib berish qiyinchiliklarini hal qilishda pedagogik texnologiyalar katta rol o'ynaydi. Xususan, multimedia va interfaol mashqlar, zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya vositalari yordamida olib borilgan o'qitish ekvivalentsiz leksikaning o'zlashtirilishini sezilarli darajada osonlashtirdi. Ma'ruza va yozma izohlarga qaraganda, vizual va eshitish materiallari bilan boyitilgan darslar o'quvchilarning tushunchalarni idrok etish darajasini oshiradi. Bu esa ingliz tilidagi ekvivalentlari bo'lmagan leksik birliklarni mashg'ulotda jonli misollar bilan qo'llashning samaradorligini oshiradi. Buning natijasida o'quvchilarda tilning milliy kechmishga oid xususiyatini anglash va chet tilini o'rgatishda tarjimonlik salohiyatini oshirish yo'lida sezilarli yutuqlarni kuzatish mumkin.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, ekvivalentsiz leksikani o'qitishda pedagogik texnologiyalarga alohida e'tibor qaratish talab etiladi. O'qitishning an'anaviy metodlariga yangi texnologiyalarni integratsiya qilish leksik birliklarni samarali o'rgatish va til bilish doirasini kengaytirishga imkon beradi. Shu munosabat bilan kelajakda maktab va oliy ta'lim jarayonlarida ekvivalentsiz leksikani o'qitish metodikalarini yanada takomillashtirib, raqamli resurslar yaratish istiqbollari joriy etilishi lozimligini ta'kidlash muhim.

Adabiyotlar

1. Arifova, U.A. (2024). *Zamonaviy tilshunoslikda ekvivalent va ekvivalentsiz leksik birliklarning o'rganilish hususiyatlari*. *Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, Educational, Natural and Social Sciences*, 4(23), 707–712. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14167172> zenodo.org.

2. Maslova, V.A. (1997). *Vvedenie v lingvokultureologiyu*. Moskva: Naslediye. tilvaadabiyot.uz.

3. Mirzaaliyev, I., Oxunov, A. (2021). *Ekvivalentsiz leksikaning o'zbek va ingliz tillarida ifodalanishi*. *Scientific Progress*, 2(2), 680–684. [Cyberleninka scribd.com](http://Cyberleninka.scribd.com).

4. Yigitaliyeva Muxlisa (2023). *Lingvokulturema yondoshuvining hozirgi kundagi asosiy tushuncha va muammolari* [Elektron jurnali]. *Qo'qon Davlat Pedagogika Instituti*, 19(7), 12–22. tilvaadabiyot.uz

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK TRADE TERMINOLOGY IN SPECIALIZED SUBLANGUAGES

Bozorova Sevara Kamol qizi,
aimatovas208.4@gmail.com

Doctoral student at Karshi State University

Abstract. This article examines English and Uzbek trade terminology within the specialized sublanguages of law, economics, and finance. Legal discourse

demonstrates stability and semantic rigidity, while economic and financial discourse reveal openness to borrowings, calques, and neologisms. Comparative analysis highlights both similarities, such as the widespread use of internationalisms and acronyms, and differences, including semantic precision in English versus greater flexibility in Uzbek.

Key words and phrases: specialized sublanguages, legal, economic and financial discourse, translation studies, lexicography, ESP.

The study of specialized sublanguages has gained increasing importance in modern linguistics, particularly as professional communication becomes more globalized and terminologically complex. Trade, as a domain of law, economics, and finance, relies on a highly specialized vocabulary that serves not only as a tool of professional interaction but also as a reflection of socio-economic development. According to Lotte, terminology forms the skeleton of scientific and technical knowledge [Lotte, 1961, p. 160]. Building on this view, in the field of trade such a role is even more pronounced, since terminological precision directly affects contractual relations, financial transactions, and market regulations.

In English linguistics, scholars such as Jennifer Pearson [Pearson, 1998, p. 242] and Cabré [Cabré, 1999, p. 248] have emphasized that specialized sublanguages are defined by functional and pragmatic features that differentiate them from general vocabulary. In the Uzbek context, Oybek Ahmedov has conducted research on taxation terminology highlighting its historical roots, semantic development, and the impact of borrowings and internationalisms [Ahmedov, 2016, p. 255]. Given that taxation represents a crucial subdomain of economic and trade discourse, his findings are highly relevant for understanding the dynamics of Uzbek trade-related lexicon in general.

Specialized vocabulary, often referred to as terminology, represents the lexical foundation of professional communication. Unlike general vocabulary, which is characterized by broad usage and semantic flexibility, specialized vocabulary is marked by precision, consistency, and functional restriction to particular domains of knowledge. Cabré argues that specialized vocabulary represents the linguistic realization of concepts belonging to particular domains of expertise, and therefore functions both as a communicative resource and as part of a structured conceptual system [Cabré, 1999, p. 248]. In this sense, trade terminology can be considered a subset of specialized vocabulary that has developed in close connection with the evolution of commerce, law, economics, and finance.

The characteristics of trade terms derive from their dual nature as both linguistic and socio-economic entities. On the one hand, they must maintain semantic accuracy, since the misinterpretation of a single term in legal or financial documents can lead to serious consequences. On the other hand, they reflect the dynamics of socio-economic life, which explains the openness of trade terminology to borrowings, calques, and neologisms. In English, expressions such as *outsourcing*, *e-commerce*, or *derivative markets* illustrate how the field rapidly absorbs innovations, while in

Uzbek, terms like *eksport*, *import*, and *aksiya* show the impact of international borrowings on local discourse.

Previous research on specialized sublanguages and trade vocabulary has taken different approaches. In Western linguistics, scholars such as Pearson [Pearson, 1998, p. 242] and Bhatia [Bhatia, 1993, p. 246] have explored the pragmatic and discourse functions of specialized terms, emphasizing that terminology not only encodes concepts but also constructs professional identity. In Uzbek linguistics, significant contributions have been made by Nilufar Atayeva [Atayeva, 2020, p. 167] and Yekaterina Shirinova [Shirinova, 2020, p. 152], who have investigated the development of banking and financial terminology as a core component of trade discourse. These works highlight both the semantic and functional shifts that occur when specialized terms enter Uzbek from global economic contexts and provide a foundation for understanding the dynamics of trade-related vocabulary more broadly.

Trade terminology cannot be regarded as a single unified lexical field. It develops and operates within several specialized sublanguages, most importantly those of law, economics and finance. Each of these domains places specific demands on language and fulfills distinct communicative functions, and these factors shape both the structure and the usage of trade-related vocabulary.

In **the legal sublanguage**, trade terms are characterized by precision, stability, and resistance to change. This can be observed in English through expressions such as *contract of sale*, *arbitration clause*, or *breach of agreement*, which retain their form and meaning across decades of usage. Similarly, Uzbek legal terminology maintains strict boundaries of interpretation in terms like *savdo shartnomasi* or *kelishuv shartlari*. The conservative nature of legal trade terms arises from their role in regulating rights and obligations, where ambiguity could lead to misinterpretation and disputes. Thus, legal terminology functions as a stabilizing force in the broader system of trade vocabulary.

The economic sublanguage, by contrast, demonstrates a higher degree of openness and adaptability. Economic discourse often absorbs new terms that describe evolving processes, policies, or institutions. In English, terms such as *liberalization*, *outsourcing*, or *trade barriers* highlight the interaction between economics and international relations, while Uzbek equivalents like *liberalizatsiya* and *bozor islohotlari* reflect the influence of global market reforms on local linguistic practice. Uzbek economic terminology has been significantly shaped by the transition to a market economy, which required the adoption of new conceptual categories largely introduced through borrowings and calques.

The financial sublanguage represents perhaps the most dynamic sphere of trade terminology. Financial markets are inherently innovative, producing a constant flow of new instruments, practices, and technologies that demand corresponding lexical representation. English financial discourse, with terms like *derivatives* or *cryptocurrency*, demonstrates the creative capacity of language to name and categorize emerging phenomena. Uzbek financial terminology has responded to these changes with borrowings such as *derivativ* and *kriptovalyuta*, while also employing native resources in expressions like *moliya bozori* or *qimmatli qog'ozlar*.

A comparison of English and Uzbek trade terminology across legal, economic, and financial sublanguages reveals both points of convergence and divergence, shaped by historical experience, linguistic traditions, and the degree of integration into global markets.

One of the clearest similarities is the shared reliance on internationalisms, particularly in economic and financial discourse. Terms such as *export*, *import*, and *inflation* in English correspond directly to *eksport*, *import*, and *inflyatsiya* in Uzbek. These parallels demonstrate the impact of globalization, which has led to the international circulation of trade-related concepts and their lexical equivalents. Both languages also exhibit extensive use of **abbreviations** and **acronyms**. English employs forms like *WTO* (*World Trade Organization*) or *FTA* (*Free Trade Agreement*), while Uzbek uses *JST* (*Jahon Savdo Tashkiloti*) and *EIH* (*erkin iqtisodiy hudud*). The pragmatic motivation here is universal: to increase communicative efficiency in highly technical environments.

At the same time, differences emerge in the degree of semantic precision and lexical flexibility. English trade terminology, particularly in legal sublanguage, tends to maintain rigid conceptual boundaries. Phrases such as *consideration* or *breach of contract* carry specialized meanings that cannot be replaced by near synonyms without legal consequences. By contrast, Uzbek legal terminology, while striving for accuracy, often allows broader semantic variation. For instance, *kelishuv* may refer to both a formal agreement and a more general understanding, depending on context. This flexibility can be advantageous in oral communication but presents challenges in translation and international documentation, where exact equivalence is required.

Another significant difference lies in the strategies of lexical expansion. **English** frequently generates new terms through **compounding** and **derivation** (*countertrade*, *underpricing*), while **Uzbek** relies heavily on **borrowings** and **calques** (*qarama-qarshi savdo*, *past baholash*). Uzbek economic discourse in the post-Soviet period has shown a preference for adopting foreign lexical items rather than creating neologisms from native roots. This has resulted in a hybrid system where native and borrowed elements coexist, but with borrowings dominating in financial and technological contexts.

From an applied perspective, these similarities and differences have practical consequences for translation, lexicography, and ESP teaching. Translators must navigate the gap between English semantic rigidity and Uzbek semantic elasticity, ensuring both accuracy and cultural acceptability. Lexicographers face the task of documenting not only direct borrowings but also local adaptations, creating dictionaries that reflect the dynamic interplay between global and national terminology. In teaching ESP, educators must prepare students to understand both international trade terminology and its Uzbek equivalents, highlighting cases where direct equivalence is absent or misleading.

Overall, the comparative analysis shows that while English and Uzbek trade terminology share a common global foundation, they diverge in their semantic organization, strategies of expansion, and functional flexibility. These differences underline the necessity of contextual and interdisciplinary approaches to studying

specialized sublanguages, especially in a world where trade communication increasingly crosses linguistic boundaries.

The analysis of trade terminology across legal, economic, and financial sublanguages demonstrates that specialized vocabulary functions as a layered and stratified system rather than a uniform lexical field. The comparative perspective highlights both convergences and divergences. English and Uzbek share a common reliance on internationalisms and abbreviations, shaped by the realities of global trade communication. At the same time, English legal and financial terminology tends to display semantic rigidity and morphological creativity, whereas Uzbek terminology is characterized by semantic flexibility and a higher dependence on borrowings and calques. These patterns point to different strategies of linguistic adaptation within specialized sublanguages.

On the whole, these insights confirm that trade terminology in specialized sublanguages is a dynamic system where stability and change coexist, shaped by the dual pressures of professional communication and globalization.

References

1. Bhatia V. K. *Analysing Genre: Language Use in Professional Settings*. – London: Longman, 1993. – 246 p.
2. Cabré M. T. *Terminology: Theory, Methods and Applications*. – Amsterdam; Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing Company, 1999. – 248 p.
3. Kayumova M. Theoretical basis of learning terms in English and Uzbek languages // *European International Journal of Philological Sciences*. – 2023. – Vol. 3, № 10. – P. 9-13. <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/eijps/article/view/25631>
4. Nizomova M. B. Pedagogical terms as an object of linguistic research // *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*. – 2022. – Vol. 8, № 3. – P. 284-290. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra2013>
5. Pearson J. *Terms in Context*. – Amsterdam; Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing Company, 1998. – 242 p.
6. Атаева Н. С. Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларида банк-молия терминларининг лексик-семантик хусусиятлари: Филол. фан. бўйича PhD ... дис. – Тошкент: Ўзбекистон давлат жаҳон тиллари университети, 2020. – 167 б.
7. Ахмедов О. С. Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларида солиқ-божхона терминларининг лингвистик таҳлили ва таржима муаммолари: Филол. фан. докт. ... дис. – Тошкент: Ўзбекистон давлат жаҳон тиллари университети, 2016. – 255 б.
8. Лотте Д. С. *Основы построения научно-технической терминологии: Вопросы теории и методики*. – Москва: Издательство АН СССР, 1961. – 160 с.
9. Ширинова Е. Т. Ўзбек тили банк-молия терминологияси: Филол. фан. бўйича PhD ... дис. – Тошкент: Алишер Навоий номидаги Тошкент давлат ўзбек тили ва адабиёти университети, 2020. – 152 б.

OLMOSHLARNING NUTQ SUGGESTIVLIGINI OSHIRUVCHI VOSITA SIFATIDA QO‘LLANILISHI HAQIDA

Shahzoda Yusupova,

*Alisher Navoiy nomidagi Toshkent davlat
o‘zbek tili va adabiyoti universiteti doktoranti*

Annotatsiya. Suggestiv nutq ta’sirchanligini oshirishda olmoshlar alohida ahamiyatga ega. Mazkur maqolada suggestiv muloqotda *You, I* kabi shaxs olmoshlari, *everything, nothing* kabi noaniqlik olmoshlari psixopragmatik vosita sifatida tinglovchi ongostiga ta’sir ko’rsatishga xizmat qilishi misollar yordamida tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: suggestiya, suggestiv muloqot, olmosh, ongostiga ta’sir, psixopragmatik vosita.

Annotation. Pronouns play a special role in enhancing the effectiveness of suggestive speech. This article analyzes, with examples, how personal pronouns such as you and I, as well as indefinite pronouns such as everything and nothing, serve as psychopragmatic tools to influence the listener’s subconscious in suggestive communication.

Keywords: suggestion, suggestive communication, pronoun, subconscious influence, psychopragmatic tool.

Zamonaviy tilshunoslikda nutqiy ta’sir etish usullari turlicha tasniflanadi. Suggestiya nutqiy ta’sir usullaridan biri bo‘lib, so‘zlovchi tomonidan biror fikr, qarash, g‘oya yoxud xatti-harakatni amalga oshirish/oshirmaslik istagini verbal va noverbal vositalardan foydalangan holda tinglovchining ongostiga singdirish jarayoni sanladi, bu jarayonda retsipyentning tanqidiy baholash qobiliyati pasaygan bo‘lishi talab etiladi.

“Suggestiya” termini asli psixologiyaga tegishli bo‘lib, fanlar integratsiyalashuvi, nutqiy ta’sir va suggestiya hodisalarining ommalashuvi natijasida so‘nggi yillarda ushbu termin tilshunos olimlar tomonidan ham faol qo‘llanila boshladi. Chunki ushbu murakkab psixologik hodisa inson nutqiy faoliyati bilan bog‘liq bo‘lib, suggestiyani amalga oshirishda eng asosiy vosita til hisoblanadi: “Suggestiya psixologiyada kishini tanqidiy yondashmasdan ishonish yoki muayyan harakatni bajarishga undash jarayoni. Suggestiya, odatda, verbal ko‘rinishda bo‘ladi va vizual yoki boshqa biror sezgi organi orqali ham namoyon bo‘lishi mumkin” [www.britannica.com]. Ko‘rinadiki, suggestiya asosan verbal xarakterga ega, ya’ni suggestiv ta’sirning yuzaga chiqishida til asosiy o‘rin egallaydi. Estralingvistik vositalar esa suggestiyaning amalga oshish ehtimolini kuchaytiradi, verbal vositalarga yordamchi sifatida qo‘llanadi. Sodda va tushunarli qilib ta’riflanganda, “suggestiya deganda informatsiya tanqidiy mulohaza qilinmaydigan va “ishonch asosida” qabul qilinadigan ma’lumot berish usuli tushuniladi” [Avdeenko, 2001].

Suggestiv nutqning ongga ta’sir darajasi yuqori bo‘lishida olmoshlar o‘ziga xos o‘rin tutadi. Y.Yudanova ingliz tiliga oid siyosiy diskursda suggerendlarning

identifikatsiyasi masalasiga to'xtaladi va bunda *You, We, Our* olmoshlarining qo'llanilishi asosiy suggestiv yukni tashishini keltiradi [Yudanova, 2004: 12-14].

Suggestiv nutqda olmoshlar nafaqat grammatik birlik sifatida, balki psixolingvistik va pragmatik signal sifatida ham xizmat qiladi. Ayniqsa, gipnotik diskursda olmoshlarining tanlovi va takrorlanishi tinglovchining e'tiborini muayyan yo'nalishga qaratishda, ongostiga ta'sir o'tkazishda va kommunikativ pozitsiyani belgilashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Xususan, bunday nutqda *I – men* va *You – sen/siz* shaxs olmoshlari keng qo'llanadi.

You shaxs olmoshi gipnotik nutqda bevosita psixologik murojaat shakli bo'lib xizmat qiladi: *You have now become so deeply relaxed..., You are now so VERY DEEPLY ASLEEP..., ...everything that I tell you that is going to happen to you...* kabi.

Ko'p hollarda suggestiv nutqda *you* olmoshi doimiy ravishda markaziy nuqtada turadi va to'g'ridan-to'g'ri murojaat va ikkinchi shaxsga nisbatan buyurish orqali ta'sir qilishni ifodalaydi. Aynan *you* olmoshi yordamida so'zlovchi tinglovchini individuallashtirilgan trans holatiga olib kiradi, bu olmoshning doimiy takrorlanishi orqali tinglovchi ongiga uning shaxsi mazkur muolajada asosiy o'rin tutishi haqidagi signallar uzatiladi. *You* olmoshi orqali murojaat qilganda so'zlovchi va tinglovchi o'rtasida kuchli psixologik yaqinlik va individual ta'sir namoyon bo'ladi, natijada tinglovchi o'zini passiv qabul qiluvchi emas, balki asosiy subyekt rovida ko'radi. Suggestiv muloqotda olmoshlarining takrorlanishi esa matnning ritmik barqarorligini ta'minlaydi, psixik ta'sirni kuchaytiradi. *You* shaxs olmoshining takrorlanishi tinglovchida "shu men bilan bog'liq, bu men haqidagi gap" degan ichki tasdiqni hosil qilishga ko'maklashadi, har bir takroriy "you" orqali tinglovchi o'zini shu holatga moslashtirishga majbur bo'ladi.

I – men shaxs olmoshi esa suggestiv nutqda hokimiyatga ega, ishonchli boshqaruvchi rovida namoyon bo'ladi: *...what I say..., ...everything that I put into your mind..., ...exactly as I tell you...* kabi.

Odatda, suggestiv nutqda so'zlovchi *I* olmoshi yordamida o'zini muntazam ravishda taqdim qilib, o'zining muloqotda dominantligini, hokimiyatga egaligini ta'kidlab turadi va bu orqali so'zlovchining psixologik ishonchlilik darajasi ortadi. Bunda *I* olmoshi avtoritetlik modelini yaratishga xizmat qiladi, ya'ni tinglovchi so'zlovchi taqdim qilayotgan har qanday ko'rsatmani "yo'l-yo'riq", "haqiqat" sifatida qabul qiladi, so'zlovchining o'zini biluvchi, boshqaruvchi, foydali o'zgarishlarni ta'minlovchi shaxs sifatida namoyon qilishiga imkoniyat yaratiladi. Bu orqali tinglovchi ongostida "men bilaman, sen bajarasan", "men buyuraman, sen itoat qilasan" modeli yaratiladi va yuqori darajada suggestiv ta'sir yuzaga keladi.

Shuningdek, suggestiv muloqotda *everything – hamma narsa, nothing – hech narsa* kabi noaniqlik olmoshlari ham keng qo'llanadi: *everything that I put into your mind..., nothing will eradicate it..., everything that I tell you...* kabi. Bu olmoshlar keng qamrovli, absolyut, rad etib bo'lmaydigan haqiqatlar tasavvurini yaratadi. *Everything* olmoshi so'zlovchi bildirayotgan fikrlarning aniqligini, muqarrarligini namoyon qilish (go'yoki har bir aytilgan so'z muqarrar amalga oshadi), ta'sirning davomiyligi va o'zgarmasligini ta'kidlash uchun qo'llansa, *nothing* olmoshi

yordamida tinglovchining soʻzlovchiga nisbatan qarshiligi bloklanadi, ichki eʼtirozi susaytiriladi, hech narsa soʻzlovchi koʻrsatmalarini yoʻqqa chiqara olmasligi haqida tasavvur uygʻotiladi.

Koʻrinadiki, suggestiv matnlarda qoʻllanuvchi olmoshlar oddiy grammatik birliklar emas, balki psixologik va semantik taʼsir kuchiga ega pragmatik vositalardir. *You* va *I* (sen va men) oʻrtasidagi munosabat modelining qatʼiy belgilanishi, *everything* va *nothing* kabi absolyut birliklarning takroriy qoʻllanilishi orqali suggestiv muloqotda shaxsiylashtirilgan, avtoritar xarakterga ega va mutlaq taʼsirga ega lingvistik makon yaratiladi.

Adabiyotlar

1. <https://www.britannica.com/science/suggestion>
2. Авдеенко И. Структура и суггестивные свойства вербальных составляющих рекламного текста. Автореф.дисс.канд.филол.наук. 2001.
3. Юданова Е. Суггестивная функция языковых средств англоязычного политического дискурса. Автореф.дисс.канд.филол.наук. – Санкт-петербург, 2004. – с 12-14.

THE ROLE AND FUNCTIONS OF METAPHOR IN SCIENTIFIC DISCOURSE

Sulaymonova Mahfuza Shavkat qizi,
PhD Student (Year 1),
Alisher Navoi Tashkent State
University of Uzbek Language and Literature
E-mail: mahfuzasulaymonova15@gmail.com
ORCID iD: 0009-0003-0749-260X

Abstract. This article explores the role of metaphors in scientific discourse, focusing on their communicative function and ideological implications within academic writing. Metaphors are shown to serve not only as literary devices but also as tools for simplifying complex concepts, clarifying abstract ideas, and popularizing scientific thought. The study analyzes metaphorical expressions extracted from various scientific texts and examines their linguistic features and contextual meanings.

Keywords: *metaphor, scientific discourse, academic style, terminological metaphor, linguistic analysis.*

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается роль метафоры в научном дискурсе, её коммуникативные функции и идеологическая нагрузка в рамках научного стиля. Показано, что метафора используется не только в художественной речи, но и в научных текстах для упрощения сложных понятий, объяснения абстрактных идей и популяризации научного мышления. В ходе исследования проводится лингвистический анализ метафорических выражений, извлечённых из текстов различных научных областей.

Ключевые слова: *метафора, научный дискурс, научный стиль, терминологическая метафора, лингвистический анализ.*

Scientific discourse is often characterized by objectivity, precision, and rationality. Nevertheless, this domain also makes extensive use of the semantic and conceptual resources of language, particularly metaphors. Although metaphor is frequently regarded as a stylistic or artistic device, it also plays a crucial cognitive and epistemological role in scientific thinking. It reflects the human tendency to conceptualize abstract phenomena through concrete models. Especially in cases where new concepts are introduced, existing knowledge is simplified, or complex ideas need to be communicated intuitively, metaphor functions as an indispensable tool in scientific language.

The history of science provides numerous examples of such metaphorical modeling. For instance, the designation of electromagnetic waves as “waves” relies on their analogy to water waves. In quantum mechanics, the notion of “superposition,” which signifies the simultaneous existence of a particle in multiple states, is metaphorically explained through analogies with musical harmony or color blending. In biology, the structure of DNA is famously described as a “spiral staircase,” which allows researchers to visualize its three-dimensional configuration.[1] Physicist Richard Feynman described particle interactions as “objects talking to one another,” thereby explaining highly complex phenomena through simple semantic imagery.[2] The power of metaphor lies in its capacity to build a semantic bridge between scientific concepts and experiential perception. This bridge allows theoretical knowledge to be expressed through empirical intuition. Metaphor enables the representation of complex theoretical constructs by means of simple illustrative models. This is particularly evident in computer science and artificial intelligence. For example, computer “memory” is compared to the human brain, while “algorithm” is often described as a “manual” or “roadmap.” Artificial neural networks are themselves modeled after the structure and functioning of the human brain, representing one of the strongest metaphorical frameworks in modern science. In immunology, the human body is portrayed as a “fortress,” viruses as “enemies,” and antibodies as an “army.” Such metaphors facilitate not only the internal development of scientific knowledge but also the dissemination of complex scientific concepts to a broader audience.[3]

The role and functions of metaphor in scientific discourse are thus of fundamental importance. By drawing parallels between one domain and another, metaphor helps to generate new meanings and makes scientific argumentation more precise and accessible. Metaphor is also an integral component of scientific terminology systems. It contributes to the emergence of new terms and enriches scientific language. Conceptual metaphors such as “the body as a machine” provide clearer frameworks for understanding scientific phenomena. They are employed to explain complex and abstract processes in plain terms, enabling learners and readers to grasp scientific information more easily.

In sum, metaphor in scientific discourse not only enriches expression but also serves as a vital instrument in the development and communication of scientific knowledge. Its diverse forms and functions help to strengthen the connection between

science and culture. Metaphors play a pivotal role in making complex ideas more comprehensible and precise. In Uzbek, too, the use of metaphors in scientific texts demonstrates their significance as linguistic devices that enhance meaning by framing abstract concepts in concrete and relatable terms. Metaphor, therefore, is a linguistic tool that deepens meaning by establishing analogies between distinct domains. Within scientific discourse, it often serves to render intricate ideas into simpler and more accessible expressions. Metaphors in scientific style are often used in scientific texts to create new terms. They help enrich scientific language and provide opportunities to express concepts more precisely. For example, through the concept of “metaphorical transfer”, information can be presented in a clearer and more concise form.

Conventional and creative metaphors. In scientific discourse, more attention is generally paid to conventional metaphors. These are usually associated with common concepts and shared knowledge. However, creative metaphors are also important, as they contribute to the development of the scientific process. In the Uzbek language, metaphors are also widely employed in scientific discourse. For instance, “restoration” is a metaphor commonly used to describe economic or ecological processes, where the act of “restoring” implies renewal and development. Similarly, “modern knowledge” functions as a metaphor in which new knowledge is labeled as “modern,” thereby emphasizing its relevance and significance.

In the formation and development of scientific discourse, metaphors appear not only as linguistic devices but also as constructive elements of scientific thinking. The cognitive and epistemological characteristics of metaphors, as well as their role in knowledge creation, have been extensively studied in recent years, particularly within the fields of cognitive science, artificial intelligence, biological modeling, and physical theories. This demonstrates that metaphors serve not merely aesthetic or stylistic functions, but also play a conceptual role in the processes of scientific cognition. Metaphors serve as conceptual foundations in the creation of scientific models. For example, in biology, the term “genetic code” is borrowed from linguistics, where the notion of “code” provides a clearer understanding of the mechanism of information transfer within DNA. Likewise, metaphors such as “cell factory,” “power station,” or “database” play a crucial role in explaining complex biological and informational systems in an intuitive manner. In physics, such metaphorical modeling is also widely applied. For instance, in quantum field theory, concepts such as “vacuum fluctuations” are metaphorically described through expressions like “boiling vacuum” or “exploding possibilities.” These figurative expressions create an effective cognitive bridge for grasping fundamental scientific concepts through perception and imagination.

Furthermore, in computer science and artificial intelligence, terms such as “artificial mind,” “learning machine,” and “intelligent systems” are grounded in strong metaphorical foundations. They allow human cognition to be represented through technological models. Such metaphors also establish a conceptual basis for the development of advanced neurocomputational models, as computer technologies are often compared to the human brain. In cognitive linguistics, the Conceptual

Metaphor Theory developed by Lakoff and Johnson substantiated the central role of metaphor in thought processes. According to them, humans tend to perceive the world not only through critical or empirical analysis, but also through existing conceptual metaphors. For example, conceptual structures such as “science is a journey” or “ideas are objects” make scientific discourse more understandable and meaningful.

In addition to the aforementioned perspectives, contemporary research highlights that metaphors function as fundamental cognitive instruments in the construction of scientific knowledge. They not only provide illustrative explanations but also shape the very frameworks through which scientists conceptualize phenomena. For example, the widespread use of the “genetic code” metaphor has profoundly influenced the development of molecular biology, guiding both research questions and experimental designs. Similarly, the metaphor of the “big bang” has become central to cosmology, framing public and academic discourse about the origins of the universe. Moreover, metaphors contribute to interdisciplinary communication by allowing scientists from different fields to establish common ground. When abstract or novel ideas are articulated through familiar metaphorical schemas, they become more easily translatable across disciplinary boundaries. This process fosters innovation, as metaphors can stimulate the generation of new hypotheses and theoretical models. From a pedagogical perspective, metaphors are equally indispensable. They transform highly technical content into more relatable forms, thereby enhancing teaching effectiveness in scientific education. Students often grasp complex principles more quickly when they are mapped onto experiential or everyday domains through metaphorical reasoning.

Finally, it is important to acknowledge that metaphors, while powerful, can also impose limitations. Overextended reliance on specific metaphorical models may lead to conceptual biases or oversimplifications. Therefore, critical awareness of the strengths and constraints of metaphorical usage is necessary to maintain scientific precision while benefiting from its explanatory and communicative advantages.

Thus, metaphors in scientific discourse serve not only as a means of presenting information but also as an effective tool for helping readers comprehend and internalize complex ideas. They enable the expression of abstract concepts through concrete images, thereby expanding the cognitive scope of scientific notions. Metaphorical expressions make scientific texts more vivid and accessible while simultaneously facilitating the assimilation of new knowledge. Particularly in the fields of science and technology, the role of metaphors is invaluable in explaining complex mechanisms and theories in more comprehensible terms. Their systematic use not only enriches scientific reasoning but also broadens the dynamism and expressive capacity of scientific language. Therefore, studying metaphors as a linguistic resource that enhances the effectiveness of scientific communication, and employing them consciously, acquires crucial significance.

References

1. Watson, J. D., & Crick, F. H. C. (1953). Molecular Structure of Nucleic Acids: A Structure for Deoxyribose Nucleic Acid. *Nature*, 171(4356), 737–738.

2. Feynman, R. P. (1985). Qiziqarli fizika [The Feynman Lectures on Physics]. Moscow: Mir Publishers.
3. Gentner, D., & Jeziorski, M. (1983). The shift from metaphor to analogy in Western science. In A. (Ed.).
4. Kuhn, T. S. (1962). The Structure of Scientific Revolutions. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
5. Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980). Metaphors We Live By. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

TIL VA TAFAKKUR MUNOSABATIDA LINGVOKONSEPTUAL YONDASHUVNING O‘RNI

Imomqulov Dilmurod O‘rol o‘g‘li,
imomqulovdilmurod1004@mail.com
Guliston davlat universiteti(O‘zbekiston)

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola til va tafakkur o‘rtasidagi o‘zaro bog‘liqlikni lingvokonseptual yondashuv nuqtai nazaridan tahlil qiladi. Tadqiqotda tilning nafaqat muloqot vositasi, balki inson ongi, dunyoqarashi va madaniyatini shakllantiruvchi muhim omil ekanligi ko‘rsatilgan. Maqolada Sepir-Uorf gipotezasi, Martin Xaydeggerning falsafiy qarashlari va Lera Boroditskiyning empirik tadqiqotlari asosida tilning idrok va tafakkur jarayonlariga ta’siri o‘rganilgan. Maqolada lingvokonseptual yondashuv orqali turli xalqlar tillariga tegishli bo‘lgan konseptlar, qadriyatlar va madaniy yondashuvlar o‘rganish imkoniyati ta’kidlangan.

Kalit so‘zlar: lingvokonseptual yondashuv, til, tafakkur, konsept, madaniyat, idrok, Lera Boroditskiy, Sepir-Uorf gipotezasi.

Abstract: This article analyzes the relationship between language and thought from the perspective of the linguoconceptual approach. The study shows that language is not only a means of communication, but also an important factor shaping human consciousness, worldview and culture. The article examines the influence of language on perception and thought processes based on the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis, Martin Heidegger's philosophical views, and Lera Boroditsky's empirical research. In conclusion, it is emphasized that the linguoconceptual approach provides an opportunity to study national concepts, values and cultural codes.

Keywords: linguoconceptual approach, language, thought, concept, culture, perception, Lera Boroditsky, Sapir-Whorf hypothesis.

Til jamiyatning asrlar davomida shakllanib kelgan, uning moddiy va ma’naviy hayotini aks ettiruvchi jonli boyligidir. U nafaqat muloqot vositasi, balki jamiyat a’zolarini voqealar va bilimlar haqida xabardor qiluvchi, ularning o‘zaro aloqasini ta’minlovchi muhim institutdir. Til shaxsning dunyoqarashi, tafakkuri, madaniyati va jamiyatdagi munosabatlarini shakllantirishda hal etuvchi rol o‘ynaydi. Til orqali inson nafaqat o‘z fikrlarini ifoda etadi, balki atrofidagi dunyoni tushunish va tasniflashga ham qodir bo‘ladi. Bu borada amerikalik lingvistlar Edvard Sepir va

Benjamin Li Uorf tomonidan ilgari surilgan “lingvistik nisbiylik” (Sepir-Uorf gipotezasi) tamoyili tilning idrokidagi ahamiyatini chuqur o‘rganib, tilning inson harakatlarini shakllantirishiga e’tibor qaratadi. Xuddi shunday, nemis faylasufi Martin Xaydegger “Til – bu Borliqning uyi” degan mashhur iborasi bilan tilni nafaqat muloqot, balki o‘zligimizni va atrofimizdagi borliqni anglashning asosiy vositasi sifatida ta’kidlaydi. Demak, til insoniyat uchun kommunikativ vositadan tashqari, butun bir dunyoni idrok etish va unga ma’no izlashning muhim omilidir.

Tafakkur esa insonning atrof-muhitni bilish va anglash jarayonidagi eng muhim jihatdir. Uni O‘zbekiston Milliy ensiklopediyasida quyidagicha ta’riflaydilar: “Tafakkur deb, voqelikdagi narsa va hodisalarni ular o‘rtasidagi bog‘lanishlarni fikran, umumlashtirib, vositali yo‘l bilan aks ettirishga aytiladi” (“Tafakkur”, 2000-2006). Tafakkur insonni boshqa mavjudotlardan ajratib turadigan asosiy xususiyat bo‘lib, u til va nutq bilan chambarchas bog‘liq holda namoyon bo‘ladi.

Tilni o‘rganishning zamonaviy usullaridan biri – lingvokonseptual yondashuvdir. Ushbu yondashuvga ko‘ra, “tabiiy til va idrok o‘rtasida juda yaqin bog‘liqlik mavjud” (Solodilova & Zaxarova, 2020, 92-bet). Bu bog‘liqlikda til so‘zlovchi tomonidan idrok etilgan dunyoni aks ettiradi. Lingvistik belgilar haqiqiy dunyo obyektlariga emas, balki “ongimizda shakllanadigan, aqliy birliklar – ya’ni konseptlarga” ishora qiladi (Solodilova & Zaxarova, 2020, 92-bet). Demak, lingvistik ifodalarimizning mazmuni haqiqiy dunyoga emas, balki ongda proyeksiyalangan dunyoga bog‘liqdir (Jackendoff, 1983, Solodilova & Zaxarova, 2020). Shuning uchun turli madaniyatlarning dunyoni har xil idrok etishi ularning ong tarkibi va, albatta, tiliga ham bevosita ta’sir qiladi. Lingvokonseptual yondashuv til va undagi birliklarni birgalikda o‘rganishdir. Har bir so‘z yoki ibora muayyan ma’no anglatadi, lekin madaniy jihatdan turli xalqlar orasida aynan shu so‘z va iboralar turlicha ma’nolarni bildirishi mumkin. Misol uchun, “uy” so‘zi yashash makoni, binoni anglatishi bilan birga, ba’zi milliy madaniyatlarda oila ma’nosini ham ifodalashi mumkin. Buni o‘rganish aynan lingvokonseptual yondashuv yordamida amalga oshiriladi.

Lera Boroditskiy va uning jamoasi tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlar til va tafakkur o‘rtasidagi bog‘liqlikni eksperimental asosda isbotlashda muhim o‘rin tutadi. Tadqiqotchilar “Til fikrlashimizni qanday shakllantiradi?” degan murakkab savolga javob topishga intilishdi. Ularning kashfiyotlari shuni ko‘rsatadiki, til inson idrokining turli jihatlarida chuqur ta’sir ko‘rsatadi. Masalan, Avstraliyaning Kuuk Thaayorre xalqi tilida fazoviy orientatsiya mutlaq koordinatalar (shimol, janub, sharq, g‘arb) asosida ifodalanadi. Bu esa ularning makonni idrok qilishida qiziqarli o‘ziga xoslikni keltirib chiqaradi. Eksperimentlar davomida bu til so‘zlashuvchilari kichik fazoviy vaziyatlarni ham nisbiy (“chap”, “o‘ng”) emas, balki mutlaq yo‘nalishlar asosida eslab qolishadi. Tadqiqot davomida ishtirokchilarga yo‘nalishni aniqlash vazifasi topshirilganda, Kuuk Thaayorre tilida so‘zlashuvchilar nisbiy (“o‘ng”, “chap”) emas, balki mutlaq (“sharq”, “g‘arb”) koordinatalar asosida javob berishgan. Chronologik ketma-ketlikni aniqlashga oid topshiriqda esa, bu til so‘zlashuvchilari suratlarni keng tarqalgan usullardan emas, balki dunyo tomonlari (masalan, sharqdan g‘arbg) asosida joylashtirishgan. Taqqoslash uchun, arab tilida so‘zlashuvchilar topshiriqni bajarishda o‘ngdan chapga gorizontol joylashtirish prinsipidan

foydalanganlar, bu ularning yozuv tizimining yoʻnalishiga mos keladi. Boshqa koʻplab tillarda (masalan, ingliz yoki rus tillari) esa chapdan oʻngga joylashtirish kuzatilgan. Bu lingvistik xususiyatlarning kognitiv jarayonlarga taʼsirining aniq namoyon boʻlishidir.

Tilning inson tafakkuriga taʼsirini yanada chuqurroq tushunishda lingvokonseptual yondashuv muhim metodologik imkoniyatlarni taqdim etadi. Ushbu yondashuv tilni faqat grammatik qoidalar majmuisi sifatida emas, balki madaniy qadriyatlar, milliy dunyoqarash va konseptual tizimlarning ifodasi sifatida qaraydi. Lingvokonseptual tahlil orqali til birliklarining orqasida yotgan maʼnaviy-mafkuraviy mazmunlar, milliy xarakterdagi idrok modellari ochib beriladi. Tadqiqotlar shuni koʻrsatadiki, har bir til oʻziga xos konseptual tizimni shakllantiradi va bu tizim soʻzlashuvchilarning dunyoni idrok etish usulini belgilaydi.

Xulosa qilib aytish mumkinki, lingvokonseptual yondashuv tilshunoslikda tilni uning asosiy vazifasi – muloqotdan tashqari, inson tafakkuri va madaniyatini shakllantiruvchi muhim omil sifatida oʻrganishga yoʻnaltirilgan muhim qadam hisoblanadi. Ushbu yondashuv til birliklarining semantikasi orqasida yotgan milliy dunyoqarash, madaniy qadriyatlar va konseptual tizimlarni ochib beradi. Sepir-Uorf gipotezasi va Xaydeggerning falsafiy qarashlari kabi nazariyalar, shuningdek, Lera Boroditskiyning empirik tadqiqotlari tilning idrok va fikrlash jarayonlariga bevosita taʼsir koʻrsatishini isbotlaydi. Turli tillarda fazoviy orientatsiya va vaqtning tasviri kabi hodisalarning boshqacha talqin qilinishi, tilning tafakkurni shakllantirishdagi faol rolini aniq koʻrsatadi. Shuning uchun, til va tafakkur oʻrtasidagi murakkab munosabatni chuqurroq tushunish uchun lingvokonseptual yondashuvning interdisiplinar metodologiyasidan foydalanish zarur. Bu yoʻnalish nafaqat tilning oʻzini, balki inson ongining sirli dunyosini ochishga yordam beradi.

Adabiyotlar

1. Boroditsky, L. (2011). How language shapes thought. *Scientific American*, 304(2), 62-65.
2. Jackendoff, R. (1983). *Semantics and cognition*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
3. Solodilova, I. A., & Zaxarova, T. V. (2020). *Linguo-Cognitive Approach in Foreign Language Teaching*. *European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 92-100.
4. Tafakkur. (2000-2006). *Oʻzbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi (T-harfi)*. "Oʻzbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi" Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti.
5. Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors We Live By*. University of Chicago Press.
6. Maslova, V. A. (2001). *Lingvokulturologiya*. Moskva: Akademiya.

“DEVONU LUG‘OTIT TURK” VA “BOBURNOMA”DA KELTIRILGAN ORONIMLAR VA OROGRAFIK ATAMALAR TAVSIFI HAQIDA

Muslima RISQULOVA,

GulDU, O‘zbek tilshunosligi kafedrası,

2-bosqich magistranti

muslimariskulova@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. Maqolada XI asr tilshunos olimi Mahmud Koshg‘ariyning “Devonu lug‘otit turk” hamda XVI asr davlat arbobi va adibi Zahiriddin Muhammad Boburning “Boburnoma” asarlarida uchraydigan oronimlar (tog‘, tog‘ tizmalari va balandlik nomlari) qiyosiy tahlil qilinadi. Har ikki asardagi oronimlarning tarixiy-etimologik ildizlari, semantik xususiyatlari va madaniy ahamiyati o‘rganilgan. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko‘ra, turkiy xalqlarda oronimlar nafaqat geografik belgilash vositasi, balki etnik, siyosiy va ijtimoiy tarixni aks ettiruvchi lingvomadaniy hodisa sifatida namoyon bo‘lgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: oronim, toponim, “Devonu lug‘otit turk”, “Boburnoma”, etimologiya, tarixiy geografiya, qiyosiy tahlil.

Abstract. The article presents a comparative analysis of oronyms (names of mountains, mountain ranges and elevations) found in the works of the 11th-century linguist Mahmud Kashgari's "Devonu lug'otit turk" and the 16th-century statesman and writer Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's "Boburnoma". The historical-etymological roots, semantic features and cultural significance of oronyms in both works are studied. According to the results of the research, among the Turkic peoples, oronyms were not only a means of geographical designation, but also a linguistic and cultural phenomenon reflecting ethnic, political and social history.

Keywords: oronym, toponym, "Devonu lug'otit turk", "Boburnoma", etymology, historical geography, comparative analysis.

Kirish. Turkiy xalqlarning yozma merosida geografik nomlar alohida o‘rin tutadi. Jumladan, tog‘ va tog‘ tizmalari bilan bog‘liq oronimlar nafaqat tabiiy hududlarni belgilash, balki tarixiy voqealar, qabila joylashuvi va siyosiy chegaralarni ham ifodalagan.

XI asrda yashab ijod qilgan Mahmud Koshg‘ariy o‘zining mashhur “Devonu lug‘otit turk” asarida turkiy qabilalar yashagan hududlarni xaritalash va ularning til boyligini izohlash jarayonida qator oronimlarni qayd etadi. XVI asrda Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur yozgan “Boburnoma” esa muallifning hayoti va yurishlari davomida uchragan tog‘lar, ularning tabiati va strategik ahamiyati haqida boy ma‘lumot beradi. Ushbu maqolada ikkala manbada keltirilgan oronimlar qiyosiy tahlil qilinib, ular o‘rtasidagi semantik o‘xshashliklar va farqlar aniqlanadi.

Asosiy qism. Dunyoda hamma narsaning nomi bor. “Tog‘” deganda balandmi-pastmi, kattami-kichikmi umuman tog‘ tushuniladi. Ko‘l ham shunday umumiy atama, turdosh ot. Bunday so‘zlarni xohlagan tilga tarjima qilish mumkin. Atoqli ot esa qandaydir bir narsani, predmetni, obyektini bildiradi va odatda tarjima

qilinmasdan hamma tillarda deyarli bir xil yoziladi va talaffuz qilinadi. Masalan, *Samarqand* deganda, respublikamizdagi Zarafshon daryosi sohilida joylashgan go‘zal tarixiy shahar tushuniladi. *Buxoro* deyish bilan O‘zbekistonning ko‘hna shahri, shu nomli viloyat markazi ko‘z o‘ngimizda namoyon bo‘ladi [3,18].

Bir joyni ikkinchisidan, bir jilg‘ani boshqa bir jilg‘adan, bir ko‘chani yonidagi ko‘chadan, tog‘-adirlarni, shahar va qishloqlarni bir-birlaridan farq qilish uchun ham kishilar nomlar o‘ylab chiqargan. Joy nomlari, geografik nomlar yoki toponimlar deb ataladi. Toponimlarni toponimika fani o‘rganadi [3,5].

“Turkologiyaning to‘ng‘ich asari” hisoblanmish “Devonu lug‘otit turk” O‘rta asrlarda yaratilgan barcha tarixiy, geografik va shu bilan birga lingvistik asarlar orasida toponimika fani uchun hozir ham o‘z ahamiyatini yo‘qotmagan.

“Devonu lug‘otit turk” va toponimika so‘zlarini yonma-yon qo‘yarkanmiz, ushbu asarda fanning katta qismi uchun asos bo‘la oladigan bir qancha toponim turlarini yodga olamiz. Oronimlar shulardan biri hisoblanadi.

Oronimiya (yunoncha **oros** — tog‘, onoma — nom) yer yuzasining relef shakllari tog‘lar, cho‘qqilar, qirlar, daralar, tekisliklar, jarlar nomlari[3,17].

Toponimlarning boshqa turlariga qaraganda oronimlar eng kam o‘rganilgan sohadir.

Tog‘ buyuklik, mangulik ramzi. Inson panoh, sihat, yemish istab doimo tog‘ga intilgan. Insoniyatning yarmidan ko‘pi tog‘ etaklarida va tog‘ oldi tekisliklarida yashaydi. Tog‘lar yer osti qazilmalarigina emas, leksik boyliklar koni hamdir. Tog‘ nomlari oronimlar, oronimlarni hosil qilgan va o‘r-qir re‘lef shakllarini bildiradigan so‘zlar esa *oronimik atamalar* deyiladi [3,69].

“Devon”da quyidagi tog‘ bilan bog‘liq terminlar keladi:

Aziz tag‘ - baland tog‘ yoki oshib o‘tish mumkin bo‘lmagan tog‘[3,88].

Boldir tog‘ - tog‘ burniga o‘xshash ko‘tarilib chiqqan narsa, tog‘ boldiri - tog‘ burni [3,425]. Surxondaryo viloyati Amudaryo bo‘yidagi Boldir nomli joy ham Ko‘hitang tog‘larining bir uchi, burni bo‘lganligidan shunday atalsa kerak.

Qurum - qoya. Qurunlig‘ tosh - toshli tog‘[3,458]. Ya‘ni tog‘ tepalaridan qulab, sinib tushgan, ustma-ust qalashib qolgan katta-katta qoya toshlar qurum deb ataladi. Osiyo markazidagi Qoraqurum tog‘lari, Pomirdagi Qurumdi dovoni va boshqa shu so‘zli joylar - siniq qoyatoshli, qoramtir, bedaraxt, xunuk tog‘lardir.

Ort so‘zi aslida orqa, bo‘yin, gardon, tog‘ tepasi ma‘nolaridadir. Joyga nisbatan ort - dovon bo‘ladi. O‘rta Osiyoda “ort” so‘zi bilan ishlatiladigan toponimlar anchagina: Badalort, Ko‘kort, Muzort, Oqort, To‘rug‘ort, Qizilort, Qoraort kabi. Hatto “Devon”da bir maqol ham keltirilgan: “Yalqovga eshik ham ort bo‘lur”[1,78]. - Yalqov odamga eshik ostonasi ham tog‘ tepasidek ko‘rinadi.

Shuningdek, ungur - g‘or, sekrik - tog‘dagi jarlik va daralardan sakrab o‘tiladigan joy, sert - kichikroq tepalardir.

Tog‘ daralarining eng tor joyi hamma tillarda “Temir darvoza” deyiladi (tojikchada Temur Qapug‘). Oddiy xalq buni bu yerda “temir darvoza bo‘lgan ekan” deb tushunadi. Aslida bu majoziy o‘xshatma, metaforik nomlar [3,37].

Ushbu fikrlarimizni “Boburnoma” bilan bog‘lagan holda davom ettiramiz. Ma‘lumki, “Boburnoma”da faqat siyosiy-ijtimoiy tarix emas, balki tabiat, geografiya,

toponimlar (tog‘, daryo, shahar va b.), o‘simlik va hayvonot olami, xalq urf-odatlarini haqida ham qimmatli ma‘lumotlar bor. Biz aynan oronimlar bilan bog‘liq qismiga alohida e‘tiborimizni qaratdik. Asarda mingdan ortiq toponimlar mavjud bo‘lsa, shundan ikki yuzga yaqini oronimlardir. Bunda tog‘, yaylov, dara, kechik, dasht, sayxonlik, tepalik, tog‘ yo‘llari nomlari bor.

“Boburnoma” asarida oronimlar bilan bog‘liq keltirilgan atamalar quyidagilar: ko‘hpoya (tog‘ etagi), pushta (tepalik), jar, yayloq (yozgi qo‘nish joyi), tuz (tekislik), tangi (tor dara), ko‘xpoya (tog‘ etagi), uchma (tik yonbag‘ir), dobon (dovon), ko‘tal (dovon, oshuv), band (dovon, tog‘ yo‘li), dara, parcha tog‘, o‘lang (o‘tloq, ko‘kalamzor), sumj (g‘or), tog‘ kamari, chig‘ir (chiyir, tor yo‘l), dasht, sahro, biyobon, balandi (tepalik), ushoq tog‘lar[3,11].

Kandirlik, Obburdon, Hubyon, Shibartu, Bodomchashma dovonlari, Kamrud, Ilono‘tdi, Sanjid, Dehi Ya‘qub daralari, Lamg‘on, Bomiyon, Kutur, Gabrak, Fon, Shohi Kobul, Xoja Xovand, Xaybar tog‘lari kabi nomlar asarda o‘rin olgan.

Oqtog‘, Bobotog‘, Qoratog‘, Qorachatog‘, Oyqor, Chimqor, Olatog‘, Zarmas, Sarimas, Boysun, Nurota, Ko‘hitang (Ko‘ytan), G‘o‘bdin, Shertog‘, Bo‘kantog‘ O‘zbekistonning turli hududlaridagi tog‘larning nomlaridir. Bu nomlar tarkibidagi tog‘, mas (mast), sun (sin), nura, ko‘h, g‘o‘b (azalda kaufa), sher/shir/jir so‘zlari o‘zaro ma‘nodosh. Barchasi tog‘ ma‘nosidagi hozirgi va qadimiy so‘zlardir. Tog‘, nura, sun so‘zlari sof o‘zbekcha so‘zlardir. Ko‘h, mas, g‘o‘b, sher so‘zlari esa qadimgi so‘g‘d va hozirgi fors-tojik tillariga mansub. Tog‘ nomlarining birinchi yo ikkinchi qismidagi so‘z tog‘ning hajm belgisini bildiruvchi ma‘nolardir. “Ola” so‘zining qadimiy shakli - ulug‘. “Boy” so‘zi tog‘ nomlari tarkibida muqaddas, ulug‘, katta ma‘nosiga ega. Tog‘ga sig‘inish, tog‘ kulti asosida ulkan tog‘lar nomlangan. Tog‘larni qadimda tabiatning buyuk mo‘jizasi deb hisoblashgan. Boldir, Bo‘ynoq, Mo‘ynoq, Tumshuq nomlari shu shakldagi geografik termin asosida yuzaga kelgan. Bu uch nom bir xil ma‘noga ega [4].

Oronimlar leksikasida geografik atamalar katta o‘rin tutadi. *Oq, qora, sari(q), qo‘ng‘ir* simbolikasi ham keng tarqalgan [3,68]. Bunga Mahmud Koshg‘ariy “Devon”idan *Qara jalg‘a*(jarlik), *Qizil*(vodiy) nomlarini va “Boburnoma”dan *Oqqapchig‘ay*(yaylov), *Olatog‘*(tog‘), *Qorategin*(tog‘ yo‘li), *Oqko‘tal*(tog‘) nomlarini misol qilib keltirishimiz mumkin.

Bundan tashqari o‘simlik va hayvon nomlari, etnonimlardan ham oronimlar tashkil topadi. Masalan, “Boburnoma”da “Mevag‘ul”(Mo‘g‘ul) tog‘i keltiriladi. Bu tog‘ Andijon va uning atrofi, ya‘ni Farg‘ona vodiysining sharqiy qismida joylashgan tog‘ tizmasiga taalluqli. Bobur o‘zining yoshlik yillarida bu tog‘larda sayr qilganini, ov qilganini yozib o‘tadi. Hozirgi kunda O‘zbekiston va Qirg‘iziston chegarasi yaqinidagi tog‘ tizimi bilan bog‘liq deb tahmin qilinadi. O‘sha davrda bu tog‘lar ko‘plab mo‘g‘ul qabilalari yashagan yoki yurish qilgan hududlarga yaqin bo‘lgan. Shu bois, “Mo‘g‘ul” nomi berilgan bo‘lishi mumkin. O‘simlik va hayvon nomlaridan: Archakent yo‘li, Ilon o‘tdi (dara), Uqobayn (qoya)larni misol qilib keltirishimiz mumkin. Uqobayn - “uqob” - burgut, yirtqich qush, “ayn” - ikkilik (qo‘shimcha) ma‘nosini beradi, ya‘ni “ikki burgut”. bu nom tabiat manzarasi yoki qushlar bilan bog‘liq holda paydo bo‘lgan.

Badalart, Buqachart, Zanbiat, Qavaqart, Yafg‘uart kabi dovonlar etimologiyasiga “Devon”ning o‘zidan javob topish mumkin [3,301].

Badalart – O‘sh(hozirgi Qirg‘iziston) bilan Barsag‘an (ya‘ni Barskoon) orasidagi o‘tish qiyin bo‘lgan bir cho‘qqi [1,373].

Buqachart – o‘tish qiyin bo‘lgan bir yo‘l [1,389].

J(Y)afg‘u art - Yafg‘uga yaqin bir tepalik [1,39].

Xulosa.

Koshg‘ariy – oronimlarni lug‘aviy-ensiklopedik tarzda keltirgan. U asosan turkiy xalqlarning yashash joylariga oid etnotoponim va oronimlarni qayd etadi.

Bobur – oronimlarni geografik-ilmiy va adabiy uslubda tasvirlaydi. Unda aniq tog‘ tizmalari, dovonlar va ularning tabiiy tavsifi mavjud.

XI asrdan XVI asrga kelib, turkiy orografik terminologiyada forsiy va arabiy atamalar ko‘plab qo‘llanila boshlagan (“dara”, “bel”, “cho‘qqi” kabi).

Adabiyotlar

1. Koshg‘ariy M. Devonu lug‘otit turk. – Toshkent, 1961-1963.

2. Hasanov H., “Mahmud Koshg‘ariy”. – Toshkent: O‘zfanakademnashr, 1963.

3. Qorayev S. Toponimika. – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashriyoti, 2006.

4. Nafasov T., Nafasova V. O‘zbek tili toponimlarining o‘quv izohli lug‘ati. – Toshkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2007

Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur. Boburnoma. – Toshkent: “O‘qituvchi” nashriyot-matbaa ijodiy uyi, 2017.

INFORMATIKA VA TEXNOLOGIYA ASOSLARI FANI TERMINLARI XUSUSIDA

**Abduvaliyeva Ra‘no,
GulDU magistranti**

Annotatsiya. Maqolada Informatika va texnologiya asoslari fani terminlarining terminologik tizimda tutgan o‘rni haqida fikr yuritiladi. Informatika fanini o‘qitishda internet terminlarining lisoniy xususiyatlarini bilish, terminlar anglatgan tushanchalarni o‘zlashtirishga yordam berishi internet terminlari tizimi amali bilan dalillanadi. 5-sinf o‘quvchilari uchun yozilgan Informatika va texnologiya asoslari fani terminlari maqolaning illyustrativ material sifatida xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: internet, manzil paneli, qidiruv tizimi, indeks, reference, plagiat, havola, bulutli xotira, forward, reply, drafts, email.

Annotation. The article discusses the role of terms from the subject *Fundamentals of Informatics and Technology* within a terminological system. It argues that understanding the linguistic features of internet-related terms in teaching informatics helps students grasp the concepts represented by these terms. This is substantiated through the practical application of the system of internet terminology.

The terms from the *Fundamentals of Informatics and Technology* textbook written for 5th-grade students serve as illustrative material for the article.

Keywords: internet, address bar, search engine, index, reference, plagiarism, link, cloud storage, forward, reply, drafts, email.

XX asrning 60-yillaridan informatika atamasi ishlatila boshlangan. Mazkur atama fransuzcha “informatique” (axborot) va “automatique” (avtomatik) soʻzlaridan kelib chiqqan. Keyinchalik informatika mustaqil fan sifatida rivojlana boshladi, bunga AQSH va Yevropada kompyuter texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi sabab boʻldi. 1895-yildan (Bryusselda xalqaro bibliografiya instituti tashkil qilingan sanadan boshlab) informatika ilmiy fan sifatida rasman shakllandi. Informatika termini oʻrniga XX asrning 60-yillarigacha “hujjatnomalar”, “hujjatnoma va informatsiya” termini ishlatilib kelingan.

Oʻzbekistonda ham informatika masalalariga katta eʼtibor berildi. Masalan, 1993-yilda informatsiyalashtirish toʻgʻrisidagi qonun qabul qilindi, 1994-yil Oʻzbekiston hukumati turli xil konsepsiyalar qabul qildi. Bu fanning taraqqiy etishiga asosiy sabablardan yana biri, kompyuterlar tarmogʻi va u bilan bogʻliq ravishda internet tizimining rivojlanishi. Umuman, informatikaning, xususan, Informatika kommunikatsiya tizimining yana-da taraqqiy etishiga sabab boʻldi. Demak, informatika va internet terminlari bir-biri bilan uzviy bogʻliq. Shuni inobatga olgan holda, mazkur maqolamizda aynan 5-sinf informatika va texnologiya asoslari darsligidagi internet terminlarining izohlanishi va ular haqida maʼlumotla beriladi.

Butunjahon internet tarmogʻi (WWW) – internet orqali kirish mumkin boʻlgan veb-sahifalar toʻplami [Informatika, 2021, 91]. Butunjahon internet tarmogʻida (WWW) axborot qidirish uchun sizga 2 ta dasturiy vosita kerak boʻladi: veb-brauzer va qidiruv tizimi. Qidiruv tizimidan samarali foydalana olish va kerakli maʼlumot uchun eng yaxshi qidiruv natijalarini tanlay bilish juda muhim koʻnikmadir.

Veb-brauzer – veb-sahifalarni tarjima qiluvchi va ochib koʻrsatuvchi dastur.

Veb-brauzer – butunjahon internet tarmogʻida joylashgan veb-sahifalarni koʻrsatuvchi dasturiy taʼminot. Veb-sahifalar internetga gipermatnli belgilash tili (HTML) kabi kompyuter tilida yuboriladi. Veb-brauzer uni biz oʻqiy oladigan tilga tarjima qilib beradi. Mashhur veb-brauzerlarga quyidagilar kiradi:

- Google Chrome
- Safari
- Microsoft Edge
- Firefox.

Har bir veb-brauzerda foydalanish mumkin boʻlgan toʻrtta asosiy qism bor. Ular quyidagilar:

- Manzil paneli
- Oldinga tugmasi
- Ortga tugmasi
- Yangilash tugmasi. [Informatika, 2021, 93].

Veb-manzil ayrim vaqtlarda *URL (Universal Resource Locator)* deb ham ataladi. *Ortga* tugmasi qaytish lozim boʻlgan har qanday *veb-sahifaga* oʻtish imkonini

beradi. Veb-sahifaga qaytish uchun *Ortga* tugmasidan foydalangan bo'lsak, *Oldinga* tugmasi bilan hozirgina kirgan veb-sahifamizga o'tish mumkin. *Yangilash* tugmasi sahifani qayta yuklash imkonini beradi. Sahifa to'liq yuklanmay qolganida foyda beradi. Saytda o'zgargan va yangilangan ma'lumot bo'lsa ham, ushbu tugmadan foydalanish kerak. Yangilash tugmasidan foydalanganda, u biz joylashgan veb-sahifani qayta yuklaydi va yangilanganini ko'rsatadi. [Informatika, 2021, 94].

Manzil paneli – biz kirishni xohlagan veb-sayt manzili yoziladigan maydon. Har bir veb-saytning o'z takrorlanmaydigan nomi bor. Masalan: *NASA* uchun veb manzil: www.nasa.gov. Uni “www” deb yozmasdan (yozishga oson bo'lishi uchun) qisqartirish mumkin. [Informatika, 2021, 94].

Qidiruv tizimi – ma'lumotlar bazasi yoki internet tarmog'idan ma'lumot topish uchun foydalaniladigan xizmat. *Qidiruv natijalari*: qidiruv tizimi tomonidan topilgan sahifalarga havolalar ro'yxati [Informatika, 2021, 91]. Qidiruv tizimlari butunjahon internet tarmog'idan (WWW) ma'lumotlarni qidirish imkonini beradi. Ko'plab qidiruv tizimlari bor: *Google, Bing, DuckDuckGo, Yahoo, Kiddle* www.uz kabilardan foydalanishimiz mumkin. Qidiruv tizimlari kitoblarga o'xshaydi, faqat ulardan ma'lumotning hajmi jihatidan ancha kattaroq bo'ladi. Kitobning oxirini ochsangiz, odatda u yerda indeksni topasiz. Kitobdagi aniq ma'lumotni topishni istasangiz, indeksdan ma'lumot olish uchun sahifa raqamini topasiz. Shundan keyin kitobning kerakli sahifasiga o'tishingiz mumkin. Ko'pgina qidiruv tizimlarida qidiruv satri mavjud bo'lib, qidiruvni boshlash uchun ushbu qatorga matnni kiritishingiz mumkin. *Butunjahon internet tarmog'ida* mavjud bo'lgan barcha veb-saytlar ma'lumotlar bazasida joylashadi. Qidiruv tizimi kerakli ma'lumotni topish uchun ma'lumotlar bazasidan foydalanadi. [Informatika, 2021, 95].

Indeks – odatda alifbo tartibida joylashadigan kalit so'zlar yoki mavzular ro'yxati.

Ma'lumotlar bazasi – oson qidirish va foydalanish uchun tartibga solingan ma'lumotlar to'plami.

Elektron xavfsizlik – internetdan foydalanayotganda xavfsiz bo'lish.

Reload – avval kirilgan veb sahifani qayta ochish.

Load – veb-sayt yoki veb-saytdagi sahifani ochish.

Havola – bu raqamli sahifadagi element bo'lib, uni tanlab, ochishimiz mumkin.

Butunjahon internet tarmog'idan (WWW) topgan ma'lumotlarimizdan ishimizda foydalanganimizda, ularning qayerdan olinganini ko'rsatib o'tish juda muhimdir. *Bu reference* (manbaga havola) deyiladi. Bunday qilmasak, biz plagiatda (ko'chirmachilkda) ayblanishimiz mumkin. Buning eng yaxshi usuli – ishimizga bibliografiya (foydalanilgan manbalar ro'yxati) qo'shish. Bibliografiyadagi har bir manbada quyidagilar bo'lishi kerak:

- sayt manzili;
- sayt muallifi (bu axborot mavjud bo'lsa);
- ma'lumotlarni olish uchun biz saytga kirgan sana va vaqt.

Reference – hujjat yaratishda foydalanilgan manbani aniqlash va uni manbalar ro'yxatida keltirish.

Plagiat – birovning hujjatlaridan havola keltirmasdan nusxa ko‘chirish.

Bibliografiya – ishimizda foydalanilgan manbalar ro‘yxati.

Email – bu elektron pochta bildiradi. Akkauntimiz orqali biz insonlardan elektron xabarlarni qabul qilishimiz va ularga javob qaytarishimiz mumkin. [Informatika, 2021, 91-107].

Email provayderi – bizga email manzilimiz bo‘lish imkonini beruvchi kompaniya.

Email manzili – bizning betakror elektron pochta manzilimiz, odamlar bizga xabar yuborganini bilish uchun foydalanamiz. Insonlar manzildan foydalanib xat yuboradilar.

Elektron xavfsizlik – internetdan, shuningdek, elektron pochtdan foydalanayotganda xavfsiz qolish.

Ulanish – barcha elektron pochta xabarlari internetga kiriladigan kompyuterda saqlanadi. Email manzilimizga kirganimizda, bu kompyuterga xabar yuboramiz (unga ulanamiz).

Ilova fayllar – email bilan birga yuborilgan hujjat (yoki fayl). Nusxasi (cc): Nusxa qismidagi email manzillarga yuborilgan xat nusxasi. Nusxasini olganlarning barchasi xatni ko‘radi.

Compose – yangi xat yozish uchun kerakli buyruq. Masalan, “Xat yozish” yangi elektron xat yozishni bildiradi.

Onlayn yuborish – email akkauntimizga ulanganlik va xatning to‘g‘ridan to‘g‘ri yuborilishi.

Outbox – send tugmasini bosganimizdan keyin provayderimiz yuborguniga qadar xatlar saqlanadigan papka.

Oflayn yuborish – email akkauntimizga ulanmagan holda xat yozish va uni yuborish jarayoni.

Address book – email akkauntimizdagi biz bilgan insonlarning email manzillari saqlangan joy.

Inbox – bizga kelgan xabarlar joylashadigan email akkauntimizdagi papka. Ularni keyinroq o‘qishingiz mumkin.

Receive – biror ma’lumotni qabul qilish, Inbox papkasiga biror kishidan xat kelsa, uni qabul qilish.

Reply – bizga kelgan va uni yuborgan odamga qaytarib yuborilgan xat. Ular yuborgan xatga odatda “Reply” tugmasi qo‘shiladi. Xatlarga javob yozganimizda mavzu satriga qo‘shilgan “Re” so‘zi lotin tilidan kirib kelgan. Bu “aloqasi bor” ma’nosini anglatadi.

Sent mail – email akkauntimizdagi boshqa odamlarga yuborilgan barcha xatlar saqlangan papka.

Drafts – yuborishdan oldin saqlangan xatning qoralama shakli. Uni keyinroq tahrirlash mumkin.

Forward – elektron xatni qabul qilib, keyin o‘sha xatni bir yoki bir nechta odamga yuborish.

Bulutli xotira (Cloud storage) – ma’lumotlarni internet saqlashga yordam beradigan zaxira va saqlash xizmati. Bulutli xotiraning afzalligi shundaki,

foydalanuvchi internet saqlangan fayllarga ixtiyoriy vaqtda, ixtiyoriy joydan, ixtiyoriy qurilma orqali kira oladi.

Cyberbullying – internetdagi ta’qiblarning bir turi. Bunga noo‘rin yoki noma’qul narsalar, elektron pochta yoki xabarlarini yuborish kiradi. [Informatika, 2021, 107-130].

E-safety – internetdan foydalanish jarayonida xavfsizlikni saqlash.)

Foydalanuvchi akkaunti (User account) – kompyuter foydalanuvchi nomi, parol va boshqa ma’lumotlarni saqlash uchun ishlatiladigan tarmoq serveridagi joy. Masalan, bizning internet yoki elektron pochta akkauntimiz. [Informatika, 2021, 130-135].

Xulosa o‘rnida shuni alohida ta’kidlash lozimki, har qanday fanni o‘zlashtirishda o‘sha fanning tushunchalarini anglatuvchi terminlar mazmun mohiyatini o‘zlashtirmay turib bu fanni ham o‘zlashtirib bo‘lmaydi. Internet terminlarining asosiy qismi o‘zlashma bo‘lganligini inobatga olsak bu masala yanada oydinllashadi.

Adabiyotlar

1. 5-sinf informatika va axborot texnologiyalari. – Toshkent –2021-yil. (Asl nashr © Cambridge University Press 2019. Ushbu nashr © Cambridge University Press 2021, RTI tomonidan litsenziya asosida tahrirlangan).

2. “Informatika”, O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi (I-harfi). – Toshkent: “O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi” Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2000-2006-yillar.

3. <https://maktab.uz>

4. <https://info-dars.uz>

5. <httpz://uz.wikipedia.org>

PSIXOLOGIK TERMINLAR O‘ZBEK MILLIY TERMINOLOGIYASINING E‘TIBOR MARKAZIDA

Shukurulloyev Sunnatullo Baxrom o‘g‘li,
Guliston davlat universiteti tayanch doktoranti

sunnat.baxromjonov@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-7597-2076>

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada o‘zbek milliy terminologiyasining amaliy masalalari psixologik terminlar misolida ko‘rib chiqiladi. Asosiy e‘tibor terminlarni standartlashtirish zarurati, milliy va o‘zlashgan atamalar uyg‘unligi, tarjima jarayonidagi muammolar hamda ularning ta’lim va amaliyotda qo‘llanilishiga qaratilgan. Shuningdek, ingliz va o‘zbek tillaridagi psixologik terminlarning o‘zaro taqqoslanishi orqali milliy terminologiyani rivojlantirish istiqbollari yoritiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: psixologik terminlar, milliy terminologiya, standartlashtirish, tarjima, amaliyot.

Abstract: This article examines the practical issues of Uzbek national terminology through the example of psychological terms. The main focus is on the

need for standardization of terms, the harmony between native and borrowed terminology, translation challenges, and their application in education and practice. Furthermore, by comparing psychological terms in English and Uzbek, the paper highlights the prospects for the development of national terminology.

Keywords: psychological terms, national terminology, standardization, translation, practice.

Kirish

O‘zbek tilining milliy terminologiyasi mustaqillik yillarida sezilarli darajada rivojlanib, ko‘plab fan sohaslarida o‘z tizimiga ega bo‘la boshladi. Ayniqsa, psixologiya sohasida xalqaro hamkorlik, ilmiy adabiyotlarning tarjima qilinishi va fan taraqqiyoti natijasida yangi terminlar keng qo‘llanmoqda. Shu bilan birga, terminlarni qo‘llashda va ularni ilmiy muomalaga kiritishda qator amaliy muammolar ham yuzaga kelmoqda. Ushbu maqolada ana shu masalalarga psixologik terminlar misolida to‘xtalib o‘tiladi.

1. Terminlarni standartlashtirish zarurati

O‘zbek tilida psixologik terminlarning yagona standart asosida qo‘llanilmasligi ilmiy muloqotda chalkashliklarga sabab bo‘lmoqda. Masalan, ingliz tilidagi **“motivation”** termini ba‘zi manbalarda **“motivatsiya”**, boshqalarida esa **“rag‘bat”** tarzida qo‘llanadi. Bunday tafovutlar ilmiy izchillikka salbiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi va yagona terminologik lug‘at yaratish zaruratini yuzaga keltiradi.

2. Milliy va o‘zlashgan terminlar uyg‘unligi

Psixologiya faniga oid terminlarning katta qismi rus va Yevropa tillaridan o‘zlashtirilgan. Masalan, **psixika, refleks, emotsiya** kabi terminlar ilmiy adabiyotlarda keng qo‘llanadi. Shu bilan birga, o‘zbek tilining ichki imkoniyatlari asosida yaratilgan **hissiyot, idrok, xotira** kabi so‘zlar ham psixologik atamalar sifatida mustahkam o‘rin egallagan. Ushbu ikki qatlamning uyg‘unligi milliy terminologiyaning boyishi va yanada takomillashishiga xizmat qiladi.

3. Tarjima jarayonidagi muammolar

Ilmiy adabiyotlarni o‘zbek tiliga tarjima qilishda terminlarning ma‘no jihatdan mos kelmasligi muammosi tez-tez uchraydi. Masalan, ingliz tilidagi **“counseling”** termini ko‘pincha **“maslahat berish”** deb tarjima qilinadi. Aslida esa u maxsus psixologik yordam, professional maslahatlashuv jarayonini anglatadi. Shu bois, psixologik atamalarni tarjima qilishda nafaqat lingvistik, balki ilmiy-mazmuniy yondashuv ham zarur.

4. Ta‘lim va amaliyotda qo‘llanish masalasi

Oliy ta‘lim jarayonida psixologik terminlarning yagona tizim asosida qo‘llanilishi muhim ahamiyatga ega. Turli manbalarda bir xil atamaning turlicha qo‘llanishi talabalar orasida chalkashlikka sabab bo‘ladi, mutaxassislar faoliyatida esa ilmiy muloqotga to‘sqinlik qiladi. Shu sababli, psixologik terminlarni yagona standart asosida o‘qitish va amaliyotda qo‘llash zarur.

O‘zbek milliy terminologiyasining amaliy masalalari, xususan, psixologik terminlar sohasida quyidagi jihatlar bilan bog‘liqdir:

1. Terminlarni standartlashtirish va yagona tizimga keltirish;
2. Milliy va o‘zlashgan terminlarning uyg‘unligini ta‘minlash;

3. Tarjima jarayonida semantik aniqlikka erishish;

4. Ta'lim va amaliyotda yagona terminologik yondashuvni qo'llash.

Mazkur masalalarni hal etish o'zbek tilining ilmiy salohiyatini oshiradi, psixologiya fanining milliy asoslarda rivojlanishiga xizmat qiladi va xalqaro ilmiy muloqotda samarali ishtirok etish imkonini beradi.

Adabiyotlar

1. Jo'rayev, M. (2019). *O'zbek tilida ilmiy terminologiya muammolari*. Toshkent: Fan nashriyoti.

2. Ayaqulov N.A., & Shukurulloyev S.B., (2024). Terminology indicating relationships with investors: A study of hypernymic and hyponymic relationships. "Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development" 28(6), 93-99.

3. Xolmatov, A. (2020). *Psixologiya fanida terminlarning qo'llanilishi va tarjima masalalari*. Toshkent: Universitet nashriyoti.

4. Vohidov, Sh. (2018). *Milliy terminologiya va uning rivojlanish istiqbollari*. Samarqand: SamDU matbuoti.

5. Crystal, D. (2003). *A Dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics*. Oxford: Blackwell Publishing.

6. Ayaqulov, N. A., & Shukurulloyev, S. B. (2024). On the terminology of linguocultural conceptology. *Til va adabiyot.uz*, 14(9), 19–22.

7. American Psychological Association (2020). *APA Dictionary of Psychology*. Washington, DC: APA.

8. Karimova, Z. (2021). "Psixologik terminlarning milliy va o'zlashgan qatlamlari." *Filologiya masalalari*, №2, 45–52-betlar.

9. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi Atamashunoslik qo'mitasi materiallari (2022).

ÖZBEK VE TÜRK ATASÖZLERİNDE ZITLIKLAR

Prof. Dr. Birsal ORUÇ ASLAN,

Balıkesir Üniversitesi Necatibey Eğitim Fakültesi

Türkçe ve Sosyal Bilimler Eğitimi Bölümü

Türk Dili ve Edebiyatı Eğitimi Anabilim Dalı,

birsal_oruc@hotmail.com

Özet

Atasözleri bir milletin, bir toplumun hafızasıdır. Toplumun kültürüne göre şekillenen atasözleri, söyleyeni unutulmuş, yüzyıllar içinde halka mal olmuş özlü sözlerdir ve halkın yaşam tecrübeleri sonucunda oluşmuştur. Ders verici veya ders çıkarıcı özelliğe sahip olan atasözleri toplumlarda ortak olabileceği gibi farklı da olabilir. Hatta aynı toplum içinde dahi farklı zamanlarda, farklı tecrübeler sonucunda ortaya çıkmış atasözleri arasında zıtlıklar da görülebilir. Bu bildiride ortak anadile sahip olan Özbek ve Türk atasözlerinde anlamsal zıtlıklar ele alınmış, bunların sebepleri ortaya konmaya çalışılmıştır. Yöntem olarak veri toplama yöntemi kullanılmış ve elde edilen atasözleri analiz edilerek zıtlıklar tespit edilmiştir.

Toplumun kültürel aynası olan ve toplum yapısında önemli bir rolü bulunan; o toplumun fertleri arasında tecrübe, yaşayış ve mental farklılıkların sonucunda birbirine zıtlık teşkil eden atasözlerinin tespitinin toplumdilbilimi açısından da önemi büyüktür.

Anahtar Kelimeler: atasözü, anlam, Özbek, Türk, zıtlık

Abstract

Proverbs are the memory of a nation and a society. Shaped by a society's culture, proverbs are aphorisms whose origins remain unknown and have become public knowledge over centuries, resulting from the people's life experiences. Proverbs that teach a lesson or draw lessons can be common or diverse across societies. Even within the same society, contrasts can occur between proverbs that emerged at different times and as a result of different experiences. This paper examines semantic contrasts in Uzbek and Turkish proverbs, which share a common mother tongue, and attempts to reveal their causes. Data collection was used as a method, and the resulting proverbs were analyzed to identify contrasts. Proverbs are a cultural mirror of a society and play a significant role in its structure. Identifying contrasting proverbs, resulting from differences in experience, lifestyle, and mentality among members of that society, is also crucial for sociolinguistics.

Keywords: proverb, meaning, Uzbek, Turkish, contrast

Резюме

Пословицы – это память нации и общества. Сформированные культурой общества, пословицы – это афоризмы, происхождение которых остаётся неизвестным, но которые стали достоянием общественности на протяжении веков, являясь результатом жизненного опыта людей. Пословицы, которые учат или извлекают уроки, могут быть общими или разными в разных обществах. Даже внутри одного общества могут возникать контрасты между пословицами, возникшими в разное время и в результате разного опыта. В данной статье рассматриваются семантические контрасты в узбекских и турецких пословицах, имеющих общий родной язык, и делается попытка выявить их причины. В качестве метода использовался сбор данных, а полученные пословицы анализировались для выявления контрастов. Пословицы являются культурным зеркалом общества и играют важную роль в его структуре. Выявление контрастных пословиц, обусловленных различиями в опыте, образе жизни и менталитете членов этого общества, также имеет решающее значение для социолингвистики.

Ключевые Слова: пословица, значение, узбекский, турецкий, контраст

Giriş

Atasözleri ne zaman, kim tarafından söylendiği bilinmeyen fakat toplumun fikrî, kültürel yapısını yansıtan, kuşaktan kuşağa aktarılarak günümüze gelen, çeşitli tecrübeler sonucunda söylendiği anlaşılan, genellikle öğüt veren özlü sözlerdir. Atasözü, Güncel Türkçe Sözlük'te "Uzun deneme ve gözlemlere dayanılarak

söylenmiş ve halka mal olmuş, öğüt verici nitelikte söz, deme, sav, darbimesel” olarak tanımlanmaktadır (URL 1). Atasözlerinin özelliklerine göre araştırmacılar tarafından çeşitli tanımları yapılmıştır. Biz burada bunları tek tek vermeyeceğiz.

Atasözlerinin anlam ve dilbilgisel özelliklerinden dolayı bugüne kadar pek çok araştırmaya konu olduğu, bu alanda önemli çalışmalar ortaya konduğu görülmektedir. Bu bildiride birbirine anlamca zıtlık teşkil eden atasözleri hem Özbek hem Türk sahasından seçilerek incelenmiştir. Zıtlık, karşıtlık, çelişki gibi sözler birbirinin eş anlamlısı gibi görünse de atasözleri bu açıdan farklı şekillerde ele alınmıştır. Yüksek lisans tezinde atasözlerini sözcüksel (söz içi) karşıtlıklar açısından ele alan Fatih Mehmet Öz, aynı atasözünde geçen “*ilişkisel, dereceli, kutupsal karşıtlık*” gibi karşıtlıkları ele almıştır (Öz, 2024, s.1). Bir başka çalışma İsmail Abalı’nın “*Çelişkili yargılar bildiren Türk atasözlerine Freudyen bir yaklaşım*” adlı makalesidir (Abalı, 2024, s.610-621). Abalı atasözlerini Freud’un psikanaliz yöntemiyle incelemiş, aç gözlülük, cinsellik, açlık, saldırganlık gibi insanın olumsuz özelliklerini ortaya koymuş ve birtakım sonuçlara ulaşmıştır (Abalı, 2024, s.610). Eyüp Sertaç Ayaz ise “*Türk Atasözlerinde Çelişki*” adlı bildirisinde değişik zamanlarda söylenmiş atasözleri arasında mesajları bakımından çelişkili olanlara yer vermiştir (Ayaz, 2011, s. 833-842).

Bu bildiride Türk atasözleri Ömer Asım Aksoy’un *Atasözleri Sözlüğü* (1988) ve To’ra Mirzäyev vd.’nin yayımladığı *O’zbek Xalq Maqollari* (1989) adlı eser ile İbrahim Yoldaşev ve Muhittin Gümüş’ün hazırladıkları *Özbek Atasözleri* (1995) adlı eserlerden veri tarama yöntemiyle seçilmiş, alanda yazılan tez, bildiri ve makalelere de gereklikçe başvurulmuştur.

Zıt Anlam İçeren Atasözleri

Dost ve dostlukla ilgili olanlar

Eski dost düşman olmaz. /Güvenme dostuna, saman doldurur postuna.

Eskiden beri kişinin huyunu, suyunu bilen, iyi gününde kötü gününde her zaman yanında olan dost, düşman olmaz. / Dostuna güvenip bütün sırlarını açma, ona sırtını dönme, postuna saman doldurur yani seni zor durumda bırakır.

Görüldüğü gibi ilki dostun, dostluğun kıymetini belirtirken ikincisinde dosta güvenilmeyeceği, her zaman açık kapı bırakılması gerektiği anlatılmıştır. Burada her ne kadar birincide eski sıfatı kullanılmışsa da ikinci atasözünde dost’un nasıl bir kişilikte olduğu belirtilmemiştir. Bu yüzden atalarımız dost seçerken de dikkatli olmamızı öğütlemişlerdir.

Eski dost düşman bolmas, yenisidan vafö kelmas (Eski dost düşman olmaz, yenisinden vefa gelmez).

Bu atasözünün Türkçede ‘*yenisinden vefa gelmez*’ kısmı bazen söylenmese de burada atasözü içinde anlam zıtlığı vardır. Eskiden beri birbirini tanıyanların kolay kolay düşman olmayacağı ama yeni tanışılan birinin bütün huyları bilinmediği için ondan düşmanca davranışların da beklenilebileceği belirtilmiştir. Ayrıca dostluğun düzeyinin de daha sığ kalacağı, bu sebeple yeni tanışılan biriyle bütün sırların

paylaşılacağı da anlatılmak istenmiştir. Bu anlamda bir başka atasözü de “*Eski dōstlik zañlamaydi./ Eski dostluk paslanmaz.*”dır.

Ayrilar dost ayovli narsanni sorar (Ayrılacak dost, olmadık şeylerini ister).

Bu atasözünde dostuyla ayrılacak kişinin dostundan beklemediği bir hareket, “olmayacak şeylerin istenmesi”dir. Dostlar birbirleriyle sıkı alış veriş içindedirler. İnsan sahip olduklarını dostundan esirgemez ama araları bozulduğunda bunların hesabı yapılır.

Türkçede “*Dostunla ye, iç, alış veriş etme/yapma!*” gibi bir atasözü de bu anlama yakındır.

Özbekçede ise “*Hisoblashgan do'st emas.*” atasözü, üçün beşin hesabını yapan kişiler arasında dostluk olamayacağını anlatır ve ‘*Dostunla ye, iç, alış veriş etme!*’ atasözündeki öğüt sanki bu yüzden verilmiş gibidir. Bir diğer Özbek atasözünde ise “*Hisobli do'st ayrilmas.*” diyerek dost da olsa dostlar arasında hesabın iyi yapılması gerektiği belirtilmiştir. Hâl böyle olunca da önceki atasözüne ters düşülmektedir.

“*Dost dostun eyerlenmiş atıdır.*” Bizim zor zamanlarımızda yanımıza gelen, özveriden kaçınmayan kişi gerçek dosttur. Bu anlamda diğer bir atasözü de “*Dost kara günde belli olur.*”dur.

Bu atasözlerine ters düşen “*Düşenin dostu olmaz.*” atasözünde ise insanın zor zamanlarında yanında kimsenin kalmayacağı, dost olarak bildiklerinin bile onu yalnız bırakacağı, ona yardım etmeyeceği anlatılmaktadır.

Akılla İlgili Zıt Anlamlı Atasözleri

Akıl yaşta değil, baştadır. / Aklı başa yaş getirir. Birinci atasözünde “*Akılın yaşla alakası yoktur. Yaşça küçük olanlar bazen büyüklerden daha mantıklı olur.*” demek istenmiştir. Akıl kişiden kişiye değişkenlik de gösterir, bu sebeple yaşça büyük birisi küçükler kadar aklını kullanamayabilir.

İkinci atasözünde ise “*İnsan, hayatında gerekli tecrübeye, görgüye, bilgiye belli bir yaşa girdikten sonra ulaşır.*” anlamı öne çıkar. İnsanın hayatı boyunca yaşanmışlıkları onu karşılaştığı olaylara karşı daha deneyimli yapar ve zamanla olgunlaşır, daha mantıklı düşünmeye başlar.

Özbekçede Türkçedeki bu atasözlerine denk olabilecek atasözü “*Aql yoshdan, Odob — boshdan.(Akıl yaştan, edep baştan.)*”dır. ‘Akıl yaştan’ ile insanın yaşlandıkça tecrübelerinin artması, aklının da başına gelmesi kastedilmektedir.

“*Aql bo'yda emas, o'yda.*” atasözünde ise bizdeki “*Akıl yaşta değil baştadır.*” atasözüne benzer bir anlam vardır. Burada “uzun boylu (bu yaşça da büyük biri olabilir, boyca da emsallerinden uzun biri olabilir.) her zaman akıllı olamaz, insana ‘o’y (öy=düşünce, fikir, zihin)/düşünme yetisi’ gerekir.” denmektedir. Bir diğer atasözünde de ‘*Aql — boshda, G'ayrat — yoshda, Asl — toshda.* (Akıl başta-Gayret yaşta-Asıl dışta/dış görünüşte)’ denilerek aklın yaşta değil başta olduğu belirtilmiştir.

Akılla ilgili diğer bazı atasözlerinde de birbirine ters anlamlar görülmektedir.

“*Bin bilsen de bir bilene danış*” ve “*akıl akıldan üstündür*” atasözleri “Ne kadar çok bilsen de senden daha iyi bilen biri olur. Onların da fikrini almalısın.” anlamındadır. Buna tezat teşkil edebilecek atasözü ise “*Akılları pazara çıkarmışlar, herkes yine kendi aklını almış*”tır. Burada “Kişi, kendi düşüncesini veya kendi doğrularını başkalarına göre daha mantıklı ve doğru görür.” anlamı barınmaktadır.

Ko'pdan ko'p aql chiqar. (Çoktan çok akıl çıkar: Çok kişinin olduğu yerde herkes kendi fikrini söyler ve bu da kişilerin karar vermesini zorlaştırır.) Bu atasözünü hem olumlu hem de olumsuz manada düşünmek mümkündür. Farklı fikirler olaylara farklı bakış açılarından bakmamızı ve geniş düşünmemizi sağlar fakat bazen de verilen bu tavsiyeler, fikirler insanın aklını karıştırır, karar vermesini zorlaştırır.

Aql aqldan quvvat olar. “Akıl akıldan kuvvet alır.” Türkçedeki ‘Akıl akıldan üstündür’ atasözüyle aynı durumlar için kullanılır.

O'z aqling aqldir, Elning aqli naqldir. (Kendi aklın akıldır, elinkisi iğreti akıldır.) Burada ‘*Aql aqldan quvvat olar.*’ atasözüne ters düşülen bu atasözünde Türkçedeki herkesin kendi aklını beğendiğini anlatan atasözüne benzer bir anlam vardır. Kişiye kendi aklı üstün görünür.

Sonuç

Atasözleri her millette görülen, bazen milletler/toplumlar arasında ortaklıklar arz eden özlü sözlerdir. Aynı kültürden beslenen Türk ve Özbek atasözlerinde pek çok ortaklıklar olduğu gibi farklılıklar da mevcuttur. Bu bildiride hem Türk hem Özbek atasözlerinden dost-dostluk ve akıl ile ilgili ortaklık gösteren atasözleri örnekseme yoluyla seçilmiş ve bunlar arasındaki anlamsal zıtlıklar ortaya konmuştur. Bildiri kapsamında ele alınan bu konu daha geniş çaplı çalışmalarını gerektiren bir konudur.

Kaynakça

Abalı, İ. (2024). Çelişkili yargılar bildiren Türk atasözlerine Freudyan bir yaklaşım. *RumeliDE Dil ve Edebiyat Araştırmaları Dergisi*, (39), 610-621. DOI: 10.29000/rumelide.1469440.

Aksoy, Ö. A. (1988). *Atasözleri ve deyimler sözlüğü 1: Atasözleri sözlüğü*. İstanbul: İnkılâp Yayınları.

Karaman, A., (2023). Özbek Atasözlerinde Akıl ve Erdem. *Folklor Akademi Dergisi*. Cilt:6, Sayı:3, 1136 – 1146.

Mirzäyev, T, vd. (1989). *O'zbek xalq maqollari*, Gafur Gulâm Nâmidägi Ädäbiyat vä Sän'ät Näşriyati, Tâşkent.

Mirzayev, T. vd. (2013). *O'zbek xalq maqollari*. Toshkent: Sharq.

URL 1: <https://sozluk.gov.tr> (Erişim Tarihi: 13.09.2025)

TASVIRIY IFODALAR IKKILAMCHI NOMINATIV BIRLIK SIFATIDA

*Utegenova O'g'iloy Pardavayevna,
Toshkent Davlat o'zbek tili va adabiyoti universiteti 1-kurs doktoranti
utegenovaugiloy@gmail.com*

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tasviriy ifodalarning ifoda maqsadi, badiiy matnda o'rni va vazifasi, matn qurshovida o'rganiluvchi nutq birligi sifatida tahlil qilinadi. Tasviriy ifodalarda lingvomadaniy jihatning aks etishi, har bir individual yozuvchining uslubi, badiiy so'z qo'llashda tasviriy ifodalardan unumli foydalanishi yoritib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: nutq subyekti, nutq obyeksi, nutq momenti, lingvomadaniy jihat, metofara, nutq tejamkorligi (lokonizm), adresat, adresant, badiiy so'z, kognitiv bilim, matn qurshovi.

Annotation. This article discusses that paraphrase is the most important means of creating imagery and emotional expression. The field of paraphrase, which has a culture, figurative meaning. Paraphrase is closely related to the spiritual culture, customs, place attitude to reality of the people who speak the language.

Key words: Subject of parole, object of parole, moments' parole, lingvoculturology, metaphor, figurative words, cognitive knowledge, paraphrase related to text.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается, что перифразы являются важнейшим средством создания образности и эмоционального выражения. Перифразы тесно связаны с духовной культурой, обычаями к действительности людей, говорящих на языке.

Ключевы слова: Перифразы, объект речи, предмет речи, момент речи, лингвокультурология, метафоры, экономия речи, адресант, адресат, художественное слово, когнитивная наука, текстовый запрос.

KIRISH

Badiiy asarlarda ko'chim, o'xshatishga asoslangan birliklar badiiy matnning qiymatini oshiruvchi asosiy mezon hisoblanadi. Tasviriy ifodalar ham metafora asosida yuzaga keluvchi birlik bo'lib, unda o'xshatilyotgan shaxs, narsa, joy nomlarining muhim tomoni aks etadi. Badiiy matn mutolaasi Gumboldt tomonidan ta'kidlangan yozuvchi-o'quvchi antinomiyasining o'ziga xos ko'rinishini namoyon qiladi. Bunday matn o'quvchisi diskursiv faoliyatda kognitiv amallar bajaruvchisiga aylanadi: u axborot qabul qiluvchi, matnni o'z lisoniy tafakkuri kodlariga moslashtiruvchi, uning mazmunini qayta tiklovchi, o'z estetik qarashlari asosida baholovchi shaxs sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Bunda uning yoshi, jinsi, bilimi, kayfiyati, qiziqish doirasi katta ahamiyat kasb etadi[1]. Badiiy matnda tasvir vositalarni tushunish, ishora qiluvchi so'zlar va yashirin ma'noli birliklarni anglash o'quvchidan yuksak tafakkur, mulohaza, shu millatga xos madaniyat bilan tanish - ya'ni idrok talab etiladi.

O'zbek millatida efemizmlar disefemizmlarga nisbatan ko'proq qo'llaniladi. Masalan, fohisha faxsh ishlar bilan shug'ullanuvchi ayolga nisbatan

qo'llaniladi. So'zlashuv, badiiy, publitsistik uslublarda ko'pincha fohisha so'zi o'rniga *tungi kapalak* tasviriy ifodasidan foydalaniladi. Bu tinglovchida estetik zavq uyg'otishi tabiiy hamda millatga xos xunuk so'z o'rniga badiiy so'zni qo'llashi nutqiy me'yor sanaladi. Tilshunos I.Umirov maqolasida tasviriy ifodalarning vazifalari, o'ni, badiiy matnda berilishiga doir misollar keltirgan[3]. Asar qahramonlarining to'laqonli bo'lishini taminlaydi deb quydagi gapni keltiradi. Abdulla issiq qozon ichida qaynaydi. (O'.Umarbekov). Yozuvchi hayotning *achchiq-chuchugini totiganligini* ta'kidlagan. Bizningcha, tasviriy ifodada faqat ko'chma ma'noli so'zdan emas, bilvosita ifoda usullaridan ham foydalaniladi. Yuqoridagi gap shunga misol bo'la oladi. Nasriy asarlarda parafrazalar jumlaning qisqaligini ta'minlash maqsadida ishlatilganda lokonizm (qisqalik), ixchamlik hodisasi yuzaga keladi. "To'g'ri rais telefon qilgandan keyin *Toshkent radiosining olg'irlari* bu xabarni kechki so'nggi axborotga berishgan edi"[2]. (A.Qahhor). Gapdagi olg'irlari ixchamlikni yuzaga keltirgan aks holda radioeshittirishni olib boruvchi kishilar so'z birikmasi qo'llangan bo'lar edi.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODLAR

Antik davrdan boshlab tasviriy ifodalar Aristotel, Kvintilian tomonidan qayd etilganligi, bundan tashqari, tasviriy ifodalar mahalliy va sharqiy slavyan tilshunosligining ham diqqat markazida bo'lganligi, ilm-fan to'la rivojlanmagan davrlardan boshlab ushbu birlik talqin qilinganligi manbalarda qayd etiladi.[10, B.143]. XX asrning 50-yillarida tasviriy ifodalar dunyo tilshunosligida, jumladan, rus tilshunosligida I.Z.Ilina, V.P.Utkinalar uni lingvistik jarayon sifatida boshqa hodisa yoki vositalar bilan bog'liq holda tasvirlagan. Yuqoridagi tilshunoslar ko'chim turlari bilan birgalikda tahlil qilgan. A.V.Arnold tasviriy ifodani predmet nomining o'rnida uning asosiy xususiyatlarini ifodolovchi birikma yoki so'zning ta'rifini ifodalash uchun keltirilgan bo'yoqdor so'zlarni misol sifatida keltiradi. Tilshunos H.Shamsiddinov tasviriy ifodalarni perifraza termini bilan ifodalashni ma'qul ko'radi. Ularni funksional-semantik sinonimlar qatoriga kiritadi. "Birinchi bor tilga olinayotgan tasviriy ifodalar hali til mulkiga aylanmagan bo'lsa, ma'lum payt qo'shtirnoqqa olinishi zarur, lekin *oq oltin, zangori olov, kumush tola, zangori ekran* singari perifrazalar qo'shtirnoqqa olinmasligi zarur. Chunki ular lisoniy me'yorga aylanib qoldi[3]. Bizningcha, yuqoridagi tasviriy ifodalar hamma uchun umumiy, lisoniy til birligi, nutqda tayyor holda uchraydi shuning uchun til birligi sifatida qabul qilamiz. Muallif ushbu maqolada tasviriy ifodani subyektiv omil mahsuli ekanligi, uning yuzaga kelishida umumiylik va xususiylik kabi falsafiy kategoriyalar amal qilishi, tasviriy ifodalarning hosil bo'lishida ekstralingvistik va psixolingvistik omillar ta'siri, matnda taqdim etish kabi masalalarini tahlil qiladi, misollar bilan dalillaydi. Tasviriy ifodalar har bir sohada ikkilamchi nom sifatida ifodalanadi. Masalan, *iqtisodning qoni*-pul (iqtisod sohasida), *insonning tabiiy qalqoni*-teri (biologiya), *tarix otasi*-Geradot (tarix fani) va hokazo. Badiiy uslubda ko'p qo'llaniluvchi, mazmunni boyituvchi birlik hisoblanadi. Tasviriy ifodalar nafaqat takronni oldini olishi balki, nazm yoki nasrni badiiyligini oshiruvchi, yozuvchining yuksak mahoratini ko'rsatuvchi birlikdir.

MUHOKAMA

Dunyo tilshunosligida tasviriy ifodalar “paraphrase, periphrase” terminlari bilan o‘rganilgan. Jahon tilshunosligida tasviriy ifodalar matn qurshovida o‘rganilib tahlil qilingan shu sabab ba’zi olimlar jumladan, I.V.Grexneva, V.P.Grigorev, A.S.Elizarov, A.N. Kojin, V.P.Moskvin, E.P.Senichkina, I.N.Genilnikova, M.R.Sarayevalar tasviriy ifodalarni tilning uslubiy vositasi desa, S. Vidlak, L.K.Julinskaya, V.I.Zabotkina, A.M.Kasayev, N.G.Komlev, S.Ulman, Y.I. Sheygal semantik xususiyatiga ega interpretatsiya, T.S.Bushueva, T.I.Bitiva, I.V.Grexneva, N.A.Yemenskaya pragmatic aspekt deb ta’rif beradi[1]. Har bir olimning yondashuvi tasviriy ifodaning muhim belgisini ochib berishini anglatadi. Birgina so‘zdan iborat, so‘z birikmasi hatto gaplardan iborat tasviriy ifodalar uchraydi. O‘zbek xalqi nutqida ayolni *ojiza*, men so‘zi o‘rnida *kamina*, prezident so‘zi o‘nida *davlat rahbari*, chaqaloq *yangi mehmon*, sinf rahbar *ikkinchi ona*, maktab *bilim maskani*, ilm *o‘chog‘i kabi* ikkilamchi nomlariga ega. Hatto turmush o‘rtoq-*er yoki xotin*, *yostiqdosh* so‘zlari, bog‘cha opa-*tarbiyachi* tasviriy ifodalari ham uchraydi. Birgina so‘zning turlicha tasviriy ifodalari uchrashi mumkin. Faqat...Xudodan, ey *Yaratgan egam*, men-nodonga bir chimdim aql ber, deb so‘ragan bandasini ko‘rganim yo‘q!(O‘. Hoshimov “Daftar hoshiyasidagi bitiklar”). Insonni *tabiat gultoji*, bu dunyoda ham, u dunyoda ham hech kinga bo‘ysunmaydigan, oqni oqqa,qorani qoraga bexato ajratadigan *Oliy hakam* bor. Bu-*Tangrining* hukmi! Yozuvchi bir so‘zni turli tasviriy ifodalarda o‘quvchini mulohaza yuritishga, denotant so‘zni bilvosita ifoda uslublarida beradi. Har bir yozuvchining dunyoqarashi, olamni idrok etishi, xulosalashi turlicha. Bu ularning badiiy ijod maydonida qay tarzda ifodalashi, o‘quvchini qiziqтира olishi, mulohazaga undashiga olib keladi. Quyidagi chizmada Alloh so‘zining xalq orasida qo‘llaniluvchi sinonimlari, badiiy asarlarda ijodkorning shu denotantga bergan ikkilamchi nomlari keltirilgan.

Xalq qo‘llovchi denotant	Badiiy asarda denotant so‘zning tasviriy ifodasi	Muallif va olingan manba
Alloh Tangri Xudo Parvardigor Yaratgan egam Tangri Taollo	Oliy hakam	O‘.Hoshimov “Daftar hoshiyasidagi bitiklar”
	Janobi Haq	Abdulla Avloniy “Turkiy guliston yoxud axloq”
	Haq Taollo	Kaykovus “Qobusnoma”
	Yagona najotkor	A.Oripov “Sohibqiron”
	Butun borliq sohibi	A. Navoiy “Muhokamat ul-lug‘atayn”
	Xudovandi taborak va taolo	A. Fitrat “Najot yo‘li”

Har bir yozuvchida tasviriy ifoda takrorlanmas, o‘ziga xos tarzda berilgan.

XULOSA

Umuman olganda, jahon tilshunosligida, jumladan, o‘zbek tilshunosligida tasviriy ifodalar asosli o‘rganilgan. Jahon tilshunosligida tasviriy ifodalarni matn

referensiyasi qurshovida- diskursiv, pragmatik, lingvokulturologik, psixolingvistik aspektida o'rganish ancha erta boshlangan va bugungi kungacha davom etmoqda.

Zamonaviy tilshunoslikda tasviriy ifodalar kognitiv tilshunoslik nuqtayi nazaridan tahlil qilinmoqda. Tasviriy ifodalar inson omili mahsuli sifatida qabul qilish, qayta ishlash va xulosalashdan iborat. Yuqoridagi jadval bunga yaqqol misol bo'la oladi. Tilshunoslikda tasviriy ifodalar o'xshatish- metofara, metonimiya, sinikdoxa kabi badiiy tasvir vositalari bir qatorda tursa-da, aynan takrorlanuvchi bir xil hodisa emas, balki subyektning tasavvuri, bilimi, xotirasidagi qayta ishlangan kognitiv hosilasi hisoblanadi.

Adabiyotlar

1. Xudoyberganova D. Matnning antroposentrik tadqiqi. Avtoreferat. – Toshkent: Fan nashriyoti, 2013. – B. 78.

2. Umirov I. Parafrazalarning badiiy asarlarda qo'llanilishiga doir. O'TA. 1996-yil. №5. – B. 45-46.

3. Shamsiddinov H. Perifrazalar xususida ayrim mulohazalar. O'TA. 1993-yil. – B. 34.

4. Евкодимова Е. В Прагматический и лингвокультурологических перифраз и сходных стилистических приемов в газетно-журнальном дискурсе. Автореферат. – Иркутск, 2008. – С. 4.

5. A.Navoiy Muhokamat ul-lugatayn. – Toshkent, 2012. – B. 8.

6. O'.Hoshimov Daftar hoshiyasidagi bitiklar. – Toshkent, 2021. –B. 24

O'ZBEK TILINI O'QITISH VA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR

Gulnoza Abdurahmonova,

Erkin izlanuvchi

Annotatsiya. Maqolada o'zbek tilini o'qitishda raqamli texnologiyalarning o'rni va imkoniyatlari ilmiy jihatdan asoslab berilgan. Raqamli vositalardan foydalanish til o'rgatishda innovatsion yondashuvlarni joriy etish, talabalarning mustaqil ta'lim olish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish hamda ta'lim jarayonining samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qilishi yoritilgan. Shuningdek, zamonaviy ta'lim platformalari, multimedia resurslari va onlayn test tizimlari misolida raqamli texnologiyalarni qo'llash tajribasi tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: o'zbek tili ta'limi, raqamli vositalar, multimedia, onlayn ta'lim, innovatsion metodlar.

Annotation. The article scientifically substantiates the role and opportunities of digital technologies in teaching the Uzbek language. It highlights how the use of digital tools contributes to the introduction of innovative approaches in language learning, the development of learners' independent study skills, and the improvement of educational efficiency. In addition, the application of modern educational platforms, multimedia resources, and online testing systems is analyzed as practical examples.

Keywords: Uzbek language teaching, digital tools, multimedia, online learning, innovative methods.

Аннотация: В статье научно обоснована роль и возможности цифровых технологий в обучении узбекскому языку. Подчеркивается, что использование цифровых средств способствует внедрению инновационных подходов в процесс изучения языка, развитию самостоятельных учебных навыков учащихся и повышению эффективности образовательного процесса. Также рассматриваются примеры применения современных образовательных платформ, мультимедийных ресурсов и онлайн-тестовых систем.

Ключевые слова: преподавание узбекского языка, цифровые средства, мультимедиа, онлайн-обучение, инновационные методы.

Hozirgi davrda ta'lim tizimi oldida turgan eng muhim vazifalardan biri — raqamli texnologiyalarni o'quv jarayoniga samarali tatbiq etishdir. Chunki raqamli vositalar ta'limning sifatini oshirish, o'quvchilarni mustaqil izlanishga undash hamda ularning bilim olishga bo'lgan motivatsiyasini kuchaytirishda katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ayniqsa, o'zbek tilini o'qitishda yangi axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanish o'quv jarayonini interaktiv, qulay va samarali tashkil etishga imkon beradi.

Raqamli texnologiyalar ta'lim tizimiga XX asrning oxiri va XXI asr boshlarida kirib keldi. Avvaliga ular kompyuter texnologiyalari shaklida, ya'ni dastlabki elektron darsliklar, kompyuter sinflari va multimedia materiallari orqali joriy etildi. 1990-yillardan boshlab ta'lim jarayonida internetning qo'llanilishi kengaydi va bu esa raqamli texnologiyalarning imkoniyatlarini yanada oshirdi. Shu davrdan boshlab ta'limda elektron kutubxonalar, virtual laboratoriyalar, onlayn darsliklar va multimedia resurslari qo'llanila boshlandi. Ta'limni raqamlashtirish bugungi kunda zaruriy jarayonga aylangan. Chunki u o'quv jarayonini qulay, tezkor va samarali qiladi. Raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida bilim olish imkoniyatlari kengayadi, har kim istagan joyidan masofadan turib o'qishi mumkin. Darslar interaktiv bo'lib, o'quvchilar uchun qiziqarli va tushunarli shaklda tashkil etiladi. Bundan tashqari, vaqt va resurslar tejab qolinadi, o'qituvchi ham, o'quvchi ham elektron darsliklar va onlayn topshiriqlar orqali o'z ishini yengillashtiradi. Eng muhimi, raqamlashtirish orqali ta'lim jahon tajribasi bilan uyg'unlashadi va o'quvchilarning bilim olishi uchun keng imkoniyatlar yaratiladi [5].

XXI asrning ikkinchi o'n yilligida esa raqamli texnologiyalar masofaviy ta'lim, elektron test tizimlari, virtual sinflar, mobil ilovalar va bulutli platformalar orqali yanada kengroq namoyon bo'ldi. Ayniqsa, 2020-yilda butun dunyo bo'ylab pandemiya davrida onlayn ta'lim shakli keng joriy qilinishi raqamli texnologiyalarning ta'lim tizimidagi o'rnini keskin kuchaytirdi. Shu davrda Zoom, Google Meet, Microsoft Teams kabi videokonferensiya vositalari, shuningdek, Google Classroom, Moodle, Coursera kabi o'quv platformalari o'qituvchi va o'quvchi o'rtasidagi asosiy muloqot maydoniga aylandi. So'nggi yillarda dunyo miqyosida raqamli ta'lim platformalari, elektron darsliklar, virtual sinflar va multimedia resurslari keng qo'llanila boshladi.

Ona tilini o'qitishda chet el tajribasi bu borada o'ziga xos yondashuvlarni namoyon etadi. Xususan, AQShda ona tilini o'qitish jarayoni asosan kommunikativ yondashuvga asoslanadi. O'quvchilar nutqiy vaziyatlarda erkin fikr bildirishga, tanqidiy tahlil qilishga va o'z fikrini mantiqiy asoslashga o'rgatiladi. Bunda Google Classroom, Edmodo, Khan Academy kabi raqamli platformalar dars jarayonini interaktiv va qiziqarli tashkil etishga xizmat qiladi [2].

Finlyandiya ta'lim tizimida esa ona tilini o'qitish boshqa fanlar bilan integratsiya qilinadi. Har bir o'quvchi uchun individual o'quv rejasi ishlab chiqiladi va bunda uning qiziqishlari hamda qobiliyatlari inobatga olinadi. Shuningdek, elektron kutubxonalar, raqamli lug'atlar va interaktiv dasturlar ta'lim jarayonining ajralmas qismiga aylangan.

Yaponiyada ona tilini o'qitishda milliy qadriyatlar va madaniyatni singdirish muhim hisoblanadi. O'quvchilar ko'proq yozma mashqlar bajarish orqali o'z fikrini aniq va ravon ifodalashga o'rgatiladi. Shuningdek, zamonaviy texnologiyalar yordamida talaffuz, yozuv va o'qish ko'nikmalari muntazam baholab boriladi.

Germaniya ta'lim tizimida esa kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosiy tamoyil sifatida belgilangan. O'quvchilar matnni nafaqat o'qiydi, balki uni chuqur tahlil qiladi, boshqa manbalar bilan solishtiradi va ijodiy topshiriqlarda qo'llashni o'rganadi. Loyihaviy ishlar orqali o'quvchilarning mustaqil izlanish faoliyati qo'llab-quvvatlanadi.

Umuman olganda, chet el tajribasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, ona tilini o'qitishda asosiy e'tibor interaktivlik, kommunikativlik, fanlararo integratsiya va raqamli texnologiyalardan samarali foydalanishga qaratiladi. Bunday yondashuvlar o'quvchilarning nafaqat til ko'nikmalarini, balki tanqidiy va ijodiy fikrlash qobiliyatlarini ham rivojlantiradi. Shu sababli xorijiy tajribalarni o'rganish va ularni milliy ta'lim amaliyotiga tatbiq etish ona tilini o'qitish samaradorligini oshirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida ham so'nggi yillarda ona tilini o'qitishga zamonaviy yondashuvlar joriy qilinmoqda. Jumladan, davlat ta'lim standartlarida kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asos qilib olingan, darslarda kommunikativ mashqlar, mustaqil fikrlashni rivojlantiruvchi topshiriqlar keng qo'llanmoqda. Elektron darsliklar, onlayn platformalar va raqamli resurslar yaratilib, o'quvchilarning bilim olish imkoniyatlari kengaymoqda. Biroq xorijiy tajribada kuzatiladigan individual o'quv rejaları va fanlararo integratsiya bizda hali to'liq joriy qilinmagan [4]. Bu jarayon O'zbekistonda ham izchil amalga oshirilmoqda. Xususan, ona tilini o'qitishda elektron testlar, onlayn mashg'ulotlar va mobil ilovalardan foydalanish o'quvchilarni tilni yanada tezroq va samaraliroq o'zlashtirishiga yordam bermoqda. Shu boisdan, o'zbek tilini o'qitishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslarini yoritish, ularning amaliy afzalliklarini ko'rsatish va ta'lim jarayonida qo'llash tajribalarini tahlil qilish bugungi kunda dolzarb masalalardan biri hisoblanadi. Oddiy qilib aytganda, barcha elektron qurilmalar, dasturiy ta'minotlar va internet tizimlari ishini ta'minlaydigan asosiy mexanizm raqamli texnologiya hisoblanadi. Bugungi kunda raqamli texnologiyalar hayotimizning barcha sohalariga chuqur kirib kelgan. Ular yordamida ma'lumotlar tez va aniq qayta ishlanadi, masofadan turib uzatiladi va keng jamoatchilikka

yetkaziladi. Telefonlar, kompyuterlar, planshetlar, onlayn platformalar, elektron darsliklar, multimedia vositalari va sun'iy intellekt asosidagi dasturlar raqamli texnologiyalarning eng ko'p tarqalgan misollaridir. Ta'lim sohasida raqamli texnologiyalar alohida ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, ular zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonining samaradorligini oshirishda muhim omil sifatida xizmat qiladi. Raqamli vositalar dars jarayonini interaktiv qilish, o'quvchilarning bilim olishga bo'lgan qiziqishini orttirish, mustaqil o'rganish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish hamda o'qituvchi va o'quvchi o'rtasida samarali muloqotni yo'lga qo'yishda katta imkoniyat yaratadi. Shu boisdan ham bugungi kunda raqamli texnologiyalar nafaqat yordamchi vosita, balki ta'lim tizimining ajralmas qismi sifatida qaralmoqda.

Masalan, elektron darsliklar o'quvchilarga matn, rasm, audio va video ko'rinishidagi o'quv materiallarini birgalikda taqdim etib, mavzuni ko'proq his qilish va yaxshiroq o'zlashtirish imkonini beradi. Virtual ta'lim platformalari esa dars jarayonini masofadan turib ham samarali tashkil etish, topshiriqlarni tezkorlik bilan tekshirish va o'quvchilar bilan doimiy aloqada bo'lish imkonini taqdim etadi. Bundan tashqari, mobil ilovalar va onlayn test tizimlari o'quvchilarga istalgan joyda va istalgan vaqtda mustaqil ravishda mashq qilish, bilimni tekshirish va takomillashtirish imkonini beradi.

Ayniqsa, o'zbek tilini o'qitishda bu vositalarning roli beqiyosdir. Chunki til o'rganishda nafaqat nazariy bilim, balki ko'nikma va malakalarni shakllantirish ham muhimdir. Raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida o'quvchilar lug'at boyligini oshirish, talaffuzni to'g'rilash, matnlarni o'qish va tahlil qilish, tinglab tushunish hamda yozma savodxonlikni mustahkamlash imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi,

An'anaviy darslar va raqamli texnologiyalar asosidagi darslar o'rtasida sezilarli farqlar mavjud. Avvalo, oddiy darslarda bilim berishning asosiy manbai o'qituvchi hisoblanadi, ya'ni o'quvchi ko'proq tayyor bilimni qabul qiladi. Raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanilgan darslarda esa o'quvchi bilimni mustaqil izlash, tahlil qilish va qo'llash jarayonida faol ishtirok etadi. Oddiy darslarda o'quvchilar ko'proq tinglovchi rolini bajaradilar, raqamli darslarda esa ular topshiriqlarni onlayn bajarish, multimedia vositalaridan foydalanish, virtual platformalarda muloqot qilish orqali faol qatnashadilar. An'anaviy darslarda ko'proq og'zaki tushuntirish va yozma mashqlar ustun bo'lsa, raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida grafikalar, infografikalar, audio-video materiallar, simulyatsiyalar va interaktiv o'yinlar keng qo'llanadi. Bu esa mavzuni tezroq va samaraliroq o'zlashtirishga yordam beradi. Oddiy dars faqat sinf xonasida va belgilangan vaqtda o'tkazilsa, raqamli texnologiyalar asosidagi darslarda o'quvchi istalgan joyda va istalgan vaqtda ta'lim olish imkoniga ega bo'ladi.

O'zbek tilini tushuntirish jarayonida raqamli texnologiyalar katta amaliy yordam bera oladi. Avvalo, audio va video materiallardan foydalanish orqali o'quvchilarga to'g'ri talaffuz, nutq ohangi va intonatsiyani o'rgatish imkoniyati yaratiladi. Interaktiv mashqlar esa so'z boyligini kengaytirish, grammatik qoidalarni mustahkamlash hamda o'quvchining faol ishtirokini ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi. Onlayn lug'atlar va elektron tarjimonlar yordamida o'quvchilar qiyin so'z va iboralarni tezda tushunib oladilar. Shuningdek, virtual doska va taqdimotlardan foydalanish darsni yanada ko'rgazmali qiladi, mavzularni esda qoldirishni

yengillashtiradi. Mobil ilovalar va test tizimlari orqali o'quvchilar mustaqil ravishda mashq qilishi, o'z bilimini tekshirish imkoniga ega bo'ladilar. Gamifikatsiya, ya'ni o'quv jarayonini o'yin elementlari asosida tashkil etish, o'quvchilarda o'zbek tilini o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqishni kuchaytiradi. Eng muhimi, masofaviy ta'lim platformalari orqali nafaqat mamlakat ichkarisidagi, balki chet ellik o'rganuvchilar ham o'zbek tilini interaktiv va zamonaviy shaklda o'rganish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar.

Ona tilini o'qitishda raqamli texnologiyalar til ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Xususan, tinglash, o'qish, yozish va so'zlash malakalari zamonaviy vositalar orqali samarali rivojlantiriladi. Birinchidan, tinglab tushunish ko'nikmasini rivojlantirishda audiomatnlar, podkastlar va turli videodarslardan foydalanish imkoniyati mavjud. Bu o'quvchilarga eshitilgan matn mazmunini anglash, asosiy g'oyani ajratib olish, talaffuz va intonatsiyani to'g'ri qo'llashga yordam beradi. Ikkinchidan, o'qish ko'nikmasi elektron kitoblar, interaktiv matnlar va onlayn maqolalar yordamida shakllantiriladi. Bunday vositalar o'quvchilarda mustaqil o'qish, tezkor ma'lumot izlash, asosiy va ikkinchi darajali fikrlarni ajratish, matnni tahlil qilish kabi malakalarni rivojlantiradi. Uchinchidan, yozuv malakasini rivojlantirish uchun elektron platformalarda insho yozish, test topshiriqlarini bajarish va interaktiv yozma mashqlardan foydalanish muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bu usullar o'quvchilarning yozuv madaniyatini shakllantiradi, grammatik jihatdan to'g'ri va mantiqan izchil fikr yuritishga o'rgatadi. To'rtinchidan, so'zlash ko'nikmasi onlayn muloqot platformalari, videochatlar va ovozli topshiriqlar orqali mustahkamlanadi. Bu jarayonda o'quvchilar o'z fikrlarini erkin ifodalash, nutqiy muloqotda faol ishtirok etish va talaffuzni to'g'rilash imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar.

Ona tilini o'qitishda o'quv materiallarini boyitish raqamli texnologiyalarning eng muhim imkoniyatlaridan biridir. An'anaviy darsliklarda berilgan matnlar ko'pincha faqat nazariy tushunchalarni qamrab oladi, biroq zamonaviy ta'limda ushbu materiallarni turli raqamli vositalar bilan kengaytirish o'quvchilarning bilimni yanada chuqurlashtiradi.

Avvalo, darslikdagi matnlarni videoroliklar bilan to'ldirish o'quvchilarga mavzuni ko'rgazmali tarzda qabul qilish imkonini beradi. Masalan, badiiy matnni tahlil qilish jarayonida asarning sahnalashtirilgan parchasi yoki animatsion ko'rinishi o'quvchida matnga nisbatan qiziqish uyg'otadi.

Shuningdek, elektron lug'atlar va mobil ilovalar darslik materialini kengaytirib, o'quvchilarning so'z boyligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi. Elektron lug'atlar interaktivligi sababli, o'quvchi nafaqat so'zning ma'nosini, balki uning talaffuzini, qo'llanish doirasini va sinonimlarini ham ko'rib chiqishi mumkin.

Bundan tashqari, grammatik dasturlar (masalan, avtomatik tahlil va tuzatish imkoniyatiga ega onlayn platformalar) o'quvchilarning yozma va og'zaki nutqidagi grammatik xatolarni tezkor aniqlash va tuzatishga yordam beradi. Bu esa o'quvchilarda mustaqil o'rganish ko'nikmasini shakllantiradi.

Demak, raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida o'quv materiallarini boyitish nafaqat darslikdagi bilimlarni kengaytiradi, balki o'quvchilarda tilni chuqur o'zlashtirish,

mustaqil ta'lim olish va zamonaviy bilim manbalaridan samarali foydalanish imkonini yaratadi.

O'qituvchiga qulaylik – raqamli texnologiyalar ona tilini o'qitishda o'qituvchining mehnatini samarali tashkil etish imkonini beradi. Avvalo, darsni rejalash jarayonida turli elektron resurslardan foydalanish o'qituvchiga vaqt tejash, o'quv maqsadlarini aniq belgilash hamda metodik yondashuvlarni xilma-xil shaklda qo'llash imkonini yaratadi. Masalan, interaktiv taqdimotlar, elektron test dasturlari, onlayn lug'atlar va til o'rgatishga mo'ljallangan ilovalardan foydalanish darsni zamonaviy talablar asosida tashkil etish imkonini beradi. Shuningdek, materiallarni turlicha shaklda – matn, audio, video yoki grafik ko'rinishda taqdim etish orqali o'quvchilarning individual ehtiyojlari va qiziqishlariga moslashish mumkin.

Bundan tashqari, o'quvchilar faoliyatini nazorat qilish raqamli vositalar yordamida yengillashadi. Elektron testlar, avtomatlashtirilgan baholash tizimlari va onlayn monitoring platformalari o'quvchining bilim darajasini tezkor va aniq tahlil qilishga yordam beradi. Bu esa o'qituvchiga har bir o'quvchining til ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish bo'yicha individual tavsiyalar berish va ta'lim jarayonini samarali boshqarish imkonini beradi [6].

Ona tilini o'qitishda xorijiy tajriba va raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish ko'plab ijobiy natijalarga olib kelishi bilan birga, ayrim noqulay tomonlarga ham ega. Avvalo, o'quvchilarning texnik vositalarga ortiqcha tayanib qolishi kitob bilan ishlash, mustaqil izlanish va o'z fikrini erkin shakllantirish odatini sekinlashtirishi mumkin. Shuningdek, barcha hududlarda internet va elektron qurilmalardan foydalanish imkoniyati teng emasligi ta'limda muayyan farqlarni yuzaga keltiradi.

Chet el metodlarini to'liq qo'llashda esa milliy qadriyatlarining chetda qolib ketish xavfi mavjud, bu esa ona tilini faqat kommunikativ vosita sifatida emas, balki madaniy merosni saqlovchi boylik sifatida o'rgatishda muammolar tug'dirishi mumkin. Interaktiv platformalarning keng qo'llanilishi ba'zan o'qituvchining yetakchi rolini kamaytirib qo'yadi, tezkor elektron testlar esa chuqur bilim olishdan ko'ra yuzaki yodlashga olib kelishi ehtimoldan xoli emas.

Bundan tashqari, kompyuter va mobil qurilmalardan uzoq vaqt foydalanish o'quvchilarda charchoq, diqqatni jamlashdagi qiyinchiliklar hamda ko'rish qobiliyatiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin. Xorijiy tajribalarni milliy ta'lim jarayoniga to'liq tatbiq etishda ham muayyan moslashish muammolari kuzatiladi, chunki har bir mamlakatning madaniy va ijtimoiy xususiyatlari turlicha. Shu sababli, xorijiy tajribalarni o'rganishda ijobiy jihatlaridan foydalanish, ammo milliy ta'lim tamoyillari bilan uyg'unlashtirish eng to'g'ri yondashuv bo'ladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, ona tilini o'qitishda xorijiy tajribalarni o'rganish va ularni milliy ta'lim jarayoniga tatbiq etish ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishda muhim omil hisoblanadi. Rivojlangan davlatlar tajribasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, interaktivlik, kommunikativlik, fanlararo integratsiya va raqamli texnologiyalarni qo'llash o'quvchilarda til ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish bilan birga tanqidiy va ijodiy fikrlashni ham shakllantiradi. Shu bilan birga, bunday yondashuvlarning ayrim noqulay tomonlari – texnologiyalarga haddan tashqari tayanish, milliy qadriyatlarining chetda

qolishi yoki o‘qituvchining rolini kamaytirib yuborishi mumkinligi ham nazardan chetda qolmasligi lozim.

Adabiyotlar

1. Abiturtest. Muammoli ta’limning nazariy asoslari haqida ma’lumot. – URL: <https://abiturtest.uz> (murojaat qilingan sana: 17.09.2025).

2. Ally, M. Foundations of educational theory for online learning // In: Anderson T., Elloumi F. (Eds.). Theory and practice of online learning. – Athabasca University, 2008. – URL: http://cde.athabascau.ca/online_book/pdf/TPOL_book.pdf (murojaat qilingan sana: 28.05.2019).

3. Shukurov V. Iqtisodiy sohalarning rivojlanishida internet texnologiyalarining o‘rni // The Journal of Economics, Finance and Innovation. – 2023. – URL: <https://sbtsuejournals.uz/index.php/EFI/article/view/98> (murojaat qilingan sana: 17.09.2025).

4. Shukurov V. Iqtisodiyot fanlarini o‘qitishda innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanish // Engineering problems and innovations. – 2023. – URL: <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/epai/article/view/189> (murojaat qilingan sana: 17.09.2025).

5. Shukurov V. Ta’lim jarayoniga interfaol elektron manbalarni joriy qilishning ahamiyati // Talqin va tadqiqotlar. – 2023. – URL: <https://talqinvatadqiqotlar.uz/index.php/tvt/article/view/605> (murojaat qilingan sana: 17.09.2025).

6. Shukurov V., Khaydarov J., Karimov A. Factors for the formation of multimedia competencies in improving the methodology of teaching specialist subjects

7. <https://daryo.uz/2021/07/13/shavkat-mirziyoyev-raqamli-texnologiyalarni-joriy-etish-choratadbirlariga-oid-taqdimot-bilan-tanishdi> (murojaat qilingan sana: 17.09.2025).

MUNDARIJA

M.T.Xodjiyev KIRISH SO‘ZI	4
Fazliddin Sharipov SO‘Z TURKUMLARI VA GRAMMATIK KATEGORIYALARNING AMALIY BOSQICHDAGI O‘RNI.....	5
Jumanazar Abdullayev TIL BIRLIKLARI TASNIFIGA AYRIM CHIZGILAR.....	9
Banovsha Mammadova Guloghlan POSTSTRUCTURALIST AND COGNITIVE APPROACHES TO THE TRANSFORMATION OF LANGUAGE IDENTITY.....	14
Azamat Uralov NOMUTANOSIBLIKNING DIAKRON VA SINXRON TAHLILI.....	16
Hamid Yodgorov AYRIM LEKSEMALARNING ETIMOLOGIYASI XUSUSIDA.....	22
Alisher Axrorov XALQ MAQOLLARI LINGVOKULTURALOGIYANING O‘RGANISH OBYEKTI SIFATIDA.....	25
Hikmatullo Dusmatov, Dilnavoz Qo‘ldasheva FURQAT IJODIDA TASHXIS.....	28
Shahodat Usmonova GAZETA MATNIDA MUALLIF “MEN”I.....	32
Hamid Bozorov ERTAK MATNIDAGI LINGVOPOETIK IMKONIYATLARNING YUZAGA CHIQUISHIDA LITOTANING ROLI.....	36
Matanat Alaga Gojayeva <u>THE</u> MAIN FEATURES OF THE OLD ENGLISH LANGUAGE.....	40
Dilrabo Ergasheva BADIY MATNNING LUG‘AVIY-USLUBIY XUSUSIYATLARI (Odil Yoqubov asarlari misolida).....	42
Хегай Валентина Михайловна СЕМАНТИЧЕСКАЯ КАК ОДИН ИЗ АСПЕКТОВ СИНТАКСИСА.....	46
Husniyya Tanriverdiyeva METONYMY IN LINGUISTIC RESEARCH: A COGNITIVE APPROACH.....	49

Xilola Yunusova FE'LLARNING GRAMMATIKALASHUVI BOSQICHLARI BORASIDAGI TURLI QARASHLAR.....	53
Kommuna Umurzakova NUTQIY NORMALARDAN CHETLASHISH VA YOZISHDAGI INNOVASION ELEMENTLAR.....	57
Dilnavoz Qo'ldasheva FURQAT G'AZALLARINING LEKSIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	59
Ramiga Oktay Shiraliyeva FROM QUANTITY TO AMBIGUITY: THE INDEFINITE USE OF NUMERALS IN LANGUAGE.....	63
Sirojiddin Mamaraximov OT LEKSEMALARINING BIRIKUVCHANLIK VA BIRIKTIRUVCHANLIK JIHATLARI.....	66
Maxliyo Furkatova THE SEMANTIC AND FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LOCATIVE-TEMPORAL CASE IN UZBEK AND ITS SYNTACTIC EQUIVALENTS IN ENGLISH.....	71
Mahliyo Jo'rayeva TARZ FUNKSIONAL-SEMANTIK MA'NOSINING FONETIK VOSITALAR ORQALI IFODALANISHI.....	78
Zaxro Abruyeva O'ZBEK TILIDAGI MUROJAAT SHAKLLARINING KOGNITIV ASOSIDAGI GENDER XUSUSIYATLAR.....	81
Mahfuza Nishonboyeva METAFORIK BIRLIKLAR QO'LLASH VA ULARNING TARJIMA JARAYONIDA YUZAGA KELADIGAN MUAMMOLAR.....	85
Allakhverdiyeva Farda Muhammadali The Variability of the Category of Negation in Linguistics.....	87
Muslimbek Makkatillayev SOTSIOLINGVISTIKANING AYRIM MASALALARI: DIGLOSSIYA VA BILINGVIZM TUSHUNCHALARINING MOHIYATI.....	93
Alisher O'razov, Nazokat No'monova O'ZBEK TILIDA LEKSEMANING LISONIY BIRLIK SIFATIDA TALQINI.....	95
Ro'ziqulov Shohruh FE'L DERIVATSIYASI HAQIDAGI ILMIY QARASHLAR.....	98

Dilrabo Suyarova	
MORFOLOGIK TIZIMDA DUALIZM VA ASIMMETRIK O‘ZGARISHLAR....	101
Gulzoda Yuldasheva	
LINGVISTIK TAHLILLARDA KORPUS PRAGMATIK YONDASHUV.....	105
Zulayho To‘ychiyeva	
MAHMUD KOSHG‘ARIYNING “DEVONU LUG‘OTIT TURK” ASARIDA SO‘ZLARNING KO‘CHMA MA’NODA QO‘LLANISHI.....	108
Eshqulov Sunnatilla	
TILSHUNOSLIKDA PESH LAVHA, REKLAMA VA TIJORIY YOZUVLARNING LISONIY XUSUSIYATLARI.....	116
Sanjar Amirqulov	
TILSHUNOSLIK TARAQQIYOTI VA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR...	118
Jamila Akhrorova	
METONYMY AS A MEANS OF FORMING NEW MEANINGS OF A WORD..	120
Nazarli Fidan Sadiq	
THE SYNTAX-SEMANTICS INTERFACE OF ELLIPSIS: ISSUES AND ANALYSES.....	122
Mashxuraxon Burxanova	
OLFAKTOR VOSITALAR TADQIQIGA OID BA’ZI MULOHAZALAR.....	126
Munisa Abduazizova	
“YOSH” TUSHUNCHASINING MILLIY TAFAKKURDAGI KONSEPTUAL XARITASI.....	130
Kamola Siddiqova	
KONSEPT LINGVOKOGNITIV VA LINGVOMADANIY HODISA SIFATIDA.....	135
Robiya Vaxobjonova	
PUBLITSISTIK MATNLARNING SOTSIOLINGVISTIK TAHLILI.....	138
Kumushoy Turdikulova	
MUHAMMAD ISMOIL SHE’RIYATI TADQIQOT OBYEKTI SIFATIDA.....	146
Moxichexra Mirzayeva	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATI TOPONIMLARINING O‘RGANILISH TARIXI.....	149

Ahmadzada Guloysha Azad gizi MONOLOGUE TYPOLOGY IN PROSE TEXTS AND NEW DIRECTIONS IN LINGUISTIC RESEARCH.....	153
G‘ulom Shayzakov O‘ZBEK TILIDA ZAMON FUNKTSIONAL-SEMANTIK MAYDONI.....	156
Xumoyun Ubaydullayev KOMMUNIKANTLAR IJTIMOY MAVQEYI VA ROLINING DRAMALARDA AKS ETISHI.....	160
Sayyora Muxamadiyeva TILSHUNOSLIK FANINING TARAQQIYOTI: YANGI YONDASHUVLAR VA YUTUQLAR.....	163
Mahliyo Hayitova O‘ZBEK TILIDA “SUV” KONSEPTI ASOSIDA SHAKLLANGAN AYRIM METAFORIK BIRLIKLAR TADQIQI.....	167
Фарангиз Музаффарова ЮМОР ЧЕРЕЗ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЗМЫ: ПРАГМАТИЧЕСКИЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ И ПЕРЕВОД.....	171
Dilafruz Abdulkhakova PSYCHOLINGUISTIC INSIGHTS INTO THE PROCESSING AND ACQUISITION OF FORMULAIC LANGUAGE IN SECOND LANGUAGE LEARNING.....	173
Сабина Наджафова СЛОВООБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЕ МОДЕЛИ ОТЗООНИМИЧЕСКИХ ПРИЛАГАТЕЛЬНЫХ (НА МАТЕРИАЛЕ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА).....	177
Sevinj Shabanova KO‘Z SO‘ZINING ISPAN VA O‘ZBEK TILLARIDAGI NUTQIY AKTLARDA QO‘LLANILISHI: FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLAR MISOLIDA QIYOSIY TAHLIL.....	180
Shirinoy Muhsinjonova MAHMUD KOSHG‘ARIY – TURKIY LEKSIKOGRAFIYA ASOSCHISI.....	186
Nasiba Mamatkulova TILSHUNOSLIKDA MORFONOLOGIK JARAYONLARNING SHAKL YASALISHDAGI AHAMIYATI.....	188
Fazilbek Orzibekov PREDIKATIV MUNOSABATNI RO‘YOBGA CHIQRUVCHI VOSITALAR TADQIQI.....	190

Ma'rufjon Azimqulov OT YASOVCHI QO'SHIMCHALAR TA'SIRIDA SO'Z VALENTLIGINING O'ZGARISHI.....	195
Mumtozbegin Negmatova O'ZBEK ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIGIDA DEYKSIS HODISASINI O'RGANISHNING AHAMIYATI.....	198
Shirin Soqiyeva LINGVISTIKADA KONSEPTLARNI O'RGANISHNING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI.....	201
Mashxura Turatova KOMRON MIRZO DEVONIDA IJTIMOYIY-SIYOSIY LEKSIKA.....	204
Manzura Imankulova ETNOGRAFIKALAR ASOSIDA SHAKLLANGAN FRAZEMALARNING LINGVOMADANIY XUSUSIYATLARI.....	209
Sevara Nematova AYRIM HOLAT FE'LLARINING PRAGMATIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	213
Rashida Xakimjonova TO'RA SULAYMON SHE'RIYATINING LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK ASPEKTI.....	216
Faxriddin Niyazov, Farrux Muxudullayev, Gulsora Ko'chimova KORPUS LINGVISTIKASI VA TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI.....	219
Dilchehra Toshpo'latova ABDUQAYUM YO'LDOSHEV IJODIDA BADIY TILNING O'ZIGA XOSLIGI.....	222
Gavhar Jo'rayeva, Xushro'ybegin Narzullayeva O'ZBEK TILINING PAYDO BO'LISHI VA RIVOJLANISH TARIXI.....	226
Farrux Muxudullayev SO'ROQ GAPLARDA POETIKLIK MASALASI.....	230
Zulxumor Akhrorova ADVANCEMENT AND PROSPECTS OF MATHEMATICAL LINGUISTICS..	234
Mahfuza Bobomurotova PIRIMQUL QODIROVNING "QADRIM" ASARIDA UMUMISTE'MOL SO'ZLARNING QO'LLASHDAGI MAHORATI.....	236

Баходир Чориев
ЯЗЫКОВЫЕ СРЕДСТВА ВЫРАЖЕНИЯ ВОКАТИВОВ В РУССКОМ
ЯЗЫКЕ.....239

2. LEKSIKOGRAFIYA VA LUG‘ATCHILIK: NAZARIY VA AMALIY MUAMMOLAR

Yorkinoy Xamrayeva
IDEOGRAFIK LUG‘ATNING ASOSIY TAMOIYILLARI.....242

Azizbek Mamatqulov
TONYUQUQ BITIKTOSHI LUG‘AVIY TARKIBINING ILMIY-TAHLILY
TADQIQI.....245

H.Dusmatov, R.N.Nuritdinova
TILGA TA‘SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR IJTIMOYILASHUV VOSITASI
SIFATIDA.....250

Durdona Rajapova
O‘ZBEK TILINING ELEKTRON LUG‘ATLARINI YARATISHDA YUZAGA
KELADIGAN QIYINCHILIKLAR.....254

Саодат Кулбаева
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ РАЗЛИЧИЙ В ФОРМАЛЬНЫХ И НЕФОРМАЛЬНЫХ
СТИЛЯХ РУССКОГО И УЗБЕКСКОГО ОБЩЕНИЯ И ИХ ВЛИЯНИЕ НА
ПЕРЕВОД.....257

Botir Raxmanov
SURXON VOHASI ETNOMADANIY MUHITI VA ETNOGRAFIK
LEKSIKASI.....259

Yelda YEŞİLDAL ERAYDIN
Reconceptualizing Multiword Expressions in Contemporary Turkic Languages: AI-
Supported NLP Approaches.....263

Boysariyeva Saodat
LEKSIK MA‘LUMOTLARINING BAZASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA
ELEKTRON LUG‘ATLARNING ROLI.....266

Ma‘rufjon Abdujalilov
RUS TILI MADANIYATINI AKS ETTIRUVCHI FRAZEOLGIK
BIRLIKMA LARNING SEMANTIK MAYDON.....268

Durdona Abdug‘ofurova
SLEEP AS AN IMAGE OF THE LIFE CYCLE IN TURKISH AND UZBEK
PAREMIOLOGY.....274

Muratkulov Amanulla ARABCHA O‘ZLASHMALARNING LISONIY TAHLILI.....	280
Ситора Ашурова СОВРЕМЕННАЯ ЛЕКСИКОГРАФИЯ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ В УЗБЕКСКОЙ И АНГЛИЙСКОЙ ПРАКТИКЕ.....	285
Елена Сурмилова ФУНКЦИИ ЧИСЛИТЕЛЬНЫХ В АНГЛИЙСКИХ И РУССКИХ СКОРОГОВОРКАХ.....	290
Aziza Pirmatova THE MAIN CONCEPTUAL FIELDS OF TOURISM TERMINOLOGY AND METHODS FOR THEIR REPRESENTATION IN A DICTIONARY.....	293
Nigora Ergasheva MADANIYATLARARO TARJIMADA LINGVISTIK VA MADANIY QIYINCHILIKLAR.....	297
Surayyo Khajibaeva MAKTAB KORPUSI ASOSIDA BAZIS SO‘ZLARNI AJRATIB OLISH VA TAHLIL QILISH.....	300
Masimova Sona Shirali THE LINGUISTIC EXPRESSION OF QUANTITY ACROSS LANGUAGES....	302
Mahfuza Nishonboyeva METAFORIK BIRLIKLAR QO‘LLASH VA ULARNING TARJIMA JARAYONIDA YUZAGA KELADIGAN MUAMMOLAR.....	308
Alisher O‘razov OTLARGA OID LEKSEMANING O‘ZBEK TILIDAGI SEMANTIK SHAJARASI TALQINI.....	310
Elshod Rajabov O‘ZBEK TILIDA “ILTIFOT” UMUMIY SEMALI LUG‘AVIY BIRLIKLARNING SEMANTIK VA LEKSIKOGRAFIK TALQINI.....	313
Mahliyo Sherqulova INGLIZ VA O‘ZBEK TILLARIDAGI REKLAMA SLOGANLARIDA SUBYEKTIV MODALLIKNING IFODALANISHI.....	317
Dilrabo Suyarova “-JON” MORFEMASINING FUNKSIONAL TRANSPOZITSIYASI.....	220
Shoxsanam Tadjiboyeva ERKALOVCHI BIRLIKLARNING MORFOLOGIK VA SEMANTIK KO‘RINISHLARI.....	322

Iroda Kenjayeva

SIRDARYO VILOYATI TOPONIMLARINING O'RGANILISHI VA TARIXIY TAHLILI.....324

Munisa Bahrombekova

ETHICAL VALUES IN ENGLISH PROVERBS: A HISTORICAL AND CULTURAL PERSPECTIVE.....329

Feruza Xazratqulova

INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA FLORISTIK OBRAZLI FRAZELOGIZMLAR: KOGNITIV-SEMANTIK TIPOLOGIYA.....333

Odilbek Xidirboyev

O'ZBEK ONOMASTIKASIDA NEKRONIMLAR: "XO'JA BOBO" QABRISTONI MISOLIDA.....337

03. ADABIY TIL VA JONLI XALQ TILI MUNOSABATI MASALASI

Cemile Uzun

Diyalektometriden Ontolojiye: Türkiye Türkçesi Ağız Çeşitliliğinin Bilgi Grafında Yapılandırılması.....342

Izzat Pardayeva

SIRDARYO VILOYATI AHOLISI LEKSIKASIDA FRAZELOGIZMLARNING QO'LLANILISHI.....346

Латыпов Фарит

ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ СОДЕРЖАНИЯ ПЯТИ РЕТСКИХ НАДПИСЕЙ, НАНЕСЕННЫХ НА РЯД МЕТАЛЛИЧЕСКИХ ПРЕДМЕТОВ И КАМЕННУЮ ПЛИТУ.....349

Dilbar Xalmuratova

DIALEKTIZMLERDİN STILISTIKALIQ FIGURALAR DÚZIWDEGI XIZMETI.....352

Dilnoza To'rayeva

TARIXIY ASARLARDA BADIY NUTQ VA XALQ SHEVALARINING O'RNI.....356

İbadova Nigar Saleh qızı

ÇEX DİLİNDƏ TÜRKİZMLƏR VƏ ONLARIN LİNGVİSTİK XÜSUSİYYƏTLƏRİ.....361

Yusifova Fidan Elxan qızı

TÜRK DİLLƏRİ ARASINDA LEKSİK PARALELLƏR VƏ FƏRQLƏR.....366

Gulchehra Ahatova	
TURKIY XALQLAR LAHJASIDA TOYLOQ SHEVASI.....	368
Tadjiboyeva Shoxsanam	
O‘ZBEK VA NEMIS TILLARIDA ERKALASH BIRLIKLARI: FOLKLOR VA MADANIY SEMANTIKA.....	371
Mardona Ibatova	
O‘ZBEK LAHJALARIDAGI MAISHIY LEKSIKANING ADABIY TILDAN FARQI.....	374
Moxigul Naxalbayeva	
ADABIY TIL VA JONLI XALQ TILI MASALASI.....	377
Maftuna Raimova	
ADABIY TIL VA JONLI XALQ TILI MUNOSABATI.....	381
04. O‘ZBEK MILLIY TERMINOLOGIYASINING AMALIY MASALALARI	
Ixtiyor Ermatov	
EKVONIMIYA VA ANTONIMIYA HODISALARI XUSUSIDA.....	384
Gulandom Mirxanova	
TERMINLARNI DAVRLASHTIRISHGA DOIR BA’ZI QARASHLAR.....	389
Otabek Xidirov	
O‘ZBEK TILIDAGI AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI TERMINLARINING LUG‘ATLARDA AKS ETTIRILISHI VA BERILISHI MUAMMOLARI.....	392
Sunnatullo Khujakulov	
SEMANTIC INTEROPERABILITY AND LINGUISTIC VARIATION IN THE STUDY OF LEGAL TERMINOLOGY.....	397
Hasanova Amalia Murad	
METHODOLOGY OF USING TERMINOLOGICAL DICTIONARIES IN TEACHING BIOLOGY SUBJECTS.....	402
Nigar Murvat Khanaliyeva	
THE DISSEMINATION OF ECOTERMS IN MULTICULTURAL AND GLOBAL COMMUNICATION: LANGUAGE, CULTURE, AND SOCIAL IDENTITY PERSPECTIVES.....	405
Sarvinoz Abdialimova	
INTERNET TERMINLARINING O‘ZBEK TILIDA BERILISHI HAQIDA.....	408
Iroda Almardanova	
LEKSIK-SEMANTIK MUNOSABATLARGA KO‘RA IQTISODIY TERMINLAR TAVSIFI.....	411

E'zoza Arzimurodova	
FUNCTIONAL FEATURES OF MOBILE COMMUNICATION TERMS IN MASS MEDIA DISCOURSE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK.....	415
Yulduz Karshibayeva	
UMUMISTE'MOL SO'ZLARI TIZIMIDA EKVONIMIYA HODISASI XUSUSIDA.....	419
Shodiya Raxmibayeva	
TIBBIY ATAMALARNING TARIXIY - ETIMOLOGIK SHAKLLANISHI VA O'ZIGA XOS LINGVISTIK XUSUSUSIYATLARI.....	421
Maftuna Sobirova	
TURK TILLARIDA KONCHILIK TERMINOLOGIYASINING LEKSIKOGRAFIK ASOSLARI VA TARIXIY EVOLYUTSIYASI.....	424
Азиза Аякулова	
МЕДИЦИНСКАЯ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЯ В РУССКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ: СРАВНИТЕЛЬНО-ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ.....	427
Dildora Karimberdiyeva	
O'ZBEK MILLIY TERMINOLOGIK LEKSIKASINING ADABIY LEKSIKA BILAN MUNOSABATI.....	430
05. FAN O'QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI VA YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR	
Suheyla Demirkol Orak	
Impostor Phenomenon in Heutagogy and Andragogy: A Narrative Literature Review in EFL Learning Contexts.....	433
Ilayda Erdem	
THE PLACE OF ACADEMIC BUOYANCY IN SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION.....	439
Maxsuda Sariboyeva	
TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA KOMPETENTSIYALI YONDASHUVNING AHAMIYATI.....	445
Guljahon Norimova	
INGLIZ TILI MASHG'ULOTLARIDA YOUTUBE ILOVASI VA TA'LIM TRENDLARI.....	449
Зульфия Хабирова	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ СИСТЕМ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ С ПОМОЩЬЮ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА.....	453

Gulkhumor Usmonova TEACHING ENGLISH BASED ON LINGUISTIC AND PSYCHOPEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES.....	458
Dilnoza Yuldasheva INGLIZ TILI FANINI O‘QITISHDA INDIVIDUAL YONDASHUVNING AFZALLIKLARI.....	461
Gullu T. Mammadova NEW METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES IN TEACHING THE ENGLISH ARTICLE.....	466
Sevara Karimova TALABALAR UCHUN INGLIZ TILI O‘QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI VA YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR.....	469
Sulurxan Raximova TURKIY ASARLARDAGI MAQOL VA MATALLARNING BADIY NUTQNI IFODALI QILISHDAGI ROLI.....	471
Günay Bədəlzadə DISLEKSILI ÖĞRENCILERDE OKUMA BECERISININ ARTIRILMASINA YÖNELİK DİLBİLİM YAKLAŞIMLARI.....	474
Maftuna To‘rayeva FAN O‘QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI VA YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR.....	477
Gunel Mahammad Mammadova MÜƏLLİM HAZIRLIĞINDA YENİ NƏZƏRİ YANAŞMALAR VƏ MODELLƏRİ.....	479
Amanulla Muratkulov, Munisa Muratkulova UZLUKSIZ TA’LIM TIZIMIDA MORFEMANI O‘QITISH MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI.....	484
Sevara Davronova MASTERING DESCRIPTIVE WRITING: FEATURES, TECHNIQUES, AND STEPS TO EVOKE VIVID IMAGERY.....	488
Sayyoraxon Qo‘shaqboyeva MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI O‘QUVCHILARDA DISLEKSIYANI ANIQLASH.....	493
Farangiz Murtazayeva INNOVATIVE DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES.....	496

Valentina Masharipova PARALINGUISTIC ELEMENTS IN CHARACTER DESCRIPTION AS A TOOL FOR FORMING INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING.....	498
Dilnura Qodirberganova ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA MATN YARATISH...501	501
Shoira Djalilova ONA TILI TA'LIMIDA KOMMUNIKATIV YONDASHUV ORQALI NUTQIY SAVODXONLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	504
Tursunoy Ortiqova LANGUAGE-SKILL DIFFICULTIES AND STRATEGIC RESPONSES OF LOCAL EFL STUDENTS: A VISUAL PERSPECTIVE.....	508
Ozoda Qayumova O'QUVCHILAR SO'Z BOYLIGINI ANIQLASHNING FALSAFIY ASOSLARI.....	510
Nargiza Ismailova O'ZBEK TILI DARSIDA O'QUVCHILARGA JOY NOMLARINI (TOPONIMLARNI) O'RGATISH METODLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH (XO'JAYLI TUMANI MISOLIDA).....	513
Hulkaroy Ahadova THE ROLE OF CONTEXT IN INTERPRETING MODALITY.....	516
Nasiba Toshtemirova DAVLAT TILIDA ISH YURITISH KURSINI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSIYA VA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	519
Vazira Egamberdiyeva FONETIKA BO'LIMINI O'RGATISHDA INTERFAOL METODLARNING AHAMIYATI.....	522
Navruzbek Soybnazarov JAMIYAT VA SHAXS DIALEKTIKASI TEODOR DRAYZER ROMANLARIDA (BAXTIQARO KERRI VA AMERIKA FOJIASI ASARLARI MISOLIDA).....	525
Gulamol Azimova INFORMAL TA'LIM MUHITIDA BO'LAJAK INGLIZ TILI O'QITUVCHILARINING NUTQIY KO'NIKMALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODIKASI.....	528
Sharipova Gulshod TA'LIMIY DISKURS: NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDAGI AHAMIYATI.....	531

Xurshida Mirzayeva, Dildora Shodmonova PROBLEMS IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AND THEIR SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS.....	534
Muhtaram Husenova BOSHLANG‘ICH SINFLARDA SO‘Z MA‘NOSI VA LUG‘AT BOYLIGI TUSHUNCHASINING LINGIVISTIK ASOSLARINI O‘RGANISH.....	537
Gulchehra Abduvoidova INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: CONTEMPORARY RESEARCH AND IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGIES FOR DIVERSE LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS.....	541
Aziza Mirzayeva KOREYS VA O‘ZBEK ADABIYOTINING RIVOJLANISHBOSQICHLARI.....	547
Gulmira Eshquvvatova RAQAMLI KOMMUNIKATSIYA SHAROITIDA INTERNET JANRLARI VA FORMATLARINING O‘ZARO ALOQASI.....	551
Sabina Muradova FAN O‘QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI VA YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR.....	554
Charos Qambarova TALABALARNI IJODIY-TADQIQIY FAOLIYATGA TAYYORLASH METODIKASI.....	558
Maxsuda Obidova PEDAGOGIK LOYIHALASH ASOSIDA BO‘LAJAK O‘QITUVCHILARNING NUTQIY FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	562
Xosiyat Navruzova LINGVISTIK BILIMNING O‘QIB TUSHUNISH KO‘NIKMASIGA TA’SIRI...	566
Xulkar Mamaraximova TIL O‘QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR VA ULARNI TATBIQ QILISH USULLARI.....	568
Shohruh Ro‘ziqulov, Munisa Anorboyeva TILSHUNOSLIK FANINING TARAQQIYOTI: YANGI YONDASHUVLAR VA YUTUQLAR.....	571
Madina Abdullajonova MOTOR DISGRAFIYANING NEYROLINGVISTIK ASOSLARI.....	573

Ertan Örgen “ANAMIN YURDU” VE “İLKİ” HİKÂYELERİNDE ALIŞILMAMIŞ BAĞDAŞTIRMALAR VE EKSİLTİLİ YAPILAR.....	577
Mammadova Sevil Alasgar HUMAN NATURE AND SOCIAL RELATIONS IN D.H. LAWRENCE'S “ESSAYS ON LOVE”.....	581
Nigar Seyidova A BRIEF EXCURSION INTO THE HISTORY OF TRADITIONAL SEMANTICS.....	586
Kanimkul Tadjiyev TAMIM ANSARIYNING “BEVANING ERI” ROMANI TARJIMASI HAQIDA.....	589
Sabina Ismayilova LINGUISTIC AND EXTRALINGUISTIC FACTORS IN SHAPING DISCOURSE.....	593
Sarvinozxon Abduxalimova COMMUNICATION AND IDENTITY IN A GLOBALIZED WORLD.....	596
Maftuna Avalboyeva MAKTAB TA'LIMIDA INNOVATION PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISH (INGLIZ TILIDAGI EKVIVALENTSIZ LEKSIKA MISOLIDA).....	599
Sevara Bozorova COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK TRADE TERMINOLOGY IN SPECIALIZED SUBLANGUAGES.....	601
Shahzoda Yusupova OLMOSHLARNING NUTQ SUGGESTIVLIGINI OSHIRUVCHI VOSITA SIFATIDA QO'LLANILISHI HAQIDA.....	606
Mahfuza Sulaymonova THE ROLE AND FUNCTIONS OF METAPHOR IN SCIENTIFIC DISCOURSE.....	608
Dilmurod Imomqulov TIL VA TAFAKKUR MUNOSABATIDA LINGVOKONSEPTUAL YONDASHUVNING O'RNI.....	612
Muslima RISQULOVA “DEVONU LUG'OTIT TURK” VA “BOBURNOMA”DA KELTIRILGAN ORONIMLAR VA OROGRAFIK ATAMALAR TAVSIFI HAQIDA.....	615

Ra'no Abduvaliyeva INFORMATIKA VA TEXNOLOGIYA ASOSLARI FANI TERMINLARI XUSUSIDA.....	618
Sunnatullo Shukurulloyev PSIXOLOGIK TERMINLAR O'ZBEK MILLIY TERMINOLOGIYASINING E'TIBOR MARKAZIDA.....	622
Birsel ORUÇ ASLAN ÖZBEK VE TÜRK ATASÖZLERİNDE ZITLIKLAR.....	624
O'g'iloy Utegenova TASVIRIY IFODALAR IKKILAMCHI NOMINATIV BIRLIK SIFATIDA.....	629
Gulnoza Abdurahmonova O'ZBEK TILINI O'QITISH VA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR.....	632

**TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI:
ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB
MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLARI, TARAQQIYOTI VA
ISTIQBOLLARI**

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari

MATERIALLARI

2025-yil 29-30-sentabr

To‘plam mualliflarning tahririda taqdim etilgan.

To‘plamda keltirilgan faktlar, atoqli otlar va boshqa ma’lumotlarning aniqligiga, hamda imloviy xatolar uchun javobgarlik mualliflarning zimmasidadir.

“Bookmany print” nashriyoti

Nashriyot tasdiqnoma raqami № 022246. 28.02.2022-y.

Bosishga ruxsat etildi: 22.09.2025.

“Times New Roman” garniturası. Qog‘oz bichimi: 60x84^{1/8}

Nashriyot bosma tabog‘i 42,3. Shartli bosma taboq 68,6.

Adadi 50 nusxa. Ofset bosma usulida bosildi.

Toshkent shahri, Uchtepa tumani, 22-mavze, 17-b uy.

“BOOKMANY PRINT” MCHJ bosmaxonasida chop etildi.

Toshkent shahri, Uchtepa tumani, 22-mavze, 17-b uy.

E-mail: bookmany_print@mail.ru

[t.me/ Bookmanyprint](https://t.me/Bookmanyprint) +998 99 180 97 10

 BOOKMANY
PRINT

ISBN 978-9910-06-724-2

